

Food Culture and Tourism of India

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A Survey of Issues Related to Genetically Modified Foods Consumed & Recommendations for Food Safety

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Abstract

Background: Genetic modification is a special set of gene technology that alters the genetic makeup of such living organisms as animals, plants or microorganisms. Combining genes from different organisms is known as recombinant DNA technology and the resulting organism is said to be 'Genetically modified (GM)', 'Genetically engineered' or 'Transgenic'. The principal transgenic crops grown commercially in field are herbicide and insecticide resistant soybeans, corn, cotton and canola. Crops grown commercially and/or field-tested are sweet potato resistant to a virus that could destroy most of the harvest, rice with increased iron and vitamins that may alleviate chronic malnutrition in countries and a variety of plants that are able to survive weather extremes. There are bananas that produce human vaccines against infectious diseases such as hepatitis B, fish that mature more quickly, fruit and nut trees that yield years earlier and plants that produce new plastics with unique properties. Technologies for genetically modifying foods offer dramatic promise for meeting some areas of greatest challenge for the 21st century. Like all new technologies, they also pose some risks, both known and unknown. Controversies and public concern surrounding GM foods and crops commonly focus on human and environmental safety, labelling and consumer choice, intellectual property rights, ethics, food security, poverty reduction and environmental conservation. Objectives: Therefore, this study attempts to access with this new technology on gene manipulation. What are the risks of "tampering with Mother Nature"? What are the health concerns that consumers should be aware of? And is recombinant technology really beneficial? This review will also address some major concerns about the safety, environmental and ecological risks and health hazards involved with GM foods and recombinant technology. Conclusion: the current study explores and discuss the implication and challenges related to Genetically Modified Foods Consumed & Recommendations for Food Safety.

Keywords Genetically modified foods. Genetically engineered foods. Transgenic foods. Food safety. Allergenic foods. Public conce.

Introduction

Genetically modified foods are foods derived from animals and plants in which genes for a particular desired characteristic(s) are added to an organism's DNA. As the animal or plant grows and develops, it begins to express the proteins of the inserted genes, this leads to changes in the organism's molecular structure, biochemistry, physiology, anatomy and morphology thus resulting in the creation of a new living entity not found in nature. These changes are unprogrammed, multidirectional and difficult to control leading to the creation of highly unpredictable organisms (Oxfam, 1999).

Genetically modified foods came to the forefront were when a single U.S. Supreme Court Ruling in 1980 allowed for the first time the patenting of life forms for commercialization. Since then thousands of genetically modified organisms have been created and patented in the U.S. (The Pew

Institute on Food and Biotechnology, 2005). The effects of genetically modified foods on human health and well being are at its infancy. There exists little reputable scientific evidence in the current literature to suggest that genetically modified foods are safe for human consumption and health. Food producers and processors in response to the increasing demand for cheap, nutritious foods have invested considerable resources in developing new products using genetic engineering. It is hoped that this new technology would be used to solve the problems of hunger, food security and pest control, but at what cost to the safety of the consumer and public (Oxfam, 2005; The Pew Institute on Food and Biotechnology, 2005).

Methodology

Methodology of this paper is explorative in nature. The study attempts to access with this new technology on gene manipulation what are the risks, effects, health concerns for consumers and recombinant technological benefits. A draft survey was developed based on a comprehensive review of existing literature. It was decided to use five point Likert scales to measure the responses to each item. The survey was circulated which consist of a total of 12 questions (closed ended questions).

The first section included questions on the biographic and demographic information of the respondents. There were also some questions about the general profiles of the investigated. The second section of the survey asked the respondents about awareness of genetically modified foods, labelling of genetically modified food, application of genetic modification, common medical ailments and consumption pattern of genetically modified foods.

RESULTS

Table-1

Results of Survey	
Demographics	
Gender	Male-(49%) Female-(51%)
Average age	25-35 Years
Marital Status	Married (78 %) Single (18 %)
Educational Qualification	Primary (26 %), Secondary (32 %), Tertiary (35 %) and Other (7 %)
Employed or Not Employed	Employed (79 %) NonEmployed (21%)
Information Source	Television (65 %), Radio (12 %), Internet (15 %), Newspaper (7 %) and Other (1 %).
Awareness of Genetically Modified Foods	
Knowledge of Genetically Modified Foods	10 %
Information Source	Internet (87 %) Magazines (13 %)
Availability In Indian Market	(91 %)
Rate Of safety (GMF)	(90 %) reluctant
Price selection	(89 %)
Food safety	(60 %)
Health	(30 %)

Public and Consumers Information	(98 %) (FSSAI and the Health Education Division, Ministry of Health)
Labelling of Genetically Modified Foods	
Certification by relevant competent authority	80%
Information origin of transferred genes	12%
Declaration of any allergic warning statement	8%
Labelling of genetically modified or non-genetically modified Mandatory and Not Voluntary.	89%
Consumption Patterns of Genetically Modified Foods	
Meat and dairy products	27%
Baby foods	15%
Soups	15%
Juice and fruit drink	14%
Fruits and vegetables	13%
Confectionery	11%
Bakery products	5%
Consumption Rate of Genetically Modified Foods	
Consumed foods identified as Genetically Modified Foods or contained ingredients	85%
Consumed on average at a rate of servings	6-8 servings per day per person
Food portion per servings	227g
Genetically modified foods comprise of the Diet	65%

Demographics

The present study surveyed 49 % males and 51 % females. The average age ranged from between 25-35 years. Most respondents were either married (78 %), single (18 %). The educational levels of respondents were primary (26 %), secondary (32 %), tertiary (35 %) and other (7 %). Most respondents surveyed were employed (79 %). All respondents had daily exposure to or access to one or more of the following: television (65 %), radio (12 %), internet (15 %), newspaper (7 %) and other (1 %).

Awareness of Genetically Modified Foods

Most respondents (90 %) did not know about genetically modified foods. Only 10 % knew about genetically modified foods. The major sources of information were the internet (87 %) and magazines (13 %). Most respondents believed (91 %) that genetically modified foods are not being sold in India. Respondents (95 %) were uncertain whether genetically modified foods were safe to eat and many (90 %) were reluctant to eat foods with genetically modified ingredients. When respondents were told that genetically modified foods may be more nutritious than non-genetically modified foods and may require less pesticides for growth, there were marked changes in responses

from denial and reluctance to the affirmative (93 %). Price was not a marked factor in the selection of genetically modified foods for the majority of respondents (89 %). Food safety (60%) and health (30 %) were the major issues affecting the use of genetically modified foods as a safe source of food.

Respondents (98 %) believed that the government through the relevant agencies such as the FSSAI and the Health Education Division, Ministry of Health should be the major agencies responsible for informing the public and consumers about genetically modified foods. Most respondents agreed that there was insufficient information on genetically modified foods available to consumers and public in India.

Labeling of Genetically Modified Foods

Information required by respondents on genetically modified foods in descending order of importance included: (i) certification by relevant competent authority on safety of genetically modified foods (80 %), (ii) origin of transferred genes (12 %) and (iii) declaration of any allergic warning statement(s) (8 %). Most respondents believed it is very important (89 %) that food products are specifically labelled as genetically modified or non-genetically modified. This labelling should be mandatory and not voluntary.

Consumption Patterns of Genetically Modified Foods

There were no marked differences in consumption patterns in respondents. Common foods consumed by respondents in descending order included: meat and dairy products (27 %), baby foods (15 %), soups (15 %), juice and fruit drink (14 %), fruits and vegetables (13 %), confectionery (11 %) and bakery products (5 %). Consumption Rate of Genetically Modified Foods

Most respondents (85 %) claimed that they consumed foods identified as being genetically modified or contained ingredients thereof. These foods were consumed on average at a rate of least 6-8 servings per day per person. One serving was considered 227 g portion of a particular food. It was generally believed that genetically modified foods comprise 65 % of the diet.

Gm Foods: Issues with Respect to India

In a major setback to the proponents of GM technology in farm crops, the Parliamentary Committee on Agriculture in 2012 asked Indian government to stop all field trials and sought a bar on GM food crops such as Bt. brinjal. Raising the “ethical dimensions” of transgenic in agricultural crops, as well as studies of a long-term environmental and chronic toxicology impact, the panel noted that there were no significant socio-economic benefits to farmers. Countries like India have great security concerns at the same time specific problems exist for small and marginal farmers. India could use a toxin free variety of the *Lathyrus sativus* grown on marginal lands and consumed by the very poor. GM mustard is a variety using the barnase-barstar-bar gene complex, an unstable gene construct with possible undesirable effects, to achieve male sterile lines that are used to make hybrid mustard varieties. In India, we have good non-GM alternatives for making male sterile lines for hybrid production so the Proagro variety is of little use. Being a food crop, GM mustard will have to be examined very carefully. Even if there were to be benefits, they have to be weighed against the risks posed to human health and the environment. Apart from this, mustard is a cross-pollinating crop and pollen with their foreign genes is bound to reach non-GM mustard and wild relatives. We do not know what impact this will have. If GM technology is to be used in India, it should be

directed at the real needs of Indian farmers, on crops like legumes, oilseeds and fodder and traits like drought tolerance and salinity tolerance. Basmati rice and Darjeeling tea are perhaps India's most easily identifiable premium products in the area of food. Basmati is highly prized rice, its markets are growing and it is a high end, expensive product in the international market. Like Champagne wine and truffles from France, international consumers treat it as a special, luxury food. Since rice is nutritionally a poor cereal, it is thought that addition of iron and vitamin A by genetic modification would increase the nutritional quality. So, does it make any sense at all to breed a GM Basmati, along the lines of Bt Cotton? However, premium wine makers have outright rejected the notion of GM doctored wines that were designed to cut out the hangover and were supposed to be 'healthier'. Premium products like special wines, truffles and Basmati rice need to be handled in a special, premium way (Sahai 2003).

India is a signatory to the Cartagena Protocol on Biosafety (CPB) since 2003.

India's apex biotech regulatory committee, the Genetic Engineering Approval Committee (GEAC) that functions as a statutory body under the Environment Protection Act 1986 of the Ministry of Environment & Forests (MoEF), has been changed to Genetic Engineering Appraisal Committee in July 22, 2010.

Discussion and Recommendations

The results of the present study revealed that the majority of respondents are unaware of the presence of genetically modified foods on supermarket shelves in India, despite exposure to at least one or more forms of communication media. Only a few respondents knew about genetically modified foods. The major sources of information were the internet and magazines. Most respondents did not believe that genetically modified foods are sold in India. A high degree of uncertainty was expressed by respondents in accessing the safety of genetically modified foods. There may be a tendency for respondents to buy foods that are more nutritious and require less pesticide. Health and safety are major factors considered by respondents in determining the acceptability of genetically modified foods. The main reason may be due to the lack of proper labelling. Most respondents consumed foods without knowing that they were genetically modified. This may constitute a violation of the individual/consumer rights to know what they are eating. Consumers should be given the choice to select their own foods which are either genetically modified. This may constitute a violation of the individual/consumer rights to know what they are eating. Consumers should be given the choice to select their own foods which are either genetically modified or foods which are not genetically modified.

Despite the presence of relevant laws to monitor regulated entry and use of genetically modified foods into India, genetically modified foods are still being allowed for sale and distribution without any restriction in India. The main reasons for this are:

- I. lack of effective monitoring and surveillance of genetically modified foods entering India,
- II. lack of sufficient information provided by manufacturers and also on labels,
- III. dependence on foreign countries to supply food to India,
- IV. lack of the necessary enforcement by the relevant authority,
- V. lack of research on the effects of genetically modified foods on human health and wellbeing,

- VI. political, economic and social acceptance that have led to resistance to change.
- VII. These apparent weaknesses in the present system have allowed the unguarded entry of genetically modified foods into India.

In order to address these weaknesses, the following recommendations have been suggested:

- Genetically modified foods present on shelves of food outlets should be carefully documented and a complaints desk should be established in each food outlet to monitor any problems arising out of the use of these foods. This information should be collected, pooled and supplied to a central processing centre for analyses, report generation and adoption and implementation of corrective actions.
- Surveillance, data collection, analysis and documentation should be established for genetically modified foods.
- Establish proper and effective monitoring and surveillance protocols and procedures to investigate on a continuous basis the effects of genetically modified foods on human health and wellbeing and the establishment of a research bank for the adoption of the necessary corrective actions.
- Networking with other international organizations on the safety of genetically modified foods such as Cartagena Protocol on Bio safety (CPB). This is an international harmonizing mechanism that sets standards in dealing with the international introduction of living modified organisms into the environment (Bail, Falker & Marguard, 2000).
- Establish a moratorium, to partially ban, restrict or to request mandatory warning labelling on all genetically modified foods. This would allow for: (i) further scientific assessment of socio-economic health and environmental impacts; (ii) public debate and development of educational programs on biotechnology; (iii) establishment of national regulatory systems; and (iv) adapting legislation and creating company liability for adverse effects.
- Adopt and implement stringent penalties for non-compliance.
- Adopt regulated health safety testing. The FSSAI should be given the financial, human and necessary infrastructure resources to conduct independent tests in order to validate health and safety of genetically modified foods.
- More countries should sign the Convention on Biodiversity (CBD). The Bio safety protocol must be finalized and enshrine in the precautionary principle in relation to transboundary movement of genetically modified crops and regulate liability and compensation in relation to prompt genetically modified technology related damage.
- Encourage and implement public research into applications of genetically modified technology.
- World Trade Organization rules should: (i) be amended to allow governments to restrict imports and/or allow mandatory labelling of genetically modified seeds and foods; (ii) transformed to allow countries to decide their intellectual property regimes; (iii) exclude privatization of traditional crop varieties and their genetic characteristics.
- Patents on living organisms should be: (i) reviewed with emphasis on the potential impact on human life and the environment; (ii) revised to exclude products and processes and should be in the public domain.

- More emphasis should be placed on food security in which everyone has access to sufficient quantities of good quality food at all times. More financial resources should be put into agriculture in India rather than relying heavily on food imports from foreign countries.

Implications of Study

The present study has revealed that the majority of respondent/consumers are unaware that there exist genetically modified foods in India and moreover that these foods are consumed unknowingly to both consumers and local suppliers. The consumption of these foods would have been different (that is, less or not consumed at all) if consumers had known that they were genetically modified or contained genetically modified ingredients. Common medical ailments claimed by most consumers included allergic reactions in the form of skin rashes, shortness of breath, respiratory problems, increased susceptibility to infections. Nevertheless, these medical claims should not be taken lightly in light of what is known about genetically modified foods and the known health effects such as allergic reactions, immune suppression. The results of the study suggest that measures need to be put in place in order to provide safeguards against real or hypothetical risks posed by genetically modified foods. Some of these measures include: (i) rigorous pre-market assessment of safety; (ii) research to improve understanding of the science of genetic modification of foods; (iii) health surveillance to provide reassurance against any unexpected adverse affects on health; (iv) collaborating and networking with international agencies and organizations on the latest updates on genetically modified foods.

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Antecedents of Dietary Regulation

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Abstract

Achieving and maintaining good health is a goal of many individuals. With the recent increase in lifestyle related diseases, the importance of healthy eating in maintaining overall health has assumed great significance. A healthy diet helps protect against malnutrition in all its forms, as well as non-communicable diseases, including diabetes, heart disease, stroke and cancer. An individual's eating habits over a period of time can have an impact on overall health. In order to achieve good health, regulation of eating habits (Dietary regulation) plays a significant role. This paper examines the association of selected antecedents that are posited to be associated with Dietary regulation. The factors that have been considered in this study are Hardiness of an individual, Future time orientation, and Cultural conditioning... The study provides a base for justifying a directional relationship between these factors, and Dietary regulation. The strength of these associations can then be examined. It appears that personality factors play a significant role in achieving behavioural changes. However, health behaviour can be affected by both-internal, as well as external sources of influence. In India, culture is posited to be a strong external influence, particularly on eating habits. Literature review reveals that the theories related to behaviour justify the inclusion of these factors as constructs for the study. An exploratory study was conducted, aimed at understanding perception and attitudes towards dietary regulation. The results of the study indicate the factors which can be associated with Dietary regulation.

Keywords: Self-regulation, Hardiness, Time orientation, Healthy eating

Introduction-

Applications of theories of health behavior have tended to assume adequate knowledge of health risks. Although knowledge creates the precondition for change in a person's behaviour, additional self influences are needed to overcome the impediments to adopting new lifestyle habits. A person's perception of need to perform behaviour is likely to underlie strength and commitment to

implementing their intentions (Paisley & Sparks, 1998; Payne, Jones, & Harris, 2004). Planning behaviour is often considered in conjunction with other self-regulatory activities, notably self-monitoring (Linde et al., 2006). Once new behaviours have been initiated they must be scrutinised to determine whether they are contributing to eventual goal attainment and if not, new strategies are needed to assist in the goal striving process. According to Bagozzi (1992), this evaluation process will contribute to determining future effort and commitment in the pursuit of a goal. Scholz et al. (2009) found that change in behaviour was associated with change in action planning and action control over and above the effects of intentions.

Objective

This paper aims to examine the relationship of Dietary regulation with its antecedents. It is proposed that Hardiness, Future Time orientation and Cultural conditioning of an individual will be related with Dietary regulation.

Methodology-

This paper follows a methodology of Literature Review and Exploratory Unstructured Interviews with Open Ended Instrument (Annexure 1). The findings of interviews are corroborated with literature review to propose a model for further testing.

Literature Review

Social cognitive theory of Self Regulation (Bandura, 1991)

Bandura (1991) explains that self-regulation is a system of conscious personal management that involves the process of guiding one's own thoughts, behaviour, and feelings toward a particular goal. Most human behaviour being purposive is regulated by forethought. People motivate themselves and guide their actions in an anticipatory proactive way.

In the exercise of self connectedness, people adopt certain standards of behaviour that serve as guides and motivators to regulate actions anticipatorily through self reactive influence. Human functioning is, therefore regulated by interplay of self generated and external sources of influence, as opined by Bandura (1991).

The operation of self regulation is further detailed by him to include a set of psychological sub functions that must be developed and mobilized for self directed change. The constituent

sub functions in the exercise of self regulation through self reactive influence are self observation, judgement process and self reaction.

Other authors have contributed to expounding the concept (Zimmerman, 2000). Scholz et al. (2009) found that change in behaviour was significantly associated with self-regulation activities including dietary planning and self-monitoring. A dual strategy of targeting behaviour and the underlying habits may be effective in improving dietary intake and self-regulation is likely to be sustainable only in an environment that facilitates healthy eating behaviour (Naughton et. al, 2015). Sniehotta et. al, (2005) consider action control to be a means of self-regulation that incorporates self-monitoring, awareness of standards, and effort.

In this study, dietary regulation is the central construct. The Social cognitive theory of self regulation helps to understand how individuals set different goals for themselves with respect to their eating habits. **The operational definition conceived from this theory is that self-regulation is a system of conscious personal management that involves the process of guiding one's own thoughts, behaviour, and feelings toward healthy eating.** The sub functions in the exercise of self regulation include self observation, judgement process, and self reaction.

Self Determination theory stated below on the other hand helps in determination of antecedents of the dietary self regulation construct.

Self-Determination Theory

According to Ryan & Deci, (2000), the regulation of a behavior can take many forms that correspond to different behavioral regulatory styles. These behavioral regulatory styles can be differentiated according to their level of self-determination. The different behavioral styles of regulation are associated with one of the three basic types of motivation: intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation, and amotivation.

Intrinsically motivated behaviors are engaged in for their own sake; for the pleasure, the interest, and the satisfaction derived from participation itself. They are performed voluntarily in the absence of material rewards or external constraints (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Performing the activity thus becomes an end in itself.

Because intrinsic motivation underlies regulation of behaviors that are freely initiated

and performed for the pleasure inherent to the activity itself, it represents the highest level of self-determination on the continuum.

Extrinsic motivation pertains to a variety of behaviors that are engaged in as a means to an end and not for their own sake. The activity is performed to prompt agreeable consequences or to avoid disagreeable ones (Deci, 1975). It was originally thought that extrinsic motivation exclusively referred to non-self-determined behaviors associated with external contingencies. Deci and Ryan (1985) have proposed that there are different types of extrinsic motivation that vary to the extent the regulation of behavior is perceived as constrained by external sources or as freely chosen by the individual. These types of extrinsic motivation (external regulation, introjected regulation, identified regulation, and integrated regulation) can be ordered along a self-determined continuum.

Amotivation refers to a state where individuals fail to perceive contingencies between their actions and the outcomes of their actions. Thus, amotivated individuals are not able to foresee the consequences of their behavior. They have a pervasive sense that their behavior are caused by external forces beyond their control. They experience feelings of incompetence and lack of control (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Individuals who once had good reasons for regulating their eating behaviors, but now wonder whether they should continue are said to be amotivated.

Amotivated individuals may not be able to foresee the consequences of their behaviour, and hence, this may act as a barrier for dietary regulation. Whereas intrinsically motivated individuals may show traits like hardiness which could play a role in dietary self regulation. Similarly, extrinsically motivated individuals could display future time orientation based on situational impulses that could also lead to dietary self regulation.

Hardiness

Hardiness is a combination of attitudes that provide the courage and **motivation** to do the hard, strategic work of turning stressful circumstances from potential disasters into growth opportunities (Maddi, 2006)

Hardiness has been conceptualized as a combination of the three attitudes (3Cs) of commitment, control, and challenge (Kobasa, 1979; Maddi & Kobasa, 1984).

If you are strong in the C of challenge, you accept that life is by its nature stressful, and see those stressful changes as an opportunity to grow in wisdom and capability by what you learn through

trying to turn them to your advantage. Another C of hardy attitudes is commitment, which involves the belief that no matter how bad things get, it is important to stay involved with whatever is happening, rather than sink into detachment and alienation.

And the third C of hardiness is control, which leads you to believe that no matter how bad things get, you need to keep trying to turn the stresses from potential disasters into growth opportunities. Persons high in hardiness involve themselves in whatever they are doing (commitment), believe and act as if they can influence the events forming their lives (control), and consider change to be not only normal but also a stimulus to development (challenge). (Kobasa et al., 1983)

In the context of dietary regulation, the three attitudes which comprise hardiness, may provide the stimulus and determination that is required for the effort of turning around an unhealthy habit. These attitudes promote progressive (health enhancing) eating habits, and suppress regressive (health detrimental) eating habits. In terms of dietary regulation, a hardy individual will be able to (1) identify a situation where one is eating unhealthy, (2) develop strategies to learn from these situations in terms of coping, or looking for healthy alternatives, and (3) persevere through a dietary plan till the health goal is achieved.

Time Perspective Theory (Zimbardo, 1999)

Time perspective is the totality of an individual's views of his psychological future and psychological past existing at a given time (Lewin, 1951)

At decision time for major or minor judgments, some individuals are totally influenced by factors in the **immediate situation**: The stimulus qualities, what others are doing, saying, urging, and one's biological urges. Others facing the same decision matrix ignore all those present qualities by focusing instead on the **past**, the similarities between current and prior settings, remembering what was done and its effects. Finally, a third set of decision makers ignores the present and the past by focusing primarily on the **future consequences** of current actions, calculating costs vs. gains. The future time perspective manifests itself in many different ways. People form beliefs about what they can do, they anticipate the likely consequences of prospective actions, they set goals for themselves, and they otherwise plan courses of action that are likely to produce desired outcomes through exercise of forethought.

The perception of time plays a fundamental role in the selection and pursuit of goals, with important implications for emotion, cognition, and motivation (Carstensen et al, 1999).

Future Time orientation

Time orientation for this study, refers to how an outcome relatively to present outcomes with respect to eating habits. Future-oriented thinking could be conducive to a healthier lifestyle. Adopting a healthy lifestyle poses a conflict between the short-term and long-term benefits of a person's actions (Joireman et al. 2012). Present oriented individuals tend to focus on the immediate consequences of their behavior, whereas future-oriented individuals give more importance to the future consequences, even if there are immediate costs (Strathman et al., 1994). Shifting the temporal focus away from immediate benefits toward the future outcomes seems necessary in order to make healthy choices (Hall & Fong, 2007). Given their intertemporal nature, one factor that predicts health behaviors is an individual's CFC i.e., the extent to which people consider the potential distant outcomes of their current behaviors and are influenced by those potential outcomes. (Strathman, Gleicher, Boninger, & Edwards, 1994). CFC-future captures concern with future consequences (e.g., achieving future outcomes), whereas CFC-immediate captures concern with immediate consequences (e.g., satisfying immediate concerns). It should be noted, however, that CFC-future and CFC-immediate are not necessarily negatively correlated.

Therefore, individuals who are future oriented would engage in dietary regulation behaviours which show results over a period of many years. They believe that maintaining healthy eating behaviours would result in longevity and better health in their senior years. Their daily eating habits are maintained keeping in mind the long-term impact of those habits on their future health. They would be able to forgo foods which are tempting, in order to achieve a positive result in the long term. The above-mentioned factors are considered to be individual traits which impact dietary regulation. Apart from these, there are normative factors which can also impact dietary regulation. In the Indian context, cultural conditioning would be considered to be part of normative influences.

Cultural conditioning

Culture is the collective programming of the mind which distinguishes the members of one group or category of people from another. (Hofstede 1994). Culture represents influences that are imposed on the consumer by surroundings. Cultural factors come from the various components related to cultural environment from which the consumer belongs. Culture is the beliefs of human societies, their roles, their behaviour, their values, customs and traditions (Durmaz et.al 2011). Culture is a powerful force in regulating human behavior (Schiffman and Kanuk 1997).

Indian food is different from rest of the world not only in taste but also in cooking methods. It reflects a perfect blend of various cultures and ages. Just like Indian culture, food in India has also been influenced by various civilizations, which have contributed their share in its overall development and the present form. Food diversity in India is an implicit characteristic of India's diversified culture consisting of different regions and states within. Foods of India are better known for its spiciness. Throughout India, be it North India or South India, spices are used generously in food. But one must not forget that every single spice used in Indian dishes carries some or the other nutritional as well as medicinal properties.

In the context of this study, cultural conditioning refers to the influence of cultural values on preferences/attitudes towards dietary regulation. (Vyas, 2014)

Given different settings, cultural diversity could be seen as a threat, or an opportunity. Hirshman (1986) predicted a preference for culturally conditioned stimuli over other options, even if it is not the best available alternative. Consistent with this, Veeck and Burns (2005) observed that some time-poor consumers continue to prefer using fresh produce over processed food when cooking because they associate fresh ingredients with the tradition of cooking, as well as the maintenance of important social relationships, both of which are central elements of the Chinese culture. Hence, the preference for fresh produce remains strong despite the convenience of processed food.

Given that there exists a wide variety of culturally influenced food preferences, there may be difference in the way individuals regulate their eating habits. While a person who is predominantly non vegetarian would have more access to foods that are rich in protein, those who eat vegetarian food may have the advantage of a diet that results in lower cholesterol, and lesser risk of heart disease. There are practices of fasting in different cultures, some of which include staying away from non vegetarian food, abstaining from fatty foods, not consuming sugary foods, maintaining

one or more days of the week as vegetarian, or abstaining from smoking. These practices may help an individual regulate their eating habits over a period of time. Conversely, there may be a reverse effect of binge eating after the fasting period. The impact of these cultural influences on dietary regulation deserves attention. How strongly a person remains rooted to cultural traditions in terms of eating habits, may decide the extent of dietary regulation that he/she is able to achieve.

In order to corroborate the above derivations from literature, an exploratory study covering interpretations of eating in the context of dietary regulation was conducted.

Method

The exploratory study used a semi structured interview with participants, to interpret their perception of dietary regulation, and understand ways in which it can get affected by factors such as those indicated in literature. This would help to guide the study further, and reinforce the rationale for the study. Participants were encouraged to speak about their eating habits in detail, and elucidate their views on dietary regulation. Convenience sampling was used to get responses for the exploratory study.

Sample

30 participants were interviewed for this study. Attempt was made to include people from different walks of life, and different life stages, to understand varied perceptions about dietary regulation. Among the participants who responded were doctors, chefs, teachers, business owners, homemakers, managers, clerical staff, office assistants, housemaids, senior citizens, members of joint and nuclear families and students.

Discussion

The following is the interpretation of responses from exploratory study in terms of operational constructs

Hardiness

One respondent said “I do not depend on others for obtaining food” This is indicative of the respondents’ belief in their own skills/ ability to prepare healthy food for themselves. Those who appeared confident in terms of maintaining healthy eating habits either know to cook, or are able to source a healthy meal for themselves, whenever the need arises.

Another respondent said “I feel confident, because my efforts over the past few months have resulted in lowering acidity and gastric problems. I feel I have a long way to go”. This could mean that the person acknowledges that there is a positive outcome of his effort, yet feels that he needs to continue the effort to reach a health goal.

One of the respondents mentioned “I am tempted to frequently buy baked foods which are high in sugar, and unhealthy”, because he is located close to a bakery. It is posited that situations like this require control in terms of resisting easily available, yet unhealthy foods. Another respondent said “I have an interest in healthy eating, desire for improved health, weight management, better self esteem, attractiveness; I am motivated to eat healthy.” This points to the component of commitment in Hardiness, which is also a characteristic of intrinsically motivated individuals.

Difficulty in giving up certain foods, giving up aerated drinks and sugar were termed as “a huge step towards a healthy diet”, indicating that there is some amount of challenge, which is a component of Hardiness. In our view, hardy individuals will view the change to a healthy diet in a positive way, and look forward to the challenge of change.

Time orientation:

An individual’s concern of eating habits and its long-term consequences might be the reason for monitoring their own eating behaviour. The following response

“If we eat healthy now, we will live better in old age.”

indicates that the food that one eats, can result in longevity, and help in avoiding diseases. There are some who feel that “lifestyle diseases can be avoided by consistently maintaining healthy eating habits”. On the other hand, individuals who have well established habits (which may not be in line with their health goals), may find difficulty in adapting to situations that warrant changes in routine eating habits.

Cultural factors

It appears that habits developed during childhood and adolescent years sustain until adulthood. This is particularly true of eating habits. Individuals, who perceive these habits as requiring change, will need to be resilient in order to make a change. A respondent who lives in a joint family mentioned

“Having someone cook nutritious food for me is a major advantage, so I don’t have to eat food outside which can be unhealthy.”

The role of culture is potentially an advantage, particularly when the individual has access to healthy home cooked food. In Indian culture, often, there is an advantage of having a family member doing the cooking. The men of the household usually work, whereas the women perform the role of homemaker, providing home cooked meals. However, this tradition is undergoing a change. With more families having both the husband and the wife working, it remains to be seen how families adapt to changing scenarios like this. Those individuals who have a traditional mindset, in terms of following cultural norms, may not easily get affected by western habits of eating fast food. One respondent mentioned

“When socialising, particularly during festivals, there is a temptation to eat more of unhealthy foods”

Some respondents indicated that they have challenges in controlling their eating habits due to socialising (frequently), and also during the festive season. Preparing and consuming sweets during the festive season is part of Indian culture. This could indicate that an environment in which tempting food/ unhealthy food is available can impact self regulation. Literature also indicates that obesogenic environments (places frequently visited, where healthy food is not available) to which an individual is frequently exposed, are a barrier to sustain healthy eating behaviour.

One participant mentioned that his parents are strictly vegetarian, and follow this eating pattern rigorously. She said, “I am not allowed to eat meat at home. If I want to, I make sure that I eat it outside, at a restaurant.”

In such cases, being restricted by cultural guidelines may “protect” an individual from eating foods that might be unhealthy. On the other hand, individuals from cultures that have no such restriction would be exposed to foods that potentially lead to weight gain.

Conclusion

The central construct of the study, namely, dietary regulation has its origin in the Social cognitive theory of Self Regulation (Bandura, 1991). The other constructs like hardiness and time orientation are derived from Self-Determination Theory and Time Perspective Theory respectively. Particularly in Indian context, it was deemed expedient to include the factor of cultural

conditioning as, culture plays a dominant role in behaviour of the people. The exploratory interviews reinforced the theoretical concepts.

This study posits that the Personality related traits of Hardiness and Time Orientation along with Cultural factors combine to impact the ability of an individual to regulate eating habits. The factors, on which the study is focused, seem significant to warrant a further investigation. The findings of this study can be used along with theory based perspectives found in literature, to further investigate directional relationships and empirical testing between these constructs, after due operationalisation

The relationships posited in this study have led to a proposed model which is mentioned below:

Limitations of The Study

It may be noted, that respondents refrain from giving elaborations about eating behaviour when using the term ‘healthy eating’. Social desirability bias may exist when respondents perceive that they are being judged about their eating habits. Self reporting of eating habits may therefore not always be accurate.

Future Research

The relationships derived from this model, would need empirical testing, to prove its validity in a larger sample. As part of future research, there may be more antecedents relating to dietary regulation which may be unearthed.

Implications

The study can help to understand the antecedents of dietary regulation, thereby motivating people to focus their efforts in right direction to achieve the goal of healthy eating.

Annexure 1

- Objective of the exploratory study on Eating behaviour:
- To analyse perception about Dietary regulation, and evaluate responses that will indicate reasons for the respondents' opinions about obtaining food, eating and maintaining dietary regulation

Questions

1. Describe your eating habits. How do you obtain your food?
Meal setting, timing, perception of current eating habits, resources
2. According to you, what is healthy eating?
Perception of healthy eating, examples of foods eaten
- 4- Is eating healthy important to you? why?
Perceived importance
- 5- What kind of foods do you eat frequently? What makes you feel that these foods are healthy/ not healthy?
Frequency of foods eaten, perceived relation to healthy eating
- 6- Would you want to change / not change the current eating habits that you follow? How? and why?
Perception of current state, need for change, reasons
- 7- What kind of foods would you like to eat more frequently? How would you do that?
Perceived ideal state, implementation intentions, plan of action
Perceived self efficacy
- 8- What helps/hinders you to maintain/follow/avoid a healthy eating pattern?
Enablers/ barriers to healthy eating
- 9- If Why do you feel/not feel confident about sustaining/changing healthy eating habits?
- 10- you want to eat healthy, would you depend on someone to provide you healthy food? Why?
Support, resources for plan of action
- 11- What do you enjoy / not enjoy about eating healthy food?
Attitude towards healthy food

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Food Heritage of Haryana: An Effective Tool for Tourism Growth

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Abstract

Food is considered as an important cultural marker of identities and societies as it has provided a medium for the understanding of social relations, family and kinship, class and consumption, gender ideology and cultural symbolism. Nations across the world are potpourri of culture, traditions, people and heritage. Tourism has many facets and is revenue and employment generator in its each form. Food tourism is one of the budding niches of tourism where the exquisite food heritage of the nations around the world. Food heritage is not merely food, it is a fantastic way to connect to the culture, tradition and people of destination authenticity. The food heritage and culture of the destination contribute prominently into making a decision for choosing a particular destination by the tourists. This paper highlights the food heritage of Haryana as effective tool for purpose of growth and promotion of tourism. This study provides the suggestion and recommendation as a potential market segment on basis of food heritage.

Keywords: Food Heritage, Food Tourism, Haryana

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Introduction

Food was consumed to satisfy the basic biological need of human being and eat to sustain ourselves. It also reflects the culture of region, ingredient of raw materials available, cooking tradition, geographic of place, economic and social status etc. how, what, when and with whom we eat the food also vary from place to place, group to group and time to time. Food also impact on health, behaviour of people, environment of religion, securities, human relation, agricultural cultivation, culture of region etc. So that Food is the identities of the individuals and group of people. Our individuals taste of food extremely effect on emotion and experience, in culture sensation of food also binds the people together. Food culture has passed by one generation to another generation as a heritage of tradition. “Food should always be worshipped and taken with the utmost reverence. The sight of food should delight one's heart and fill itwith joy. It should always be cherished whatever the situation.”(Dvivedi, 1917)

Heritage denote the collection of patrimony of tangible and intangible good that a society inherits from past, preserve in the present and pass on the future. Political, economic and ideological goals play a linkage member role in heritage. Particular Heritage bring own value which claim by people or historian. In intangible cultural heritage is very difficult to preserved as compare to tangible heritage and food heritage is a part of intangible heritage. Heritage refer to characteristics and practices of past, preserved for future. It can be defined as to hand down from the past as a tradition and feature belonging to particular society culture, such as tradition, languages and buildings created in past (“Cambridge Dictionary,” 2017). Heritage help in understanding of past, present and future resource of world and identity. Heritage is defined according to social conception, as a resource for collective action rooted in local distinctive identities (Baêta Neves Flores, 1995). All the component of heritage, can be tangible (e.g. monuments, buildings, object, artwork pieces, railway stations) and intangible (e.g. belief, flavors, sound, tradition, taste) considered as identity (Bessière, 1998). Food stands out as an important identity factor in a society and could therefore be considered an Immaterial Cultural Heritage. According to United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), this can be defined as a manifestation of the intangible portion of the cultural inheritance of a people, including traditions, folklore, language, festivals and other manifestations, citing gastronomy as part of this heritage.

A country like India is blessed with a rich food heritage ranging from Starters to Main Course and Desserts including Beverages. Over the years, India has emerged as a favoured destination for the tourism, hospitality and Food Lovers. Various hotel groups both national and international are investing into the Indian hotel and Food Industry, with the boom in economy and elevated life standards India is the market for multinational companies. Even foreign eateries are offering customized delicate with Indian twist. Now food tourists are patronizing India as well. However, Indian food heritage has been to a great extent passed on as an art from generations to others. Although some documentation in terms of food heritage is documented in Indian History which is dedicated to the Royal Palaces and Highness Culinary delights. The modern cookery has been documented by Thangam E Phillip and Modern India chefs, Culinary Writers like Manjit Gill, Sanjeev Kapoor, Rakesh Sethi, Sudhir Sibbal, Krishna Arora and others have showcased the Indian culinary heritage via books, media, television shows and websites. Yet much is needed to be done in this sector.

Food Heritage and Tourism

The national identity of the people is defined as much as by their local food and costume, language and literature, arts and artifacts. Local food is governed by taste, as a taste reflects the intrinsic temperament and acquired preferences. The preference of taste also attracts to people for travelling one place to another place, so it's an essential source of tourism. Today scenario more tourist is travelling for the purpose of food-related reason (Hall & Sharples, 2003; Long, 2004). Through local food tourist recognised the importance of food and its influence on generating satisfaction and destination experience (Wolf, 2006). Due to biological need of human, tourist must eat and play an important role as an attribute of destination. As attributable of food, a tourist spends more than 25% of tourism expenditure (Correia, Moital, Da Costa, & Peres, 2008).

As a food culture, it provides a medium for the expression of local culture. As such food are the base to build the image of the destination and also stimulates the local economy through local food purchased by tourist (Richards, 2002). Food culture also present through food related event, these events provide the opportunity to regional people to express the regional food and that is increasing in recent year (Getz, 1997). If regional people encourage the tourist to participation in regional food it also enhances the destination experience (Renko, Renko, & Polonijo, 2010). So that local food also contributes to increase the sustainability of tourism, local economy, authenticity of destination and provide the healthy environment to the tourist (G. Du Rand, Heath, & Alberts, 2003).

Many study shows the relationship between Food and Tourism. The following table showing the relationship between dimension of food and tourism.

Author Name	Food Dimension	Relation	Tourism Dimension
(Bessière, 1998)	Traditional Food and Cuisine	Attract to	Tourist in Rural Area
Nield Kozak & Le Gys g 2000	Food Service	Play a Role	Tourist Satisfaction
(MacLaurin, 2001)	Food Safety	Association with	Travel and Tourism
(Telfer, 2001)	Food Production	Linkage	Tourism

(G. Du Rand et al., 2003)	Local and Regional Food	Significant role	Destination Marketing
(Frochot, 2003)	Food Image	Associated with	Regional Position
(Andersson & Mossberg, 2004)	Dining experience	Impact on	Tourist Satisfaction
(G. Brown & Getz, 2005)	Wine preference	Linkage to	Wine Tourism Destination
(Che, 2006)	Culinary Heritage	Branding the	Agritourism
(Pendergast, 2006)	Food Safety and Hygiene	Reaction	Tourist gut
(Tellström, Gustafsson, & Mossberg, 2006)	Food Culture	Branding Relationship	Heritage Tourism
(G. P. Brown, Havitz, & Getz, 2007)	Wine involvement	Relationship Between	Wine related Tourism
(G. E. du Rand & Heath, 2006)	Local food	As an Element part	Sustainable Tourism
(Kivela & Crofts, 2009)	Gastronomy	Influence on	Tourist Experience
(Ab Karim et al., 2010)	Food Image	As an Attraction	Culinary Tourism
(Y. H. Kim, Goh, & Yuan, 2010)	Food Event and Festival	Relationship with	Tourist personality traits
(Chang & Yuan, 2011)	Food Festival	Motivate to	Taste of Tourism
(Lin, Pearson, & Cai, 2011)	Food	As identity	Destination
(Everett & Slocum, 2012)	Food Production Place	Linkage to	Food Tourism
(Timothy & Ron, 2013)	Cuisine Heritage	Relationship	Sustainable Tourism

Above previous studies indicated that varieties or form or dimension of tourism exist around the food either as primary or secondary motivation.

Food Tourism also associated and impact on various dimensions and source of tourism (e.g. tourism suppliers, destination, culture etc.). For motivation of tourist also differ as comparison to

general event and food related event, due to personal traits of traveller in food event and food consuming experience also differ (S. S. Kim, Choi, Agrusa, Wang, & Kim, 2010). During travelling, the appreciation of local food is a significant motivation factor for food tourist and some other pull factor are food history, food tradition and culture, rural territory and traditional dishes (Mason & Paggiaro, 2009).

In UNWTO report on food Tourism (2012) highlight the importance and recommendation of food tourism as a growing segment of tourism. UNWTO affiliate member described the association between food and tourism and also provide insight into traditional economy sector of tourism. Hence, Rural communities get opportunities, generate income and provide the job in local food related industry (agriculture, local chef, local food provider etc.) through food tourism. So that food is deeply connected with regional destination and these destinations should focus on marketing the local unique food identity for purpose of attracting food tourist. This report also proposed the case study on food tourism, in which explore the food tourism experience of regional destinations and business origination.

Quan & Wang, (2004) identify that food related event is one source of enhance the regional communities and during travelling tourist spent one third of the total budget of trip. American culinary traveller also identifies that the increasing of 11% unique dining experience during 2006 to 2013. These events build the regional loyalty for attracting the more tourist and increase the local economy sector (Yuan, Morrison, Linton, Feng, & Jeon, 2004). Many studies highlighted that food as a main component or strong effect on revisit, repurchasing local product, re-use the service for future intention on the basis of satisfaction and perceived values (Barsky & Labagh, 1992; Choi & Chu, 2001; Petrick & Backman, 2002; Yoon & Uysal, 2005). Sims, (2009) conducted a study on association benefits of offering local food experience to visitor boost the sustainability of rural regions. Local food may be a close relationship with tourism experience (Clark & Chabrel, 2007). Indeed, food tourism also have great potential or opportunities for export the regional food to visitor's place. Food Tourism does not mean that visit any food place like restaurant or hotel, as far as experience the specific local food or authentic dishes.

On the basis of above review, there are some important aspect of food heritage should be used as an effective tool for Tourism growth

- Food as a symbol of identity and authenticity
- Food as a sign of communication in social activity
- Food as a sign of exchanging experiences
- Food heritage also carry the regional loyalty
- Food is the basic needs of tourist during travelling
- Food heritage can be available round of the year
- Food is heavy connectivity between economic, social, psychological and political empowerment (Scheyvens, 1999)

So, food heritage also an effective tool for building nationalism, collective social identities and contribute to more sustainable tourist destinations.

Potential of Food Heritage in Haryana

Haryana has been symbolized as “Desa me des Haryana, Jit doodh-dahi ka Khana” . In this context, people living in Haryana people were in the habit of consuming the cereals which contained largely the coarse grains that included millet, barley, wheat and maize. Since agriculture was the main stay of the people in Haryana, besides coarse grain they were also known to be pastoral group and had learnt to use the milk of cow, buffalo, camel, goat etc. This is the reason why the diet of the people consumed in Haryana was considered lactovegetarian. It meant the coarse grain and milk products were consumed and relished. The village people attached special importance to coarse grain food consumed by them. The food consumed is depicted in folk songs, folk culture and traditional art form of the people in this part of region. So far as culture of the people in Haryana is concerned it was basically the folk culture which contained details about the different food items consumed in various cultural regions of Haryana and festival, which dominated the life of the people. For example, the haryaliteej is considered the main festival of the month locally known as sravan. This is the time when monsoon sets in. There is a great competition on the part of people when they celebrate this occasion with all fun and enthusiasm. It also provides a great occasion for preparing sweetmeat which have special significance for them. For example, in the month sravan itself, swalhi is prepared which is part of sweet bread and gulguley which is part of deep fry sweet pakora preparation. Numbers of such food items constitute the basic sweetmeat consumed by the people all over the Haryana. Since the month of Saaman that is July and August

is associated with rainy season therefore people who largely depend upon agriculture find food to be an occasion of creating delight for them.

Haryana also represents cultural diversity and therefore, ethnic groups which go to constitute the basic social structure of Haryana include groups such as ahir, jat, gujjar and rajput. All these communities which form part of social structure are known with an acronym known as “vtxj”(Prasad & Dahiya, 2016). All these four ethnic groups, were primarily agriculturists. They still continue to depend upon agricultural products for meeting their consumption requirements. Traditionally they were the major land holding groups. The ethnic groups such as Punjabi who came to stay in Haryana after independence also began to relish food items consumed by the native people.

It was in 1947 that our country witnessed, large scale settlement of Punjabi migrant in North West region of India. In Haryana also, there are several districts where Punjabi refugee were made to settle. There are camp areas in Rohtak, Bahdurgarh, Ambala, Yamunanagar, Karnal, where large segments of Punjabi refugees were rehabilitated. They settled in camp area and introduced food and related culinary skill which had large acceptance. The tandoori roti, leafy vegetables, pulses, were some of the special dish that they ate, which were not consumed by native people. Thus, the demographic composition of the society in Haryana has become quite heterogeneous in nature as a result of which the people living in Haryana have come across with people belonging to different culture having distinct food items. Thus, the new food items brought by migrant people were not earlier part of the basic dietary habits of native people. It is this diversity of culture that also formed part of people living in Haryana today. Haryana cultural heritage is coming up as an attraction of travel destination due to nearness to Delhi. According to Haryana census 2011 state has 19% growth rate and 76% literacy rate. In major part Haryana, people lives in rural areas (65.12%) and are Hindus (87.46%) with 879 sex ratios. In Haryana, 53.67% house are in good condition and 41.89% are in livable condition.

Haryana offers delicious cuisines as it cannot be anticipated from the tourist to carry their food. The traditional cuisine of Haryana welcomes the folks. The inhabitants of this state drink well and eat well. Mostly the population of Haryana are vegetarians. The Haryanvi food as it is called has a very special attachment with the land. The eater relishes his food without any fuss. The food has evolved from the culture. The food is simple as their civilisation. People make ghee and major

chunking use of ghee can be found in the cuisine of Haryana. The butter which is made at home is known as moony or tindi in Haryana. Haryana Thandai is the local delight which is a sweet drink made from milk.

In any country, culinary art never be constant and Indian culinary art also develop continually. Day by day Haryanvi people also aware and influence by Indian and international culinary art. For Increasing food awareness credit goes to published culinary books, television culinary shows, famous TV shows and Restaurant or fast food. In Haryana, medial society trend for having food outside the home also increasing rapidly. However, these new tradition means, flake off the old tradition. Traditionally Haryanvi people food depend on their religion, life cycle stage, city or area, cast and social identity, family tradition, health anxiety and spiritual inexhaustible faith. Harynavi people diet is simple and lacks of varities. It consists of three meals. The morning meals comprises of lassies and rotis. Rotis made from wheat flour and gram flour in canal area, Bareley and gram flour in the bangar area and maize flour rotis is used in the Kadar area.

In Lunch menu includes rotis and one dish of vegetable or pulses or Kari (prepared from gram flour). In evening meal varies according to season. Milk and roti (Made from wheat, maize and barley) along with raabdi are taken in summer. Raabdi is a special dish of area prepared by fermenting flour in butter milk before cooking it. Dalia (porridge of broken wheat) is eaten in the raining season, and Khichri (porridge of bajra and moth or moong or chino dal) in winter. The use of vegetable oil instead of ghee, for cooking purpose has become very common.

Before the partition there were no eating houses even in the bigger towns of Haryana. Parsimonious villager used to bring his sattu, parched gram and roti with him on his visit to town unless he had friends in whose houses he could eat. Since the influx of displaced persons dhabas, hotel and restaurant have sprung up and become quite popular. Haryanvi people who had served in the army ate meat and took strong drink, bur since 1947 butchers' shops have sprung up in towns to meet demand for non-vegetarian food on the part of young villagers who have begun to eat in dhabas on their visit to town.

Tourism department of Haryana and Haryana Tourism Corporation Limited are the main body in the state which regulates tourism in Haryana. The main objective of the tourism department is to develop tourism infrastructure in the state. Whereas the corporation has the responsibility of running and maintaining commercial as well as the non-commercial units such as: restaurants,

motels, petrol pumps, rest houses etc. According to the Ministry of Tourism Report (MOT) 2014, Haryana has witnessed a growth of 88.59% in domestic tourist's arrivals in Haryana. It has also witnessed 88.59% steep rise in foreign tourist arrivals in state. Due to its direct positive impact on the economy Haryana government has declared tourism as an industry in June 2016. Every occasion (festival, fair, family function, arrival of new season etc.) in the life to share good/special food with in family, friends and relative is an old tradition. There are various fairs promoted by Haryana Tourism such as Suraj Kund Craft mela (1-15 February) every year. This is one of the largest craft fairs in the world. Mango mela till 2017, 26 mango melas have been conducted by Haryana Tourism Corporation. It not only promotes varieties of mango fruit but also food courts, crafts, folk and culture performances with provisions to encourage farmers to adopt latest technologies. Also, Pinjore Heritage Festival is celebrated in december at Pinjore Gardens every year. In the month of Nov/Dec, Geeta Jayanti Samaroh is celebrated every year at Kurukshetra dedicated to SrimadBhagvad Gita. Haryana food also documented by Prof. Ashish Dahiya in which 56 types of Haryana dessert (Dahiya, 2013), 58 types of Haryanvi bread (Dahiya & Duggal, 2016) and 21 types of chutney (Dahiya, 2012) are available as a promotion of food heritage.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Food heritage have been an important part of culture heritage and that can be used as a tool for tourism growth. Cultural heritage is a destination image builder of india (Chand, 2012). This article highlights the various relationship between food heritage and tourism. It also provides the information on various aspect of Haryana food heritage. However, cuisine of Haryana has been constantly evolving under the influence of various visitor and invaders who come in India. So, Haryana have diversified culture have potential to attract the tourist or can use as an effective tool. Haryana must brand the identity of food heritage by organized various food related events. Recommendation for tourism department using food heritage of Haryana as a tool for tourism growth

- Start traditional or authentic cooking or tasting course
- Promote the local fine dining restaurant
- Organized various food related event or culinary event or food festival
- Use local food ingredients for food preparation for maintaining the identity
- Recognized the local regional food and provide the official heritage food label

- Provide the food information guide and map of existing food heritage location.
- Teach to the student the local food heritage as a curriculum of hotel management course.
- To create a proud or good feeling for their local food in the communities
- Promote and empower the local people for using or setup the local food service enterprise
- Initiate to start regional food show through media and regional food competition for young generation
- Appreciate and award should be given to the local culinary chef for the purpose of promotion of culinary professional

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Journey of Potato

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Abstract

Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), a very fond and popular food item because of its high nutrient content and easy cultivation. In India, Potato was introduced as an exotic food after 16th century, however cultivation of potato in South America may go back 10,000 years. It was one of the very sought-after food in Royal families and very easily became an important staple crop all over the world. The introduction and domestication are two different stories of potato. The first evidences of domestication of potato were found in the modern-day southern Peru and extreme northwestern Bolivia around 8000 years ago. Potato was one of the main reasons of economic development during the Industrial Revolution of the 19th century in Britain as it served as the cheapest source of calories and nutrients for urban workers. This paper deals with the facts of potato as an exotic delicacy which is now even used for microbial growth cultures as there are a number of microorganisms (fungus and bacteria) that thrive on the nutrients found in potato. The arrival, domestication and establishment as the King of vegetables is the fact of nourishment provided by potato.

Keywords- Potato, domestication, staple, delicacy, microbial growth culture and nutritional values

Introduction and Background of Study

Potatoes are a boon from mountains. Andes, in Peru were the first lands where cultivation of potatoes are marked. Incas, an Indian native community are supposed to grow this tuber species in western temperate climates in 8000-5000BC. Potato is most widely used vegetable and world's fourth largest food crop, following rice, wheat and maize.

Introduction in Spain

During 1537-38 the Spanish Conquistadors and historian Pedro de Cieza de Leon, in the Canca Valley of Colombia, introduced Potato to new world. This tuber soon found its recognition in a book, "Chronicles of Peru" published in 1540, written by Pedro de Cieza de Leon. 'Potato' got its name in 1564 by French Botanist, CarolusClusius while he was describing rare plants. Evidences

also say that Carolus Clusius received tubers from Phillippe de Sivery of Belgium. He also holds the credit to introduce them in Germany and France in 1588 (1).

Potato gained more importance as a food for sick people for it being easily digestible and rich in nutrients such as vitamin C in Seville in 1573(1). Introduction of potatoes in Spain was two ways: one from Peru and other from England side. Sir Walter Raleigh introduced potatoes to Ireland in 1589 on 40,000 acres of land near Cork (1).

Potato in Industrial Revolution

Potato gained interest of people for its nutritional values. In Europe, it was popular for three reasons; being cheap, its bulk to satisfy hunger and less spoilage. All these were good for poor people or the laborious people who served as good workers in industries. Potatoes served 10% of the total caloric requirement of Europeans.

The industrial Revolution of 19th century in Britain was indirectly promoted by Potato consumption. The reasons being same as Europeans. Marxist Friedrich Engels even declared that the potato was the equal of iron for its "historically revolutionary role". The Dutch potato-starch industry grew rapidly in the 19th century, especially under the leadership of entrepreneur Willem Albert Scholten (1819–92) (2,3,4)

Introduction in India

Potato was introduced in India by Europeans in 16th century. The food was new and good however its acceptance was reluctant and slow. According to Dr. T.K. Achaya, they were the Muslims in contact with Europeans who accepted them first. Gradually it percolated to Dutch and quite late to Hindus. They also did not have any qualms in accepting potato as a food in India. The mountains of Dehradun were the Indian Andes for potatoes.

As good as Money

Germany, Russia and Poland are the greatest potato producers in world. In 1897-98, Potato was traded in competence of Gold by migrating people from Yukon to North-West Canada, 'The Alaskan Klondike Gold Rush.'(5)

As a food for poor

The history of world wars also has mentioned potatoes to keep the people of Germany alive during wars. Among Irish people it was known as 'Breadroot' for feeding themselves. The dependency

on Potato as food could be measured by one example. Due to a disease in Potato, potato blight, caused by *Phytophthora infestans*, it was a condition like famine in Europe resulting in widespread disease death and emigrations.

As a King of Biodiversity

This demonization of a food forced Irish people to learn a lesson forever. Andes people grew almost dozens of species of it, and those of Ireland grew only a few species and biodiversity here marked its role. Many millions were killed and many sailed to America for this Monoculture. In India today's scenario is also matching growing a few variety. Andes had many species of them many were disease resistant also so there the food may never out.

Now Potato in India

Potato is a well-known name now in India. The Central Potato Research Institute at Shimla has a gremplasm bank of about 1200 varieties. Its Regional centers are also well-known institution in scientific world. India is a part of project Sequencing Genome of Potato.

Nutritional Values

Potato was always known for its good nutritional values and high number of vitamins. Robert Koch also proved this in his preliminary experiments with potato as a base for microbial growth. Though Potato is good in nutrition and easy to digest but it restricted growth of many microbes. A few of them however could grow and helped in microbial isolations. The present-day scientists also confirm their nutritional values, some are listed below (6).

Nutrition facts: Potatoes, boiled, with skin, peeled- 300 grams per serving

	Amount Per Serving
Total Carbohydrate	63.2g
Dietary Fibers	6.6g
Starch	51.6g
Sugars	3.5g

Table 1: Carbohydrates Found in Potatoes. Source: <http://nutritiondata.self.com>

	Amount Per Serving
Total Fat	0.4g
Saturated Fat	0.1g
Monounsaturated Fat	0.0g
Polyunsaturated Fat	0.2g
Total Trans Fatty Acids	~
Total Omega 3	38.9mg

Total Omega 6	129mg
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Table 2: Fats and Fatty Acids Found in Potatoes. Source: <http://nutritiondata.self.com>

	Amount Per Serving	Percent daily value
Vitamin A	29.9IU	1
Vitamin C	28.7mg	48
Vitamin D	~	~
Vitamin E	0.1mg	1
Vitamin K	6.0mcg	7
Vitamin B6	0.9mg	46
Vitamin B12	0.0mcg	0
Thiamin	0.2mg	13
Riboflavin	0.1mg	8
Folate	83.7mcg	21
Niacin	4.2mg	21
Pantothenic acid	1.2mg	11
Choline	44.2mg	
Betaine	0.6mg	
Protein	7.5	15

Table 3: Vitamins and Proteins Found in Potatoes. Source: <http://nutritiondata.self.com>

Table 4: Minerals Found in Potatoes. Source: <http://nutritiondata.self.com>

	Amount Per serving	Percent daily value
Calcium	44.8mg	4
Iron	3.2mg	18
Magnesium	83.7mg	21
Phosphorus	209mg	21
Potassium	1600mg	46
Sodium	29.9 mg	1
Zinc	1.1mg	7
Copper	0.4mg	18
Manganese	0.7mg	33
Selenium	1.2mcg	2
Fluoride	~	

	Amount Per Serving
Alcohol	0.0g
Water	224 g
Ash	4.0g
Caffeine	0.0mg
Theobromine	0.0mg

Table 5: Other Substances Found in Potatoes. Source: <http://nutritiondata.self.com>.

“Approximation’ indicates a missing or incomplete value. Percent daily values are for adults or children aged 4 or older, and are based on a 2,000-calorie reference diet.

Prime experiments of Robert Koch

Koch, a German physician and microbiologist was convinced that microbes caused some diseases. He was trying to isolate them for particular studies. He tried with the methods of dilution very common at that time. He succeeded in his experiments when he used potato as a solid medium. Koch used potato slices as a solid medium and observed that a boiled potato left in the open air would develop tiny circular raised spots. By examining those spots, he revealed that they were made up of single type of microorganism. A boiled potato remained sterile until it was kept in a sterile container with a lid. But if a sample from a disease animal was smeared across the potato, colonies arose, each being pure isolates from the animal. Testing these isolates in animals, Koch was able to isolate the cause of anthrax, *Bacillus anthracis* (7,8).

After this, various experiments and testing was done and now we are using potato in the form of Potato Dextrose Agar (PDA) for growing fungus and conducting various studies on them.

Material and Methods

- We took normal potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), readily available from market.
- Boiled in normal water
- Before incubation, the potatoes were mashed into smooth paste and 6 petri plates were prepared.
- The 6 petri plates were exposed to 6 different open areas of our university campus for 15 minutes.
- Petri plates were kept in incubator at 25°C for incubation.
- The final results were taken on day 5.

Results and Discussion

Location of petri plate	Petri plate	Growth on day 2	Growth on day 5	No. of species of fungus
Lab	A	Present	Present	3
Corridor	B	Present	Present	2
Office chamber	C	Absent	Present	2
Open garden	D	Absent	Present	3

Open garden	E	Present	Present	3
Open garden	F	Present	Present	3

Potato- Boiled and Mashed

Observing the petri plates and by morphological examining the growth obtained, we can say that the common fungus which are found to grow on the plates are Alternaria, Fusarium and Phytophthora Spp. Out of the six petri plates, fungal growth was seen on four plates on day 2 and on day 5, we clearly can see the fungal growth on all of the plates. Prominent growth was seen on the plates which were kept in open garden prior to incubation. This growth shows that potato has all the nutritional requirements for fungal growth.

Conclusion

The Journey of Potato which started from its introduction to the world has reached at the stage that it is now widely used for microbiological growth and studies in the form of PDA. Identification, cultivation and extraction of fungus is mainly done on this agar and in the future, its use will surely increase and it will help in identification of various microbiological agents for various studies on them.

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Food and Nourishment: Special Reference to old Age Group

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Abstract

Food has been given a very significant place in our lives because it is our primary requirement. It is our basic need because it is the source of mental and physical energy and nourishment. The food that we eat not only affects our body and the efficiency of our mind but directly affects our nature and habits also. The practice of nutrition for old age group is no longer limited to those who are frail, malnourished, and ill. They leave their actual diet due to various physical problems and discomfort. This study is a selection of analyzes of the conceptions of healthy nourishment of elderly persons attending. The age group displayed a conception of healthy nourishment related to growing old with as few limitations as possible, or in other words, with better health conditions, that allowed the possibility of a range of life experiences. The elderly persons considered healthy food to be “that which doesn’t make one ill”, as they understood that not all types of food were good for them, that the older body cannot withstand excess eating and that diseases result in dietary restrictions. There was a perception of the difference between body limitations (internal rule) and medical recommendations (external rule). At the same time, practicality was also a determinant in the eating habits of the elderly persons who, in keeping with the pace of modern life “did not have time to waste”. There was a consensus among the group that learning about nutrition was necessary in later life, in order to find a balance between scientific knowledge relating to a longer life, the demands of the modern world, the aging of the body and the pleasures of eating.

Key Word- Nourishment, Malnourished, Body Limitations, Health Conditions.

Introduction

Eating the right type of food is important for a healthy lifestyle. Generally, we select foods that we like in our daily meals. We do not think of the nutrients or their health benefits. Old age is not a disease but a biological process that no one can avoid. A little care and caution will prevent or

delay many disabilities. With proper care everyone can enjoy long, healthy ageing. As age advances, several chronic diseases affect our health. Many of these like obesity, hypertension and diabetes are diet related and hence can be controlled and even prevented by modifying our diet. The last section will help you to select the right type of foods to prevent and control such ailments (Colin, 2016).

Nutrition deserves special attention as people reach older age because good nutrition is essential for good health. Healthy ageing is associated with a number of physiological, cognitive, social and lifestyle changes that influence dietary intakes and nutritional status. Access to and consumption of healthy food for older people is influenced by the wider determinants of health. These determinants include cultural, social, historical and economic factors. A life course approach to ageing recognises that the effects of these determinants accumulate throughout the life span and have an impact on health. Because of this cumulative impact, interventions modifying the determinants of health are important at all stages of life (Ministry of Health. 2013).

Review of Literature

Successful aging is a multidimensional concept that is characterized by avoidance of disease and disability, maintenance of high levels of physical and cognitive functioning, and sustained engagement in social and productive activities (Rowe and Kahn 1997). Aging of an individual is influenced by genetic and environmental factors. It has been estimated that environmental factors may account for as much as 75% of the aging process (Ozaki et al. 2007, Steves et al. 2012, Mangino 2014). Good nutrition throughout the lifespan supports healthy aging (Mathers et al. 2013). Nutrition has multidimensional effects on cognition, mood, functional ability, and survival (Tolmunen et al. 2004, Morley et al. 2010, Anderson et al. 2011, Safouris et al. 2015). Good nutritional status and diet quality prevent cognitive decline, loss of muscle mass, frailty, and loss of functional ability (Morley et al. 2010, Bauer et al. 2013, Safouris et al. 2015). Nutrition is also important in preservation of normal immune functioning (Lesourd 2004). Essential macro- and micronutrients and trace elements are needed in maintaining the health of individuals and play crucial roles in both immune functioning (Lesourd 2004, Woods et al. 2013, Mocchegiani et al. 2014).

Health issues contributing to the development of malnutrition include oral and dental problems, difficulty in swallowing, gastrointestinal (GI) symptoms, conditions, diseases, and changing

nutritional requirements (Hickson 2006, Vuoristo 2010). In addition, metabolic disorders, cancer, infections, and many other diseases may contribute to malnutrition (Vuoristo 2010). Furthermore, unhealthy behaviors may restrict food choices, and alcohol abuse usually limits nutrient intake. Lack of knowledge of nutrition and healthy eating as well as old customs may result in unbalanced and poor-quality-diets. Physical inactivity may contribute to development of malnutrition and it further accelerates the loss of muscle (Bernstein et al. 2012, Bauer et al. 2013). Diseases, stress, and medications may increase energy and nutrient needs and at the same time reduce food intake. Inadequate or suboptimal intake of nutrients in older people is an important issue to address, because poor nutrient reserves accelerate the inflammation process that is associated with aging and diseases causing poor recovery from illness and increases mortality (Morley et al 2010). Protein and micronutrient malnutrition are associated with increased mortality and comorbidity, loss of muscle mass, depression, impaired immunity, skin problems, and poor cognition (McNaughton et al. 2012).

Objectives

There are some valuable objectives are listed below.

- Determine various nutrients and nutrition for old age group.
- The role of nutrients in maintaining health of old age group.
- To determine correlation between health and old age groups.
- The role of food ingredients in supporting older people to remain well-nourished and healthy.
- Various challenges faced by peoples in old ages.

Research Methodology

This study would be based on secondary research primarily through a literature review of peer reviewed journals mainly in the field of nutrition.

Significance of Proper Nutrition

In Old Age As we all know, ageing is an inevitable, irreversible and progressive phenomenon. Advancing age is accompanied by progressive physiological changes in functions of most organs. As people age, there also tends to be a concomitant increase in the presence and number of chronic

conditions such as hypertension, cardiovascular disease, osteoporosis, diabetes and dementias among others. These further compromise the quality of life in old age. Nutrition has emerged as a major modifiable determinant of chronic disease and age-related decline. Most importantly, dietary adjustments not only influence present health but also determine whether or not an individual will develop diseases like cancer, cardiovascular disease and diabetes much later in life. As we grow old, certain changes occur in our body, some which are visible like greying hair, wrinkling skin, loss of hearing and weak eyesight. Several other changes occur internally, which we cannot see. Some of these changes influence the diet patterns of the elderly.

The nutritional needs of the elderly, especially those over 80 years of age, are very different. Activity levels decrease and the body's metabolism also slows down. As we grow older, we therefore require less energy and correspondingly smaller quantities of food (Puri, 2015).

Even though the elderly need less energy, they need the same amount or even more of vitamins and minerals than they needed as adults. Some of these like vitamin E and C are known to have anti ageing benefits as well as protect us from diseases like cancer, heart disease and cataract. A liberal use of vegetables and fruits will help to provide these nutrients (Andrew, 2015).

Loss of teeth with advancing age leads to several dental problems. Many elderly are partially or totally toothless. As a result, chewing becomes extremely difficult. Liquids or soft cooked, mashed foods are preferred by them. However, such foods may not supply sufficient nourishment and supplements may be necessary (Michèle et. al 2013).

The power to digest and absorb food gradually decreases. Changes in digestive system occur necessitating certain modifications in the kind and amount of food we can eat and number of meals to be taken. Elderly people commonly complain of heaviness, fullness in the stomach, even gas formation and acidity. The diet should therefore be carefully selected (Puri, 2015).

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Nutrition in Old Age

As we grow older, the pleasure of eating diminishes. Food preferences also alter with advancing age. This occurs because of a decrease in the sensitivity of the taste buds. The ability to perceive tastes like sweet and salty diminishes. The taste of food appears bland. Therefore, meals should be made more attractive and appealing by including a variety of foods.

- Recommended Nutrient Intakes for Older Persons as per (WHO, 2002) is:
- Energy: 1.41.8 multiples of the basal metabolic rate (BMR) to maintain body weight at different levels of physical activity.
- Protein: 0.91.1 g/kg per day
- Fat: 30 en% in sedentary older persons and 35en% for active older persons. Saturated fats should not exceed 8% of energy.
- Calcium: 8001200 mg/day
- Iron: 10 mg/day assuming no excessive iron losses.
- Selenium: 5070 ug/day
- Zinc: Moderate Zn availability (30%) Men 7.0 mg/day, Women 4.9 mg/day
- Riboflavin: 1.3 mg for men and 1.1 mg for women.
- Folate: 400 ug/day
- Vitamin B12: 2.5 ug/day
- Vitamin C: 60100 mg/day
- Vitamin A:600700 ug retinol equivalents/day
- Vitamin D: 1015 ug/day • Vitamin E:100400 IU/day

Ageing and health

It is increasingly accepted that the health of the population is primarily determined not by health services or individual lifestyle choices, but by social, cultural, economic and environmental influences (Public Health Advisory Committee 2005). Understanding the range of factors that contribute to the nutritional health of the older population can help to identify ways to develop policies and programmes that have a positive impact on the health and wellbeing of older people (Public Health Advisory Committee 2005).

Determinants of health may individually or in combination interact with the normal physiological and lifestyle changes associated with ageing to affect the nutritional status of older adults. The rates at which changes in health occur may depend on whether these factors occur individually or in unison.

Nutrition and health in older people

- Health status is closely related to the ageing process, and nutrition is one factor that has beneficial or negative effects on the rate of the ageing process (British Nutrition Foundation 2009). Food has an important influence on physical health and independence, and also contributes to social, cultural and psychological quality of life (American Dietetic Association 2005). In New Zealand in 1997 approximately 11,000 deaths, or 40 percent of all adult deaths, were estimated to be attributable to the combined effects of high total blood cholesterol, high systolic blood pressure, high body mass index (BMI), and inadequate vegetable and fruit intake and physical activity levels. Approximately 8000 to 9000 of these deaths reflected poor diet and 2000 to 3000 reflected inadequate physical activity (Ministry of Health Wellington, 2003).
- Overall, good nutrition in older people is associated with:
 - Preventing malnutrition
 - Supporting physical function
 - Reducing the risk of chronic disease
 - Supporting mental health
 - Preventing disability
- Many factors associated with ageing affect food and nutrient intake and may promote poor nutritional status. Although some factors associated with age are irreversible, such as sarcopenia and dementia, other factors are modifiable, such as food skills and knowledge, living arrangements, and the physical and social environment. Targeting the modifiable factors at a population level may slow or even reverse a decline in health.

Guidelines for Healthy Eating

- Eating a variety of foods is important, no matter what your age. If you eat well, you are likelier to feel healthier, stay active for longer and protect yourself against illness. To make it easier for you to plan nutritious meals for yourself a simple guide is given below by (Department of Nutrition of India, 2018)
- **Five Steps to Healthy Eating**
Cereals are the basic foundation of our daily diet. Try to include at least 1-2 servings of any cereal preparation in every meal chapati, rice, bread, dalia, upma etc. These foods provide energy, vitamins and minerals. Remember to eat some unrefined cereals because they are rich in fibre, vitamins and minerals. Whole wheat flour (atta) should be preferred to refined flour (maida), undermilled rice is better than polished rice.
- **Vegetables and Fruits** on the second step are excellent sources of numerous nutrients especially fibre, minerals and vitamins. These foods are rich in antioxidant nutrients which protect us from several diseases like cancer, heart disease etc. Try to include plenty of vegetables and fruits in the daily diet. Remember to eat some amount of these in the raw form.
- **Pulses, nuts, milk and milk products, fish and chicken**
 On the third step are good sources of protein and hence useful to the body. Include at least one food item from this group in every meal. Milk and its products like cheese, curd, paneer etc. contain calcium which helps to keep the bones strong.
- **Eggs and red meat** should be taken in limited amounts, as one grows older. They are rich in fat and cholesterol and may lead to diseases like high blood pressure, heart disorders and cancer in later life.
- **Oil, ghee, butter** on the fifth step provide energy. Excessive consumption of these fats in old age is harmful to health. Avoid eating too much of fried foods as we grow older. Use vegetable oils like sunflower, corn or soya oil for cooking food rather than ghee or vanaspati.

- **Salt** is considered to be an essential constituent of our diet. However, the taste for salt is an acquired one. Too much salt is harmful for the body. Its use should be restricted as it can lead to high blood pressure and other related disorders.
- **Sugar and Jaggery** also provide energy. However, their use in the diet should be restricted as it can lead to diabetes and other degenerative diseases. In general, food on the fifth step oil, butter, ghee, salt sugar and jiggery though essential and beneficial in young age should be consumed with caution as age advances.

Tips for Healthy Eating

- **Enjoy a wide variety of nutritious foods.**

The benefits of variety are that it increases the possibility of obtaining enough nutrients, reduces exposure to small amounts of toxic substances and offers protection against chronic diseases. If you eat a varied and nutritious diet, the impact of factors such as changes in taste perception and interactions between medication and nutrients which can impair your nutritional status will be reduced. Eat a variety of cereals, vegetables and fruits, nuts and seeds. Where refined fats are necessary for cooking, select from a variety of liquid oils, including those high in omega-3 and omega-6 fats (Department of Nutrition of India, 2018).

Eating in company can increase your enjoyment of food. Make an effort to enjoy some meals with children, grandchildren, friends and neighbours. However, avoid the regular use of celebratory foods (e.g. mithais, ice cream, cakes and pastries).

- **Select nutrient-dense foods**

such as fish, lean meat, liver, eggs, soya products and low-fat dairy products, yeast-based products, fruits and vegetables, herbs and spices, whole-grain cereals, nuts and seeds.

- **Emphasize healthy traditional vegetable- and legume-based dishes**

Introduce healthy traditional foods or dishes from other cuisines (e.g. wheat, bajra etc in South Indian diets and ragi in North Indian menus). Limit traditional dishes/foods that are heavily preserved /pickled in salt and encourage the use of herbs and spices. Transfer as much as possible of one's food culture, health knowledge and related skills to one's children, grandchildren and the wider community.

- **Include some of your favorite foods in your daily meals**

As one grows older, the pleasure of eating diminishes. The taste of food appears bland. Therefore, meals should be made more attractive and appealing by including a variety of foods. Use a variety of seasonings but do not eat very spicy foods.

- **Eat at least 3-4 meals every day**

Everyone must make sure that they eat 3-4 meals, at fixed times, every day. Missing an occasional meal may not cause any harm but doing so habitually would deprive the body of essential nourishment. If your appetite is poor and you are gradually losing weight, consult your doctor.

- **Overcome chewing problems**

Most elderly complain of dental problems like loose teeth, ill fitting dentures or problems in chewing. Soft, well-cooked foods like vegetable dalia, khichri etc. can be eaten by these individuals. Hard foods like raw vegetables and fruits can be included in the grated, boiled or stewed form.

- **Ensure easy to digest meals**

Difficulty in digesting food is another common complaint in old age. Hence, one should avoid fried, fatty, spicy and very sweet foods. Very large meals may not be tolerated, so 3-4 small meals may be preferred. Eating small nutritious snacks in between meals may help to alleviate acidity and heartburn.

- **Prevent constipation**

The elderly often suffers from constipation. Eating fibre rich foods like whole cereals pulses, vegetables and fruits helps to overcome constipation. Drink at least 6-8 glasses of fluids like water, milk, juice, tea, soup etc. daily.

- **If you drink alcohol, limit your intake**

Small amounts of alcohol have been shown to have health benefits one of the best known is the reduction in stroke. However excess alcohol has potential side effects, such as liver damage, which outweigh the benefits of a moderate intake. Older persons are more susceptible to the toxic effects of alcohol. In addition, alcohol interacts with medication and thus may be harmful to health

- **Ensure food safety**

Older people are particularly at risk from complications from food poisoning. The main causes of food poisoning could be not cooking food for long enough, not storing food at the correct temperature, using contaminated equipment such as chopping boards, purchasing an unsafe food and poor personal hygiene. You therefore need to be very careful while eating out and also while handling food in your own kitchen.

- **Be physically active**

Be physically active on a regular basis and include exercises that strengthen muscles and improve balance.

Age Challenges and Nutrition

Some main challenges are listed below:

- Thirty percent of older people are ‘frail’ and at high risk of age-related disease in which malnutrition is a factor.
- Muscle wasting (sarcopenia) is a serious cause of loss of independence and disability.
- Cognitive decline is more likely to affect the frail.
- Movement and good nutrition are critical for successful ageing.

Nutrition is one of the most important factors in the development of age-related diseases. These include diabetes, vascular diseases, cancer and osteoporosis. More recently these age-related diseases have been extended to include sarcopenia, frailty, cognitive decline and Alzheimer’s disease. Approximately 60% of the older population can be described as healthy, 30% frail, and the remaining 10% dependent and the needs of these three groups vary (Song et. al 2010).

Healthy older people are more likely to get fractures since they are relatively mobile and independent, and thus more likely to encounter falls. Because they live longer they are more likely to develop cognitive impairment and, again because they are not frail, many will actually be overweight and obese and suffer the major morbidities of obesity such as type 2 diabetes. The 30% of the population who are frail have both the risk of becoming dependent and the opportunity to build strength and return to the ranks of the healthy older people. For the remaining 10% or so that are dependent, living in nursing homes or cared for at home, the main nutritional risk is protein energy malnutrition (PEM) (Kinsella & Phillips, 2005).

The three main nutritional issues in older people are frailty and sarcopenia, cognitive decline and malnutrition related to dependency. The cycle of frailty starts with chronic malnutrition leading to muscle loss known as sarcopenia. This in turn has two consequences: a reduced resting metabolic rate as a result of a loss of lean body mass, and a reduced mobility because of loss of muscle mass and quality. Consequently, there is a reduction in energy expenditure leading to reduced appetite thus completing the cycle of chronic malnutrition (Eeles et. al. 2012).

FIGURE ONE: The Cycle of Frailty

Sourced by- a Department of Rehabilitation and Geriatrics, Medical School and University Hospitals of Geneva, Geneva , Switzerland; b University of Reims Champagne-Ardenne, Faculty of Medicine, EA3797, Reims , France

The clinical features of frailty include:

- Sarcopenia
- Weight loss/under nutrition
- Decreased strength, exercise tolerance
- Slowed motor processing
- Decreased balance
- Low physical activity
- Cognitive vulnerability
- Increased vulnerability to stressors

This progressive functional decline in frail elderly is associated with increasing dependency and co-morbidities, leading to hospitalisation and institutionalisation.

Summary

Nutrition plays a key role in the development of many age-related diseases, with potentially devastating consequences for individuals and significant impact on health resources. Good nutrition combined with physical exercise, is essential to successful ageing. Nutrition therapy can interrupt the cycle of malnutrition in frail older adults and improve nutritional status and outcomes in dependent patients.

The elderly individuals sought to understand the multiplicity of today's world and this space enabled them to keep up to date and connected to the innovations of tomorrow, which was reflected in their conceptions of healthy nourishment. They wanted to understand what "good nourishment" meant in today's world, in accordance with old age, nutritional rules and the needs of modern daily life.

Their conceptions related to healthy nourishment were affected by several modern, symbolic values, such as practicality, diversity and functionality. At the same time, these values were mixed with the individuals' perception of their body and the singularities that aging represents to each person.

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Food Safety and Hygiene Practices among Food Handlers in Hospitality Industry in Uttarakhand

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Abstract

As food safety includes food hygiene, hygiene of food handlers, hazard related to food and its risks is becoming an important issue to guests making purchase decisions. Therefore, the food processors and food handlers either in hospitality industry and food processing industries should improve their knowledge and skill on food safety assurance. A systematic and continued training and education with behavioural changes, and supported with good law enforcement are likely to minimize the hazard related to food and its risks.

This study seeks to examine the awareness of food safety knowledge and handling of food, personal hygiene among food handlers. Although food handlers may be aware of the need for personal hygiene, they do not understand critical aspects of personal hygiene such cleaning work surface, sanitation and control food temperature value while cooking. In order to prevent food borne illnesses and hazard, food handlers need to access and improve food safety knowledge, personal hygiene and the hygiene practices on food safety to guests.

Keywords: food safety, food hygiene, food handlers, hospitality industry.

Introduction

The Indian tourism and hospitality industry has emerged as one of the key drivers of growth among the services sector in India. Tourism & hospitality is also a potentially large employment generator besides being a significant source of foreign exchange for the country. During 2006–17, direct contribution of tourism and hospitality to GDP is expected to register a CAGR of 14.05 per cent. The rapid technological changes in all aspects of life to a certain extent have affected the food pattern and food habit of people especially in the metropolitan areas. These changes also bring the impressive growth of hospitality industries such as international and national tourism, restaurants, fast food outlets and catering businesses.

This increasing number of tourist is bringing the people eating more outside their homes. Over the past several years, people have begun eating more meals in restaurants & hotels. Hence, the control of their food safety is now moving from the housewives to the food handlers in the food outlets and it is indirectly also enforced the local health departments to imply a strict food safety standard. The food pattern, food habit and other newly developed technologies increased the importance of food safety management systems, as the food supply chain sources as well as consumers become more knowledgeable and discerning on all issues associated with food particularly the one related to food safety.

Working in the food processing and manufacturing industry is a challenging yet fulfilling career, especially when working within either the hotel or the hospitality industry where standards need to be maintained high in order to not fail expectations. Food processors and food handlers either in hospitality, hotel industries and food processing industries are advised to improve on any knowledge for food safety assurance.

Working in any food processing industry entails keeping up with target production for the day and working vigorously to make sure the food processed is on par with the standards for customers. Also, it requires that the workplace, the food being processed, and the whole workforce comply with the food safety and hygiene practices.

With the huge amount of food processed in hotels and hospitality, and large workforce to monitor, food safety is sometimes hard to track. However, it can be effectively done by educating workers on what to do and what is expected of them. Also, they must have a complete understanding about the implications if they do otherwise.

Literature review

Food is an essential part of life, but if it is contaminated it can cause illness even death, and food can be contaminated with toxic substances from outside or even it is already in the food itself. There are possibilities of contamination with microbiological, chemical and/or physical hazards with or without the growth of micro organisms in each step of food preparations.

Food safety is a scientific discipline describing handling, preparation, and storage of food in ways that prevent food-borne illness. The occurrence of two or more cases of a similar illnesses resulting from the ingestion of a common food is known as a Food-borne disease outbreak. This includes a number of routines that should be followed to avoid potential health hazards.

A food safety can be defined as “the minimum frequency and/or concentration of a (microbiological) hazard in food at the time of consumption that provides the appropriate level of health protection”. Some scientists think of food safety in terms of hazard and risks (Anonymous, 2003).

Griffith (2006) had reviewed the history of food safety and presented a model for studying food safety. A timeline of food safety had also been listed and he recorded that food safety had been known since 5000 BC, here people avoided the food contain natural toxic. Early times of fermentation (4000 BC) as well as people knowing food safety in related to religious beliefs (2500 BC) were also recorded. The first recognition of existence of micro organism by Antonie van Leuwenhoek in 1676, the founding of basis of commercial heat processing by Louis Pasteur in 1857 up to the Food Safety (General Food Hygiene) regulation in Europe in 1995 were also the part of the history of food safety in human life. Furthermore, he noted that the estimation of the size of risks that the hazard will occur can be first identified by the hazard which related to foods or food components. Thus, the food safety should reduce the size of risks to minimum level without severe disruption of the food supply.

According to Schmidt (1995), the World Health Organisation (WHO) defined the food and water borne illness as regardless of the presenting symptoms and includes any disease of an infectious or toxic nature caused by or thought to be cause by the consumption of food or water. Therefore, food and water borne disease is caused by various microbiological, chemical and physical hazard includes illness which may be present in food or water. Food safety synonymous with food hygiene embracing anything in the processing, preparation or handling of food to ensure it is safe to eat (Griffith, 2006). While Yeung and Morris (2001) noted that a hazard is an activity or process which can result in negative consequences and thereby provide a source of risk to receiving environment or population.

Furthermore, they suggested that the identification of food hazard can be used as the beginning of analysing the risk relating to the food safety. Rhodehamel (1992) cited the definition of hazard from The National Advisory Committee on Microbiological Criteria for Foods (NACMCF) as any biological, chemical or physical property that may cause an unacceptable consumers health risks. According to the (Ministry of food and agriculture and the World Bank 2007) In every 40 Indian suffer serious food borne illness per year 420000 cases are reported with an annual death rate of

65000 which cost the government India Rs. 6900000000 annually. This report could be an under estimate as report rate is low and the calculation of cost is developing countries only the cost born by individuals through hospitalization and medication is considered whilst others in developed countries consider the cost to employers, institutional bodies like laboratories, surveillance, disability cost and cost from other family members. Who take care of the sick members and premature mortality according to FDA the loss of productivity in India (2010 due to food born disease was approximately 594,279 days 19,809 months) this could be huge in terms of cost to the state.

Food safety nowadays has become a very important issue to be discussed and also become a considerable and increasing interest in many sectors including hospitality industry, food and beverage industry, government officials and public health institutions.

Two in every 10 food samples tested for quality over the past year have been found to be either adulterated or misbranded, revealing alarming trends in the country's food safety sector. What's worse, conviction rate in these cases of poor food quality has been less than 10 percent, meaning only one in every 10 cases of food adulteration and misbranding are ending in convictions. These trends are contained in the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI)'s Annual Public Laboratory Testing Report 2014-2015, which shows that food testing labs under the regulatory network analysed 74,010 food samples for quality and mandatory health disclosures over the past year and found 14,599 of these either adulterated or misbranded. This implies 20 per cent of all samples failed the test of quality and branding regulations.

Objective of the Study

1. To study about the food borne illness disease in food hygiene.
2. To study about various hazards related to food under the food safety.

Research Methodology

This study is exploratory basically based on secondary research primarily through a literature review of peer reviewed journals.

Food Borne Illness

5.1 Bacterial Diseases

There are two kinds of diseases caused by bacteria and effect Food Safety and Hygiene:

- **Intoxicatious** – caused by poisons (toxins) that the bacteria produce while they are growing in the food. It is these poisons, not the bacteria themselves that cause the diseases.
- **Infectious** – caused by bacteria (or other organisms) that gets into the intestinal system and attacks the body.

5.1.1 Botulism (Intoxication)

- Caused by toxins produced by the bacteria “clostridium Botulisium”, attacks the nervous system and is usually fatal, even if only a small amount of poisoned food is eaten. The bacteria are anaerobic and do not grow in high – acid foods. Most outbreaks are caused by improper canning techniques. The toxin (although not the bacteria) is destroyed by boiling at 100°C/212°F for 20 minutes.
- Contamination usually takes place through soil on vegetables and to the foods. It is common in home – canned low acid vegetables (very rarely in commercially canned foods)
- Use only commercially canned foods. Discard without tasting any bulged or damaged cans or foods with off odours.

5.1.2 Staphylococcus Food Poisoning (Staph) (Intoxication)

- Caused by toxins produced in foods by the bacterium ‘Staphylococcus Aureus’, staph is usually the most common food poisoning, characterized by nausea, vomiting, stomach cramps, diarrhea, and prostration.
- Contamination usually takes place through food workers, the foods usually involved include custards and desserts made with dairy products, potato salads, protein salads, ham, hollandaise sauce and many other high protein foods.
- Always maintain good Food Safety and Hygiene and work habits. Do not handle foods if you have an illness or infection. Clean and sanitize all equipment. Keep foods below 7°C/45°F/ or above 60°C/140°F.

5.1.3 Escherichia Coli (Intoxication/ Infection)

- Causes severe illness either as an intoxication or an infection. Severe abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting, diarrhea and another symptoms result. As an infection, it causes

intestinal inflammation and bloody diarrhea. While the illness normally lasts from one to three days, it can lead to long term illness in some cases.

- Contamination usually occurs through the intestinal tracts of humans and some animals, especially cattle, contaminated water. The foods usually involved are raw or undercooked red meats, unpasteurized dairy products, sometimes fish from contaminated water, prepared foods such as mashed potatoes and cream pies.
- Cook foods, including red meats, thoroughly and avoid cross-contamination. Practice good Food Safety and Hygiene.

5.1.4 Salmonella (Infection)

- Caused by salmonella bacteria, exhibits symptoms that are similar to those of staph poisoning though the disease may last longer. Most poultry carry these bacteria.
- Contamination usually occurs through contaminated meats and poultry and faecal contamination by food workers. Poultry, meats, eggs, poultry stuffing's, gravies, raw foods and shellfish from polluted waters are usually affected.
- Always maintain good personal hygiene to balance Food Safety and Hygiene. Proper food storage and handling and insect and rodent control. Wash hands and sanitize all equipment and cutting surfaces after handling raw poultry. Use certified shellfish.

5.1.5 Clostridium Perfringens (Infection)

- Nausea, cramps, stomach pain and diarrhea characterize it. The bacteria are hard to destroy because cooking temperatures does not always kill them. Contamination usually occurs through soil, fresh meats and humans. Meats and poultry and reheated or unrefrigerated gravies and sauces are mostly affected.
- Keep foods hot (above 60°C/140°F) or cold (below 7°C/45°F)

5.1.6 Streptococcal (Strep) Infections

- Symptoms include fever and sore throat.
- Coughs, sneezes and infected food workers transmit the disease. The foods that usually transmit it are those that are contaminated by coughs, sneezes, or infected food workers and then served without further cooking.

- Do not handle food if you are infected. Protect displayed food (salad bars, pastry carts, etc) from customer's sneezes and coughs.

5.1.7 Infectious Hepatitis (Infection)

- This is a severe disease that can last for many months. It is caused by a virus.
- Contamination usually occurs through shellfish from polluted waters and infected food workers. Food contamination usually occurs through shellfish eaten raw and any food contaminated by an infected person.
- Maintain good health and hygiene and use only certified shellfish from safe waters. This way you can always ensure Food Safety and Hygiene also.

5.1.8 Trichinosis (Infection)

- It is often mistaken for the flu at first, but can last for a year or more. It is caused by a tiny worm that becomes unbedded in the muscles.
- Contamination occurs through pork products from hogs that ate unprocessed garbage.
- Pork products should be cooked to an internal temperature of at least 65°C/150°F. To be on the safe side, many authorities recommend 74°C/165°F.

5.2 Chemical Poisoning

- Except for lead poisoning, the following diseases show their symptoms very quickly, usually within less than 30 minutes of eating the poisoned food. To prevent these diseases, do not use the material's that cause them.
- Antimony– caused by storing or cooking acid foods in chipped grey enamelware.
- Cadmium– caused by cadmium-plated ice cube trays or containers.
- Cyanide– caused by silver polish containing cyanide
- Lead-caused by lead water pipes, solder containing lead or utensils containing lead.
- Copper-caused by unclean or corroded copper utensils, acid foods cooked in unlined copper utensils or carbonated beverages in contact with copper tubing.
- Zinc– caused by foods cooked in zinc plated (galvanized) utensils.

Hazard Related to Food

As pointed earlier, hazard related to food is due to biological, chemical and physical contamination which can cause a food poisoning, food borne illness and/or food borne disease. The largest cause of the outbreaks is improper food preparation, handling and storage; where most of these activities occurring in homes, institutions or restaurants. Based on the relation of hazard to food, there are four broad general categories of hazard namely biological or microbiological hazard, chemical hazard, physical hazard and cross-contamination.

Food contamination happens when something gets into food that shouldn't be there.

6.1 Biological or microbiological hazard

This hazard is mainly caused by bacteria, fungal, viral and parasitic (protozoa and worms) micro organisms and/or their toxin. There are only few pathogenic micro organisms related with food, which cause illness and disease; and these micro organisms are usually known as food pathogens. Potter and Hotchkiss (1995) grouped the hazardous micro organisms and parasites based on their risk severity into a group of severe hazard micro organisms, moderate hazard with potentially extensive spread micro organisms and moderate hazard with limited spread micro organisms. It is important to note that there are two types of food borne disease caused by the food pathogens micro organisms (i.e infections and intoxications). If the viable food pathogenic micro organisms are ingested and multiply within the body and produce disease, it is called as infections. On the other hand, if the toxins are produced by those food pathogenic micro organisms within the food, then consuming it can cause intoxications. Intoxications can occur even if no viable micro organisms are ingested, and this condition usually occurs in stored food where food pathogenic micro organisms grow and produced toxin. Although processing of food may destroy the food pathogenic micro organisms, but such treatments do not destroy the toxin which is already within the food.

Biological contamination is when bacteria or toxins contaminate food and is a common cause of food poisoning and food spoilage.

Food poisoning can happen when harmful bacteria, also called pathogens, spread to food, and are consumed. Bacteria are small microorganisms that split and multiply very quickly. In conditions ideal for bacterial growth, one single-cell bacteria can split so many times that in just seven hours, it has multiplied into two million.

Some bacteria such as salmonella, staphylococcus and listeria are extremely toxic by themselves. And, sometimes it's not the bacteria that are toxic to humans, but the process of the bacteria multiplying and producing waste. However, not all bacteria are harmful to humans; many are quite beneficial, such as those found in yoghurt.

As a food handler, it's your job to control the spread of harmful bacteria by maintaining food safety. Bacteria can be found everywhere and are impossible to see with the naked eye. Some of the most common places for bacteria to grow are:

- The human body
- Dust
- Raw meat
- Pets and pests
- The air
- Kitchen cloths
- Food handler's clothing

How Bacteria Survive

- Food: Bacteria need a constant source of food to survive, especially protein. High protein foods such as meat are particularly vulnerable to biological contamination from bacteria, which means they're considered high-risk foods.
- Water: Water is essential to bacterial growth and without it, most bacteria will die. Which is why drying foods as a way of preservation is so effective and has been performed for thousands of years.
- Oxygen: Most bacteria require air to survive, these are called aerobic bacteria. Although some bacteria - called anaerobic bacteria - can survive without oxygen. Which is why it's still possible to get food poisoning from canned food items.
- PH Levels: PH refers to food acidity and is measured on a scale of 1 (acidic) to 14 (alkaline). Most fruits generally have a PH level of between 1 - 5.9, so are considered acidic. While many alkaline foods such as vegetables have a PH level at the other end of the scale. Bacteria thrive in neutral foods that are neither acidic nor alkaline and

generally have a PH level of between 6 - 8.9. Foods such as meat and seafood are prime examples of neutral foods.

- Time and temperature: Bacteria need both time and the right temperature to multiply to dangerous levels. A temperature of between 5°C and 60°C - also referred to as the 'danger zone' - allows for maximum bacterial growth, so it's important not to keep food at this temperature for too long.

High-risk foods are those that have ideal conditions for bacterial growth. This means they're usually:

- Neutral in acidity
- High in starch or protein
- Moist

Foods such as seafood, cooked rice or pasta, and dairy are all considered high-risk because they provide the perfect environment for bacteria to grow. This is why it's essential to practice proper food handling when dealing with these foods.

Low-risk foods are those that don't have particularly good bacterial growth conditions. These foods are:

- High in acidity
- High in salt or sugar
- Dried
- Canned or vacuum packed

Some examples of low-risk foods would be pickles, uncooked rice or pasta and jams. Although these foods are not common sources of biological contamination, the appropriate care must still be taken when handling them.

6.2 Chemical hazards

Chemicals which cause a hazard associated with food can be classified as naturally occurring, indirectly and directly added. Naturally occurring chemicals which cause a hazard in food are toxicants that already exist in the food itself such as histamine in seafood can cause an allergy or intoxication, mushroom toxins and mycotoxin in certain variety of legumes. Those toxicants can

be considered as fast acting toxicants which mean that it can directly cause illness after ingestion. However, some natural foods also contain slow acting toxicants, where if it is consumed over a long period of time it could potentially promote chronic disease and called as carcinogenic substances (Potter and Hotchkiss, 1995; O’Keefe and Kennedy, 1998).

Chemical contamination occurs when food comes into contact with chemicals and can lead to chemical food poisoning.

Some common sources of chemical contamination can include:

- Kitchen cleaning agents: Proper storing of kitchen cleaning chemicals is essential. Never keep food stored in the same place as your cleaning chemicals, and always use cleaning products designed especially for kitchen use.
- Unwashed fruits and vegetables: The pesticides and fungicides often used on fruits and vegetables to help them grow free from diseases are harmful if consumed. Which is why it’s vital to properly wash all fruits and vegetables before eating them.
- Food containers made from non-safe plastics: Single use items - such as plastic containers - are not designed to be reused again and again. Always store food in containers that are specially designed to safely be reused.
- Pest control products: Items like fly spray and rat poison are extremely hazardous if consumed. Always store these products away from food items.
- Chemicals used in equipment maintenance: Some kitchen machines and equipment with moving parts - such as slicers and mixers - can need regular oiling. Always use food-safe oil to help make sure this doesn’t contaminate the food you use them to prepare.

In their recent studies, Park and Lewis (1992) found that the use of food preservatives such as benzoic acid, nitrites and sulphites as antimicrobial agent and Butylated Hydroxy Anisole (BHA), Butylated Hydroxy Toluene (BHT), ascorbic acid and tocopherol as antioxidants have probably changed food productions patterns and eating habits more than the use of any other class of food additive.

These food preservatives chemicals will offer substantial benefits on man not only by the preservation and increased palatability of food, but also by its function to protect against the

pathogenical affects of reactive oxygen species micro organisms which associated with cancer, cardiovascular disease and aging.

The important issue where food processors and food handler should be aware of is that the usage of food additives are regulated by the Food and Drug Administration or by the Department of Health in each country as well as listed in the International and/or National Standard agencies such as Codex Alimentarius (WHO/FAO). There are guidelines to be followed and where it listed the food additives can be used and the maximum amount permitted to be added to foods. Unfortunately, due to lack of knowledge or information, there are still some food processors or producers using the non-listed food additives or chemicals which are not for food such as formalin or borax in their food products. Some of them are also using an excessive amount of permitted food additive, where such of misused practices will promote a health hazard to the consumers.

6.3 Physical Contamination

Physical contamination happens when actual objects contaminate foods. Sometimes when a food is physically contaminated, it can also be biologically contaminated. This is because the physical contamination might harbour dangerous bacteria, for example a fingernail.

Common sources of physical contamination are:

- Hair: Always wear hair neatly tied back and use a hair net if possible.
- Glass or metal: This can occur when kitchen items are not maintained. Cracked or broken crockery and utensils should be thrown away, as well as any food that might have come into contact with it.
- Pests: Pests - such as mice, rats and cockroaches - leave droppings that can contaminate food. Also, pests themselves - such as flies and insects - can also make their way into food.
- Jewellery: Always keep jewellery to a minimum when preparing and handling food.
- Dirt: Because dirt is so small, it's easy not to notice that it's contaminating your food. It usually gets into the food from unwashed food and vegetables.
- Fingernails: Always keep nails short and clean to prevent contamination. Also, avoid wearing fake nails as these can fall off and may contaminate food.

Bennion (1992) and Potter and Hotchkiss (1995) suggested that to reduce the risks of those physical contaminants, the food processors and producers should implement the good

manufacturing practices and careful analysis of the critical control points in their production line. This program is actually a part of the well-known Hazard Analysis Critical Control Points (HACCP) system.

6.4 Cross-Contamination

Cross-contamination occurs when bacteria or pathogens are transported from one object to another. This can happen in many different ways and some of the more common sources of cross-contamination include:

- **Clothing:** Dirty clothes can transport bacteria from one place to another. If possible, clothing should be replaced when moving from one work area to another. You should also thoroughly wash your face and hands. This is especially important when working with allergens or high-risk foods.
- **Utensils:** Separate utensils should always be used to prepare different types of foods. For example, never use the same chopping board or knife to prepare raw meat and ready-to-eat foods.
- **Personal hygiene:** Coughing, sneezing or even touching your face and hair before handling food can also result in cross-contamination. Washing hands regularly when handling food is essential.
- **Pests:** Flies, cockroaches, mice and rats carry harmful bacteria, which they can transport from one place to another. Pest control is vitally important in the workplace when it comes to preventing cross-contamination.
- **Raw food storage:** One of the most common types of cross-contamination is when raw food comes into contact with cooked or ready-to-eat food. If this happens, it's a good idea to assume the raw food has been contaminated. Raw food should always be covered and stored below cooked foods to prevent this type of contamination.
- **Waste control:** Garbage should be stored and sealed correctly to prevent cross-contamination. It should always be stored away from other items in the kitchen to ensure it never comes into contact with food preparation. Regular cleaning and sanitising of waste bins should also be carried out to prevent the risk of pest infestation.

7. FOOD SAFETY IN HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY

Food technology development in the last decades brings both market opportunities and food safety perils. Therefore, food safety has become major interest in many sectors including hospitality industry, food processing industry, government institutes and public health agencies. Those involve in food preparation and service play a vital role in the prevention of food borne illness and/or food borne disease and their actions can be critical in preventing outbreaks of food borne illness and/or food borne disease. Hence preventing the outbreaks is more a matter of understanding where food borne disease originates and how food manufacturing and storage can increase the risks of that disease. This understanding should belong not only to the food handlers but also the managers of industries related to food as well as the consumers themselves.

The best and most effective method of assuring food safety is to establish a systematic and continuous training and education for the food handlers in hospitality and food processing industries, managers of hospitality and food processing industries, government officers in charge with food safety as well as the consumers. Once the food safety issues are understood the hazard and its risks in foods can be minimized.

However, Clayton et al. (2002) found that although the number of food handlers receiving food safety training is increased, a high proportion of food poisoning outbreaks still occur as a result of poor food handling. This study also highlights the need of training based on a risk-based approach and demonstrates that behavioural changes will not occur merely as a result of training only.

Although the concept of training is endorsed by many managers in the hospitality industries, only very few managers put these ideas into practice. Whilst, Go et al. (1996) defined the hospitality training as a systematic process through which an organisation's human resources gain knowledge and develop skills by instruction and practical activities that result in improved corporate performance. Furthermore, they noted that the effective achievement can be obtained from repeated learning measures and not a one-time activity.

Krammer and Scott (2004) noted that safe food handling in ready-to-eat food establishment is a basic element in the reduction of food borne disease and it can give a better food safety assurance for their consumers. Whilst Kidd (2000) had discussed the consumers concern on food safety, he observed that the consumer is concerned about a lack of information and knowledge, and they feel that there is a corruption about the facts.

Besides education and training, the food legislation also plays a supportive role for the success of the food safety assurance. Adams (1995) had reviewed the past and present food hygiene legislation and made a recommendation in the production of an industrial guide for food safety in the hotel and catering industries.

Conclusion

Food safety includes food hygiene, hazard related to food and its risks become important issues if we are preparing and handling safe foods. Microbiological hazard is the most considerable and increasing interest in the food safety programmes as the outbreaks are world wide and also can be a transnational issue.

Chemical hazard is less crucial, but it needs a special attention especially in developing countries, where most of the food processors and food handlers quite often misused those chemicals in foods. The excessive amount of permitted chemicals and the non-food grade chemicals are still found in foods especially in developing countries.

Knowledge and attitudes related to food safety are critical among the hospitality industry managers who will supervise their food handlers in preparing foods in their food outlets. The food legislation and education with emphasis on the later can give a food safety assurance. However it should involve the behavioural change and enable people to set and implement their own food safety agenda.

Therefore integrated education, training, behavioural change, food legislation and the consciousness of food handlers, government officers in charge with food safety, educators in hospitality studies and consumers are necessary together to minimize the unintended consequences from the technological development and its hazard and risks related to food.

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Food and Law

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Abstract

Even after the 70 years of Independence, the people of India particularly poor and vulnerable groups experiencing everyday for basic necessities of life. The government of our country has faced a lot of troubles to solve this problem and to ensure Right to Food as a fundamental right. This paper focuses on the topic 'Food and Law' in which there are many Laws given in our constitution of India. Every human being is entitled to have right to be free from hunger. As a matter of law, the Right to Food has at least in formal terms, been accorded universal recognition as a human right.

Since a long time, India had lagged behind in reconciling its Food Laws with contemporary needs. As a result, India overhauled its food regulatory regime in 2006, there were also some changes in food safety and standards Act, popularly known as FSS Act and had been implemented in the beginning of 2007. The FSS act is a host of regulations as well as rules which was framed to regulate whole spectrum of activities for example manufacture, import and retail. With the advent of the FSS Act, India has taken a large step in unifying laws and regulation regime, which also looks over the quality of food and standards.

Even with the tremendous effort of unification India still has a lot of laws that apply to the food sector with implication on entities ranging from a small tea shop to a KFC of this world. Hence these requirements may not be strictly followed or enforced but in future it will not be the same instead will be a successful country in implementing laws as well as regulating it.

Key Note

Here we will talk about eight Food laws which are, The Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954, The Fruit Products Order, 1955, The Meat Food Products Order, 1973, The Vegetable Oil Products (Control) Order, 1947, The Edible Oils Packaging (Regulation) Order, 1998, The Solvent Extracted Oil, De oiled Meal, and Edible Flour (Control) Order, 1967, The Milk and Milk Products

Order, 1992, Essential Commodities Act, 1955 (in relation to food) etc are repealed after commencement of FSS Act, 2006.

Introduction

There is always an effort be made by the state and by civil society to eradicate the poverty and hunger that constitute an affront to the dignity and worth of the human persons. First and foremost, among the United Nations Millennium Development Goals (MDG) is the pledge made by all heads of the State and Government to make it half, by the year 2015, the proportion of the world's poor and of people who suffer from hunger. India has a special responsibility in this regard. The prevalence of extreme poverty and hunger is unconscionable in this day and age, for not only does it militate against respect for human rights, but it also undermines the prospects of peace and harmony within a State. As a party to the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights and the Convention on the Rights of the Child, India has committed itself to add the right to adequate food. This means that there is a fundamental right to be free from hunger. Hence starvation constitutes a gross denial and violation of this right; they are the direct concern to the commission under the provisions of the Protection of Human Rights, 1993.

Like many other developing countries, India has a wide variety of feeding programs, food subsidies, and other sorts of “schemes” to alleviate hunger, but somehow these programs are never quite enough. They can be empowered, however, through clear acknowledgment of their human rights. Over the centuries, many millions of people have gone hungry in India. Now, for the first time, the claim has been made that the government has a positive obligation to do something to enforce this right, and if government does not meet its obligation, it can be called to account in the nation's courts.

In terms of the law, the human right to adequate food is a part of the right to an adequate livelihood, which is a part of economic rights, which is a part of human rights generally, which is a part of international law. The right to food is one of the most basic human rights, closely linked to the right to life. No government practice or action can be allowed to deny this right to people. Human Rights are indivisible and inalienable. The right to food in particular, must be made justiciable in courts of law.

India today is not only self-sufficient in grain production, but also has a substantial reserve. The progress made by agriculture in the last four decades has been one of the biggest success stories

of free India. Agriculture and allied activities constitute the single largest contributor to the Gross Domestic Product, almost 33% of it. Agriculture is the means of livelihood of about two-thirds of the work force in the country. It is true that the country now produces enough food to feed its entire people because India no longer suffers through large scale famines as it has in the past. India have implemented many laws such as Public Distribution System to provide food at a cheaper rate and also Mid Day Meal Schemes for the government school students so that they can have food as well as they can get education, etc

Food and Law in Detail

The Indian food processing industry is regulated by several laws which govern the aspects of sanitation, licensing and other necessary permits that are required to start up and run a food business. The legislation that dealt with food safety in India was the Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954. The act brought into force in place of PFA is the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 referred as “FSSA”, which looks over the food related laws. It specially repealed eight laws which were in operation prior to the enforcement of FSSA:

- The Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954
- The Fruit Products Order, 1955
- The Meat Food Products Order, 1973
- The Vegetable Oil Products (Control) Order, 1947
- The Edible Oils Packaging (Regulation) Order, 1998
- The Solvent Extracted Oil, De oiled Meal, and Edible Flour (Control) Order, 1967
- The Milk and Milk Products Order, 1992
- Essential Commodities Act, 1955 (in relation to food) etc are repealed after commencement of FSS Act, 2006.

Hence, The Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) has been established under Food Safety and Standards, 2006 which consolidates various acts and orders that have hitherto handled food related issues in various Ministries and Departments. FSSAI has been created for laying down science based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage, distribution, sale and import to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food for human consumption.

The FSSA Act also aims to establish a single reference point for all matters relating to food safety and standards, by moving from multi-level, multi- departmental control to a single line of command. To make it possible the government of India has established an independent statutory Authority- the Food Safety and Standards Authority of India, which head office is located at Delhi. The Food Safety and Standard Act of 2006 were enacted on August 24, 2006. This body consists of 1 chairperson and 22 members, with the objective of regulating and monitoring the manufacture, processing, distribution, sale and import of food and this authority is to be advised by Central Advisory Committee in administrative and Enforcement matters and also by the Scientific Committee and Scientific Panels on technical matters and more details of the authority's role can be seen in Section 16.

Explanation of the Laws

Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954

The Act was promulgated by Parliament in 1954 to make provision for the prevention of adulteration of food. Broadly, the PFA Act covers food standards, general procedures for sampling, analysis of food, powers of authorized officers, nature of penalties and other parameters related to food.

It deals with parameters relating to food additives, preservative, colouring matters, packing & labelling of foods, prohibition & regulations of sales etc. The provisions of PFA Act and Rules are implemented by State Government and local bodies as provided in the rules.

In every case where the milk or milk product is packed Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954 is repealed from 05.08.2011 by the Central Government as per the Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006.

The act clearly defines “What is meant by Food Adulteration and what is the punishment given to person/manufacturer involved in the crime?”

The food is considered adulterated if it fulfills any of the below

- If food is sub-standard rotten, decomposed or obtained from diseased animal or is insect-infested or is otherwise unfit for human consumption.
- If food contains any other substance which affects, or if the article is so processed as to affect, injuriously the nature, substance or quality thereof

- If the article has been prepared, packed or kept under insanitary conditions whereby it has become contaminated or injurious to health;
- If any constituent of the article has been wholly or in part abstracted so as to affect injuriously the nature, substance or quality thereof.
- If the article contains any poisonous or other ingredient which renders it injurious to health
- If any colouring matter other than that prescribed in respect thereof is present in the article, or if the amounts of the prescribed colouring matter which is present in the article are not within the prescribed limits of variability
- If the article contains any prohibited preservative or permitted preservative in excess of the prescribed limits;
- If the quality or purity of the article fall below the prescribed standard or its constituents are present in.

Fruit Product Order (FPO), 1995

Objective

The Main objective is to lay down quality standards to manufacture fruit and vegetable products maintaining sanitary and hygienic conditions in the premises. It is mandatory for all manufacturers of fruit and vegetable products including some non-fruit products like non-fruit vinegar, syrup and sweetened aerated water to obtain a license under this order.

Some of the requirements are laid down in the Fruit Product Order for hygienic production and quality standards

- Location and surrounding of the factory
- Sanitary and hygienic conditions of premises
- Personal hygiene
- Portability of water
- Machinery and Equipment with installed capacity
- Quality control facility and Technical staff
- Product Standards Limits for preservatives and other additives

Fruit product means any of the following articles, namely

- Non-fruit beverages, syrups and sherbets
- Vinegar, whether brewed or non-fruit, Pickles
- Dehydrated fruits and vegetables, Fruit cereal flakes
- Frozen fruits and vegetables, Chutneys
- Canned and bottled fruits, juices and pulps, Canned and bottled vegetables
- Sweetened aerated water and without fruit juice or fruit pulp
- Preserves, candied and crystallized fruit and peel
- Tomato products, ketchup and sauces, Jams, jellies and marmalades
- Squashes, crushes cordials, barley water, barreled juice, and ready to serve beverages, fruit nectars or any other beverages containing fruit juices or pulp
- All unspecified fruit and vegetable products which are considered microbiologically safe and contains only permitted additives within permissible limits.

Each container in which any fruit product is packed shall specify a code number indicating the lot or the date of manufacture of such fruit product.

No person can carry on the business of a manufacturer except under and in accordance with the terms of an effective license granted to him/her under this order in Form B and shall not use the License number on labels of non-Fruit products. FPO mark should be printed on the label with license number. The labels shall not contain any statement, claim, design or device which is false or misleading in a particular concerning the fruit products contained in the package or concerning the quality or the nutritive value or in relation to the place of origin of the said fruit products.

Meat Food Products Order (MFPO)

Objectives

The main objective is to regulate production and sale of meat food products through licensing of manufacturers, enforce sanitary and hygienic conditions prescribed for production of wholesome meat food products, exercise strict quality control at all stages of production of meat food products, fish products including chilled poultry etc. Meat & Meat Products are highly perishable in nature and can transmit diseases from animals to human-beings. Processing of meat products is licensed

under Meat Food Products Order, (MFPO) 1973 which was hitherto being implemented by Ministry of food Processing industries

Under the provision of MFPO all manufacturers of meat food products engaged in the business of manufacturing, packing, repacking, relabeling meat food products meant for sale are licensed but excluding those manufacturers who manufactures such products for consumption on the spot like a restaurant, hotel, boarding house, snack bar, eating house or any other similar establishment.

Vegetable Oil Products Order, 1998

The Vegetable Oil Products industry is regulated by this Order through the Directorate of Vanaspati, Vegetable Oils & Fats, Department of Food, Public Distribution, Ministry of Consumer Affairs, and Food & Public Distribution. The earlier two Orders – Vegetable Oil Products (Control) Order, 1947 and Vegetable Oil Products (Standards of Quality) Order, 1975 have been replaced by a single Order called “Vegetable Oil Products (Regulation) Order, 1998 for proper regulation of manufacture, distribution and sale of Vegetable Oil Products.

Salient Features of the Order:

- The procedure of Registration has been simplified.
- The Standards of quality prescribed under the Schedule have been tightened.
- The requirement where which are vogue and non-measurable and thus open to arbitrary
- Interpretations have been done away with.
- Consumers’ protection through quality assured.

Solvent Extracted oils, De-oiled meal and Edible Flour Control Order, 1967 and Vegetable Products Control Order, 1976

The manufacture and distribution of solvent extracted oils, de-oiled meals, edible flours and hydrogenated vegetable oils is controlled by this order. The order stipulates that any vegetable oil product like Vanaspati or bakery shortening or margarine, unless it conforms to the standards of quality shall not be manufactured, stocked or sold. A license is granted by the Directorate of Vanaspati, Vegetable oils and fats under the Ministry of Civil Supplies Consumer Affairs and Public Distribution. The Directorate also controls the market price of Vanaspati.

Edible Oils Packaging, 1998

In order to ensure availability of safe and quality edible oils in packed form at pre-determined prices to the consumers, the Central Govt. promulgated on 17th September, 1998, an Edible Oils Packaging (Regulation) Order, 1998 under the Essential Commodities Act, 1955 to make packaging of edible oils, sold in retail, compulsory unless specifically exempted by the concerned State Govt.

Salient Features

- Edible oils including edible mustard oil will be allowed to be sold only in packed form from
- 15th December, 1998.
- Packers will have to register themselves with a registering authority.
- The packer will have to have his own analytical facilities or adequate arrangements for testing the samples of edible oils to the satisfaction of the Government.
- Only oils which conform to the standards of quality as specified in the Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954 and Rules made there under will be allowed to be packed.
- Each container or pack will have to show all relevant particulars so that the consumer is not misled, so also the identity of the packer becomes clear.
- Edible oils shall be packed in conformity with the Standards of Weights and Measures (Packaged Commodities) Rules, 1977, and the Prevention of Food Adulteration Act, 1954 and Rules made there under.
- The State Governments will have power to relax any requirement of the packaging order for meeting special circumstances.

Milk and Milk Product order (MMPO)

The objective of the order is to maintain and increase the supply of liquid milk of desired quality in the interest of the general public and also for regulating the production, processing and distribution of milk and milk products.

As per the provisions of this order, any person/dairy plant handling more than 10,000 liters per day of milk or 500 MT of milk solids per annum needs to be registered with the Registering Authority appointed by the Central Government.

In every case where the milk or milk product is packed by the holder of a registration certificate in a tin, barrel, carton or any other container, the registration number shall either be exhibited prominently on the side label of such container or be embossed, punched or printed prominently thereon.

Essential Commodities Act, 1955

Under this act, there are a number of control orders. The main objectives of this act are to regulate the manufacture, commerce, distribution of essential commodities including food.

Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI)

The Food Safety and Standards Authority of India (FSSAI) has been established under Food Safety and Standards Act, 2006 which consolidates various acts & orders that have hitherto handled food related issues in various Ministries and Departments.

FSSAI has been created for laying down science based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage, distribution, sale and import to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food for human consumption.

Functions performed by FSSAI

- Framing of Regulations to lay down the Standards and guidelines in relation to articles of food and specifying appropriate system of enforcing various standards.
- Laying down mechanisms and guidelines for accreditation of certification bodies engaged in certification of food safety management system for food businesses.
- Laying down procedure and guidelines for accreditation of laboratories and notification of the accredited laboratories.
- To provide scientific advice and technical support to Central Government and State Governments in the matters of framing the policy and rules in areas which have a direct or indirect bearing of food safety and nutrition.

- Collect and collate data regarding food consumption, incidence and prevalence of biological risk, contaminants in food, residues of various, contaminants in foods products, identification of emerging risks and introduction of rapid alert system.
- Creating an information network across the country so that the public, consumers, Panchayats etc receive rapid, reliable and objective information about food safety and issues of concern.
- Provide training programmes for persons who are involved or intend to get involved in food businesses.
- Contribute to the development of international technical standards for food, sanitary and phyto-sanitary standards.
- Promote general awareness about food safety and food standards

Powers

- Take sample.
- Seize any article of food.
- Can enter and inspect any place.
- May destroy, deteriorated, perishable product after giving notice in writing.

Food Safety Officer

- May seize any article of food and books of account or other documents found in position of manufacturer, distributor and dealer where position of adulterant found.
- In case of non-availability of the FBO, the FSO may seize the adulterant food and seal the premises for investigation after taking a sample of such adulterant or food for analysis.
- May cause a person to be examined by a qualified medical professional duly authorized by the Designated Officer.

Food Authority Under the FSS Act, 2006- India General Provisions as to Articles of Food under the FSS ACT, 2006

Use of Food Additive or Processing Aid

No article of food shall contain any additive or processing aid unless it is accordance with the provisions of the Act and regulations made there under (Section 19 of FSS Act, 2006).

Contaminants, naturally occurring toxic substances, heavy metals, etc

No article of food shall contain any contaminant, naturally occurring toxic substance toxins Or hormone or heavy metals in excess of such quantities as may be specified by regulations (Section 20 of FSS Act, 2006).

Pesticides, veterinary drugs residues, antibiotic residues and microbiological counts

- No article of food shall contain insecticides or pesticides residues, veterinary drugs residues, antibiotic residues, solvent residues, pharmacological active substances and micro-biological counts in excess of such tolerance limit as may be specified by regulations;
- No insecticide shall be used directly on article of food except fumigants registered and approved under the Insecticides Act, 1968 (Section 21 of the FSS Act, 2006).

Genetically modified foods, organic foods, functional foods, proprietary foods, etc

- No person shall manufacture, distribute, sell or import any novel food, genetically modified articles of food, irradiated food, organic foods, foods for special dietary uses, functional foods, nutraceuticals, health supplements, propriety foods and such other articles of food which the Central Government may notify in this behalf (Section 22 of the FSS Act, 2006).

Norms for Packaging and Labelling Of Food Products in India

Packaging and Labelling of Foods under Section 23

- No person shall manufacture, distribute, sell or expose for sale or dispatch or deliver to any agent or broker for the purpose of sale, any packaged food products which are not marked and labeled in the manner as may be specified by regulations;
- Provided that the labels shall not contain any statement, claim, design or device which is false or misleading in any particular concerning the food products contained in the package

or concerning the quantity or the nutritive value implying medicinal or therapeutic claims or in relation to the place of origin of the said food products;

- Every food business operator shall ensure that the labeling and presentation of food, including their shape, appearance or packaging, the packaging materials used, the manner in which they are arranged and the setting in which they are displayed, and the information which is made available about them through whatever medium, does not mislead consumers.

Food Safety and Standards (Packaging and Labelling Regulations), 2011

General Labelling Requirements

Every pre-packaged food shall carry a label containing information as required here under

- The particulars of declaration on the label shall be in English or Hindi in Devnagri script;
- Pre-packaged food shall not be described on any label that is false, misleading or deceptive or is likely to create an erroneous impression regarding its character in any respect;
- Label in pre-packaged foods shall be applied in such a manner that they will not become separated from the container;
- Contents on the label shall be clear, prominent, indelible and readily legible by the consumer under normal conditions of purchase and use;
- Where the container is covered by a wrapper, the wrapper shall carry the necessary information or the label on the container shall be readily legible through the outer wrapper and not obscured by it.

Labelling of Pre-packaged Foods

In addition to the General Labelling requirements, every package of food shall carry the following information on the label:-

- Name or description of food, List of Ingredients
- Instruction for use
- Best Before and Use by Date, Date of manufacture or packaging
- Country of origin for imported food, Lot/Code/batch identification

- Declaration regarding Food Additives, Declaration regarding Veg or Non veg
- Name and complete address of the manufacturer
- Net quantity-by weight or volume or number
- Nutritional Information per 100 gm or 100ml or per serving of the product shall be given on the label.

Regulations on Labelling Of Food Products In India

Restrictions on Food Labels under Food Safety and Standards (Packaging and Labelling) Regulations, 2011

- Labels shall not contain reference to Act or rules or regulations contradictory to required particulars;
- Unauthorized use of words showing imitation prohibited
- Imitations not to be marked “pure” The word “pure” or any word or words of the same significance shall not be included in the label of a package that contains an imitation of any food.
- There shall not appear in the label of an package, containing food for sale the words” recommended by the medical profession” or any word which imply or suggest that the food is recommended, prescribed, or approved by medical practitioners or approved for medical purpose.

Laws on Import of Food Products In India

Statutory Provision for Import of Articles of Food Section 25 of the FSS Act, 2006 provides that no person shall import into India: - Any unsafe or misbranded or sub-standard food or food containing extraneous matter;

Key Regulations of FSSA

Signage and Customer Notices

It is necessary to understand the statutory and regulatory requirements with respect to signage and customer notices more from the point of view of a food outlet. It is important to note that though the provisions of FSSA do not specifically provide for any statutory and regulatory requirements

either for signage or customer notices, but it has certain provisions with regard to advertisement of products by food business operators.

Section 3 (1) (b) of FSSA defines the term "advertisement" (which includes a "notice") as any audio or visual publicity, representation or pronouncement made by means of any light, sound, smoke, gas, print, electronic media, internet or website and includes through any notice, circular, label, wrapper, invoice or other documents.

Section 24 of the FSSA provides that no advertisement shall be made of any food which is misleading or deceiving or contravenes the provisions, rules and regulations made there under. No person shall engage himself in any unfair trade practice for purpose of promoting the sale, supply, use and consumption of articles of food or adopt any unfair or deceptive practice including the practice of making any statement, whether orally or in writing or by visible representation which:

- falsely represents that the foods are of a particular standard, quality, quantity or grade-composition;
- makes a false or misleading representation concerning the need for, or the usefulness;
- gives to the public any guarantee of the efficacy that is not based on an adequate or scientific justification thereof, provided that where a defence is raised to the effect that such guarantee is based on adequate or scientific justification, the burden of proof of such defence shall lie on the person raising such defence.

FSSA being applicable to all food business operators in India, the provision with regard to advertisements would have to be complied with.

C. Licensing Registration and Health and Sanitary Permits

It is also important to note that FSSA, being the only legislation applicable to the food industry throughout the country, will also apply as far as the national health and sanitary permits are concerned. The Food Safety and Standards (Licensing and Registration of Food Business) Regulations, 2011 (hereinafter referred to as "License and Registration Regulations") govern the aspect of license and registration of a food business operator.

Under Regulation 2.1 of the License and Registration Regulations, all food business operators in the country are required to be registered or licensed in accordance with the License and Registration Regulations, hence no person shall commence any food business unless a valid license

is possessed by the food business operator, and the conditions with regard to safety, sanitary and hygienic requirements have to be complied with at all times by them.

One of the prime purposes of these conditions is to ensure that the food business operator maintains sanitary and hygienic standards as specified in each food category. It is hereby recognized and declared as a matter of legislative determination that in the field of human nutrition, safe, clean, wholesome food is indispensable to the health and welfare of the consumer of the country.

It shall be deemed the responsibility of the food business to comply with the labeling, safety and health and sanitary requirements laid down in the License and Registration Regulations. The labeling requirements are specified under the regulations and they need to be complied with at all times especially with regard to pre-packaged goods.

Penalties

The FSSA provides for penalties in case of any non-compliance. Generally, non-compliance with various provisions of the FSSA may attract penalty of up to Two Lakh Rupees (approx USD 4000). However, under Section 63, it provides that if any person or food business operator (except the persons exempted from licensing under sub-section (2) of Section 31 of FSSA), himself or by any person on his behalf who is required to obtain license, manufacturers, sells, stores or distributes or imports any article of food without license, shall be punishable with imprisonment for a term which may extend to six months and also with a fine which may extend to Five Lakh Rupees (approx USD 9000).

Other Licenses

The FSSA being a central act has to be complied with by all the food business operators in the country. However, India being a big market, each state may have their local laws which may also need to be complied with. Some of the other approvals and licenses that a food operator may be required to obtain from various authorities under other laws include: health and trade licenses from the municipal corporation of the relevant area, environmental clearance, no-objection certificate for fire prevention and safety, registration under the police act of the respective city/state, verification certificate under the Standards of Weights and Measures Act, 1976 for each of the outlets issued by the Department of Legal Metrology of the respective areas, registration under the shops and establishments act of the respective state, eating house license and liquor license.

A license for playing music in restaurants is also required for playing recorded or live music. It is mandatory for a food business to obtain insurance from any insurance company with regard to public policy, product liability, fire policy, building and assets. Other insurances though are not mandatory may be useful if taken.

Some of the other registrations and permissions may include registration under the Employees' Provident Funds and Miscellaneous Provisions Act, 1952 if it is engaging more than 20 employees. Registration is also required under the Central Excise Act, 1944 as in respect of goods specified in Third Schedule of the said act, repacking, re-labeling, putting or altering retail sale price etc. will fall into the category of manufacture. Subject to applicability, other statutory and regulatory compliances may also include registrations under Income Tax Act, 1861, Customs Act, 1962, sales tax, service tax and other labour laws.

Foreign Direct Investment in the Food Processing Industry

Foreign Direct Investment (hereinafter referred to as "FDI") is permissible for all the processed food products under 100% automatic route (except for items reserved for micro, small and medium enterprises, where FDI is permissible under automatic route up to 24%), subject to applicable laws/regulations/securities and other conditions.

Bureau of Indian Standards

Indian standards institution now known as bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) set up on 6 January 1947 BIS is functioning under ministry of consumer affairs, food and public distribution, government of India as a statutory body under BIS act, 1986 with effect from 1st April 1987.

Agmark

The Directorate of Marketing and Inspection enforces the Agricultural Produce (Grading and Marketing) Act, 1937. Under this Act Grade standards are prescribed for agricultural and allied. It functions by:-

- Quality Certification Mark .
- It ensures quality and purity of a product.
- It acts as a Third Party Guarantee to Quality Certified.
- Quality standards for agricultural commodities are framed based on their intrinsic quality.
- Food safety factors are being incorporated in the standards to complete in World Trade.

Standards are being harmonized with international standards keeping in view the WTO requirements. Certification of agricultural commodities is carried out for the benefit of producer/manufacturer and consumer.

Products available under AGMARK are as follows

- Pulses
- Whole spices & ground spices
- Vegetable oils
- Wheat Products
- Milk products.
- Other products such as Honey, Compounded asafetida, Rice, Tapioca Sago, Seedless tamarind, Besan (Gram flour)

National Standards Body of India

Objectives

Harmonious, development of standardization and quality control in national and international arena Certification schemes for products and systems

- Growth and development of Indian industry, commerce and exports
- Consumer protection

Sample Collection Techniques:

The FSO/ Authorized Officer must obtain the following Information;

- name of the food;
- lot number;
- container size or sizes;
- product code numbers;
- labelling information;
- condition of the lot, i.e., broken packages, evidence of rodent or insect infestation, debris, etc.;

Form-B duly completed and signed (in duplicate)

- Blueprint/layout plan of the processing unit
- List of Directors with full address and contact details Name and List of Equipments and Machinery Photo _ I.D and address proof.
- List of food category desired to be manufactured.
- Authority letter with name and address of responsible person nominated by manufacturer along with alternative responsible person.
- Analysis report (Chemical & Bacteriological) of water to be used as ingredient in food from a recognised/public health laboratory to confirm the potability.

Mandate of the Act Food

General Principles to be followed in administration of The Act (section 18)

The Central Government, the State Governments, the Food Authority and other agencies, as the case may be, while implementing the provisions of this Act shall be guided by the following principles, namely: -

- Endeavour to achieve an appropriate level of protection of human life and health and the protection of consumer's interests, including fair practices in all kinds of food trade with reference to food safety standards and practices;
- Carry out risk management which shall include taking into account the results of risk assessment, and other factors where the conditions are relevant, in order to achieve the general objectives of regulations;
- Where in any specific circumstances, on the basis of assessment of available information, the possibility of harmful effects on health is identified but scientific uncertainty persists, provisional risk management measures necessary to ensure appropriate level of health protection may be adopted, pending further scientific information for a more comprehensive risk assessment;
- In case where there are reasonable grounds to suspect that a food may present a risk for human health, then, depending on the nature, seriousness and extent of that risk, the Food Authority and the Commissioner of Food Safety shall take appropriate steps to inform the general public of the nature of the risk to health, identifying to the fullest extent possible the food or type of food, the

risk that it may present, and the measures which are taken or about to be taken to prevent, reduce or eliminate that risk;

●Where any food which fails to comply with food safety requirements is part of a batch, lot or consignment of food of the same class or description, it shall be presumed until the contrary is proved, that all of the food in that batch, lot or consignment fails to comply with those requirements.

These are exciting times for food safety regulations in India. The recent proposals mentioned in the new Draft Regulations will soon be finalized to become the new Food Safety and Standards Regulations, 2015. They will provide new directives in areas such as nutraceuticals and health supplements, which is the need of the hour as these are becoming popular food categories. Standardization for thousands of foods is on the anvil. Food business operators are certainly anticipating some positive changes in food regulations, which could ease product approval process and food operations.

Conclusion

Today, food safety is an important issue with public health implications. Effective means of food quality can be legislative measures, certification schemes and public participation and involvement in the program. There are several acts and regulations that are in force. Violation of these acts is against the law and any person who fails to comply with these codes may have to pay a heavy fine or undergo prosecution. The food operator has a lot to gain by cooperating with the regulatory agencies and conforming to the rules laid down by them. There are some of the Food items which are ban to import in India like Milk and Milk Product, etc.

The preamble of PFA laid emphasis only on provisions for prevention of food adulteration. FSSA lays emphasis on consolidating the laws related to food and to establish FSSAI for laying down science based standards for articles of food and to regulate their manufacture, storage, distribution, sale and import, to ensure availability of safe and wholesome food for human consumption and for matters connected with them. The new objectives clearly go far beyond the objectives of PFA. The strict penalties imposed in FSSA may lead to increase in corruption, as enterprises may resort to unfair practices to avoid these penalties.

Apart from the harmonization of laws relating to food quality and standards with established international norms, FSSA aims at regulating food hygiene and safety laws in the country in order

to systematically and scientifically develop the food industry. Thus, the food processing industry may see FSSAI as a mixed blessing but the practical application of this legislation, being at its nascent stage, will require some time to come into full force.

Hence, there should be a proper implementation of the food law to secure the wastage of food and to establish a proper body which would look over the people who are not following these laws and take action on them.

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- *dr. jitendra p dongare*
- *parna dasgupta head – regulatory, external affairs & csr gskch*

A Study on The Ayurvedic Food Practice Among the Natives of Delhi

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Abstract

Background: Ayurveda is a traditional system of food and medicine that developed in Ancient India. It offers deep insights about food and health based on the nature (*Prakriti*) of individuals. It also defined Health as a state of equilibrium with one's self to the environment. Traditional Ayurvedic text throw light on different medicinal properties of foods from the diversity of natural sources and their medicinal properties in relation to season. The Ayurvedic perspective of good health is entirely different from the modern day allopathic medicinal system of health. The Ayurveda emphasises greatly on the prevention of any disease through good food practice where as Allopathic medicines emphasise on curing the diseases. Modern day health systems are based on personalised medicine and it provides quick and temporary relief from the health-related problems of individuals. Research in the field of Ayurveda would be very important as it would help us in developing relations between good food and good health. It will provide solutions to modern day health problems. Ayurveda takes the holistic view point of health and establishes some of the complex connections with Nature. **Objective:** Objective of the study was to understand the awareness and practice of Ayurvedic food amongst the natives of Delhi. **Methodology:** Correlational quantitative design was used. Locale of the study was New Delhi. Sample size taken was 309. Questionnaire technique was used as tool. For analysis, percentage and mean were used. **Conclusion:** This study will give an insight to the stakeholders of the food industry about the impact of the Ayurvedic food.

Key Words: Ayurvedic food, Health, *Prakriti* of one self

Background

Ayurvedic principles believe in eliminating the root cause of the disease rather than suppressing it. Keeping this in mind, Chauhan et al (2015), mentioned in his study that Ayurveda is a science of life with a holistic approach to health and personalized medicine. It is one of the oldest medical systems, which comprises thousands of medical concepts and hypothesis. Ayurveda has the ability to treat many chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, arthritis, and asthma, which are untreatable in modern medicine.

Guha (2006) said that Ayurveda places special emphasis on *Aahaar* (diet) and *Anna* (food) and believes that healthy nutrition nourishes the mind, body and soul. Ayurveda does not discriminate food to be good or bad, instead it emphasizes various factors that influence food, such as its biological properties, origin, environmental factors, seasons, preparation, freshness, and provides a logical explanation of how to balance food according to one's *dosha* and physical needs. Ayurveda typically classifies *dosha* into three broad categories, viz, *vaat*, *pitta* and *kapha* and balances the diet of an individual in a manner wherein the body attains perfect harmony balancing these *doshas*.

Payyappallimana and Venkatasubramanian (2016) said that Ayurveda recreated the methodologies that enabled the holistic view point about health. Ayurveda unravels some of the complex connections with Nature. As a matter of fact, almost all the medicines mentioned in the Ayurveda are directly derived from natural sources.

Nausad and Priyadarshan (2018) presented a report on the Role of Food in Ayurveda “Whether it can be a lifestyle option or not” which mentioned that the Ayurvedic theories and practices on the health, food and nutrition are quite different from those of biomedicine and modern nutrition. Systematic exploration can provide new insights to the health and nutritional science to provide contemporary solutions in healthcare.

According to Dey and Pahwa (2014) Ayurveda is based on the concepts of *tridosha* and *prakriti* being core philosophies. Tridosha and prakriti concepts allow personalized medicine, treatment and prevention. In the light of modern or current science, evidence has surfaced connecting the concepts of *tridosha* and *prakriti* with metabolic pathways, chronic diseases, and various genotypes.

As per Press Information Bureau, Government of India, Ministry of Science & Technology (2015), Ancient Indians believed that everything that they saw was made up of five elements – Space, Air, Fire, Water and Earth. *Vata* is related to elements of space and air; *pitta* is related to elements of fire and water and *kapha* is related to elements of water and earth. Each individual would have different levels of these three *doshas*, hence the diversity. However, each person can be classified, belonging to one or the other type, if one of the *doshas* predominates.

Sarkar et al (2015) mentioned in their study that there is so much similarity in Ayurvedic dietetics and traditional foods that many of the traditional health foods in India can be called Ayurvedic foods. In the era of globalization of the population and international food trading, health conscious citizens around the globe will benefit from the wealth of knowledge on traditional Indian and Ayurvedic health foods of Indian origin.

Patwardhan (2014) critically analysed the status of Ayurvedic medicine based on personal observations, peer interactions and published research. His reviewed article concluded that traditional knowledge systems like Ayurveda and modern scientific evidence-based medicine should be integrated. The author advocated that Ayurvedic researchers should develop strategic collaborations with innovative initiatives.

Lallanilla (2015), stated that Ayurveda is widely practiced on the Indian subcontinent — more than 90 per cent of Indians use some form of Ayurvedic medicines, according to the University of Minnesota's Centre for Spirituality & Healing — and though, the tradition has gained popularity in the Western world, it is still considered an alternative medical treatment. Ayurvedic medicine is entirely holistic. Its adherents strive to create harmony between the body, mind, and spirit, maintaining that this balance prevents illness, treats acute conditions, and contributes to a long and healthy life.

Rastogi (2010) suggested that a prospective approach through primary understanding of Ayurveda followed by a search into scientific linkage would be more appealing.

Chopra (1990) said that a balanced diet does not revolve around fats, carbohydrates, protein, calories, vitamins and minerals. These nutrients are known to us intellectually, not through direct experience. One cannot detect the vitamin C in his or her orange juice. The knowledge of nutrients comes through laboratory analysis. Ayurvedic nutrition comes directly from the nature. When your taste buds greet a bite of food, an enormous amount of useful information is delivered to the

Prakriti of individuals. Working on that information, Ayurveda allows us to eat a balanced diet naturally, guided by our own instinct. When food talks to your *Prakriti*, it says many things to the different GUNAS – heavy or light, dry or oily, hot or cold – that are present in the food. Ayurveda recognizes six different types of taste: sweet, sour, salty, bitter, pungent and astringent. All spicy food is pungent. Astringent is the taste that puckers your mouth. The tannin in tea is astringent and so is the mealy taste of beans.

Most of the researches worked on Food & Ayurveda have indicated that food plays an important role in building the health of individuals. When the food consumed is not in conformity with rules laid down in Ayurveda, it takes the health of individual into the wrong direction which may lead to much complex diseases in later part of life. But on the other hand, right food practices can lead the individual to a disease-free life. Food also shows history, culture, agriculture of a particular place.

Sengupta et al (2004) mentioned in their study that an impressive amount of data existed in support of the concept that Indian food ingredients can be used in preventive strategies aimed at reducing the incidence and mortality of different types of cancers because of their antioxidative, antimutagenic and anticarcinogenic properties. Vital ingredients used in Indian cooking include turmeric, cloves, ginger, aniseed, mustard, saffron, cardamom and garlic which help in curing and preventing chronic disease.

Lurie (2013) mentioned in his research that in Ayurveda, health centres on nutritious food, and a good digestion depends upon our lifestyle. Our lifestyle depends on our environment, and our environment affects the quality of our food, which in turn affects the quality of our health.

Keeping in mind the importance of food and health this study has been taken up. This study will give an insight to the stakeholders of the food & health industry about the impact of the Ayurvedic food practices among the natives of Delhi regions. We often talk about the rich and diverse cultural heritage of our country but seldom have we realised that the diversity in our cuisines also make our nation in every sense, “Incredible India”.

Objective of the present study was to understand the awareness and practice of Ayurvedic food amongst the natives of Delhi.

Methodology

The research design used for the study is co-relational quantitative design. Locale of the study was New Delhi, India. A sample size of 309 from different age group was taken. Random sampling technique was used for collection of data. The data was digitally collected through Google forms. The data collected was compiled and analysed using percentage, mean and standard deviation.

309 respondents were approached with questions pertaining to the study which included name, age, email address & average annual income of the respondent, and to what extent they knew about Ayurvedic foods, do they really know about *PRAKRITI* of themselves, do they consume foods as per Ayurvedic food and health concepts and what percentage of their income they spent annually on the health of their family members. All the people approached responded enthusiastically so the response rate of the data collection was 100%.

Details of the demography of the respondents are presented in below tables. Table 1(a) shows the details of the age bracket of the respondent. Table 1(b) shows the average annual income of the household of the respondents.

Table 1(a) - Details of the age bracket

Age Bracket	Frequency	Percentage
20 to 29	129	41.70
30 to 39	55	17.80
40 to 49	69	22.30
50 to 59	48	15.50
Above 60	8	2.60

Fig. 1(a) - Details of the age bracket

The age bracket of 20 years above and below 29 years had the highest number of respondents, since the young citizens are more active on the internet.

Table 1(b) - Average annual income of family

Average Annual Income	Frequency	Percentage
Below 5 lakh	142	46.00
5 lakh to 8 lakh	67	21.70
8 lakh to 10 lakh	23	7.40
10 lakh to 15 lakh	30	9.70
Above 15 lakh	47	15.20

Fig. 1(b) - Average annual income of family

Average annual income of 46% of the respondents was below 5 lakh per annum, since the maximum number of respondent were in the age bracket of 20 to 29 years and comprised of people who either were still studying or in the early stages of their professional career.

Findings and Discussion

The objective of the study was Ayurvedic Food Practices among the natives of Delhi Region. To achieve the results for the objective, the question asked to the respondent was to what extent they know about Ayurvedic foods, do they really know about *PRAKRITI* of themselves, do they consume foods as per Ayurvedic food and health concepts and how much they spent annually on the health of their family members. Here, the respondent had to answer on a scale of 1 to 5 wherein 5 indicted the highest value for response and 1 indicated the lowest value for response. The findings of the questionnaire are mentioned below:

Fig. 2 (a): Findings for the objective

The findings for objectives indicated that out of 309 respondents, only 16, i.e., 5.2% of respondent knew in detail about the various aspects of Ayurvedic food and their health benefits whereas 135 respondents, i.e., 43.7% had negligible or very little knowledge about the Ayurvedic foods and their health benefits. 51% of respondents, who had chosen option 3, had moderate knowledge on Ayurvedic foods and health benefits.

The mean value of the aforementioned data is 2.61. This indicated that in spite of the Ayurvedic principles originating in this very country, most of the population in today's time is largely unaware of the various principles and aspects of the Ayurvedic food. This though does not mean that these people do not use food for medicinal benefits. A number of respondents when questioned did suggest that they used food items like ginger and turmeric as a part of their daily, both foods

featuring in Ayurveda for their medicinal properties, but were unaware of the exact benefits of these food items. The above findings are in alignment with the statement of Lallanilla (2015) in the study carried out by University of Minnesota's Centre for Spirituality & Healing wherein it was mentioned that 90 per cent of Indian use Ayurvedic food in some form or the other on a day to day basis.

Fig. 2 (b): Findings for the objective

Do you know about the PRAKRITI of yourself (As per Ayurveda)
309 responses

In process of data collection when respondent were asked question that do you know about the PRAKRITI of yourself (As per Ayurveda), the majority of respondent, i.e., 67% said that they are not aware about their Ayurvedic *PRAKRITI*. These findings are again in line with previous finding wherein a mean of 2.61 clearly indicated that the people are largely unaware about the various benefits of Ayurvedic food.

Fig. 2 (c): Findings for the objective

Do you consume food as Ayurvedic Food & Health Concepts

309 responses

In process of data collection when respondent was asked question do you consume food as Ayurvedic food & health concept, more than one third of respondents, i.e., 36.2 % said that they did not consume food & beverage as per the Ayurvedic concepts, whereas, only 9 respondents, i.e., 2.9% consumed their meals as per the guidelines prescribed by the Ayurveda. Lurie (2013) mentioned in the study that the modern environment is radically different from that of the previous thousands of years, and people are not well educated about how the environment impacts our food, particularly in terms of freezing, microwaving, and processing with chemical additives. Ayurveda proposes that food is best eaten when it is lightly cooked or steamed. Because of this the results of the present study reflects that only 2.9% of the natives of Delhi follow Ayurvedic food practices. The mean for the practice of Ayurvedic food was 2.19 on the rating of 5, which suggest that majority of the people in Delhi do not consume food as per Ayurvedic principles.

This lack of knowledge may largely be due to the fact that the maximum numbers of respondents were youngsters, who, quite understandably, may have been unaware about the large number of principles of Ayurvedic medicines. The above findings are in alignment with the statement of Lallanilla (2015) in the study carried out by University of Minnesota's Centre for Spirituality & Healing wherein it was mentioned that 90 per cent of Indian use Ayurvedic food in some form or the other on a day to day basis.

Table 2 (d): Findings for the objective

Average Annual Expenditure on health of family members	Frequency	Percentage
Below Rs 10000	142	34.3
Between Rs 10001 to Rs 25000	67	34.6
Between Rs 25001 to Rs 50000	23	20.4
Between Rs 50001 to Rs 100000	30	6.1
Above Rs 100000	47	4.5

Fig. 2 (d): Findings for the objective

How much money do you spend annually on the overall health of family members including yourself
309 responses

The table 2(d) indicates that 68.9% of respondent were spending less than Rs. 25,000/- annually on the health of their family members whereas 10.6% of respondents were spending more than Rs. 50,000 per year on the health of their family members.

The findings indicated that the majority of natives of Delhi region do not know about the tremendous potential of Ayurvedic foods and they do not eat their foods & beverage as per their inborn *PRAKRITI* of themselves. As results the natives are getting unhealthier. The natives of Delhi region were also not spending a large amount of money on the health of their family members with more than two third of the respondents spending less than Rs. 25,000 per annum.

Binorkar et al (2018) in his research regarding present status and scope of Ayurveda mentioned that about 47% Ayurvedic students, faculty members and research scholars from various states of India were not appreciating the quality of education provided by Ayurveda institutes and researches conducted therein over their respective states. Approximately 49% participants were satisfied with the field chosen as a career. A significant proportion of participants agreed about the lack of pertinent initiation by Government and research institutes for the reinforcement of Ayurveda. Such findings by different scholars suggest low popularity of Ayurveda so is reflected in the present study. He also concluded that Ayurveda education & research in India can be further strengthened with innovative & creative motivations. Strategies and futuristic plans are essential to be implemented with active initiation by concerned Government bodies for creating awareness among the faculties, students and upcoming scholars of Ayurveda.

The present study results i.e. the knowledge of Ayurveda by common people of Delhi which is just 2.61 mean out of 5 scale rating, suggest that majority of the people do not know about Ayurveda consciously.

Contrary to the results of the present study, Imran et al (2017) concluded in their research that there was widespread utilization of Ayurveda (62%). The complementary and alternative medicine (CAM) was preferred by 60% of the respondents and 71% consider it to be more effective over Allopathy. This study was done in the rural area of Mewat, Haryana. This may be an indication that in metro cities like Delhi, the dependency of Ayurvedic practices are limited i.e. 2.9% whereas in rural areas the dependency is more as seen in the above research.

Conclusion

Ayurveda is a very old system of health care that developed in India during the golden Vedic periods of the country. It is a compilation of knowledge of all Rishi. It asserts that food, science, philosophy and spirituality are necessary aspects for a healthy living. Ayurveda is considered not only a comprehensive medical system but also a way of life. It states that the individual is inseparable from his or her surroundings. The human body is constantly under the influence of vast environmental transformations. Although these changes may not be inherently apparent to the naked eyes, these concepts are unique and establish the fact that individuals should be treated within the context of his/ her surroundings. Similarly, in order to live healthy, one must live in harmony with his/ her surroundings.

The result of present study shows that the natives of Delhi region have moderate knowledge of Ayurvedic foods i.e. 2.61 mean on the scale of 5 and the eating habits of the natives of Delhi are not in consonance with principles of Ayurveda. The natives are not consuming the foods as per their individual PRAKRITI.

Good health is responsibility of individual, society and government. Society and government should promote healthy and holistic lifestyle. Promoting Ayurvedic eating habits to generation millennial would be daunting challenge as so many eating habits and patterns are available to citizen to enhance their life qualitatively and quantitatively. Southern states like Kerala are emerging centre for promoting holistic lifestyle. Ayurveda has deep rooted and wide spread influence on Kerala as mentioned by Nair (2005) in his study.

Recommendations

The wisdom of Ayurveda must be introduced at school level and related professional institute/ culinary institute. Research must be done to develop the Ayurvedic based food recipes as per the PRAKRITI of individual.

Food channels like FOOD - FOOD etc. should promote the traditional wisdom our ancestor and effort should be made to eat Ayurveda food as style of fashion. Vegetarian food, Vegan food should also be promoted by stakeholders.

Ayurvedic food village must be developed by stake holders/ government/ local bodies etc. to promote Ayurvedic Tourism in the Country. The ministry of Tourism & External Affairs should give wide publicity on the foreign soil.

It is really heartening to see a large number of shows on television that are promoting food from various parts of the country. The Ministry of Tourism has taken a wonderful step to promote “Khichdi” as the national dish of India. This not only shows the sensitivity of the Ministry towards a humble yet highly popular and diverse local food which is prepared in a large number of ways. Khichri’s popularity dates back to pre-historic period and is still consumed by many people. Annambhotla (2018) mentions in the website mavcure.com that khichdi is considered as a nourishing, light and simple meal without any spices. It is greatly acknowledged by doctors and recommended to patients especially children and elderly who are recovering from diseases. It is greatly liked by people who pursue a Saatvik diet of Ayurveda. The hotel and catering industry may also come up with the concept of “Kichdi Parlour” to promote Ayurvedic dishes.

For different stakeholders of the food & beverage industry, the Government or NGOs can come up with campaigns on Ayurvedic food at school level. This can help in strengthening the knowledge of the students for Ayurveda and its health benefits. Inter-school Essay competitions, local food fairs, themes in annual day or founders’ day may be selected emphasising Ayurvedic cuisines, educational trips focusing on authentic Ayurvedic food may be planned for the school going children. This will help the children to understand the culture, heritage and Ayurvedic food of our country making them the brand ambassadors of our rich cultural and culinary heritage. Thus, they will not only learn about the wide variety of regional cuisines in our nation, but will also be hungry to explore more and more options as they grow up.

The restaurants, eating joints or other outlets servings authentic Ayurvedic food should be promoted by giving relaxations in licences fee, marketing support in local newspapers and magazines, and likewise. More food festivals should be organised to promote the authentic Ayurvedic food of India.

Ayurvedic centres and spice gardens should be showcased by building the roads through the agricultural belts or orchards as has been done in various parts of Kerala.

The cost of food items should be under the control of the authorities of the region. It is quite an astonishing fact that the price of Ayurvedic products is higher than regular products in the market. Ayurvedic food and ingredients festivals should be organised at various locations to popularizing the health benefits of each ingredients. For example, such promotions can be done at events like Bharat Parv, Kitchen Studios and may be arranged to showcase live cooking shows on Ayurvedic food in public gatherings. This will not only promote Ayurvedic food, but will also allow the people to get their queries answered on the spot.

Going forward, research may also be carried out in the other parts of Country. More Research should be carried out on origin of various popular items, their primary ingredients, Menu planning with Ayurvedic food, methods of cooking and cooking medium used with health benefits across different regions of the country. Studies can also be done on the various Ayurvedic foods that make them stand out from others and attract the connoisseurs towards them.

Statement by Moghadasian (2018) in an article that supports the result of this study is “And as we mature, it becomes harder to welcome new tastes.”There's a phenomenon in nutrition we call programming," If you get used to specific types of food or drink when young, then your brain will be programmed to accept the flavours, colours and other features of these foods." If immigrants are over 35 or 40, he says, they will usually stick to their traditional cuisine, whereas children will adapt to the local food.” So Ayurvedic foods must be introduced to children at very young age.

Government should make concentrated efforts towards organising awareness campaign to promote the Ayurvedic food habits, health benefits of each locally grown ingredient as done in Kerala as one of the study by Augustine (2009), mentions that Ayurveda is the most popular tourism product among the domestic and international tourists. Ninety four percent of the domestic tourists and 81% of the foreign tourists are aware that Kerala is well known for Ayurvedic treatment.

Food Festivals should be organised focusing on the Ayurvedic cooking methods/ styles. Food Shows on the television should also promote the Ayurvedic cooking & food habits.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Festive Food of Haryana

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Abstract

Haryana is a state of great cultural heritage. Haryana is a land where Veda was written on the bank of river Saraswati. A legendary land where Rishi Ved Vyas wrote epic Mahabharata. A land where Lord Krishna delivered the immortal message of Gita to humanity at large at the battlefield of Kurukshetra. Apart from, Haryana is a rich land of festivals, such as Makar Sankranti, Holi, Teej, Deewali, Guga Navmi, Basora etc. Each festival celebrates with an excitement and peoples celebrate festivals with preparing of different kinds of food. As the peoples of Haryana like to have milk and milk products for their daily consumption. In most festivals, they make foods in their homes with milk. With this paper, an attempt has been made to explore the festive foods of Haryana and their recipes. The data has been collected from the various source such as published articles, journals, books and websites. An informal discussion with family has been conducted for gather the more information about festive food those they are prepared for festivals, their recipe and cooking style. It has been found that Kheer, Halwa, Puri, Sakkarpare (Sahwali), Ghewar, Pakode, Malpua (Puda) and Gulgulle are some famous festive foods of Haryana that are made on various festivals.

Keywords: Festivals, Food, Tradition, People, Cuisine, Haryana

Introduction

“Desan me Des Haryana, Jit Doodh Dahi ka Khana”

“Bajre ki tati Roti pe nooni ghee, Sag bna khas ho,

or kundi me ragdi chutney, lassi ka gilasa ho,

Baith ke Chulhe aage Maa ka jimana ho se,

Yo Mera Haryana ho se”

The name of Haryana means the abode of God. It is made with two Sanskrit words ‘Hari’ which mean God and ‘ayana’ which meaning home. It is a land where guests are treated as God. On 1st

November 1966, Haryana came into existence as a newly created state carved out of Punjab state. Haryana represents the face of modern India. the one which is heralding the future yet prides itself of being rooted in its magnificent culture. Today Haryana is positioned among one of the wealthiest and most economically developed regions in South Asia. Haryana is a vivid kaleidoscope of diverse landscapes, showcasing magnificent archeology and celebrating art and culture. A state that has transcended on a journey and preserved the best of both worlds – the footprints of the bygone era and futuristic vision. From being referred to as ‘heaven on earth’ in ancient Sanskrit texts to be the bedrock of Indus valley civilization, Haryana has one of the most unique histories. This land has also witnessed historical battles, including the famous battles at Panipat and has lent canvas for the epic battle of Mahabharata at Kurukshetra. Haryana has been apprised of promoting Highway Tourism and giving a new mark to Hospitality and Tourism Industry. Haryana has a very rich cultural heritage and eating habits. Haryanvi cuisine is also like its people, simple and vigorous. Haryana has maintained simplicity in its food with its agrarian culture. Haryana is well known for its agriculture and cattle wealth, so there is abundance of milk, butter, ghee, lassi, thandai, buttermilk, vegetables which are quite like Punjab. Haryana is also known as ‘land of roties’ as people here are very fond of eating several kinds of roties like wheat, bajara, barley, gram flour etc. Haryana food is famous for its cattle wealth and claim to be the house of popular murreh buffalo and Haryana cow. This is main reason for abundance of milk as well as milk products in cuisine of Haryana. So, cuisine/gastronomy of Haryana is very rich and vibrant and has a wide array of choices in it. It has its own long history and a dominant role in culture and festivals of Haryana. Apart from, Haryana is also a rich land of festivals, such as Makar Sankranti, Holi, Teej, Deewali, Guga Navmi, Basora etc. Each festival celebrates with an excitement and peoples celebrate festivals with preparing of different kinds of food. As the peoples of Haryana like to have milk and milk products for their daily consumption. In most festivals, they make foods in their homes with milk. Keeping the above discussion in view an attempt has been made in this research paper to investigate and explore the festive food of Haryana.

Review of Literature

- Very little study has been attempted on food of Haryana. Even no study has been conducted on festive food of Haryana state.
- Dahiya A. (2012) in his book titled “Food of Haryana: The Great Chutneys” highlighted the features of food accompaniment ‘chutney’, various types of chutneys and investigated the rich food culture of Haryana. Chutneys can be highly spicy, sweet, bland, sour, pungent or a combination of tastes. In his book he has given recipes of thirty-four types of chutneys. They may be raw or cooked. Chutneys are popularly eaten in Haryanvi meals. Most of the people in Haryana enjoy freshly made chutney with their meals. Most of the chutneys at home in Haryana are cooked, spicy and free from oil ghee or any fat. Chutneys are best eaten within 90 minutes after preparation. Majority of Haryanvi people enjoy having a glass full of butter milk (sweet or salted) along with chutney meals.
- Dahiya A. (2013) in his book titled “Food of Haryana: The Great Desserts” highlighted the dessert food of Haryana. Present volume of sweets comes with popularly consumed sweets in the Haryanvi homes. In his book, 57 kinds of dessert dishes include: Laddus, Halwa, Kheer, Burfi, Churma and other desserts. Traditionally, People of Haryana relish sweets at the beginning of meals in villages. A Typical Marriage in village offers Laddus at the beginning of meals to guests.
- Gunjan Malik, Amit Kadyan, Vivek Balyan (2013) examined the food habits of Haryana’s people which include their liking for spicy/ non spicy food, number of meals taken in a day, eating out habits, preferred eating outlets, cooking equipments preferred. It has found that people of Haryana believe in simplicity and prefer eating simple and desi food and that too at home. They don’t prefer eating spicy food and believe in simple living. They are not very outgoing and do not prefer eating out frequently. Haryanvi people consume simple and healthy food so as to perform physical as well as mental work. They use traditional cooking equipments like Chulha and gas stove, but a small percentage is shifting towards the new technology. People of Haryana have healthy eating habits.

- Ram Mehar Attri (2015) found in his paper that the traditional Haryanvi Dishes were still quite popular among the respondents even however there is a clear trend towards growing influence of western food on the food habits of people of Haryana.

Objective The objective of this paper to explore the traditional festive food of Haryana and their recipe.

Methodology

As the aim of paper is to explore the traditional festive foods of Haryana and their recipe. The data has been collected from the secondary source such as published and unpublished articles, journals, books and websites. An informal discussion with family has been conducted for gather the more information about festive food those they are prepared on festivals, their recipe and cooking style.

Festivals of Haryana

*“Aayi Teej Bakhair gi Beej,
Aayi Holi Bhar le gi Jholi”*

A famous quote of Haryanvi on festival, which mean that Teej is the symbol of starting the festival season and Holi as like of ending the festival. All the festivals celebrated with the joy. Different festivals of Haryana as follow:

Makar Sankranti: Makar Sankranti is one of the most auspicious day for the Hindus, and it is celebrated in almost all parts of the country, with great dedication, fervor & fun. The festival of Makar Sankrant traditionally coincides with the beginning of the Sun's northward journey (the Uttarayan) when it enters the sign of Makar (the Capricorn). It falls on the 14th of January every year. Lakhs of people take a dip in places like Ganga Sagar & Prayag and pray to Lord Sun.

Holi: Holi is one of the major festivals of Hindus. Holi is the festival of colours. This festival is celebrated for two to three days. People pour colored water on each other and cook many types of sweets and other food. Holi is celebrated in the spring season because it is welcoming spring. This day is celebrated with joyful colours to mark the victory of virtue and goodness over evil.

Basant Panchami: Basant Panchami is celebrated to welcome the season of spring. People celebrate this festival with much enthusiasm. The main attraction of this festival is kite flying. Basant Panchami is meant to welcome the season of spring as also maa Saraswati known as Shri

Panchami and Saraswati Panchami. It is one of the most colourful and wonderful festivals of Haryana.

Teej Festival: Teej is one of the most celebrating festival of Haryana. On this festival girls play on swings that are set up under trees or open courtyards and sings folk song. Girls and woman get new clothes and accessories from their in-laws, husbands and other family members. Boys fly kites. People prepare churma and sweets especially ghevar at their home. On Teej, the mother sends a baya (which consists of a variety of foodstuffs) or gift to her married daughter. The puja is always performed in the morning time. The baya, is placed on a thaali and place it on a particular chowk (square) that has been decorated where worship will take place and an idol or picture of Parvati has been placed on that particular chowk. In the evenings singing and dancing takes place and women prayers for their husbands' long life and their families.

Gugganavmi: This festival is celebrated on the next day of Janmashtami. This festival is celebrated by both the Hindu and the Islam community and reflects the true secular spirit in the state of Haryana. A dance procession is also taken out in which the Panch Pirs are the main dancers. They sing songs in the honour and praise of Gugga.

Akadshi: Akadshi forms a very important part in the lives of the women in the state of Haryana. The women folks perform some religious rites and rituals for the welfare of their family. They keep fast for the whole and also remain abstained from water. Those who fast on this day are considered to get rid of malefic planetary influences, experience happiness, and gain the right peace of mind to think of Ishvara and attain moksha.

Dushera: It marks the end of "Ramlila" and remembers God Rama's victory over the demon Ravana. Haryanvi's people make kheer, puri and halwa on Dushera festival.

Diwali Festival: The word 'Diwali' means "rows of lighted lamps". It is a festival of lights and which is celebrate in every state with joy. During this festival, people light up their houses and shops with Diyas. It is celebrated to mark the homecoming of Lord Rama from 14 years of Exile and his victory over the Demon Ravana. People buy or make sweets for their own families and send them as presents to their friends and relatives. In Haryana, brother going to sister home with sweets and present before Diwali. At night, the goddess Lakshmi, is worshiped in the form of earthen images and silver rupee.

As Haryana is a state of different culture. Peoples live here from different culture and religion. They celebrate their different festival. Baishakhi by Punjabi and Sikhs, Eid by Muslim peoples. Some other festivals of Haryana are Mahashivratri, Ramnavmi, Karwachauth, Gyas (Served kacchi lassi and ruhafza drink), Amawas&Purnima (prepared kheer, halwa, puri and sabzi).

Festive Food

The food of Haryana is like the people of Haryana - simple, earthy and inextricably linked to the land. In Haryana, the emphasis is on food that is wholesome, fresh and prepared with little or no fuss at all. Food always evolves out of a certain cultural context. The simpler the culture or civilisation, so is the cuisine which is uncomplicated and essentially implies sustenance. Haryana with its essentially agrarian culture has retained simplicity in its cuisine. As discussed above, there are numerous festivals in Haryana and thus, followed by, many mouth-watering and jaw-dropping sweets and meals. Special dishes are prepared and offered to the respective God(s) and seasons play a very important role in celebrations of different festivals. Here are some of the major food delicacies that every person loves to get their mouth on.

Kheer

It is observed that peoples of Haryana are fond of milk and milk products and as we are aware kheer is prepared with milk, which make is more special between them. The people of Haryana like kheer especially which is made with gur (Jaggery). Most of the people in Haryana prepare plain kheer i.e. adding rice to milk till done and eat it with shakkaron top (coarsely ground thin jaggery) both hot and cold. Sugarcane juice kheer also famous in Haryana. However, few do prefer with sugar and nuts. Traditionally kheer is prepared in Haryanvi homes on Holi, Diwali, Guga Navmi, full moon night and Half-moon night along with other festivals as well.

Recipe: (Serving: 4 Portion)

- Ingredients Quantity:
- Full cream milk 1 litre
- Rice 100 gms
- Sugar 150 gms/Grinded Jaggery – 150 gms

Method of Preparation: -

- Take a heavy bottom pan and grease it with pure ghee, especially the bottom of the pan .

- Add milk and give it a boil.
- Wash rice and add in the boiling milk. Mix properly.
- Cook on medium heat, when it starts boiling, lower the heat and cook till rice get cooked well and become soft.
- Keep stirring in between, and gently mash the rice grains with the ladle while mixing.
- Now add sugar and cook on low heat.
- Keep stirring the kheer in between to avoid sticking to the bottom.
- Cook for 5 minutes and serve garnished. (can be served both hot and cold)

Traditionally, kheer is made without sugar and served with bura (Refined Sugar) and shakkar. Almonds, saffron, pistachio, cashewnuts, grated coconut such ingredients can add to make a better taste.

Sevai

Sevai is a pudding made from vermicelli, milk and sugar. Sevai is prepared on Teej and Raksha Bandhan festival.

Recipe: (Serving: 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Sevai (vermicelli) 1cup
- Milk 1 litre
- Sugar 150 gms
- Ghee 30 gms

Method of Preparation:

- Heat ghee in a pan, add Sevai in it and shallow fry it on low heat till it becomes slightly golden. (you can even roast sevai on griddle without fat)
- Pour the milk and let the milk boil for 10-12 minutes on low flame.
- Add milk and sugar, & again allow it cook on low flame till done.

Handmade sevai is often boiled in water with ghee and served hot with bura/shakkar and ghee. At some places in Haryana, it's called as Meethe Joe.

Suji Ka Halwa

Sooji halwa is a simple yet delicious and yummy sweetened semolina fried in ghee and garnished with nuts. It's also popularly known as Sheera in the northern region of India.

Recipe: (Serving: 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Suji (Semolina) 1 cup
- Sugar 1 cup
- Desi Ghee (Clarified Butter) ½ cup
- Water 2.5 cup
- Cashew nuts and Raisins 30 gm

Method of Preparation: -

- Cook semolina in a dry pan preferably with thick base, cook till light to golden brown.
- Add ghee, cook for few minutes
- Cook for a while.
- Add water, stir consistently, cook till water evaporates and the dish leaves ghee on its sides.
- Add nuts (Almond, Cashew nut, Grated Coconut, Raisins)
- Serve hot.

Ghevar

Ghevar (Devanagari) is a sweet traditionally associated with the Teej Festival. It is disc-shaped sweet cake made with all-purpose flour and soaked in sugar syrup. There are many varieties of Ghevar, including plain, mawa and malai ghevar.

Recipe:

Ingredients quantity:

- Refind flour (Maida) 250 gm
- Pure ghee 50 gm
- Sugar 400gm
- Water 100 ml
- Milk 50 gm

- Ghee/oil to fry ghever

Method of Preparation:

- Combine the sugar and water in a pan and simmer till it reaches a 1 string consistency.
- Remove from the heat and keep warm. Combine the flour and melted ghee in a bowl.
- Add water in a thin stream, whisking continuously but at no point should the ghee and water separate.
- The batter should be of a coating consistency. Keep the batter in a cool place away from the heat.
- Place the ghevar mould in a kadhai and pour melted ghee in it till it reaches 3/4 of the height of the mould.
- Heat the ghee on a medium flame and put in one spoonful of the batter into the mould in a thin stream. The batter should settle in the mould.
- When the froth subsides, pour in another spoonful in the centre in a thin stream.
- Increase the flame and allow it to cook in the centre by pouring ladlefuls of hot ghee in the centre of the mould 2 or 3 times.
- When the centre is firm and cooked then Deep in sugar syrup and serve at room temp.

Note: Alternatively, you can use a large mould to get fewer ghevar in which case the cooking time will increase. Rabdi or mava also use on top the ghevar.

Gulgula

Gulgula is a deep-fried dumpling made from wheat flour and jaggery. Gulgulla is made on various festivals in Haryana like Teej, Basora. People of Haryana like to eat gulgule in rainy season.

Recipe: (Serving: 4 Portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- 1/4 cup and 2 and 1/4 teaspoon wheat flour
- 1/3 cup and 1 and 1/4 tablespoon mustard oil
- 1/3 cup and 2 and 1/2 tablespoon cane sugar
- water as required

Method of Preparation:

- To start with, take a bowl and add hot water, cane sugar in it. Let the cane sugar dissolve in the bowl. Once dissolved, let it cool down. In a bowl, combine flour, cane sugar and little water in order to make a smooth paste.
- Take a kadai and keep it on medium flame. Heat oil in the kadai and one by one insert the mixture with the help of a spoon in the kadai. Deep fry the gulgula. Keep in mind to fry it till golden brown from both the sides.

Sawali

Shakkarpare (Sawali) Sakkarpore or Sawali is a deep-fried crunchy sweet dish of wheat flour and jaggary made on Teej festival.

Recipe: (Serving 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Whole Wheat Flour 200 gms
- Pure ghee 200 gms
- Jaggery 75 gms

Method of Preparation:

- Take 3 cups of water in a pan and heat till the first boil.
- Put Jaggery and let it melt and mix with water.
- Make a hard dough with flour, Ajwain and jaggery water and add two tea spoons of ghee in while making dough.
- Make small sized about 3-inch diameter and point 5 cm thick round shaped chapattis.
- Take a kadhai, pour ghee in kadhai.
- Deep Fry sawalis and store in air tight container.

Pude

Pude is also known as Malpua. It is a shallow frying sweet bread of wheat flour and jaggery made on Teej, Basora, Guga Navmi and in rainy season.

Recipe: (Serving 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Wheat flour 200 gms
- Mustard Oil/Pure ghee for shallow frying
- Jaggery (Gur) 200 gms

Method of Preparation:

- Take one cup water in a pan, add jaggery and remove from heat once mixed well.
- Make semi-liquid mixture with wheat flour and above jaggery solution.
- Heat mustard oil/ghee on a flat pan.
- Pour a ladle full of mixture in the form of pancake.
- Cook on medium heat. Turn it over when it starts to colour slightly. When both sides are done, drain and served.
- Tastes well if served with Mango Pickle.

Churma

Churma is made with Roti, Clarified Butter (Desi Ghee) and Jaggery or Sugar. Churma (Dal Bati Churma) is also famous sweet dish of Rajasthan.

Recipe: (Serving 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Wheat flour 250 gms
- Pure ghee 150 gms
- Shakkar (Coarsely ground Jaggery) 150 gms

Method of Preparation:

- Make soft dough with wheat flour.
- Keep it for half an hour and prepare equal quantity of balls.
- Prepare Chapati/ Roti.
- Now grind the Chapati or mash with the hands add desi ghee and gur.
- Make oval shaped balls and Churma is ready to serve.

Meethe Chawal

It is sweet preparation of rice. Rice is boiled in sugar or gur. Meethe chawal is prepared on Basora festival and as parsad of peer(God). The rice prepared in night and in morning (before sunrise) gives the bhog to Thandi Mata.

Recipe: (Serving 4 portion)

Ingredients quantity:

- Jaggery/Sugar as per your taste
- Rice 1 glassful
- Water 3-4 glasses
- Desi Ghee 2 to 3 tablespoons.

Method of Preparation:

- To start with, we make a syrup of gur (jaggery) by boiling it in a large pan with 1 glass of water.
- Meanwhile, we take a glass full of rice and wash it a large bowl with normal water.
- Now, take a spoon and check if the syrup is prepared, if you still find pieces of gur in there let it be for 2-3 more mins. on mid flame.
- Let the syrup cool down and meanwhile take a cooker put washed rice in it and ghee and a glass full of normal water and now put the syrup.
- Close the lid carefully and after one full whistle, let the pressure cooker cool down for 5 min.
- Open the lid carefully and serve meethe chawal with cold milk.

Apart from above discussed dishes, roti-bura-ghee, ghee-bura-chawal, pakode, ghee-shakkar-chawal, puri-sabzi, and Mathi etc. are some another food of Haryana which are prepared widely in festivals.

Cooking Style

All the dishes prepared in Haryana on Chulha and hara (A round shaped mud made small tandoor). Chulh, Hara, Uple/Kande/Dung Cake .Wood, and uple used as fuels in it. Uple is also known as kande/gosse or buffalo/cow dung cake. Even now a day in villages, peoples prefer to prepare on

chulha and hara. Peoples said that food prepared on chulha and hara is more delicious in comparison of gas and other modern cooking equipment.

Conclusion

The food of Haryana is like the people of Haryana - simple, earthy and inextricably linked to the land. In Haryana, the emphasis is on food that is wholesome, fresh and prepared with little or no fuss at all. Food always evolves out of a certain cultural context. The simpler the culture or civilization, so is the cuisine which is uncomplicated and essentially implies sustenance. Haryana with its essentially agrarian culture has retained simplicity in its cuisine. As the Indian likes to eat sweet dish in all festivals and happiness moments, the Haryanvi's peoples also like to eat sweet dishes in festival occasion. It has been concluded that kheer, malpua, gulgulle, sevia, shakkarpare, halwa, meethe chawal and pakode are traditional festive foods of Haryana. Gur found widely used sweetened ingredients in sweet preparation instead of sugar because its benefits. All the dishes prepared in Haryana on Chulha and hara (A round shaped mud made small tandoor in which uple used as fuel). Even now a day in villages peoples prefer to prepare on chulha and hara. Peoples said that food prepared on chulha and hara is more delicious in comparison of gas and other modern cooking equipment.

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Food, Culture and Tourism: The Changing Scenario

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Abstract

Tourism is a growing industry in India. The World Travel and Tourism Council calculated that tourism generated 15.24 crore or 9.4% of the nation's GDP in 2017 and supported 41.622 million jobs, 8% of total employment. This sector is predicted to grow at an annual rate of 6.9% or 32.05 lakh crore by 2028. The World Food Travel Association estimates that food and beverage expenses is around 15% to 35% of all tourism spending depending on the affordability of the destination.

Food is a physical necessity. To live we have to eat. Our health and physical fitness depends on taking nutritious and balanced diet. Choice of food varies from person to person and place to place. Food is related with religion and culture of a person. Food is a bridge between land and culture, through taste, food preparation and the whole eating environment. In this research paper an attempt has been made to highlight: (a) Importance of food in tourism promotion, (b) Food and culture interlinked (c) New trends in Tourism: changing attitude of Tourists and (d) The factors which can promote culinary tourism in particular and tourism industry in general.

Importance of Food in Tourism Promotion

Food is one of the essential elements of tourist experience. For many tourists while booking a holiday destination food is also a significant factor in the decision-making process. A tourist today can easily collect data through website about hotels, restaurants, local food and select a destination accordingly. Many popular tourist destinations remain popular because of food. So a unique and memorable culinary identity is an indispensable asset for any successful tourist destination. Culinary tourism could be commercial, domestic, festive or ordinary. It involves restaurants, special food stores, food events, cooking classes, cook books through which food reaches the customers. . Food serves both as entertainment and as cultural activity and helps in tourism promotion.

For many tourists when booking a holiday, the destination image alone is no longer a key element, as food is also now a significant part in this decision-making process when tourists are choosing a destination. Furthermore, there are tourists who travel to a destination purely because of the food,

likewise there are other tourists who do not have food as their main reasons for travel but who are key foodies, and who will seek out authentic food and base on their judgement of the destination upon that food. Food is the essential components while on vacation. Sightseeing begins and ends with an indulgence in the local cuisine. In fact, many popular tourist destinations remain popular only because of the food. The concept intends to allow the tourist to explore and connect across regions and cultures. In other words, it is noted that a great food experience not only boosts tourism, but also the destination. Europe, Asia and the Far East thrive on the significant role that food have on tourism.

Food and Culture interlinked

Culture is the mirror of a nation. It is reflected through the art, faith, religious beliefs, festivals and food habits of the people. Culture promotes tourism so also food. Culinary Tourism encourage tourists to visit a place famous for some specific food. The tourist can get information about food and tour through brochures, advertisements in social media, newspaper etc. Besides these tangible aspects, the tourists can experience through food, intangible aspects like knowledge base into religion, customs and traditions, history and culture are interlinked.

New trends in Tourism: changing attitude of Tourists

Today's tourist is more cultured than visitors of 20 years ago, is well travelled, is searching for new experiences, is concerned about the environment, is interested in taking part in a health/well-being lifestyle and wants to experience the local culture when he goes on holiday. Trend analyst, Ian Yeoman writes that food is a significant aspect of the tourist's experience of a destination, driven by the growing trends of authenticity and the need to have a high-quality experience. Food tourism shapes gastro destinations such as France, Italy and California whereas in emerging destinations such as Croatia, Vietnam and Mexico food plays an important part of the overall experience.

Special food in Odisha

Odisha, the land of Lord Jagannath, has a very rich religious culture and this is reflected in the food as well. Odia cuisine is very simple yet delicious, prepared in little or no oil which not only enhances the taste, but makes them very healthy as well. Here, you will find a mix of vegetarian and non- vegetarian dishes. Again, people here loves eating sweets and may be this is the reason they themselves are so lovable

The state of Odisha is so diverse and vibrant that each of its district exhibits a unique tradition, culture and even a distinctive food specialty. Such is their appetizing taste, that these delicacies should have rightly found a place in India's desirable food map. The special dishes of some of famous districts of Odisha are-

- **Dahibara Aludum, Cuttack**

This legendary street food needs no introduction but for those who haven't had it yet, it's a must try. Dahibara when combined with a little hot & spicy aloodum and ghuguni gives such a heavenly taste that the inhabitants of Cuttack simply drool and preach about it. Moreover, when garnished with finely chopped onions and coriander leaves, it renders an unforgettable savour.

- **Bara, Dhenkanal**

Typically served as a traditional tiffin in various parts of Odisha, the Bara of Dhenkanal is said to be the tastiest and relishing. Crispy from outside and tenderly soft from within, Bara is prepared from black-gram dal or urad dal along with rice. This cuisine lures many for its luscious taste and aroma.

- **Badi, Keonjhar**

Unique in itself for its crispiness & taste, these badis are made up of black-gram being grinded on a slit-stone and given the shape of a flower, making it a rather eye-catching dish. PhulaBadi's are delicate & fragile in nature because of their light weight. Whether eaten in a roasted or fried manner, it tastes delectable when consumed with rice or even solely.

- **Rasabali Kendrapara**

Offered to Baladevjew and believed to have originated from the Baladevjew Temple of Kendrapara, Rasabali happens to be the most famous sweet dish found in this province of Odisha. Soaked in thick flavoured milk and garnished with cardamoms on top, this authentic reddish-brown toothsome dish is even served as one of the chappanabhogas at Lord Jagannath temple.

- **Chena Poda, Nayagarh**

This is the quintessential cheese dessert of Odisha. The enduring taste of burnt cottage cheese equaling with the sweet sugar syrup that's added to it, makes the taste of

ChhenaPoda kind of hard to forget. Though available at many places, but Nayagarh happens to be the birthplace of this sweet dessert. And to add onto the flavour, dry fruits like cashew nut and raisins are mixed during its preparation.

- **Mudhi Mansa, Baripada**

Baripada, a small town of Mayurbhanj district, gained enormous popularity for its mudhi (puffed rice) and mansa (mutton) combination. You have to try it to believe it, that Mudhi tastes utterly delectable with its mutton gravy counterpart. Not only do the denizens have it with this gravy, instead they prefer having it with anything and everything starting from tea to a list of endless things.

- **ChhenaJhili, Nimapada**

ChhenaJhili's birthplace happens to be Nimapada which is a town notified under the Puri district of Odisha and is preferably known for this popular dessert. Although one can get it all over the state, but the craving for Nimapada's ChhenaJhili is just and righteous. This delectable sweet is prepared by frying fresh cheese balls and caramelising it with sugar syrup, making it a sweet dish not to be missed while visiting Odisha.

- **Achaar&Papad, Berhampur**

Berhampur, the Silk City of Odisha, is situated in Ganjam district. Not just noted for the intricately designed silk sarees, Berhampur is highly famous for its Achaar&Papad. This duo gives such a heavenly zest to the mouth that it is liked by the folks of Odisha, just any day & anytime!

- **Khaja, Puri**

A typical and unique sweet used as one of the chappanabhogas of Lord Jagannath in Puri, Khaja is prepared in the temple of Lord Jagannath daily and served as a mouth-watering prasad. Starting from the Shree Mandir to the street side shops, this cuisine is found nearly in every corner of Puri. And what makes this extraordinary cuisine famous is its crispiness along with the flavours of sugar-coat that is layered on top of it.

- **Rassoguolla, Salepur (Cuttack)**

A syrupy dessert made from ball shaped dumplings looks alike of the Indian cottage cheese balls dipped in semolina and caramelized with sweet sugary syrup. Rassogolla is what makes Salepur pretty famous and unlike other counterfeits which are spongy and whitish

in color, this desi version is brownish which melts in the mouth as soon as one has it. BikalanandaKar's Rassogolla are the famous ones in town serving this sweet delicacy over the years.

- **Kora Khai, Bhubaneswar (Khurda)**

Believed to be a traditional Odia food, Kora Khai has a special mention when it comes to offering in temples. Served as prasada at the famous Lingaraj temple of Bhubaneswar, this eatable is extremely famous for its taste. Prepared from spices like cinnamon and cardamom along with puffed rice, and caramelized with jaggery or sugar, coconut pieces and cashew on top, Kora Khai is a perfect blend of taste. Baya Baba Kora Khai in Old Town area of Bhubaneswar is one of the noted outlets selling Kora Khai.

- **Gajja, Balasore**

Though there exist many authentic and traditional dishes in Balasore, Gajja serves to be one of the famous cuisines of Odisha. Blended with a mix of sugar and semolina, which afterwards is dried and then fried before being wrapped up in sugar syrup, Gajja is another type of Rassogolla that will elevate your sweet buds.

- **PaluaLadu, Bhadrak**

One of the sweetest desserts originated from the state of Odisha's Bhadrak district, PaluaLadu is a special kind of ladu that one can ever taste. Available at some of the best locations in Bhadrak including the ones at Sai Sweet Stall, the recipe of its making is still guarded secretly since decades.

- **Chaula Bara, Bolangir**

Bolangir, the culturally rich city of Odisha offers a wide range of mouth-watering delicacies but what makes it more remarkable is chaula bara. Rice which is the primary food component in this part of the state, serves to be the chief ingredient for preparing this delicacy. And what adds up to its ravishing taste even more is the sour and spicy chutneys served alongside.

Factors Motivating Food Tourism

- **Disposable Income and Spending Patterns**

All across world, growing affluence of the population has a profound impact on consumer spending. Consumers spend a higher proportion of their income on prepared food, gourmet products, eating out and food items with some form of health or ethical benefits. In today's society, with so many people having a lot more disposable income, tourists are better informed, well-travelled and more culturally aware ready to spend on food.

- **Demographics and Household Change**

According to research by the Future Foundation families are also becoming increasingly democratic in food choice, as children get older they have more influence in what they eat and where the family eats. By 2015, those aged between 45 and 59 will be part of the most populous age group in the United Kingdom who have earning capacity and so spend more on food. Households headed by those aged 50 plus will account for around 50% of all households, and this same age group will account for over 39% of all consumers spending on leisure goods and services.

- **Individualism**

Individualism means uniqueness as tourists search out local, fresh and good quality cuisine that reflects the authenticity of the destination. The search for authenticity has been identified as being central to tourism motivation, and food provides opportunity for many authentic encounters with different cultures.

- **The Multi-Cultured Consumer**

The whole process of globalization has significantly amplified the meaning of the term multi-culturalism within our social order. Access to an even wider range of ideas and interests has never been easier. The Internet boom, the expansion in specialist and minority TV channels, the relentless growth in international tourism, etc., combine to stretch perceptions and eliminate that what we might call mono-culturalism; seeing the world through only one set of pre-ordained, inherited notions. The consumer of today will watch the latest Bollywood film, consume a curry, purchase exotic spices for cooking and will read about Rajasthan in the latest edition of the Lonely Planet. Multiculturalism has now

become an everyday concept in the daily life of the consumer; today curry is the United Kingdom's favourite dish.

- **The Role of the Celebrity Chef and Media**

The media has substantial influence in determining food product selection. The emergence of the niche food programs, TV channels and magazines means the food celebrity and expert has been created. Today, that celebrity chef shapes tourism products.

Well-Being and Food

There is a higher awareness of health issues and food purchase decisions. Around 30% of adults say that they have been eating less fat and sugar compared to the previous year and 28% say they are eating less salt, whereas other food groups, notably vegetables, fruit and bread/cereal/pasta/potatoes are on the rise. Restaurants are also aware of specialist diets, whether it is catering for gluten free or the Atkins diet. Consumers will even visit a food nutritionist or advisor or seek opinion about 'food balance' or 'sensitivity towards certain foods'. The specialist diet is becoming more mainstream with individuals avoiding certain foodstuffs like 'dairy products' or the promotion of detox diets to cleanse the body. Consumers are therefore becoming ever more demanding and cautious regarding the food they eat. These concerns and fears can be exploited in order to maximize potential marketing of certain products.

Thus, Culinary Tourism is one of the fundamental economic drivers of tourism. It has been hailed as a vehicle for regional development, strengthening local production. Food tourism is an important niche that fosters economic and community development inserting new intellectual insights. Through food the culture of the area is reflected and that encourages tourists to visit the destination again and helps in tourism promotion.

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Intangible Cultural Heritage: A Case Study of Tathera Community of Punjab

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Abstract

Culture is the comprehensive pattern of human knowledge, belief and behavior that depends upon the capacity for learning and transmitting to the succeeding generations. Culture cannot be touched, it can only be felt. Hence, it is intangible. It encompasses aspects like religion, lifestyle, customs, traditions etc. The Intangible Cultural Heritage is one of the paramount values that make a nation gain a stature on the world platform. According to UNESCO, Intangible Cultural Heritage means “the practices, representations, expressions, knowledge, skills – as well as the instruments, objects, artifacts and cultural spaces associated therewith – that communities, groups and, in some cases, individuals recognize as part of their cultural heritage”. It can only be experienced through a vehicle giving expression to it called ‘Human Treasures’ by the UN. At the critical moment when Intangible Cultural Heritage is inching towards the stage of cessation due to modern cultural shock owing to globalization, it is important to keep Intangible Cultural Heritage active for its survival for a long-time and sustainable economic growth. This paper is aimed at exploring the evolving concept of Intangible cultural heritage in the context of Tathera Community of Punjab. The Intangible Cultural heritage of Tathera community is on the verge of gradual demise and it is becoming extinct due to a number of factors. This paper also sets out to highlight the level of satisfaction of locals from Tathera Community and the perception of tourists towards it as a tourist spot. It also suggests the measures for safeguarding of Intangible Cultural Heritage in the Tathera Community. The principal results of this research will be handy for not only to the government but also for those seeking to preserve Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Keywords: Intangible Cultural Heritage (ICH), Tathera Community, Cultural, Heritage, Intangible

Introduction

Culture is people's way of life. It is the characteristic of group of people defined by everything they possess such as language, religion, lifestyle, belief, attitude, food, rituals, customs, behavior, etc. Culture is a set of knowledge acquired overtime. Heritage, on the other hand, is the valued objects and qualities such as historic buildings and cultural traditions that have been passed on from previous generations. It could be tangible, intangible or natural heritage. Thus, culture and heritage have one thing in common i.e. both are inherited from the previous generations. Each individual undoubtedly carries many different sorts of heritage which may be in the form of physical material or spiritual values which reflect in their norms and traditions.

The definition of Cultural Heritage has developed with history. At present, it doesn't end at monuments and collection of objects. It also includes traditions or living expressions inherited from our ancestors and passed on to our descendants, such as oral traditions, performing arts, special practices, rituals, festive events, knowledge, and practices concerning nature and the universal knowledge & skill to produce traditional crafts. The Cultural heritage could either be in tangible or intangible form. The tangible cultural heritage or Cultural Property can be touched and felt whereas the intangible cultural heritage can only be seen as an abstract attribute. The tangible cultural heritage could either be moveable like paintings, pottery, books, epics, verses etc or immovable like buildings, monuments, gardens etc. However most of Cultural Heritage is Intangible like songs, dance, cuisine, festivals, drama, skills etc. They can't be touched but can be preserved in museums with the help of technology. According to United Nations (UN), the Intangible Cultural Heritage can only be experienced through a vehicle giving expression to it called 'Human Treasures'.

UNESCO initiated the process of addressing on the issue of Intangible Cultural Heritage in 1972 to ensure the proper identification, protection, conservation and presentation of the world's heritage as far as possible. Progressively, major efforts have been made in this respect, which justify and support the fieldwork and the creation of specialized systems of knowledge management. The following could be mentioned as milestones of such efforts taken at international level:

Source: Preservation and Documentation of ICH; the strategic Role of the Library and Information Science professionals in Srilanka by Navaneethakrishanan (2013)

Intangible cultural heritage (ICH) was defined in various frameworks. In 1989 during the 21st General Conference, UNESCO represented a group of recommendations for safeguarding the traditional culture and folklore. The conference intended on discussing the idea of folklore in totality. According to the discussions, it was found out that folklore is a tradition-based creation of a cultural community, expressed by individuals or groups of the community that reflect its cultural and social identity. Its forms are, among others, language, literature, music, dance, games, mythology, rituals, customs, handicrafts, architecture and other arts.

UNESCO (2003) in its convention on Safeguarding of ICH proposed 5 broad domains in which ICH is manifested:

- Oral traditions and expressions
- Performing Arts
- Social practices, rituals and festive events
- Knowledge and practices concerning nature and the universe
- Traditional craftsmanship

UNESCO clearly tells that the boundaries between domains are extremely fluid and often vary from community to community. It's difficult to impose rigid categories. For example, while one community might view their chanted verse as a ritual, another would interpret it as a song. India, known for its cultural diversity and heritage has countless cultures, traditions, craftsmanship and handicrafts. There are notable communities like the Baiga tribe of Madhya Pradesh, the Banjaras. Craftsmanship like the art of making Banarasi and Kanjeevaram Saree, pottery, carpet-making, Zardozi Embroidery etc. Traditions and rituals like Pind Daan rituals in Gaya (Bihar), Aarti during Dev Deepawali in Varanasi and many more. From India, a total of 13 Intangible cultural heritage (ICH) elements been inscribed till date on the UNESCO's Representative List

of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity including like tradition of Vedic chanting, Ramlila- the traditional performance of the Ramayana, Yoga and Kumbh Mela.

Punjab has a well-endowed tradition of arts and crafts. The wealth of the land is reflected in its handicraft. The people of Punjab are very particular about their artistry and the minute details of their work. The Art of Basketry, Durry-making, Paranda-making, Phulkari-making etc are quite a few notable craftsmanship from Punjab. UNESCO, in 2014 recognized the traditional brass and copper craft of utensil making of the Thatheras of Jandiala Guru.

Case Study: Tathera Community

The Tathera Community resides in a town named Jandiala Guru in the Amritsar district of Punjab, India. The Municipality was created in 1867 during Colonial period of British rule and formed part of Amritsar Tehsil. The members of this community are known as ‘Tatheras’.

This Community is reputed for its age-old tradition of brass and copper craft of utensil making among the Tatheras of Jandiala Guru. In 2014, UNESCO has been inscribed on the UNESCO’s Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. It was announced at UNESCO’s 9th session of Inter-Governmental Committee for safeguarding of ICH in Paris, France.

Jandiala Guru has population of 29,232 of which 15,655 are males while 13,577 are females as per report released by Census India 2011 (www.census2011.co.in). Out of the abovementioned population size, barely 20 families are left in this Community that carries their tradition to the next generation. The town has religious diversity. A number of popular and well visited religious places for Sikhs, Hindus, Jains and Muslims exist in and around the town. The craft of the Thatheras constitutes the traditional techniques of manufacturing brass, copper and ‘Kansa’ (an alloy of copper, zinc and tin) utensils. The skills of Tatheras are transmitted from one generation to the next generation. These craft utensils of Thatheras have both utilitarian and ritualistic value. They have a unique ethnic and historical identity with an oral tradition that underpins their skill i.e. all the expertise and skills pertaining to their traditional craft are passed on to the younger generations in a verbal manner. The Thatheras crafts colony was established in Jandiala Guru, Punjab during the reign of Maharaja Ranjit Singh (1883) – the great 19th Century Sikh Monarch. Thus, Jandiala Guru became an area of repute due to the skill of Tatheras.

Review of Literature

The relationship between intangible heritage and tourism is one of the most discussed subjects in recent years by the academic literature. Thus, an important part of the recent articles accept the idea that in order to safeguard the Intangible Cultural Heritage of any nation, it has to be practiced continuously so that it doesn’t freeze and contribute to the tourism development. Mohamed Badry Kamel Basuny Amer (2016) has discussed on the role of ICH in the process of sustainable development where as Nur Izzati Mohd Rodzia, Saniah Ahmad Zakib and Syed Mohd Hassan

Syed Subli (2013) have presented past studies on tourism in relationship to ICH. They have also highlighted the positive and negative aspects between cultural tourism and ICH.

Nobuo ITO (2001) has stressed upon the relationship between intangible culture and tangible cultural heritage. Francisco González Santa Cruz and Tomás López-Guzmán (2014) have contributed to the study of the relationship between WHS and Cultural Tourism. Furthermore, there are different studies in which relationship between role of libraries, museums and Intangible cultural heritage is analyzed. Navaneethakrishnan (2013) has stressed upon the professional development of librarians in the process of safeguarding of ICH. Marilena Alivizatou (2006) has pointed out the role of ethnographic museums and social history museums in the way ICH is being dealt.

Among others we can highlight those focused on the relationship between World Heritage Sites and Tourism. Research work has been done on World Heritage Sites of countries like Egypt, Spain, China, Malaysia and Singapore, to name a few. Judy Xu (2009), Rebecca A. Clay (2015) have emphasized on the community participation as the key to preserve Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Dr. Gerald Pocius (2002), Paolo D. Farah and Riccardo Tremolada (2008) have discussed the laws and legislations that prevail in the field of Intangible Cultural Heritage.

Jack Tsen-Ta Lee (2016), Ozlem karakul (2009) and Nur Izzati Mohd Rodzia, Saniah Ahmad Zakib & Syed Mohd Hassan Syed Subli (2013) have accentuated on the fact that the any tangible culture must be supported by intangible value and any intangible culture must rely on the tangible things to be visualized.

In the Indian context, ICH preservation is not a new concept. Even prior to the UNESCO Convention there were so many attempts in safeguarding the ICH. In 1984, the Indian National Trust for Art and Cultural Heritage (INTACH) was founded. Since 1984, INTACH has pioneered the conservation and protection of India's natural and cultural heritage and is today the largest membership organization in the country dedicated to conservation of ICH. Today it has chapters in 170 Indian cities, as well as chapters in Belgium, and the United Kingdom.

As far as the research work is concerned, work of Sashi Bala (2006) presents a focus on the need of Digital documentation to help in record step by step procedure of the addition or deletion of anything in ICH. An emphasis has also been laid on the need of National Inventory System for the

identification of categories for documentation of ICH. However, there is not enough literature available on ICH in the Indian scenario.

Research Gap

Globally various authors have contributed significantly to the subject of Intangible Cultural Heritage and most of them have emphasized on its changing definition followed by elucidating the measures to safeguard ICH. However, on the national level, not many researches have been undertaken in this area. Moreover, no research has been done on Tathera Community of Punjab in particular. Hence, this paper has described the significance of the chosen community and its value towards ICH. The tourism aspect for this community is also elaborated.

Research Methodology

The objective of this paper is to put impetus on the concept of ICH with the case Study of Tathera Community. It uses a mixed methodology including both quantitative & qualitative approaches and case study as research strategies in order to have the best possible understanding of such an abstract and complex topic. It is a descriptive research paper which is explorative in nature. The paper is conceptual; paper based on literature review and secondary data. Primary Data has been gathered from semi-structured interviews of members of Tathera Community via a questionnaire survey in order to analyze the existing situation of ICH in tourism development. Observations & field notes were made by the researchers with an aim to analyze the attitude of community members towards their own traditional skill of utensil making. The survey instrument i.e. the questionnaire with demographic information and 12 items was formulated in both English and Punjabi language for the easy understanding by the respondents. Using an intercept approach, the respondents were randomly intercepted in the Tathera community of Jandiala Guru. Data collection via an intercept approach was selected as it enabled the researchers to access potential respondents over a short period of time, screen potential respondents and allowed respondents to seek clarifications of questions, if needed. Survey of 120 respondents was collected out of which 96 questionnaires were found out to be valid, remaining 24 were not acceptable because of incomplete information and reluctance in filling the questionnaire. The data analysis was done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) 22.0 for windows.

Findings

Among 96 respondents, 64 (66.7%) were male and 31 (32.3%) were female. It was found out that the average age of respondents was 43.51 or 44 years approximately. Majority of the respondents were undergraduate with the frequency of 74 (77.1%). However, 18 (18.8%) were graduate and 4 (4.2%) were post-graduate and above. The occupation statistics of the respondents shows that 44 (45.8%) of the respondents were occupied as a labor/worker followed by 36 (37.5%) being engaged in business activities. Respondents working in government sector stood at 6 (6.3%) only. Also, 10 (10.4%) of respondents were engaged in other occupations which was not mentioned by them. In order to learn if the people of Tathera Community knew about the recognition given to their handicraft by UNESCO, we asked if they are aware of this fact. The following data emerged out of the r

esponses received:

Table 1: Statistics of Community Knowledge of respondents regarding UNESCO's recognition of the community

Valid	96
Missing	0
Mean	1.86
Mode	2

Table 1 suggests that the mean (average) value is 1.86 indicating that average respondents are not aware of the fact that UNESCO has recognized Tathera community. The mode value is 2 indicating that majority of respondents chose the option 'No'. The respondents were asked to outline the key problems that are being faced by the community in sustaining the tradition of Utensil making. The following data has emerged from the responses received:

Table 2.1: Statistics of Community's Opinion On The Key Problems Faced By The Tathera Community In Sustaining

Valid	96
Missing	0
Mean	2.18
Mode	1

Table 2.1 indicates that the mean (average) value is 2.18 indicating that average respondents felt that Competition is the main problem in sustaining their tradition. The mode value is 1 indicating that majority of respondents felt that the Community is facing a lot of competition.

Table: 2.2 : Community’s Opinion wise distribution of respondents on the key problems faced by the Tathera community in sustaining the tradition of Utensil making

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Competition	35	36.5	36.5	36.5
Technological Advancements	24	25.0	25.0	61.5
Lack of Demand	23	24.0	24.0	85.4
Others	14	14.6	14.6	100.0
Total	96	100.0	100.0	

The table 2.2 indicates that out of 96 respondents, 35 (36.5%) of respondents opined that competition is the biggest problem being faced by the community. 24 (25%) of respondents perceived technological advancements, 23 (24%) of respondents considered lack of demand and 14 (14.6%) of respondents felt there are other key problems faced by the community in sustaining their tradition of hand-made brass utensils and jewelry making.

Chart: Bar Chart depicting the key problems faced by the community in sustaining their tradition. To find out the satisfaction level of members of Tathera Community, post the recognition of this community, by UNESCO, Friedman’s rank Sum Test was applied on the information given by 96 respondents. For the same, the researchers generated a Null Hypothesis (H0) - “There is no

significant difference between the ranked opinions of the locals of Jandiala Guru after Tathera Community was recognized by UNESCO”. The following data emerged:

Table 3: Ranked Opinions of Locals of Jandiala Guru post recognition of Tathera Community UNESCO	
Opinion Statement	Mean Rank
Increase in the tourist footfall	4.91
Improved Standard of Living	4.18
Expansion of the Community	4.15
Increase in funding by the Government	1.77
Preservation of the community	4.63
Improved connectivity of other cities	7.70
Opening up of new hotels	7.06
Increase in the demand of Handmade Utensils	5.42
Downfall in the migrations to the cities	5.19

Source: SPSS

Table 3 indicates the mean ranks of the statements on the 5 point Likert Scale question (1= Strongly Disagree to 5= Strongly Agree). The highest mean rank 7.70 corresponding to the statement “Improved connectivity to other cities” has been positively favored by the respondents followed by the mean rank 7.06 corresponding to the statement “Opening up of new hotels”. The third most favored statement “Increase in the demand of Handmade Utensils” has the mean rank of 5.42 followed by the statement “Downfall in the migrations to the cities” having mean rank of 5.19. The mean rank of 4.91 corresponds to the statement “Increase in Tourist Footfall”. However, the respondents do not favor much the statement “Preservation of the community” with a mean rank of 4.63. The third least favored statement is “Improved Standard of Living” with the mean rank of 4.18. The second least favored statement is “Expansion of the community” with mean rank of 4.15. And, the least favored statement “Increase funding by the Government” has the mean rank of 1.77. Hence, we can conclude that there is significant difference between the ranked opinions of the locals of Jandiala guru after the Tathera Community was recognized by UNESCO. Thus, we reject the Null hypothesis and affirm that ‘There is significant difference between the ranked opinions of locals of Jandiala Guru after the Tathera Community was recognized by UNESCO.

Conclusion and Suggestions

At the beginning of the paper, doubts were expressed as to the difference between the concept of Tangible and Intangible Cultural Heritage which has been vividly discussed in the introduction of this paper. During the research, the past studies on this particular area of intangible cultural heritage of different countries were analyzed. Based on this analysis of precedent literature, it can be said that the importance of ICH is gradually fading in this era where tourists are majorly fascinated towards tangible attractions. Although, for the revival of ICH, various countries are engaging organizations concerned for emphasizing the significance and role of this particular aspect of heritage for coming generations. They are entrusted with the responsibility of involving the tourists in sustaining the ICH by using it as a product. The research revealed that the members of Tathera Community are now not willing to carry on with their customary art of making handmade traditional brass and copper utensils because of influence of number of factors like increased competition, technological impacts, inflation, migration for jobs, etc. They are losing their uniqueness of traditional craftsmanship and the same skill is not being transferred to the succeeding generations.

For the alleviating these issues, the government can play a vital role by resuming the initial schemes wherein these artisans were given rebates on the raw materials (kacchha dhaatu) and working on improvising the Infrastructure like transportation facilities; inculcating public spaces such as gardens, museums, exhibition grounds; establishing bureaus for guiding the locals regarding concessions and funding etc. in this area of Jandiala Guru. Technology or modern ways of communication can also help the community to prosper and exhibit their proficiency to the other parts of the world.

As the preservation of ICH endorses any community's identity at global level, therefore, attempts should be made to safeguard the talent of the Tathera Community by encouraging these craftsmen through tourism as well. We can encourage the star hotels, predominantly the five star hotels, to have an alliance with the Tatheras for providing them with customized copper and brass utensils. This will not only give the Tatheras a platform to showcase their traditional skill but also will give the country a stage to exhibit its' heritage to the guests which further can help in enhancing the image of the destination. The tourist packages for Amritsar can include Jandiala Guru as a part of the itinerary. Also, exporters of utensils can collaborate with the Tatheras for making an overseas

market for their craft that can fetch money and recognition for them at the same time. This will not only increase the employment opportunities for the Tatheras, but also help their craftsmanship to continue without freezing. The products of the Tatheras can be displayed in the Crafts Emporiums so that people can be sensitized of their handicraft and help sustain it. Their products can also be put on sale on online platforms and thus, reaping the benefits of web-marketing. To sensitize the younger minds, the schools can also organize a trip to this community. The Ministry of skills development can also contribute by adding a chapter on ICH in the curriculum of ITI and Vocational Training Institutes.

The revelations of this research can further be projected for designing of tourist packages, framing of curriculum and collaborating with the exporters and the hotel industry by the future scholars. Similar researches can be taken up to find out other communities, not only in India but also in the world, that have such a rare talent, skill or know-how. This research can be continued further in the area of protection of ICH and its varied forms which are of great importance and necessity to both the traditional culture and modern society.

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Intercultural Communication and Tourism

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Abstract

Communication is a system or a medium which plays a vital role in our society. In this world, there is plenty of country who is involved with each other with good communication. When we talk about intercultural tourism then it might be important to have a better communication.

Nowadays tourism is a sector which depends on good communication environment. Throughout the journey has started by any traveler who want to enjoy oneself knows the value of communication. Intercultural tourism helps tourists to know the culture of others and to appreciate the same. It is about to communicate with the people who are different by religion, caste and languages.

Often when we travel then we are exciting to know the culture of another country state or city. When we make a talk with them and try for better communication. Then sometimes we don't know the language, but we understand each other by gestures and it creates some funny moments. Tourism has promoted intercultural activity in the world. It premises with the culture, art, music, dance, cuisine and rituals.

Every culture shows the way where the people behave according to their belief system, attitudes, mentality, creativity etc. when they communicate to another then they understand the values of the culture and that's all make our tour to more exciting, knowledgeable and interesting. Intercultural tourism creates a social connection between peoples. It also delivered a cultural awareness between two countries or any two places.

Keywords: - Culture, Tourism, Communication, Intercultural Tourism

Introduction

Basically, tourism is an activity which focuses for the leisure, pleasure and recreational activity. Every person in the world has an excitement about the nature and other culture. From the ancient time people were used to go for tour with friends and family where they make a purpose for their journey. There were many problems because that time there was no technology. But nowadays we have all the things in our mobile phone. So easily we can make our journey good.

Communication is a key by which the tourist makes a better understanding between oneself and others. [1] Proper communication has a positive impact in tourism where tourist shares the information to other. It may be possible in intercultural tourism that lacking of a good communication misunderstanding cause and this make a negative approach for the same for e.g. it may exist between tourist and local people, to the hotel manager or staff, cab driver etc.

Culture

Every culture shows the way where the people behave according to their belief system, attitudes, mentality, creativity etc. when they communicate to another then they understand the values of the culture and that's all make our tour to more exciting, knowledgeable and interesting. Culture is a living standard of human in the society where it forms different for different places. In India, there are a lot of culture trends. It is believed that "The world's first culture is India". Everything which relate to human being is known as culture such as art, music, dance, rituals, living style, cuisine, manners etc. it also provide the opportunity to know the history, traditions and customs of other country or place. [2]

Literature Review

How can one become more successful in intercultural communication? As

- Discussed earlier, it requires the awareness of cultural differences and a nonjudgmental
- attitude towards those differences. It also requires good self-knowledge.
- In order to achieve more successful intercultural interaction,
- several researchers have identified the key factors to that success. These factors
- are called intercultural communication competences- Anne Sipola Intercultural Communication in Experience Tourism in Inari Area 2011

2. The communication and establishment of relationships with people from different cultures can lead to various benefits (e.g. healthier communities, increasing of international, national and local commerce, reduction of conflict and personal growth through increased tolerance) (Neuliep 2006, pp. 2 - 4).

3. On the one hand, the term “culture” refers to all the characteristics common to a particular group of people that are learned and not given by nature (Kroeber and Kluckhohn 1952).

4 According to Collier and Thomas (1988) intercultural communication can be described as a communication between persons who identify themselves as distinct from others in a cultural sense

5. Samovar and Porter (1991) state that intercultural communication occurs whenever a message is produced by a member of one culture for consumption by a member of another culture, a message must be understood

Source <https://www.quora.com/What-does-the-word-culture-mean-and-what-is-Indian-culture-Is-it-the-things-which-people-follow-or-Is-it-the-things-written-in-some-books-myths> -[3]

Fairs and Festivals

From January to December, every month comes with a particular fair or festival. Makar Sakranti, Basanti Panchami, Holi, Ram Navami, Janamashtami, Diwali, Eid, Mahavir Jayanti, Buddha Purnima, Guru Purab and Christmas; the festival of every religion has a significance and it is celebrated in a boisterous way. Here people don't need a floor to dance. Celebrations on streets during Durga Puja, Ganesh Chaturthi, Janamashtmi and Holi show the real dancing talents of Indians. [4]

Intercultural Tourism

Intercultural tourism has promoted the culture from one country to the other for e.g. Ibn Battuta came to India in 1333 and appreciated the Indian culture especially cuisine

According to Nick Bartel and ORIAS: “ Ibn Battuta described a royal meal: bread (which is thin round cakes); large slabs of meat (sheep); round dough cakes made with ghee (clarified butter) which they stuff with sweet almond paste and honey; meat cooked with ghee, onions and green ginger; "sambusak" (triangular pastries made of hashed meat and cooked with almonds, walnuts, pistachios, onions, and spices put inside a piece of thin bread fried in ghee - like our modern samosas); rice cooked in ghee with chickens on top; sweetcakes and sweetmeats (pastries) for dessert. They drank sherbet of sugared water before the meal and barley-water after. Then they had betel leaf and areca nut (a mild narcotic).

“He also described the following: mango; pickled green ginger and peppers; jack-fruit (like a large melon weighing three to four pounds) and "barki" (like a yellow gourd with sweet pods and kernels) - "the best fruits in India"; tandu (fruit of the ebony tree); sweet oranges; wheat, chickpeas and lentils, and rice which was sown three times a year! Sesame and sugar cane were also sown. He said the Indians ate millet (a type of grain) most often and he especially liked pounded millet made into a gruel (porridge) cooked with buffalo's milk. They also ate peas and mung beans cooked with rice and ghee which the Indians ate for breakfast every day. Animals were fed barley, chickpeas, and leaves as fodder and even given ghee. (Gibb, pp. 609 - 612)

“On a hunting trip with the Sultan Muhammad Tughluq, he describes the following food: flesh of sheep, fattened fowls, cranes, and other kinds of game. A favorite dish of the Muslim community in Kerala in the southern state of India (where Ibn Battuta had his disastrous ship-wreck) is rasoi (made of rice, lamb, grated coconut and onion). Ibn Battuta reported told that Muslim women ate separately from the men in India, as in most of the Muslim countries he visited. [5]

Intercultural Communication

Communication is a process where we get and share information with others by speaking, writing and gestures. It is an interaction between any two cultures to communicate with each other. Every country has their own culture which communicates with peoples. In India there is an ancient quote “Atithi Devo Bhava” means “A guest must be treated as God”. There is a culture for welcoming for e.g. “Namaste” is the culture of India. [6]

Many tourists from the world came to india to attain the spiritual knowledge for e.g.

Xuanzang was a chinese traveller who came to india in the seventh century and established the interaction between indian culture and chinese culture. [7]

Source- <http://www.mansivora.com/ic.html> [8]

Cultural Awareness

It create a social awareness’ where the tourist mesmerized and they want to explore things with their friends, relative or society then he look for writing a book or making films. In India many tourists have visited from abroad and gave the knowledge to empower their country. for e.g.

In 602 A.D. Hiuen Tsang was born in China. At the age of twenty, he became a Buddhist monk. To satisfy his spiritual hunger he longed for knowing more and more about Buddhism. He knew his desire for learning would remain unfulfilled without a visit to India. When he was about the

age of 30, he secretly left China for an adventurous journey towards India. He traveled through rough to the mountain and rocky and rugged mountainous region to reach India.

He visited various places of northern and southern India during his stay in India. He wanted to visit all the sacred places connected with the life of Buddha, as well as to learn about Buddhism through study in India. He covered many more places and observed keenly the social, religious, political, cultural and economic conditions of the country during his travel [9]

Conclusions

Intercultural communication is totally depending on the experience by which tourists understand the culture and the value of that culture from their perspective. They should be inspired from the culture and have appreciated for the same. So, for promoting the intercultural activity in the world tourism has played an important role because it makes practically to recognize the culture by talking to the peoples, by the historical background of the country or place and get motivated. Intercultural tourism creates a social connection between peoples.

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Cross Cultural Views on Nature with Special Reference to Indian Culture: A Review

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Abstract

This review paper is emphasized on cross cultural views on Nature and environmental components with special reference to Hinduism. Nature has always been very vivacious, giving and flexible to a very large level. Culture and religion protect and nurtures nature since pre-historical time. Culture and nature closely associated, culture includes foods, festivals, religions, traditions, languages. If we study the religions like Hinduism, Islam, Buddhism, Jainism, Sikhism we will find they respect sun, wind, land, trees, plants, and water which are the fundamentals of survival on this earth. Likewise, respect and conservation of wildlife (eagle, lion, peacock, snake etc.) are part of cultural ethos from time immemorial. Almost the entire living of God and Goddess was very close to nature and environment. In fact, whole civilizations have come into existence near sources of water like Indus Valley Civilization. In this sense, nature and culture become intertwined. Culture reflects our history, tradition and our beliefs. A country like India is a culturally rich and diverse country where people speak many different languages, with many communities, many religions which live in their particular social structures entirely depending on their environment to ensure their livelihood. Culture and traditional knowledge had always contributed to medicine and health care. Further for centuries, indigenou communities were used to surviving and adjusting their agriculture, fishing and hunting in the event of changes in climate. This paper is focused on interpretation of environmental components by the different religions.

Key words: Culture, Environment, Nature, environmental conservation

Introduction

The Indian culture protects nature through various ways. According to the Greendex (National Geographic & research) “India is the most sustainability minded country in the world”. Traditional Indian Lifestyle can give us hundreds of examples of living in harmony with nature. Living a life with nature and giving back to nature is not new to Indians. Physical world includes plants, land,

soil, animals and other elements of earth. There is profound relation between human and nature as man has long association of trees, dependent on each other, striking a balance in the eco-system. Both man and nature have been bound by a bond of association since ancient time. Every component provides by nature and used by men in various ways. Trees supply food, furniture, and shelter to men while the latter manure trees, water them and transplant them from place to place. Water provides different cultures (Pisci-culture, prawn culture, pearl culture etc.) and employment to human being. Man cannot live without air, water and biodiversity. This healthy ecological balance now rapid disturbed due to industrialization, urbanization, over exploitation and other man-made activities. Virgin forests are being destroyed, rivers are being polluted due to industrial and domestic sewage, and land pollution is common due to excessive use of fertilizers, pesticides and insecticides. Various components of nature such as Sun, Air, water, flora and fauna have interrelated with Indian culture. Sun is also known by many alternative names in different cultures such as: Savitr (the Nourisher), Bhaskara (Light-maker), Dinakara (Day-maker), Lokacaksuh (Eye of the World) etc. In Hindu literature, it is said that O sun, the eye of the universe, origin of all things, acts of all religious men. Many people of world worshipped Sun in the form of Surya Namaskaar by offering water and flowers. Rays emitted from sun cured various skin diseases. We all know that sun is primary source of energy to all life of this planet. Firstly, plants use this energy by the process of photosynthesis and then transfer to the animals. Flora and fauna of the globe are distributed according to light and temperature provided by Sun. Therefore, sun and energy which are essential components of nature have very close relation to man. Air is most important component of nature to sustain life on this earth. Human take breathes about 22000 times per day. Plants play important role in producing oxygen by the process of photosynthesis. About 75% of earth covered with water. Water present on earth in various forms such as: glaciers, water vapors, rivers, ponds, lakes, streams, oceans and estuaries. Many human civilizations established near the water bodies on the other hand many occupations like agriculture, aquaculture, pearl culture etc. only because of aquatic bodies. River not only provides employment for millions but also provide electricity through Hydro-power plants. Many water bodies used for navigation and transportations since prehistoric time. Water bodies provide different habitats to aquatic animals. Earth referred as Bhumi or Prithvi Mata in Indian culture and also understood to be the solidification of all natural elements, the solidification of energy into matter. She has a collection of beautiful hymns

dedicated to her in the Atharvaveda called Prithvi Suktam. Earth contains soil which consists of minerals and some organic matter which differ from their parent materials in texture, structure, & color, chemical, biological and other characteristics. "Earth" is also a word to define the solid element of the Panchmahabhutas (five elements) and is the solidification of all other elements in the material world. Journey of human being started with plants and still human being depends on plants for their survival. Culture has closely associated with plant community for food (Triticum aestivum, Oryza sativa, Pisum sativum, Cajanus cajanus, Mangifera indica), medicines (Embllica officinalis, Azadirachta indica, Ocimum tuniflorum, Curcuma longa, Saraca asoca, Aloe vera), wood & timbers (Terminalia arjuna, Acacia nilotica, Cedrus deodara, Tectona grandis, Shorea robusta, Pinus sp. etc), honey, silk, lac etc. Besides these benefits, plants are essential for climatic change and rotation of biogeochemical cycles. On the basis of plant diversity, the tribal community and ethnic races throughout the world have developed their own culture, customs, folk song, foods, medicinal practices, etc. There are 248 plant based medicines enlisted from ancient Indian literature Rigveda. Around 70 % of India's medicinal plants are found in tropical areas. Medicinal plants are distributed across diverse habitats and landscape. Although less than 30 % of the medicinal plants are found in the temperate and alpine areas and higher altitudes they include species of high medicinal value. Around 70-80% population of India live in rural areas; utilize traditional medicinal system, which are based on largely Ayurvedic medicine. Indian culture and animals have coexisted together from time immemorial. This relationship between these two different types of beings can be seen from different perspectives both positively or negatively. Human being started their journey with many domestic animals such as dog, goat, cow, horse, etc. Human being obtained their need such as food, milk, ghee, cheese from these animals. Some animals such as dog and horse are being used for protection and transportation, respectively. Bulls, insects, birds are like friends of human being since agricultural progression. Many societies of man entirely depend on fishes, birds, silk moth, honey bee etc. for their survival. Human being also used different animals for entertainment. Besides the positive relationship man and animals also has negative relationship. Mosquitoes, flies, rats and cockroach spread many diseases in human being, some birds, rats, termites, elephants etc. also responsible for great damage to crops and cultivated products of human being. Human-animal conflict also seen in many societies in which tiger attack, snake biting is common.

It is well understood that history of culture is very small as compare to history of nature. Cultures of world divide or evolved according to nature and natural components. Firstly, nature divides itself in to different ecological, biogeographic zones and then culture has divided. For examples ten main biogeographic zones of India are: Trans Himalayan, Himalayan zone, desert, semiarid, Western ghat, Deccan plateau, Gangetic plain, North east zone, Coastal zone and Islands. If you look the rainfall, forests, temperature flora and fauna, people of area of these biogeographic zones are totally different. Communities and societies are depending on natural resources and these zones have specific diversity of natural resources. There are some examples of Indian culture and their interpretation about the nature.

Food: The respect of food items has been a way of Indian culture. Local and seasonal foods locally grown and seasonally produced fruits are recommended for good health which significantly reduces the need for preservation and transportation. Every seasonal has its specific fruits and crops, Indian culture applies these food as medicine and curing of certain types of diseases. Indian culture also focusses on food preservation techniques and it has also been done in a very environment friendly manner without using energy generated by fossil fuels instead simple method of pickling, sun drying etc. Women use pickling methods for lemon, amla, mango pickle at their home which is easiest and eco-friendly technique to preserve these food items.

Children in Indian culture are taught about respect for food at a young age. Indian diet is primarily plant based and approximately 42% of the households in India are strict vegetarian.

Sustainability: In Indian culture sustainable consumption values, such as switching off unwanted Electrical appliances are imbibed in homes as well as schools from a young age. During summers, people often prefer to sleep out in the open, in courtyards or on the terrace, thus leading to reduced usage of cooling appliances in homes. For generations, earthen pots or “matkas” have been used to store water and keep it cool during summer season. This helps reduce the refrigeration requirement during summers. In Indian culture the practice of sun drying of clothes and hand washing dishes the usage of energy intensive tumble driers and dish washers, respectively. This also results in reduced water consumption as compared to dishwashers. Some people also prefer to bathe in cold water for most of the year.

Clothing: India is a home to many unique types of hand woven fabrics or handlooms. Traditional practice of weaving textile with a weaving loom does not require any energy; it only requires the

skill to weave. People of India generally women weave clothes for their children. Indian culture has a rich heritage of various hand embroidered fabrics. Examples like banarsi, kanjivaram, patola, zardozi, kalamkari, sujani, phulkari, kashida, kantha, Nagaland weaves etc. Khadi is made from cotton, silk or wool. Indian culture prefers cotton handkerchiefs & kitchen towels are used over a long period unlike the use & throw tissue papers. Paper products are harsh on the environment as use timber & are cause of water & air pollution. Tradition of passing cloths & Books to younger siblings: Recycling of used cloths to make new products. Indian culture of recycling is evident from the fact that most of the household have dusters made up of used cloths. Another examples of nature conservation in Indian culture through reusing and recycling of solid waste in which they made carpets from old blankets, foot mats from jute sacs, cushion covers and bags from used clothes.

Views of Hinduism on Nature

Hinduism is oldest religion of world and there is no specific founder of this religion. Views of Hinduism on nature have been mentioned in Vedas, Upanaishads, Puranas, Sutras, Mahabharat, Ramayan and other sacred scriptures. Many of Hindus describe mantras daily to respect their rivers, mountains, trees, animals and the earth. Hinduism believes in peace even they have mantra for peace as “Om Dyau Shanti antariksha gwam shanti prithvi shanti rapah shanti roshadhayah shanti vanas patayah shanti vishwed devah shanti brahma sarvag wam shanti shanti reva shanti sa ma shanti redhi om shanti shanti shanti” which means unto the heaven be Peace, unto the sky and the earth be Peace, Peace be unto the water, unto the herbs and trees be Peace, unto all the Gods and Goddess be Peace, unto Brahma and unto all be Peace. Earth can be seen as a manifestation of the goddess, and must be treated with respect. You can understand view of Hinduism by Atharvaveda verse which says that “माताः भूमिः पुत्रोहम् पृथिव्याः” which means “Earth is my mother and I am the dutiful son of Her”. The five elements space, air, fire, water and earth are the foundation of an interconnected web of life. According to Hinduism Dharma (Religion) as “duty” can be reinterpreted to include our responsibility to care for the earth.

The five great elements called as “Pancha Mahabhutas” create a web of life that is shown forth in the structure and interconnectedness of the cosmos and the human body. Hinduism teaches that the five great elements (space, air, fire, water and earth) that constitute the environment are all derived from Nature (Prakriti). Hindus says that the human nose is related to earth, tongue to water,

eyes to fire, skin to air and ears to space. This bond between our senses and the elements is the foundation of our human relationship with the natural world. Hinduism says that nature and the environment are not outside us, not alien or hostile to us. They are an inseparable part of our existence, and they constitute our very bodies. Ishavasyam says that divinity is omnipresent and takes infinite forms. Hindu scriptures such as the Bhagavad Gita (7.19, 13.13) and the Bhagavad Purana (2.2.41, 2.2.45), contain many references to the omnipresence of the supreme divinity, including its presence throughout and within nature. Hindus worship and accept the presence of God in nature. For example, Hindus believe mighty rivers such as the Ganga, Yamuna, Narmada, and Krishna as goddesses and mother. Hindus believe that our environmental actions affect our karma (actions). Moral behavior creates good karma, and our behavior toward the environment has karmic consequences. Because we have free choice, even though we may have harmed the environment in the past, we can choose to protect the environment in the future, replacing environmentally destructive karmic patterns with good ones. Hindu believes that the earth is a goddess and our mother and deserves our devotion and protection. Many Hindus touch the floor before getting out of bed every morning and ask Earth (Devi) to forgive them for trampling on her body. Surya Namaskaar (Praying to Lord Sun) is common in Hinduism. Hindu scripture stated that Ahimsa (Non-Violence) is the greatest dharma (duty) and Ahimsa to the earth improves actions of individual. Holiest scripture of Hindu Srimad Bhagwatam 7.14.9 says that everyone should look upon deers, camels, monkeys, donkeys, rats, reptiles, birds and flies as their own children. The most important aspect of animal worship among the Hindu is related to incarnations. Among various incarnation of God, He incarnated first himself in the form of Fish, then on to tortoise, boar and dwarf. His fifth incarnation was man-lion. As Rama He was closely associated with monkeys and as Krishna He was always surrounded by the cows. Hindu say that our Lord Shiva and their family lives in harmony with nature, they live in Himalaya in which vehicle of Lord Shiva is Bull, vehicle of Maa Durga (Wife of Shiva) is Lion, snakes are jewelery of Lord Shiva, vehicle of Kartikeya (First son of Shiva) is Peacock, and vehicle of Lord Ganesh (Second son of Lord Shiva) is rat. They all are live in harmonic condition even they are natural enemies to each other. Narsimhapurana 13.44 says that “O wicked man! If you roasted a bird then your bathing in sacred river, pilgrimage, worship and yajna are useless”.

Hinduism says that “Tain tyakten bhunjitha” means “take what you need for your sustenance without a sense of entitlement or ownership”. Hindu scripture very keen about pollution (Vikriti) Vishnu Puran (3.11.11-12) stated that people should not cause excrement in ploughed field, land having crop, dwelling place of cow, public paths, sacred places like rivers, water, graveyard and forests. According to Charaka Samhita, Vimansthana, 3.6 (1), the polluted air is mixed with with bad elements. The air which is against the virtues of season, with full of moisture, speedy, hard ice cool, hot dry colliding from two or three sides, bad smelling oily, full of dirt, smoke sand and steam creates diseases in body and is polluted. Padampuran, Bhoomikhanda 96.7-8 says that a person who is engaged in killing creatures, polluting wells, ponds and tanks and destroying gardens certainly goes to hell. Hinduism in ancient time provided a system of moral guidelines towards nature preservation and conservation. Ancient scripture has stressed that man and nature need to live in close harmony and plants and animals should be objects of unlimited kindness since they make no demand for their sustenance. We have been warned in Charak Samhita which stated that when air, water and other element of nature will be polluted the seasons start working against their routines and cycle and vegetable gradually begins to damage, this is most dangerous to both earth and human being. Therefore, we must follow the rules and regulations set by Vedas, Upanisads, Purans and all Holy Scriptures.

Table-1: Animals associated with God and Goddess in Hinduism

	Associated Animals	God and Goddess
1.	Lion	Durga
2.	Wildgoose	Brahma
3.	Fish	Vishnu, Kama
4.	Monkey	Rama
5.	Horse	Sun
6.	Owl	Lakshmi
7.	Peacock	Kartikkeys, Saraswati
8.	Crocodile	Ganga
9.	Tortoise	Yamuna, Vishnu
10.	Ass	Sitla

11.	Deer	Vayu
12.	Dog	Bhairav, Dattatrey
13.	Snake	Shiva, Sun
14.	Swan	Saraswati
15.	Eagle	Vishnu
16.	Rat	Ganesh
17.	Bull	Shiva
18.	Vulture	Shani
19.	Parrot	Kama
20.	Elephant	Indra and Ganesha
21.	Tiger	Katyayani
22.	Cow	Vishnu

Table-2: Plants associated with God and Goddess in Hinduism

	Associated Plants	God and Goddess
1.	Tulsi	Vishnu, Lakshmi, ancestor worship
2.	Bel/Bilwa	Shiva, Spirits
3.	Asoka	Indra, Buddha
4.	Kadamba	Krishna
5.	Pipal	Vishnu, Shani
6.	Soma	Moon
7.	Neem	Sitala, Manasa
8.	Palasa	Gandarvh, Brahma
9.	Amalaki	Lakshmi, Kartik
10.	Tamal	Krishna
11.	Sij	Sitala

Islamic Views on Nature

Islam asserts that there is one God creator of the universe and that is the God of providence, mercy and justice. The universal order is mentioned in Quran as follows: Everything in the universe is

coordinate and well adjusted and there is no disorder, discord and unbalanced. Nature is essentially constructive, not destructive bringing about order not disorder and making for improvement and progress not deterioration and retrogression. Quran says man is born with nature made by Allah (Q30:30) and he indeed prospers who purify it and he is ruined who corrupts it (Q91:9-10).

Further Quran says your lord is Allah who created the nature and earth. He is the creation and its regulations. He doesn't love those who exceed the limits of nature. The lord has created plenty of things for the survival of all living creature on earth. The Quran also says the sun and the moon move according to a fixed reckoning and the stars and tree submit to him. He has raised the heaven high and set up the measures. Important thing is Quran related to ecological balance mentioned as "al mizan" means Allah created the universe and human being and then subjected to him whatsoever exist in the heavens and in the earth all of it but he clearly says that "who follow the rule and regulations made by Me (Allah) definitely get the heaven (ultimate peace)"

Views of Islam allow us to successfully interact with environment and nature and guide us to follow divine regulations, right order and observe the ecological balance. Views of Islam are very clear about environmental pollution. Quran specifically says that "And of mankind there is he whose conservation on the present life will please you and he will call Allah to witness as to that which is in his heart, yet he is most rigid of opponents. And when he raises the power his effort in the land would be to create disturbance therein and to destroy crops and life. Allah does not approve of pollution and ecological disturbance". Water has been considered as purifying agent in Islam. The air pollution cause by smoke and gases in present time has been predicted in Quran. Quran says "Watch for the day when the sky will bring forth visible smoke that will engulf this will be afflictive distress and this is really happening now in the atmosphere". Islam interprets the indiscriminate use of fertilizers, pesticides, insecticides, preservatives, drugs and emission and discharge from industries and nuclear waste demonstrates that man has become instrumental in changing Allah creation. According to Islamic view of ideal environment "no such alteration of God creation is permissible" The Quran in a suggestive and meaningful verse says:

"A picture of garden which is promised to those who are safeguarded, therein are rivers of water and rivers of milk, river of wine, river of honey, all kind of fruits with protected from their sustainer and evolver".

In Islam aestheticism is preceded by cleanliness, as the holy prophet says “Clean and purify yourself with all possible means, for Allah has founded on cleanliness and none will ever enter paradise except every clean one. Several actions which lead to pollution in society are prohibited in Islam. For example an exposition of things disapproved of in the matter of streets has been mentioned as “Loading pack animals beyond what they can bear casting out the sweepings in to the upper part of the roads, throwing out water melon peel and dirty water which may cause folk to a slip fall. Thus Islam cannot exist with pollution. Protection of fauna is directly associated with moral values. The teaching of mercy is essential part of the faith of Islam. The Quran says that “God loves those who are kind to his creation. Besides, the wild animals even for animals which are used for assistance in agriculture, Islam recommended using them according to their capacity. The Quran not only discourages the killing of animals for mere fun and sport, but also kind treatment towards them. It says “There is no animal on earth nor being that flies on wings, they are community like you”. The Quran also says “the activities of destroying agricultural and bio-culture have clearly been defined in Islam as “Fasad”, birds which are the flying beauty of the biosphere should not be touched merely for sport and fun. The Prophet say “A sparrow killed just for entertainment would on the day judgment complain against the person who did so just for fun and not for any material gain” Islam is much aware for the conservation of life (both wild and domestic) on earth. It regards the killing of the single soul in terms of entire community and saving of the single soul as the saving of million’s life.

Water, plants and trees are often repeated as favorite themes of the Quran since they stand in vital relations to animals and human life. A tree in the Quran symbolizes eternity and never decaying ownership, as well as medium of life, light and inspiration. The attributes of sacredness blessedness and holiness are attributed to some trees. For example the Olive and Fig by which God swears. All this natural wealth is His creation and has been provided by Allah. He grows corns, olive, datepalm, grapes and all kind of fruits for you (Quran16:12). The ideals set by Quran may well acceptable as a basis of elaborating conservational strategies.

Views of Buddhism on Nature

Various references related to nature and environment has been cited in Buddhism. The home of Buddha is India Buddha himself obtained inspiration from the occult beauty of nature and expressed his keen appreciation. “I saw in the lap of forest, among the pleasing region of earth, a

river flowing while pious and pleasant shore of the stream attached by heart. I decided to be most appropriate place of calmness, where I may indulge myself in spiritual meditation and obtained the realm of truth as the life is full of miseries, sorrows and agonies. Thus, I reached in the state of enlightenment “Bodhi” this is because the bank of rivers, peaceful sea, a valley at the foot of mountain, green forest have had pleasant seat for the ancient meditators. The great Buddha has laid down religious sanction against the indiscriminate use of trees and plants. In a Jataka Akhyana a story is mentioned as “There was an old Bhaddasala tree and regarded as dwelling place of God. Once king wanted to cut it down to make use of its thick wood for new palace. Bhaddasala was struck with wonder to imagine his act and said I have passed 60,000 years at this place none of your ancestors ever injured even my branches, leaves and roots, they always worshipped me so you do also. Finally, the king gave up his idea of cutting the tree. It is explicitly mentioned in several scriptures that in the trees there live different God and Goddess. In fact, trees and plants have a very important place in the social life of India as well as in other countries where Buddhism practiced due to the fact where a tree is propagated usually there is mythical apprehension associated with a higher or folk God or defiled saint or any other socio-religious personality. Bhikkhu and Buddhist always required that their dwelling be near the mountains or in the forest under the shade of tree. Pollution is prohibited in Buddhism. Buddhism says “why vitiated you the cistern O! gentle! this which is purified after long period-penance and meditation of Risis, who lived in forest”. The views of Buddhism on nature if rightly interpreted and propagated may show us the right path for the world welfare and beautiful nature.

Views of Sikhism on Nature

Views of Sikhism on nature are vast and elaborated. Sikh theory of creation of earth is mentioned in the Moolmantra (Seminal formula) where Guru Nanak calls God as Karta purakh (Creating power of universe). Guru Granth Sahib (holy book of Sikh religion) states that God is only creator of nature without nature no animal and plant can survive on this earth. “Magnificent nature is the symbol of His creative vision”. The Creator gave the shape to nature from five important elements, which means a state in which the five basic elements are in perfect equilibrium, coexistence and harmony. When these elements misbalance in nature it leads to abnormalities in natural components of earth. Sikh Gurus say that Air is vital force, water is progenitor, the earth is mother of all living and non-living things, Day and night are nurses feeding all. These elements are essential for peace,

happiness, tranquility, development of humanity and balance in nature. There is no moment when separation happened between man and nature and this balance is an integral part of universe. The life giving process in water which leads to the development of flora or vanaspati has been widely acclaimed by Sikhism. Sikhism says that water enters in to the womb of earth to produce vegetations which is used by animals and human being as food. Plants and trees are used in medicines and animals feed in plants and give milk, honey, silk, lac etc. to human beings. Sikh philosophy deals with garden, fields flowers, tress, manuring and weeding. As Guru Granth Sahib says “The tiller tills the soil with his whole heart ploughing and making effort that his progeny may thereby find substance”.

The natural environment and wildlife also very closely linked to Sikhism. Sikh Gurus says that “most of the animals survive in forests and they grow only in natural environment, even for domestic animals green plants are required”. In the present ecological crisis perhaps animals are the creature the most affected due to manmade activities. When forests are degraded how can animals increase? God himself has been depicted as a big tree which sheltering birds, insects, mammals. Sikh Gurus believed in universe love and respect for all creatures. According to Guru Granth Sahib “Birds do not have God, Property or lands their demand is only water and trees, which gives them food and shelter, fish cannot live without water and Chatrik (bird) cannot survive without rain”. Among Sikh scripture mentioned about Kamdhenu (wish cow) occurs at several places. She is known as Surabhi and she first appearance on earth during the churning of ocean. In legend she has described as a powerful animal that can fulfills all the needs of human being. Sikh Gurus say that Vand ke Chakko (eat after sharing). If we take care of all the animals, plants and human being then this nature will be in perfect balance. Sikhism teaches that so far as man and nature live in perfect harmony of the divine will ecology remains caring to man. But ecological imbalance is caused by ignorance, over exploitation of nature.

Conclusion

Indian culture is very keen about nature and many example have been found in Indian culture related to nature in which Hinduism, Islamic, Sikhism, Buddhism have been interpreted the nature with wonderful examples. Culture and nature are interrelated in which man associated with sun, water, rainfall, air, earth, plants and animals for their existence in nature.

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Pilgrimage as a Tool of Socio Economy at Haridwar (Uttarakhand)

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Abstract

Economic and socio-cultural consideration must be well understood in order to plan, develop and manage pilgrimage or tourism successfully. The growth of pilgrimage tourism in India has been astonishingly impressive. India is blessed with plenty of well known religious destinations. Pilgrimages to these destinations bring enormous economic gains to local residents, Haridwar. Devotees in large number from all over India and abroad visit Haridwar every year to take a dip in the holy river Ganga preferably at Har Ki Pauri to earn virtue. Among the positive impacts of pilgrimage has supported the living standard and economic gain in the concerned areas. In this series the pilgrims, local residents and shopkeepers were consulted to get their views about various components.

In the present study to know the impact of pilgrimage on socio-economic aspects, pilgrims, shopkeepers and local peoples were interviewed to get their view about the environmental condition and civics facilities in the concerned area. During the survey 49% respondent were satisfied about the food facilities and 27% were not satisfied while 24% were not sure with the food facility and showing a very casual or neutral approach. 60% respondents were satisfied about the transport facilities, 34% were not satisfied and 6% were not sure about the transport facilities in the concerned area. Among the interviewed shopkeeper about the economy, 90% shopkeeper were satisfied about the economic growth, and 10% shopkeeper did not give any answer about the economy. About the environmental condition of the city, out of the total respondent 45% were satisfied while 55% were not satisfied about the environmental management in Haridwar city. In case of the facilities, 70% respondent were in the favor for more facilities on the different festive occasions and they says that all the modes of services and basic amenities should increase during the festive occasions, while 24 % respondents were not in favor of more facilities 6% were not

sure about the facilities. In case of local people, 60% respondents were in favor of pilgrims and satisfied with the increasing pilgrims about the socio-cultural aspects and rest of the local people did not give any affirmative answer.

Keywords: Socio-economic, Environmental management, Pilgrimage

Introduction

India is yet to realize its true potential of vitalizing its tourism assets to make a significant contribution to the country's economic development with inclusive growth. The 12th plan document represented a significant departure from a primary focus on international tourist arrivals and foreign exchange earnings being the principal objective and attempts to integrate the role of tourism in accordance with the Millennium Development Goals and the Sustainable Development Goals conceptualized by the United Nations World Tourism Organization. According to the 12th Plan document, "Tourism has the potential to help achieve the objectives of the Twelfth Plan for faster, more inclusive and sustainable growth. More importantly, it is a powerful antidote to poverty. It eliminates the disadvantage of market inaccessibility suffered by the poor in respect of their goods and services by bringing the consumer to their doorstep.

Pilgrimage is the journey to sacred place and the pilgrims are traveling to places of spiritual solaces, temple etc. On the other hand with changing concept of pilgrims, people are traveling to the shrines and other pilgrim spots for satisfying their aesthetic needs, spirit of adventure, enjoyment and health, on the name of tourism. Before some decades, some areas of Himalaya were unexplored and very remote due to scarcity of roads and vehicles and people reached there in lesser number on foot. But in these days equation has been changed due to increased infrastructural facilities in the form of road, vehicles, accommodation and food everywhere. All these facilities have motivated a large number of pilgrims to find access to remote areas of forested Himalayan valleys. It is surprising that there was hardly any tourist in Ladakh before 1974 but they were reported 10 thousand in 1981. During early sixties the most famous shrine of Badrinathji attracted about 40,000 devotees to the shrine, the number swelled to 1,50,000 just after completion of road to Mana in 1968 (**Singh 1984**). This increase of modern pilgrims, undoubtedly creates a burden on the environment by affecting the ecosystem of the concern area and its resources.

Tourism has greatly influenced the economic scenario of the region and has indeed proved to be fundamental for the economic upliftment of the society. Tourism transforms the life style of a

sizable number of people. Dwelling the remote areas in and around the places of pilgrimages, people have shifted for the unproductive agricultural and pastoral practices to small business related to tourism e.g. small huts stalls have been opened at places where no one could have imagined such facilities (**Garg and Porwal 1986**).

Tourism creates income which is interlinked with the employment. It is being a labor intensive industry; the greatest proportion of income is derived from wages and salaries. From an economic point of view, tourism encourages the consumption of goods and services, which directly stimulate those sectors in each country which produce these goods and services. The spin off from tourist activities is most important in the sector covering food, construction, arts, craft and commerce. **WTO (World Tourism Office)** statistics show that in the countries where tourism is firmly established the sector dealing with accommodation alone can provide 3-5 % of the total number of jobs available for the whole tourism sector (**Sinha 1998**).

Material and methods

In the present study, a survey was carried out to know the economic, socio cultural aspects and basic amenities at Haridwar. In this survey tourists, local peoples and shopkeepers were selected (In this survey 700 respondents (500 visitors and local people and 200 shopkeepers) were interviewed.) to know the view of visitors and local people about the selected site.

Results and Discussion

The data recorded of socio economic parameter at the study site has been presented in Fig 1. Among the total respondent 48% said that pilgrimage has certainly very positive impacts 22% said it has both positive and negative impacts and rest of the visitors did not give any response about the aspects. The study clearly shows the positive impact of pilgrims in the concerned area, as maximum number of respondent are fully satisfied by the activities carried out by outsiders.

Fig 1: Map showing the view of visitors and local people about the basic amenities in the concerned area

Pilgrimage is an ancient term which indicates visiting and worshipping the deities of the faith and interest by the pilgrims at various places. But now with changing concept of pilgrimage, people are travelling to various places also for the spirit of adventure, enjoyment and to gain healthier environment in different manner. A few decades ago some pilgrims centre was unexplored, remote due to the scarcity of facilities, but now situation has been changed due to increased facilities. Therefore, a large number of pilgrims reached in that area. It is true that pilgrimage certainly improve the economy of the local people but it is equally true that pilgrims/tourism activities create a lot of burden on environmental resources in the concerned areas. Pilgrimage and tourism have a close relationship with the environment as most of the literature on impacts has described the relationship between pilgrimage and environment. Pilgrimage has both positive and negative impact on the concerned area. Pilgrimage improves the economy and infrastructure of the area and on the other hand it degrades the various components of the environment like as air, soil, water, silence etc. Consequently, unplanned pilgrimage and tourism have lead to deleterious effects on the natural and socio-cultural environment, which is contrary to the original function of pilgrimage as also benevolent forms of tourism, such as responsible tourism and ecotourism. Positive impacts

of pilgrimage/tourism have been discussed by various researchers like **Frechtling (1982)** discussed the positive impact of travel and tourism on economy and environment of the concerned area. **Gruber (1989)** reported that touristic activities affect the living standards, economy, natural environment and infrastructure of the concerned area. **Sullivan and Jackson (2002)** has examined the impact of festival tourism on the local economy of the concerned area and pointed out that the activities related to the festival tourism have potential to enhance of economy as well as local cultural heritage.

Bernbaum (2006) conducted a study on pilgrimage and related activities on sacred mountain and observed that the sacredness of these mountains also encourages to maintain a sacred groove. **Marandola (2006)** studied the tourism in a rural area of Southern Italy and found that coordination between rural tourism enterprises, business persons and local leadership is essential need to establish a strong tourism industry in any region. **Libison and Murleedharan (2008)** pointed out high positive effect of pilgrimage growth, employment and standard of living of local resident in Pandlam rural locality in Kerla. **Raj (2008)** described the tourism and human capital needs and challenges in south Asian countries. Kaushik and Joshi (2014) have been made a comparative study on the impact of pilgrimage on mansa devi and chandi devi temple at Haridwar.

Liu et.al. (2008) gave reported significant effect of tourism on local agriculture system as well as the economy and environment in the Lugu Lake. **Nihalani (2008)** described the international tourism as one of the fastest growing industry and bringing massive impact on the socio-economic and the environmental fabric of any economy.

Conclusion

Basically, the pilgrimage provides various facilities to the concerned area in the form of many developmental activities and economy to the local people. But along with the positive impacts, these activities also create some negative impacts on the environment. It is right that economy play an important role to the city as well as nation, but we cannot neglect the environment in the exchange of economy.

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Culture - A Vision to Tourism

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Abstract

Tourism has been defined differently by the scholars depending upon various sectors it involves in like the trade & commerce, the economy, the sociology, the history and the management etc.

Tourism is an interface for knowledge and cultural exchange, facilitating the interaction between the involved communities and visitors (domestic and international). Economic benefits aside, outside contact draws attention to the host community. People want to interact with others and their cultures, learn and understand their traditions and even confront themselves with new developments and perspectives on life and society. It has been said that travel is a means to “discover those things unknown or forgotten within ourselves.”

India, since times has always been recognised a country with great potential for tourism and for everyone in all seasons & for all reasons. In addition to the sites of ancient, historical, monumental and archaeological interests, the varied wild life sanctuaries and national parks, beach resorts and winter sports attract tourists from all over the world. India has been since times a land of highly rich cultural.

Culture and tourism are inseparable faces of the coin playing a very significant role in present times as the concept of alternate tourism is coming up. Culture tourism can be explained as that part of this growing smokeless industry wherein tourists find themselves engaged in a country's culture like that of life style of people, historical background of the peoples, art and architecture, music and dance forms, rituals & beliefs, dress & styles, food & festivals and lot more to mention. The paper runs to explain the significance of culture in tourism and how the same can be taken and developed as a part to increase the inflow of travellers and tourists.

Key words - Tourism, culture, culture and tourism, India

Introduction

Tourism is one of those significant activities in which every one of us have been involved & participated at some point of time in our lives. Tourism is simply explained as travelling for fun

and entertainment. The school trips, the day picnic, trip to religious, cultural and historical centres and even to the ethnic sites all form part of the bigger spectrum of tourism. The pleasure, excitement, knowledge of new culture and destination is what make tourism activity such a popular activity among the masses all over the world.

Tourism has been explained differently by the scholars depending upon various sectors it involves in like the trade & commerce, the economy, the sociology, the history and the management etc. Tourism is an interface for knowledge and cultural exchange, facilitating the interaction between the involved communities and visitors (domestic and international). Economic benefits aside, outside contact draws attention to the host community. People want to interact with others and their cultures, learn and understand their traditions and even confront themselves with new developments and perspectives on life and society. It has been said that travel is a means to “discover those things unknown or forgotten within ourselves.”

Definition of tourism:

“Tourism is the activities of people traveling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for leisure, business or other purposes for not more than one consecutive year.”

Tourism is a dynamic and competitive industry that requires the ability to adapt constantly to customers' changing needs and desires, as the customer's satisfaction, safety and enjoyment are particularly the focus of tourism businesses.

United Nations View:

The United Nations (WTO) classified 3 forms of tourism in 1994 in its Recommendations on Tourism Statistics as follows:

- Domestic tourism, involving residents of the given country travelling only within this country;
- Inbound tourism, involving non-residents travelling in the given country;
- Outbound tourism, involving residents travelling in another country.

Components of Tourism

Tourism comprises a number of activities of people travelling to and staying in places outside their usual environment for not more than one consecutive year for the purpose of leisure, business and social, recreational, and knowledge seeking purposes. One of the main components of tourism, accessibility, refers to the ability for tourists to get to the destination. This mostly includes

transportation and various modes types of travel like surface, water and air travel, which needs to be regularly scheduled, economical, safe and comfortable. Depending on the destination, this includes cars and buses, boats and ships, trains and airplanes.

The second significant component of tourism is accommodation, meaning thereby that tourists always need to have a space to rest and stay upon reaching the destination and a service to get food & beverage. Much like accessibility, accommodation also needs to be economical, safe and comfortable. The type of accommodation varies according to the requirement and location at the attraction site. For instance, a stay in the mountains may require a cabin or a place to pitch tents. Other accommodations include hotels, motels and floaters etc. whereas the technical arrangements today include capsule and condominiums.

The third and arguably most important component of tourism is attraction. This means that the destination needs to have some draw that makes tourists pull and want to visit. In some cases the draw is scenic, like mountains and lakes. In other cases, the draw might be historical relevance or some academic and scientific site.

The tourism industry is primarily service and people oriented sector; it is an amalgamation of businesses and organisations belonging to various other industries and sectors. It is an interplay among these businesses and organizations / persons which offer remarkable “travel experience” to tourists and visitors. The tourism industry thus comprises hospitality (related to accommodation and dining), travel (transportation services through different modes), and various other businesses which offer services and products to tourists.

Tourism today is the world’s well known largest and fastest growing smokeless industry. It is an invisible export, which earns valuable foreign exchange without any significant or tangible loss of internal resources. It is an affirmatively rich source of earning revenue and providing directly and indirectly employment to millions. There are countries in the world whose main source of revenue is nothing but tourism just like Thailand. India, since times has always been recognised a country with great potential for tourism and for everyone in all seasons & for all reasons. In addition to the sites of ancient, historical, monumental and archaeological interests, the varied wild life sanctuaries and national parks, beach resorts and winter sports attract tourists from all over the world. India Tourism Development Corporation (ITDC) is a public-sector undertaking, whose main task is the development of a sound foundation of tourist infrastructure in the country.

Founded in 1966, the Corporation has made a noteworthy phenomenal progress during the last two decades. It has come up with unique and appealing range of tourist services for both at domestic as well as international fronts.

India, since times has always been recognised a country with great potential for tourism and for everyone in all seasons & for all reasons. In addition to the sites of ancient, historical, monumental and archaeological interests, the varied wild life sanctuaries and national parks, beach resorts and winter sports attract tourists from all over the world. India has been since times a land of highly rich cultural.

Culture and Tourism

Cultural tourism allows travelers to be immersed in local rituals and routines, taking away not only pretty photos but also shared memories of unique experiences. For destinations, it encourages local communities to embrace their culture and boosts economic growth. Developing culturally geared tourism programs encourages destinations to celebrate and promote what distinguishes their communities, and in doing so, provides the opportunity for authentic cultural exchange between locals and visitors.

The power of cultural tourism is unlimited. We appreciate the fascinating plethora of cultures around the globe and believe it is possible to promote cultural tourism without exploiting local populations via sustainable tourism practices. The World Tourism Organisation tells us that cultural tourism accounts for 37% of global tourism, and furthermore affirms that it will continue to grow 15% each year. With all of this market interest, destinations should leverage what makes their societies unique and invest in developing cultural tourism programs.

Tourism and culture were viewed as largely separate aspects earlier. Cultural resources were seen as part of the cultural heritage of destinations, related to the education of the local population and the underpinning of local or national cultural identities. Tourism, on the other hand, was largely viewed as a leisure-related activity separate from everyday life and the culture of the local population. This gradually changed towards the end of the century, as the role of cultural attractions in motivating tourists and distinguishing destinations from one another become more obvious.

Cultural tourism was seen as a growth market and “quality” tourism and an increasing supply of culture as a result of regional development helped the tourism industry. Growing accessibility of

information on culture and tourism through new technologies further increased the demand. The emergence of new nations and regions eager to establish a distinct identity e.g. the impact of newly-independent states in Central and Eastern Europe created new curiosities Partnership is essential. The complexity of both the tourism and cultural sectors implies that platforms must be created to support collaboration, and mechanisms must be found to ensure that these two sectors can communicate effectively. Local communities are beginning to come together to develop cultural products for tourism rather than competing directly with one another. New policies are likely to feature new structures and projects involving public-private partnership and bringing together a wider range of stakeholders to use culture not only to make destinations attractive for visitors, but also to promote regions as destinations to live, work and invest in.

Culture in all its forms is likely to figure strongly in the tourism product and promotion of most regions, even those which have traditionally relied on their natural assets, such as sun and beach or mountains, for their attractiveness. Destinations are also trying to increase their comparative advantage by adding to their stock of cultural attractions. They are also trying to develop their intangible culture and creativity.

Cultural Impacts of Tourism

As tourists, we are lucky to see and share experiences with people whose cultures, beliefs and world views differ from our own. New cultural experiences, including dress, food and festivities, are an essential ingredient of fulfilling travel for many of us. However, all too often, those very cultures that help to make our holidays so special are being violated and exploited.

A basic lack of cultural awareness about the places we go on holiday can lead us to cause inadvertent offence to local people. Topless sunbathing on beaches and scant clothing when visiting religious sites are examples of such violations of cultural norms.

In other instances, tribal villages become showcases for visiting tourists, with little benefits shared with the communities themselves. Cultural dances and artefacts become little more than commodities for tourists, often bought very cheaply and sold by middlemen and even mass produced in factories overseas. All of this can lead to feelings of frustration and resentment amongst local people towards tourists, undermining the positive experience that should come with equitable cultural exchange.

Potential Positive Impacts of Tourism

- Tourism as a force for peace
- Strengthening communities
- Reevaluation of culture and traditions

Tourism as a force for peace

Travelling brings people into contact with each other and, as tourism has an educational element, it can foster understanding between peoples and cultures and provide cultural exchange between hosts and guests. Because of this, the chances increase for people to develop mutual sympathy and understanding and to reduce their prejudices.

For example, jobs provided by tourism in Belfast, Northern Ireland, are expected to help demobilize paramilitary groups as the peace process is put in place. In the end, sympathy and understanding can lead to a decrease of tension in the world and thus contribute to peace.

Strengthening communities

Tourism can add to the vitality of communities in many ways.

One example is that events and festivals of which local residents have been the primary participants and spectators are often rejuvenated and developed in response to tourist interest.

The jobs created by tourism can act as a vital incentive to reduce emigration from rural areas.

Local people can also increase their influence on tourism development, as well as improve their job and earnings prospects, through tourism-related professional training and development of business and organizational skills.

Reevaluation of culture and traditions

Tourism can boost the preservation and transmission of cultural and historical traditions, which often contributes to the conservation and sustainable management of natural resources, the protection of local heritage, and a renaissance of indigenous cultures, cultural arts and crafts

Negative Socio-Cultural Impacts of Tourism

- Change or loss of indigenous identity or values
- Tourism can cause change / loss of local identity and values by
- Co-modification
- Standardisation

- Loss of authenticity / staged authenticity
- Adaptation to tourist demands

Co-modification

Tourism can turn local cultures into commodities when religious rituals, traditional ethnic rites and festivals are reduced and sanitized to conform to tourist expectations, resulting in what has been called "reconstructed ethnicity." Once a destination is sold as a tourism product, and the tourism demand for souvenirs, arts, entertainment and other commodities begins to exert influence, basic changes in human values may occur. Sacred sites and objects may not be respected when they are perceived as goods to trade.

Standardization

Destinations risk standardization in the process of satisfying tourists' desires for familiar facilities. While landscape, accommodation, food and drinks, etc., must meet the tourists' desire for the new and unfamiliar, they must at the same time not be too new or strange because few tourists are actually looking for completely new things.

Tourists often look for recognizable facilities in an unfamiliar environment, like well-known fast-food restaurants and hotel chains.

Loss of authenticity and staged authenticity

Adapting cultural expressions to the tastes of tourists or even performing shows as if they were "real life" constitutes "staged authenticity". As long as tourists just want a glimpse of the local atmosphere, a quick glance at local life, without any knowledge or even interest, staging will be inevitable.

Adaptation to tourist demands

Tourists want souvenirs, arts, crafts, and cultural manifestations, and in many tourist destinations, craftsmen have responded to the growing demand, and have made changes in design of their products to bring them more in line with the new customers' tastes.

While the interest shown by tourists also contributes to the sense of self-worth of the artists, and helps conserve a cultural tradition, cultural erosion may occur due to the commodification of cultural goods.

Culture clashes

Because tourism involves movement of people to different geographical locations, and establishment of social relations between people who would otherwise not meet, cultural clashes can take place as a result of differences in cultures, ethnicity, religion, values, lifestyles, languages, and levels of prosperity.

The result can be an overexploitation of the social carrying capacity (limits of acceptable change in the social system inside or around the destination) and cultural carrying capacity (limits of acceptable change in the culture of the host population) of the local community.

Cultural clashes may further arise through:

Economic inequality

Many tourists come from societies with different consumption patterns and lifestyles than what is current at the destination, seeking pleasure, spending large amounts of money and sometimes behaving in ways that even they would not accept at home.

One effect is that local people that come in contact with these tourists may develop a sort of copying behaviour, as they want to live and behave in the same way.

Especially in less developed countries, there is likely to be a growing distinction between the 'haves' and 'have-nots', which may increase social and sometimes ethnic tensions.

In resorts in destination countries such as Jamaica, Indonesia or Brazil, tourism employees with annual salaries of US\$ 1,500 spend their working hours in close contact with guests whose yearly income is well over US\$ 80,000.

Irritation due to tourist behaviour

Tourists often, out of ignorance or carelessness, fail to respect local customs and moral values.

When they do, they can bring about irritation and stereotyping.

They take a quick snapshot and are gone, and by so acting invade the local peoples' lives.

Job level friction

In developing countries especially, many jobs occupied by local people in the tourist industry are at a lower level, such as housemaids, waiters, gardeners and other practical work, while higher-paying and more prestigious managerial jobs go to foreigners or "urbanized" nationals.

Due to a lack of professional training, as well as to the influence of hotel or restaurant chains at the destination, people with the know-how needed to perform higher level jobs are often recruited from other countries.

This may cause friction and irritation and increases the gap between the cultures.

Even in cases where tourism "works", in the sense that it improves local economies and the earning power of local individuals, it cannot solve all local social or economic problems.

Sometimes it substitutes new problems for old ones.

Examples of negative impacts: -

In many Muslim countries, strict standards exist regarding the appearance and behaviour of Muslim women, who must carefully cover themselves in public.

Tourists in these countries often disregard or are unaware of these standards, ignoring the prevalent dress code, appearing half-dressed (by local standards) in revealing shorts, skirts or even bikinis, sunbathing topless at the beach or consuming large quantities of alcohol openly.

Besides creating ill-will, this kind of behavior can be an incentive for locals not to respect their own traditions and religion anymore, leading to tensions within the local community.

The same types of culture clashes happen in conservative Christian communities in Polynesia, the Caribbean and the Mediterranean.

Ethical issues:

Crime generation

Crime rates typically increase with the growth and urbanization of an area, and growth of mass tourism is often accompanied by increased crime.

The presence of a large number of tourists with a lot of money to spend, and often carrying valuables such as cameras and jewellery, increases the attraction for criminals and brings with it activities like robbery and drug dealing.

Repression of these phenomena often exacerbates social tension.

Child labour

Studies show that many jobs in the tourism sector have working and employment conditions that leave much to be desired: long hours, unstable employment, low pay, little training and poor chances for qualification.

In addition, recent developments in the travel and tourism trade (liberalisation, competition, concentration, drop in travel fares, growth of subcontracting) seem to reinforce the trend towards more precarious, flexible employment conditions.

For many such jobs young children are recruited, as they are cheap and flexible employees.

Cultural Tourism Leads the Growth of Travel Industry

With the tourism industry growing steadily, we became curious to see if cultural tourism is a key contributor. Over the past couple of weeks, we have found that an expanding number of travelers are more interested in cultural heritage and cultural activities when planning a trip now than ever before. Their search for cultural exposure brings them to off the beaten path destinations in search of authentic experiences. Today, more and more people seek to learn something new during their travels.

Significant Statistics

- International tourist arrivals reached 1.138 billion in 2014 - 4,000% higher than the 25 million annual tourists in the 1950s and 4.7% increased compares to 2013
- The travel industry contributed \$7.6 trillion of world GDP in 2014, which equates to 9.8% of the total world GDP
- The tourism industry employed nearly 277 million people in 2014 and projected to increase to 356 million by 2025
- 81% of the U.S. tourists are considered as ‘cultural tourists’
- Over one-third of U.S. tourists agree that specific arts, cultural or heritage events will influence their choice of destination
- Many travellers extend their stay in a destination because of cultural activities

These positive statistics indicate huge potential for cultural tourism to continue to thrive in the industry. Its upward tendency makes it a force, driving the industry forward.

Benefits of Cultural Tourism

Many destinations are famous for their cultural elements: Spain, Italy, France, and the United Kingdom. However, the benefit of cultural tourism is more recognizable in developing countries. One of the examples is China, which is becoming a Mecca for cultural tourism with its long and profound history. There are numerous historical encounters and human moments that should not be missed. And its long distance from source markets like North America and Europe is not a

hindrance. In 2014, China received 3,846 million tourists. They brought in a total revenue of about ¥3,380 billion, a 14.7% increase compared with 2013. Travel industry contributes over 4% to the growth of the China's GDP and greatly enhances employment and economic development.

The concern is how to promote cultural tourism sustainably, so it brings positive benefits to a destination instead of harm. The Global Sustainable Tourism Council's criteria for destinations and travel trade addresses this and, replete with its own set of project indicators, offers destinations in development a measureable way to protect cultural heritage in parallel with the rising success of tourism.

Culture and tourism are inseparable faces of the coin playing a very significant role in present times as the concept of alternate tourism is coming up. Culture tourism can be explained as that part of this growing smokeless industry wherein tourists find themselves engaged in a country's culture like that of life style of people, historical background of the peoples, art and architecture, music and dance forms, rituals & beliefs, dress & styles, food & festivals and lot more to mention a few.

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Intercultural Tourism & Communication - A Key to Peace

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Abstract

Tourism may look quite easy going for travellers but is in fact, much a complex industry for the stakeholders that involves a broad range of businesses, organisations and government agencies working together at different levels to deliver a package performing complete tourism experience and satisfaction. The very intentions of the Indian government to tap & care tourism sector is not very recent rather initiated almost in the mid of the last century and are still continuing with an objective to make India a world known destination. Going through the various social impacts of tourism, we today have a firm understanding that caring for tourism and its planned development leads to a peaceful and growing harmonious living.

Communication plays a much vital role in learning and developing for specific purposes curriculum mainly in the service sectors like tourism where in speaking and listening is of utmost significance for the host and the guest. Nowadays, the role of communication has attained a cogent importance for the tourism industry as an international means to communicate, negotiate, and execute transactions with tourists. Misunderstandings and communication breakdowns are said to mark many intercultural encounters as participants rely on the norms of their mother tongue and native culture to perceive meaning in a foreign language.

The work here is an attempt to explain the significance of an appropriate approach for intercultural tourism and communication development so that we are able to compete at the international front in tourism sector and project a real image of the country existing with higher level of understanding and peace among the intercultural societies at global level.

Key words: Tourism, Tourism development, culture, communication, peace

Introduction

Tourism may look quite easy going for travellers but is in fact, much a complex industry for the stakeholders that involves a broad range of businesses, organisations and government agencies working together at different levels to deliver a package performing complete tourism experience and satisfaction. The very intentions of the Indian government to tap & care tourism sector is not

very recent rather initiated almost in the mid of the last century and are still continuing with an objective to make India a world known destination. Going through the various social impacts of tourism, we today have a firm understanding that caring for tourism and its planned development leads to a peaceful and growing harmonious living.

The sole aim of increasing the inflow of the tourists has now been coupled with the required and desired concept of sustainable tourism may it be of course involving culture tourism. A part of its marketing strategy, “Incredible India” campaign had been initiated recently and consequently the rise in data and the status is significantly felt as an outcome for the same. So which fronts and factors, we should look into and work with better observantly while India enters the second phase of its tourism development? It becomes very important in this phase to build on to already running campaign. It is also much imperative to get to the root of various issues such as infrastructure, superstructure, maintaining and developing heritage sites, education & training for the skill developing professionals but the very base for the same lies in marketing of destinations as equally significant rather than moving ahead aggressively with branding tourism and travel in the country. Implementing best international practices in tourism development with well marketed destinations is one of the significant tasks that should be keenly looked into with utmost care along with adopting the sustainable concept in letter and spirit.

Tourism is an interface for knowledge, awareness and cultural exchange, facilitating the communication between the involved communities and visitors (domestic and international). Outside contact and communications draws attention to the host community. People want to meet new individuals, new groups and new communities and interact with them and their cultures, learn and understand their rituals & traditions and even confront themselves with new developments and perspectives on life and society. Tourism has been felt largely an experience driven industry, and to interact with local culture is a unique experience – more so local personality, hospitality and food than the built super structure. The more one knows and learns about an attraction & destination, the more fulfilling and satisfying the experience will be. Tourism can be used as a tool for raising awareness specially to raise awareness of local issues and needs. There is a global trend towards investment in interpretation of natural and cultural resources. Attraction to natural and heritage icons often helps fund conservation efforts and provides opportunities for effective

management of sensitive and significant areas and cultural attractions play the sole draw card for visitation and provide one of many experiences having a long-lasting impact on the visitors' mind. For a common man, tourism looks easy going for travellers but in fact is a complex industry for the stakeholders that involve a broad range of businesses, organisations and government agencies working together at different levels to deliver a complete tourism experience. Each front in the chain contributes to the overall holiday experience of the customer in the name of visitors and tourists - from initial attractions marketing through to the ground level know-how. The very intentions of the Indian Government to pat and care tourism sector initiated in almost in the mid of fourth decade of the century and is still continuing with an objective to make India a world known destination.

Tourism has been defined differently by the scholars depending upon various sectors it involves in like the trade & commerce, the economy, the sociology, the history and the management etc. Over the decades, tourism has experienced rapid and continued growth deepening diversification to become one of the fastest growing economic sectors in the world. Tourism has now become a thriving global industry with the power to shape the developing countries in both positive and negative ways. No doubt, it has today become the fourth largest industry in the global economy. Similarly, in developing countries like India, tourism has become one of the major sectors of the economy, contributing to a large proportion of the National Income and generating huge employment opportunities directly and indirectly. It is the fastest growing service industry in the country declared having scope with great potentials for its further expansion and diversification.

Great communicative skills are among the most critical aspects of a job for anyone in the customer management industry like that of tourism and travel management, and business process management (BPM) industry as a whole. Often, large BPM companies are also global players, with employees spread in various locations, serving clients and customers from countries and cultures all over the world based on the communication skills one has to interact, understand and convince the other side. Customer service – helping millions of people meet their needs or get the most out of a product or service – is also delivered through various channels that customers use to get help for telecommunications, financial, technology or healthcare products or services they use as voice interaction through phone, or email, chat, SMS or social media. Those who provide customers excellent services are trained world-class professionals – and we have it right here that

they have great interactive & communication skills. The skills they possess and continue to have in the job which also become of life - long career and personal value.

“The ability to communicate accurately, clearly and courteously is vital for anyone who wants to have a successful career and more so when we talk of careers in tourism sector. It leads to better understanding of the other persons leading to less confusions and altercations meaning thereby a step towards peace.

Objective of the Study

The objective for this work is to know and understand the need and significance of culture and communication for tourism development leading to peace and harmony in a social setup. The study of various impacts of tourism development explains the significance of social impacts of this phenomenon wherein peace and understanding among communities has been felt with better understanding among individuals who travel and visit to the varied destinations.

Knowing Tourism

Tourism has been observed differently by the scholars basically depending upon the sectors it involves in like the trade & commerce, the economy, the sociology, the history and the management etc. to mention a few. It thus becomes much pertinent to know and understand the concept of tourism if we desire to see the impacts of the phenomena on to a social setup. While going through the various definitions of tourism, we find one of the earliest concept of tourism was provided by the Austrian economist Herman Von Schullardin 1910, who defined it as, "sum total of operators, mainly of an economic nature, which directly relate to the entry, stay and movement of foreigners inside and outside a certain country, city or a region."

Theo bald (1994) suggested that etymologically, the word "tour" is derived from the Latin term 'tornare' and the Greek term 'tornos,' meaning 'a lathe or circle; i.e. the movement around a central point or axis.' The meaning changed in modern English to represent 'one's turn.' The suffix -ism is defined as 'an action or process; typical behaviour or quality' whereas the suffix -ist denotes one that performs a given action. When the word tour and the suffixes -ism and -ist are combined, they suggest the action of movement around a circle. Therefore, like a circle, a tour represents a journey that is a round trip or a circular journey i.e., the act of leaving and then returning to the original point, and therefore, the one who takes such a journey, we refer as a tourist.

Over the decades, tourism has experienced rapid and continued growth deepening diversification to become one of the fastest growing economic sectors in the world. Tourism has now become a thriving global industry with the power to shape the developing countries in both positive and negative ways. No doubt, it has today become the fourth largest industry in the global economy. Similarly, in developing countries like India tourism has become one of the major sectors of the economy, contributing to a large proportion of the National Income and generating huge employment opportunities. It is the fastest growing service industry in the country declared with great potentials for its further expansion and diversification. However, at the same time we must not ignore the pros and cons involved with the development of tourism industry in the country.

Tourism & Culture

Tourism and culture have been dealt as largely two aspects earlier and cultural resources were seen as part of the cultural heritage of a nation. Whereas tourism, on the other hand had been considered largely an entertainment and merry making activity. The concept gradually changed and later it was observed that the role of cultural attractions in appealing tourists & visitors and differentiating destinations from one another become more obvious. This growing articulation between culture and tourism was stimulated by a number of factors.

Increased interest of masses in culture and culture related activities worked as a motivation and a new force for alternate tourism. Growing levels of cultural capital along with stimulated by rising education levels helped the process run faster. Furthermore, the growing percentage of aging populations in developed regions having enough wealth and time also increased the demand for more heritage and culture visits. Increased mobility catalyzed in the present times creating easier and frequent access to other cultures also make tourism grow.

High tech media & growing accessibility of information on culture and tourism increased the demand. Culture has been increasingly employed as an aspect of the tourism product and destination imaging strategies, and tourism has been integrated into cultural development strategies as a means of supporting cultural heritage and cultural production. This synergy between tourism and culture is seen as one of the most important reasons for encouraging a more direct relationship between these two elements. This relationship is even more significant, given the growing importance of both tourism and culture for economies around the globe. The significance of the relation between tourism and culture was recently highlighted in a press release from Madrid

(Spain) on the occasion of 2nd UNWTO/UNESCO World Conference on Tourism and Culture which can be epitomized as -

“Tourism and Culture to work together for the SDGS”

The conference was attended by Over 800 participants from 70 countries in Muscat, capital city of the Sultanate of Oman on 11-12 December 2017 for the Conference, an official event in the calendar of the International Year for Sustainable Tourism for Development 2017.

The Conference held under the patronage of H.H. Sayyid Fahd bin Mahmoud al-Said, Deputy Prime Minister for the Council of Ministers of Oman, brought together Ministers of Tourism and Ministers of Culture as well as private sector stakeholders and experts with the objective of building and strengthening partnerships between the tourism and culture sectors and enhance their role in the UN’s 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development.

The Muscat reaffirms the commitment to:

- Strengthen the synergies between tourism and culture and advance the contribution of cultural tourism to the 2030 Agenda on Sustainable Development and the 17 SDGs;
- Enhance the role of tourism and culture in peace building and heritage protection, especially in conflict affected areas;
- Promote responsible and sustainable tourism management of cultural heritage;
- Encourage a creative and innovative approach for sustainable urban development through cultural tourism; and
- Explore the inter-linkages between culture and nature in sustainable tourism.

“With over 1.2 billion people now crossing international borders each year, tourism represents a golden opportunity to break down barriers of ignorance and prejudice. It plays an important role as a vehicle for inter-cultural dialogue and, ultimately, peace.”, said Francesco Bandarin, UNESCO Assistant Director-General on Culture, in his opening speech, on behalf of UNESCO Director-General, Audrey Azoulay. “UNESCO and UNWTO are also united in our commitment to tackling the challenges of poverty and development through sustainable tourism.” he added.

The Conference initiated with a Ministerial Dialogue moderated by John Deferios from CNN International, focusing on policy and governance frameworks between tourism and culture to support responsible, culturally-aware, and inclusive tourism that contribute to the socio-economic

development of host communities, promote cross-cultural exchanges, and generate resources for the safeguarding of tangible and intangible heritage.

A Special Ministerial Dialogue addressed the role of cultural tourism as a factor of peace and prosperity. Ministers from Cambodia, Libya, Somalia, Iraq and Vietnam shared views on the capacity of tourism to support the recovery of their countries.

The technical sessions focused on tourism development and protection of cultural heritage and promoting responsible and sustainable tourism management at World Heritage sites, culture and tourism in urban development and creativity and the relevance of cultural landscapes in tourism and the integration of natural and cultural heritage philosophies and procedures for sustainable tourism development.

The widespread cultural, economic and social benefits lead to at policies promoting linking culture and tourism or the narrower development of, “cultural tourism” worldwide at continental, national and regional levels. In Europe, the European Commission promotes cultural tourism as a means of underpinning the “unity in diversity” of the EU population. Travelling to experience the culture of others allows tourists and hosts to appreciate cultural difference as well as underlying cultural ties. In Australia and Canada, culture and tourism have been linked to the development of economic opportunities for indigenous peoples. In Africa, Latin America and Asia, cultural tourism is often seen as a means of supporting heritage conservation as well as raising local incomes.

Communication and Tourism Sectors

Communication plays a much vital role in learning and developing for specific purposes curriculum mainly in the service sectors like tourism where in speaking and listening is of utmost significance for the host and the guest. Nowadays, the role of communication has attained a cogent importance for the tourism industry as an international means to communicate, negotiate, and execute transactions with tourists. Misunderstandings and communication breakdowns are said to mark many intercultural encounters as participants rely on the norms of their mother tongue and native culture to perceive meaning in a foreign language.

Communication plays a vital role in learning and developing language for specific purposes curriculum mainly in the service sectors like tourism where in speaking and listening is of utmost significance. Nowadays, the role of communication has attained a cogent importance for the

tourism industry as an international means to interact, negotiate, and execute transactions with tourists. Since tourism industry is one of the fastest-growing businesses in the world today, it plays an important role in the world economy too.

Most of these tourists working people live in countries where English is required for external purposes: to communicate and do business with people in other countries and to catch up with the advances in the field of tourism business. In addition, English is used as a means to share and transfer thoughts and cultures and to create good relationships between people in different countries. As a result, English has become an international language and is widely used as a medium for understanding and exchanging ideas among people all over the world.

As the tourism earnings stand much higher than the income compared to the other service industries and creating a variety and multi level of jobs in tourism and tourism related activities, many education institutions both government and private Indian Universities and colleges, offer undergraduate and post graduate level communication courses related to tourism business for students who intend to work in tourism or hospitality industry after graduation or even at undergraduate levels.

Due to great success of many nations in promoting tourism to increase the number of foreign tourist's inflow, tourism needs to be further developed. Due to its promotion, the role of tourism industry in generating income and creating jobs had increased manifolds. To be good hosts therefore, the people who are directly involved in tourism business should improve their communication skills especially in terms of the language used in hospitality industry. At present, tourism employees who work in international tour companies around the world especially in India have more chances to use English and certain other foreign languages like French, Japanese etc. because of the number of foreigners who come to visit to this great land of unity in diversity and an attraction for all reasons and seasons. Although these tourism employees are tried best to be skillful and are trained to use the professional communication in real situations using the syllabus written by the experts of the field, a formal need analysis to help determine the requirements of the such course for tourism employees has never been conducted in the area. Following communications skills can be summed up to grow and succeed in the customer management industry like that of travel & tourism specially as:

Active listening

- Accent comprehension
- Fluency
- Clarity of Thought and Speech
- Pronunciation
- Tone
- Rate of Speech
- Presentation of Ideas / Introduction of Concepts
- Cultural Sensitivity and Adeptness
- Confidence
- Appropriate Response
- Open mindedness to adapt to global environment

The more of these skills an employee has and hones on the job, the better suited and successful he/she will be. If someone has great communication and interactive skills, wish to get trained and further master those skills to become a world-class professional, having zeal to grow, the customer management industry specially the tourism industry is the perfect entry for him to grow!

Intercultural Tourism and Communication Leading to Peace

For a peace, loving society there should be cordial and affectionate human relationship among its individual units. A person having the knowledge of self or Brahman feels, sees and promotes oneness everywhere. There is no duality or separateness in the existence of individuals and the whole world is observed like one family, 'VasudhaivaKutumbakam'. Such a person overcomes duality and there is absence of egoism and selfishness instead oneness prevails. If a person thinks other as belonging to him or her then chances of conflicts are lesser. When a person thinks other as belonging to different group than his or her own then interpersonal relation may not be cordial relationship. A man is never happy when he is alone, signifies that the deeper truth of life exists in union and joy and it cannot be realized in isolated individuality. It can be realized only in inner spiritual non-duality and integrity which can concretely and empirically realized in a diversity of beings. Many of the present problems can be solved by following such principles in our day to day life. Egoism, arrogance and selfishness are the root cause of various problems in this world like increase in divorces, environmental problems, family problems etc. Diversity is one of the features

of today's world community, with globalization people belonging to diverse culture are coming closer to each other, interacting with each other and tourism, no doubt is the leading force for the movement of individuals and groups.

Today, tourism is one of the largest and dynamically developing sectors of external economic activities. Its high growth and development rates, considerable volumes of foreign currency inflows, infrastructure development, and introduction of new management and educational experience actively affect various sectors of economy, which positively contribute to the social and economic development of the country as a whole. Most highly developed western countries, such as Switzerland, Austria and France have accumulated a big deal of their social and economic welfare on profits from tourism.

Tourism has the power to affect cultural change leading to various modifications and merging of cultures. Successful development of a resource can lead to numerous negative impacts too if not well cared likewise overdevelopment, assimilation and conflict etc. While presenting a culture to the visitors and tourists may help preserve the culture, it can also dilute or even destroy it. The point is to promote tourism in the region so that it would both give incomes and create respect for the local tradition and culture. However, from the ecological point of view tourism is often more acceptable and preferable than any other industrial production, as it is environmentally friendlier. The big hurdle is that it is a slow process and is not easy to change the traditional way of life of the local communities. Undoubtedly in some regions or countries the alternative industries are even more harmful to the environment than tourism. Besides that in many countries of Asia and the Pacific, for example in Cook Islands, Samoa and others, tourism is the main source of income or the friendliest to the environment. It is at least better than chopping down the forests or destroying coral reefs which are a main source of livelihood for the local communities and their harmonious settlement.

Social considerations are another important reason. Government participates in tourism development in order to maximize the socio-cultural benefits of tourism (such as cultural exchange, revival of traditional crafts and ceremonies, rural development etc.). The state may also have a general responsibility to protect the social well being of individuals by minimizing tourism's adverse socio-cultural effects (such as- deterioration of important historical and archeological sites, social degradation, overcrowding of tourist attraction and facilities).

Furthermore, excessively high visibility of foreigners can lead to anxieties on the part of the local people and a tendency to blame local problems on them, and thus to a social rejection of the growth of tourism and other unfavourable impacts.

A very significant factor in sustainable tourism development today most sought-after need, is the tourist carrying capacity of the destinations, in environmental, social and cultural terms. At peak periods, visitors are known to outnumber nationals by multiples in several of the attractions world over. Whereas in larger destinations local concentration of tourism often give rise to localized problems of carrying capacity, such as overcrowding of beaches, traffic congestion, noise pollution, increased incidence of drugs and crime, and the spread of diseases brought in from outside just as has been observed in Goa, Shimla, Nainital and many other tourist spots in India.

Conclusion

India has become only the third country in the world to improve its Travel and Tourism Competitive Index by double digits in a single year. Ranked 52 in 2015, India climbed up by a healthy 12 places to be ranked 40 this year. Marketing and promotion of India as a major tourist destination is critical for the industry to achieve its potential. Lack of adequate budgetary support for promotion and marketing, compared with competing tourist destinations, is a major reason for India lagging behind as a tourist destination. Marketing under the “Incredible India” campaign helped place India as a good tourist destination on the global tourism map. Newer tourism concepts, which include cruise tourism, adventure tourism, agri tourism or rural tourism and cultural tourism, are emerging in India and these require support to develop and flourish. Hence, greater marketing push for these different products is required. To remain competitive in the fiercely competitive field, India needs to change its traditional marketing approach to a more competitive and modern approach displaying the unique cultural existence on the land. There is a need to develop a unique market position and the brand positioning statement should capture the essence of the country’s tourism products: i.e., they should be able to convey an image of the product to a potential customer as a frequent destination for the tourists from across the world. The mission “Make in India” is certainly boosting the campaign “Incredible India” to be a promotional campaign for the image of the country at international level and stability in the Indian social set up.

Communication use is being perceived a part of the professional and career development and is basically required before a syllabus development for the prospective as well as working professionals in the tourism sectors. The study can be used as guidelines for developing a tourism communication syllabus that could lead to the improvement of the learning, understanding and use by the students, workers and organizers as well. It can be helpful if utilized by those who are responsible for policy and planning as well as the related organizations in order to have a clearer understanding of communication needs for tourism students, employees and prospective job seekers who plan to work in the tourism and travel management sectors in the country and across the borders.

The study indicates that tourism can aid and assist in preserving customs and cultures by providing incentives to invest in and promote them. If properly planned, managed and promoted, local cultures can be given an impetus by the presence of tourists may be national or international. Thus, going through the various concepts of intercultural tourism, one can know that the impact of tourism on local communities can be favourable and unfavourable, when it comes to social and cultural effects depending to which extent tourism is developed in a particular region and destination. Every region has its bearing capacity, that is to say the limit of the incoming influence that does not harm and does not go against the host community. If we overcome that limit negative impacts of tourism follow.

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Sustainable Cultural Tourism: Need of the 21st Century

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Abstract

Tourism is multi-segmented industry growing worldwide & has an important & effective impact over the growth & development of any nation. The inter-relationships between culture, tourism and development are universal, affecting both developed and developing nations. In line with the overall thrust of the sustainable development agenda, the principles adopted at the Johannesburg Summit in 2002 and the priorities of the United Nations system, the issues outlined are critical in the context of lesser developed and developing countries linking as they do to agendas of poverty alleviation, human rights, social and political stability, democracy, and environmental degradation. This research paper highlights four key aspects of the discussion surrounding tourism, culture and sustainable development. First, the issues surrounding the mobilization of culture (and the closely related concept of heritage), for tourism and development are discussed. Second, the problems and opportunities relating to using cultural tourism as a focus and mechanism for economic development are discussed. Third, the potential and the realities of cultural tourism as a form of inter-cultural dialogue and exchange are explored. Fourthly, the role of cultural tourism in the agendas of environmental protection and biodiversity is discussed.

Cultural tourism can encourage the revival of traditions and the restoration of sites and monuments. But unbridled tourism can have the opposite effect. Here there is a real dilemma. Is there not a risk that the boom in cultural tourism, by the sheer weight of numbers involved, may harbour the seeds of its own destruction by eroding the very cultures and sites that are its stock in trade.

In the present scenario growth and development is one sided i.e. it does not focus on the sustainability of particular culture and we find the result of such outcomes doesn't last long. Hence this paper tried to put forward the sustainable development approach which is the need of the 21st century.

Keywords: Sustainability, Tourism, Cultural Tourism, Development, 21st century

Introduction

Tourism is the growing industry of 21st century. Each and every nation's culture is being highly influenced by the waves of tourism. Many sensitive zones of the world in terms of cultural importance have been deeply affected by the flow of tourists. Tourism have both positive and negative lasting effects on cultural and natural heritage, on creativity and cultural diversity, and on the environment and balance of societies. Generally, it is seen that sensitive zones are badly affected through the expansion of tourism and tourist activities. These circumstances arise the need of sustainability in this field. The inter-relationships between tourism and culture have attracted considerable scholarly attention over recent years and, quite rightly, have become a focal point for policy at regional, national and international level. In policy and planning terms much has been done to 'protect' culture, heritage resources and related natural environments from the excesses of unplanned and uncoordinated tourism development (Robinson and Boniface, 1999). Focus has very much been on attempting to alleviate the unwanted consequences of tourism (de Kadt 1979). However, as our understandings on the complexities of culture have evolved, and the pace and extent of change has increased within the context of globalization, so new challenges have emerged and new ways of addressing problems are required.

Sustainability refers: The term sustainability used by the Bruntland Commission has become the most often-quoted definition of sustainable development, as development that 'meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs'.

Cultural Tourism refers: Tourism the principal purpose of which is to share and enjoy physical and intangible heritage and culture, including landscapes, buildings collections, the arts, identity, tradition and language.

Sustainable Cultural Tourism: The concept of sustainable cultural tourism (SCT), has grown out of the concept of sustainable development whose most popular definition has arisen from the World Commission on Environment and Development (the Brundtland Commission). Their 1986 report (Our Common Future) defined SD as: development which meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs.

Since the landmark UNESCO 'Convention concerning the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage' (1972), we can broadly identify four key changes relating to the tourism and culture interface. First, our understanding of culture as a concept and its fundamental importance

for the construction of social identity has both broadened and deepened considerably. The definition of cultural heritage now also relates not only to material expressions such as sites and objects, but also to intangible expressions such as language and oral tradition, social practices, rituals, festive and performative events. Culture is seen much more to refer to 'ways of life' and everyday practice as well as being manifest in buildings, sites and monuments. Moreover, the diversity of culture(s) is recognized to be fundamental to, and in line with, the principles of sustainable development and thus something which needs to be both "recognized and affirmed for future generations" (UNESCO, 2001).

Circumstances of 21st century

21st century is far forward from the previous centuries in all matters. Tourism and culture are also not exception in this regard. This is the century of information technology. World has become global village due to advance communication system. Globalization, industrialization, urbanization and liberalization has brought drastic change towards development. Every information can be fetched with in a fraction of second. 21st century generation is super advance. Life has become more cozy and comfortable.

The above description is incomplete without the other part of coin. Development of 21st century has many draw backs we have all luxuries but on the cost of our original culture. Because of over interaction in cultures become influenced and affected by globalization. Tourism between cultures creates positive impact one side but affect sustainability on the other side.

Growth of Tourism and Cultural Heritage

What is clear is that tourism is growing and will have an increasing impact on cultural heritage. In its forecast Tourism: 2020 Vision, the World Tourism Organization (WTO) predicts that cultural tourism will be one of the five key tourism market segments in the future, and notes that growth in this area will present an increasing challenge in terms of managing visitor flows to cultural sites. The focus of this report is how to promote symbiosis rather than conflict, and particularly how development cooperation can facilitate achievement of this objective. Stanford University predicted that nature tourism would grow at an annual rate of 25 to 30 percent during the 1990s. Cultural tourism was expected to grow at 10 to 15 percent per year.

Understanding Culture

Culture, in its widest sense, provides a set of material and symbolic resources that are abundant in supply (arguably infinite), and highly mobile. Culture is certainly at the basis of international tourism and indeed has facilitated its growth and allowed various societies and sections of societies to participate in the development process. However, in treating culture as a resource we should not neglect aspects of agency, as the value and priority of culture(s) relates not only to its intrinsic worth, but to the ways that it is used.

This in turn begs questions about ownership of, and access to, culture, and also raises issues with regard to the ways in which culture is ‘read’ by particular typologies of tourists. So called ‘cultural products’, as Therkelsen (2003) points out: “generate associations and meanings that are influenced by the cultural backgrounds of the potential tourist”.

In this sense, tourists do not encounter culture as some value-neutral form or process. Rather, they decode culture(s), in social spaces and times in relation to particular formal and informal knowledge regimes accrued through exposure to formulated tourism packages and through the normative processes of socialization (Hennig 1997).

It is important to acknowledge that although tourism is founded upon culture(s), culture – through its practices and manifestations – exists independently and for reasons other than tourism. In line with the conclusions of the World Conference on Cultural Policies (MONDIACULT, 1982), of the World Commission on Culture and Development (Our Creative Diversity, 1997), of the Intergovernmental Conference on Cultural Policies for Development (Stockholm, 1998) and of the UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity, “culture should be regarded as the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group, and that it encompasses, in addition to art and literature, lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs” (UNESCO, 2001).

Cultural Exploitation and Irregular Development

While on the whole, international tourism continues to enjoy an on-going period of expansion and sophistication, spatially and in terms of costs and benefits, the economic, social and environmental impacts remain very uneven between and within countries. For developing countries tourism is an increasingly important export and the year on year growth in tourist arrivals has been higher than the world average.

According to UNCTAD (2004c) if the 49 Least Developed Countries (LDCs) are taken together, tourism is the single most important source of foreign exchange earnings (apart from the oil industry which is located in only three of them). However, in 2001 the LDCs accounted for less than 1 % of in terms of international tourist receipts.

For developing countries, mass tourism development is an attractive option precisely because it can generate foreign currency quickly, particularly by relying on international tour operators who can access international markets easily. However, as has been highlighted by numerous studies, there are serious drawbacks to this. First, it tends to shift the power of development away from the host government and communities toward the tour operators and the tourist generating nations. This includes the power to terminate development and switch investment to other destinations. Second, it tends to be limited spatially to particularly attractive development sites and pristine environments and does not seek to engage with problem zones and communities. Third, and related to the above, levels of investment tend to be directed toward surface issues of aesthetic concern and the needs of tourists rather than to deep-seated socioeconomic problems and the needs of host communities. Fourth, economic returns tend to be restricted to short term gains in terms of employment in the tourist sector and in related services. Frequently this results in poorly paid and insecure jobs in the service sector. The majority of revenue generated through large international tour operators tends not to flow into the destination but back to the country of the operator. Fifth, the culture(s) of the host country is only marginally engaged through mass tourism.

Because the emphasis of development is upon fixed and limited locations, and upon the provision for predominantly hedonistic activities, culture can often be reduced to brief and selective displays through limited interaction between host and guest.

Despite these drawbacks, a growing number of tour operators are seeking to establish longer term relationships with destinations and are starting to develop ethical practices. In 1999 the World Tourism Organization adopted the Global Code of Ethics for Tourism, to encourage good practice and sustainable relationships. Still, there is considerable variation amongst the practices of tour operators in particular with respect to their responsiveness to change. At one level, it would appear that those tour operators involved with mass tourism have little to contribute in terms of protecting cultural heritage and seeking to utilize culture as a development tool. However, in seeking to move toward more sustainable forms of development, founded upon cultural heritage and diversity, it is

important that the large international tour operators are brought into the networks of partners that are required to preserve, promote and mobilize culture.

Exploitation of cultural resources for tourism does not only take place by tour operators however. Within host communities some local elites and entrepreneurs can play key roles in the harnessing of cultural resources for both tourists and tour companies without due regard to both ethical and legal frameworks, often in direct response to the demand from agents and markets in the developed world. Examples include trading in antiquities (literally selling the material culture of a destination), poaching rare species in protected areas, and clearing land and communities for sale to unscrupulous tourism developers. In certain cases such practices can be seen to be a response to the pressures of poverty, as individuals attempt to utilize what resources they have to make a living. In other cases, clear crimes are being committed for short-term gains with Tourism, Culture and Sustainable Development disastrous results for the host communities and their environment. To deal with such situations it is important that remedial action is directed to the markets in demand as well as the local suppliers.

Potential negative impacts include:

- co - modification and cheapening of culture and traditions;
- alienation and loss of cultural identity;
- undermining of local traditions and ways of life;
- displacement of traditional residents;
- increased division between those who do and do not benefit from tourism;
- conflict over (and at times loss of) land rights and access to resources (including the attractions themselves);
- damage to attractions and facilities;
- loss of authenticity and historical accuracy in interpretation; and
- Selectivity in which heritage attractions are developed.

Principles for Sustainable Cultural Tourism

The ten basic principles set out below reflect common themes that emerge in the light of both this analysis and the discussion above of the issues posed by the interaction between tourism, culture and heritage in historic places. The principles should guide an integrated approach to the development of sustainable cultural tourism.

- Priority should be given to forms of cultural tourism that reduce carbon emissions, conserve rare and precious resources, in particular water and energy, and avoid waste production.
- Cultural tourism should maintain authenticity and distinctiveness and respect the dignity, rights and beliefs of local cultures.
- Tourism is an economically important activity and cultural tourism should contribute to an overall program of sustainable development.
- Cultural tourism should contribute to conservation of the cultural and heritage assets.
- Cultural tourism should be agreed and owned by the host community and the aspirations for it communicated to visitors.
- Cultural tourism should aim to provide benefits equitably to the local community.
- All local stakeholders, including municipal governments, local communities and businesses must be involved in the development of cultural tourism.
- Cultural tourism must respond to the needs of visitors and aim to deliver a high-quality visitor experience.
- The impact of tourism should be reflected in the prices to consumers and producers, prices reflecting the real cost to society and the environment.
- Cultural tourism will be built around more sustainable transport both to and within the place.

Figure 1 Sustainable cultural tourism – a dynamic process

Johannesburg Declaration on Sustainable Development (2002)

While UNESCO has pushed forward a number of multilateral normative actions and instruments relevant to the wider field of tourism, culture and development, it has also contributed to major equally relevant frameworks developed by other United Nations organizations. One important case here is the contribution to the 2002 Johannesburg Declaration on Sustainable Development and its attached Plan of Implementation of the World Summit on Sustainable Development (Rio+10) (UN 2002a, 2002b).

Reaffirming the need to respond to the problem of environmental deterioration agreed during the United Nations Conference on the Human Environment (1972) in Stockholm and the principles defined by the Rio Declaration on Environment and Development and its attached global program entitled Agenda 21 (UN Conference on Environment and Development 1992) in 1992, the Johannesburg Declaration re-emphasizes sustainable development as a guiding principle for human development and poverty eradication. It focuses in particular on the progress made in rethinking development in terms of the interdependent and mutually reinforcing principles of sustainable development – economic development, social development and environmental protection – at local, national, regional and global levels.

At the same time, it stresses that the implementation of these principles is seriously threatened by the unequal distribution of wealth at the local, national, regional and global level. In line with the Final Report of the Intergovernmental Conference on Cultural Policies for Development (1998) held in Stockholm, the UNESCO Universal Declaration on Cultural Diversity (2001c), the

UNESCO Convention on the Protection of Underwater Cultural Heritage (2001a) and the UNESCO Convention for the Safeguarding of the Intangible Cultural Heritage (2003), it relates this situation to unequal conditions of accessibility to, and ownership of, tangible and intangible, movable and immovable, natural and cultural resources. To enable and reinforce policy and practice to safeguard and enhance, but also to recreate such resources for future generations and, in line with the Millennium Declaration (UN 2000) by the Secretary General of the United Nations(3), to make poverty eradication a priority, the Johannesburg Declaration re-emphasizes the central role of culture and carefully planned cultural policy in development strategy.

**Fig 2 Model of Sustainable Development
Strategies for attaining Sustainability in Cultural Tourism**

Getting the Framework Right: Policy and Planning

This strategy is very broad, but also extremely important. Without effective policy and planning, it will be difficult to achieve sustainable tourism and protection of cultural heritage. As noted by the EU, private enterprise is the mainspring of tourism, but the sustainable development of this sector requires public sector involvement in establishing the necessary legislative framework and regional planning, in coordinating the various administrative levels of competence, and ensuring coordinated action amongst the various stakeholders.

Organizing for Sustainability: Institutional Issues

As noted by the EU (European Union), many different bodies share responsibility for the development of tourism, and inadequate coordination is often the cause of unbalanced growth, as well as the failure to fully reap the benefits of tourism. Lack of coordination is not, of course, unique to tourism. However, tourism cuts across several sectors, including transport, finance, immigration/foreign affairs, and culture/nature/environment. Moreover, the tourism ministry, if it exists, often is less powerful than many of the other ministries; the same often is true for the culture/nature management ministries.

Partnerships: A Key Component

There are a multitude of actors in CHT, as well as a multitude of scales (e.g., local, national, international) at which they interact. Achieving coordination and partnerships across these groups is challenging, but can be a key to sustainability. The EU stresses that: the industry, the public authorities and civil society must work in concert, taking account of the needs of the market, the needs of the local population and the special features of the destination. Such partnerships not only promote the setting of balanced objectives, but also promote achievement of these objectives through utilization of the varied skills and contributions each actor can make. For example, government clearly has an important role in CHT, but the private sector and NGOs offer skills, contacts, flexibility, and political independence that government agencies and local communities may lack. Existing tourism businesses, and related associations or consultancies, can play particularly important roles in terms of product evaluation, product development, and marketing.

Financing: The Funding Necessary for Sustainability

Many heritage resources are lost due to physical deterioration brought about by inadequate maintenance or by simple neglect. Often these conditions are the result of a lack of financial resources. In short, public funding for cultural heritage sites is very limited. Moreover, site visitation typically generates additional costs for underfunded heritage managers. In such circumstances, some people speak of capturing tourism industry profits in order to finance culture. A more realistic approach is to view culture as an input to the tourism product, an input for which the industry should pay, just as they pay for petrol/gasoline for tour busses. In other words, the “user pays” principle is adopted, and cultural and natural attractions are “sold” at a price high enough to generate the funding needed to encourage their establishment and maintenance.

Information and Communication

As with certification programs, the information and communication approach relies on voluntary actions and thus should be only one part of a broader approach to achieving sustainability.⁶⁹ Nonetheless, it can be an important strategy for sustainable tourism, one which has not been pursued to its potential. Within this area, at least three target groups can be considered: visitors, host communities, and professionals within the industry and/or government.

Research and Information Gathering

Though the single most important input to achieving sustainable tourism is probably political will, knowledge and information is also vital. A significant amount of knowledge and information already exists in various forms, from the “local knowledge” of communities to the academic knowledge of tourism and heritage researchers. Nonetheless, the discussion of strategies highlights the importance of gathering additional information in various arenas, from consumer research (e.g., on visitor preferences and decision-making processes) to tourism’s impacts (economic, environmental, social, and cultural). This information can serve as vital input to effective planning and management.

Initiatives Taken by GOI For Sustainable Culture Tourism: -

AdarshSmarak: ASI has identified 100 monuments to be developed as Model Monuments. These monuments would be provided necessary tourist facilities including Wi-Fi, security, signage, encroachment free area, interpretation centers showing short films about the importance of monuments and signboards of Swachh Bharat Abhiyan.

‘Bharat Parv’

The ‘Bharat Parv’ event is being organized by the Government of India at the Red Fort, Delhi from 26th to 31st January, 2018 as part of the Republic Day 2018 celebrations. The Main Objective of this event is to promote the rich culture diversity of the country and to ensure wider participation of the general public.

HRD Ministry has taken up several initiatives under Ek Bharat Shreshtha Bharat campaign:

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The main objective of EBSB is to foster national integration by a co-ordinate mutual engagement process between States, Union Territories, Central Ministries, Educational Institutions and general

public through linguistic, literary, cultural, sports, tourism and other forms of people-to-people exchanges.

Adopt A Heritage (Apni Dharohar, Apni Pehchaan): -The project plans to assign heritage sites/monuments and other tourist sites to private sector companies, public sector companies and individuals for the development of tourist amenities. They would become 'Monument Mitras' and adopt the sites.

Heritage City Development and Augmentation Yojana (HRIDAY): -This scheme to preserve and rejuvenate the rich cultural heritage of the country. In the initial phase, 12 heritage cities have been identified which will be rejuvenated and developed under HRIDAY.

Discussion and Interpretation

Sustainability is obtained only when we are deeply attached to our Culture. When everyone and everything feels connected with bondage of Oneness then automatically development that is achieved is always Sustainable. The present scenario has become reversed as everyone has become ego-centric and full of greed which has adverse effect on all. Everyone is telling oneself civilized but they are not attached to the core of Culture. The people are marketing Cultural Tourism without being cultured. The form of Cultural Tourism is deteriorated as only the peripheral elements of culture are being promoted as tourism product without giving any message. So there is essentiality of making everything sustainable. If we really want to see our future existing with all the resources we have to think upon the sustainability of our culture. All the developments strategies must be cross checked with the principles of sustainability and the real development of 21st century resists upon the base of the strategies for sustainable cultural tourism development. Any Nation can utilize the optimum of Cultural resources saving it for the Future this depicts the Sustainable culture.

Conclusion

In nutshell researchers resides at a single conclusion that if we really want better 21st century then sustainability should prevail in each and every aspect of our vision and action. Tourism can flourish only on the base of Culture. Intact Culture is the basic requirement for the world's prosperity which needed to be preserved and conserved with approach of sustainable cultural tourism.

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Cultural Tourism Dimensions of Sacred Grooves in Uttarakhand

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Abstract:

Uttarakhand, also referred as Devbhoomi or the abode of Gods, has a unique cultural ecological Landscape. Even as Uttarakhand's Himalayas have attracted pilgrims across the globe to the sacred landscape pilgrimage sites for centuries, the locals have sacred landscapes of their own where deities are worshipped in or around forests. These communities follow customs and taboos that serve to protect these forests treating the ecology as a living whole. The age-old tradition of protecting the vegetation is believed to belong to the deity and is a protected resource. The folks strongly believe that their deity resides in these forests so protect these grooves at the best of their ability. Grazing, cutting trees are strictly forbidden.

It is estimated that there may be more than 1000 such sacred natural sites in Uttarakhand. Some of sacred landscapes have already been reported and researched for ecological biodiversity. Most of the material, however, has wide geographical sweep and caters to one field – botanical, zoological, ecological or ethnological. This paper provides an overview of the cultural and ecological dimensions of the Sacred Grooves in Uttarakhand and the new opportunities in terms of Ecotourism. Also aims to study how culture, ecotourism and architecture are related and what strategies can be figured to create a positive impact on the natural habitat.

Keywords: Sacred Natural Landscape, Culture, Ecotourism, Sustainable, Architecture, impact

Introduction:

Sacred Natural Landscapes (SNL's) are the best examples of conservation of living resources which have been deeply associated with nature worship. This is an initiative taken by the local people or a community for conserving native biodiversity. Since historic time period, nature worship had been an integral part of human society representing the culture, religion and social norms of these old societies. A symbiotic relation of human beings with nature is presented in the form of sacred Natural Landscapes-a concept depicting significant tradition of protecting the patches of forests dedicated to their divines.

Uttarakhand, state that lies on the southern slope of Himalayas range, also referred as Devbhoomi or the abode of Gods, has a unique cultural ecological landscape. For centuries, where pilgrimage sites of Himalayas have attracted pilgrims across the globe, ancient mountain societies have protected the patches of natural vegetation, on the basis of religious practices and cultural traditions. A 'Vernacular Conservation' practiced by local people for centuries with associated taboos and beliefs. They believe that their deities reside in that natural vegetation and will protect their community from any calamity. It's only the faith and regard for the deity, the grove is kept undisturbed, varying from community to community. Only the dead and dried parts are sometimes allowed to be used.

The provision of declaring Biodiversity Heritage Sites (BHS) in the National Biodiversity Act 2002 provides an opportunity to give recognition to the community initiatives vis-a-vis the institution of the sacred natural sites.

Socio-Ecological-Cultural Benefits:

Looking from an ecological point of view, when ecological degradation and deforestation have been going on at an alarming rate, these Sacred Natural Sites offer a protection to the inherent diversity of flora and fauna for present and future human use. While the adjacent areas were cleared for agriculture, the sacred groves are maintained intact for generations to support relict vegetations from human interference. Our ancestors were fully aware about the importance of conserving the natural resources, for the sustenance of future generations, which played an important role in conservation of bio diversity. The deep-rooted links with nature was understood by our ancestors and evolved the methods to conserve nature not only in the form of sacred groves only but along with the sacred plants, sacred animals, sacred mountains and sacred rivers, etc. To maintain a stable human ecosystem, such traditional cultures and beliefs were implemented. The basis of these beliefs systems is the social conventions and religious practices that were adapted as a unique system to save our environment. To save our country from the weather patterns, massive biodiversity loss, deforestation and ecological degradation, these sacred natural sites, have offered protection to landscape. These are called ‘Sacred Natural Landscape Sites’. The concept of sacred groves has been found to exist across the world including ancient Greek, Romans, Japanese, and Chinese and Indian mythology. Own sets of rules and practices of diverse cultures have recognized it in different ways in many parts of India under different names.

‘Natural Museums of living giant trees, treasure-house of rare, endemic and endangered species, dispensary of medicinal plants, recreation centre for urban life, garden for botanists, gene bank of economic species, paradise for nature lovers and laboratory for environmentalists’ [Vartak,1983]. In Uttarakhand, they are named as ‘Devvan’. These groves are the best examples for maintaining bio-diversity in terms of flora, fauna and cultural identity. Every Sacred Grove has landed down its own lore and legend of the oral community tradition through stories and songs over generations. Local people treat it as a holy place; devote the area to their local deities and ancestral spirits. They hold a strong belief that any activity that will destroy this sacred site, will invite the wrath of these Local Gods and will culminate in the form of disaster, whereas, if these sites are looked after, Gods will bring good fortune upon them. Along with the religious beliefs, Sacred Groves are the social cultural hub for the indigenous communities. In association with many of Sacred Groves, local people living near it, celebrate various local festivals with both religious and cultural fervor. An

ecological dimension is also added with an inherent idea of biodiversity conservation. As these areas are untouched for centuries, many species of flora and fauna exist undisturbed. These virgin forests have become a treasure of biodiversity with existing rare flora, fauna and endangered species.

Sacred Groves work as the reservoirs that help the vicinity to adapt to its own cool and fresh microclimate. Maximum sunlight is absorbed by the dark colored leaves of the vegetation and for the effective transportation of moisture back into the air, which results in cooling the atmosphere even in dry seasons. Vegetation covers the soil and prevents heat loss and radiation that helps to regulate the temperature of the soil, dust is filtered from air and acted as windbreak and suntrap. Also ground water table is maintained due to the absorption of the rain water, which completes the local water cycle. SNL's are only one way to understand the perception of indigenous communities toward sustainability and environmental conservation. Their respect and intelligence for the environment can be showcased in their rituals, customs, belief systems, taboos and festivals.

Ecotourism

This concern for the environment and the social-cultural aspects emphasized the concept of 'Ecotourism'. Ecotourism not only creates impact on people but also nature. It is a tourism that creates compatibility with the fragile landscapes and provides enhanced livelihoods to local communities. It can be both an effective conservation tool for a successful community development model, if practiced correctly. It has a scope to build conservation support, while creating awareness about the fragility of such ecosystems in the public. It also benefits the local communities living around these natural sites and is dependent on these threatened landscapes. Ecosystem is a big business, generating direct and indirect revenue for the state government and the local people. Increase in tourist's influx has enhanced livelihood opportunities to local people, who are not regular employees of ecotourism site. It also helps to create awareness in masses about the conservation of biodiversity and natural resources by synchronizing these valuable assets with livelihood of local people. The Himalayas, rich in biodiversity and scenic beauty has been the major destination centers for nature lovers from historical Times. Uttarakhand, lies in Himalayas and is well known for rich biodiversity, scenic beauty and tourist destination. This state promotes ecotourism activities especially in the forest areas of the state. A specially designed Tourism Wing

seeks to draft policies and provide funds for various ecotourism projects and provide a framework for the promotion and development of eco-tourism in the state.

Devbhoomi has an incredibly diverse culture, people, climate and landscapes in different parts of state. It features a complex geological landscape which integrates several rich ecosystems ranging across different altitudes. This landscape covers Alpine Pastures, Forest Ecotourism, Moraine, Degraded Landscape, Agro Ecosystems, River Forest Ecosystems, Grassland, Wet land, Aquatic, Agro Forest, Agro river, Glacial Moraine, Rocky Landscape, Village Landscape. These ecosystems form one of the state's special places, unparalleled in its biodiversity. This state is considered to have 280 natural landscape sites in different districts. Out of which, 152 sacred grooves, 83 Sacred Forests, 31 Sacred Water Bodies and 14 Sacred Pastures (Alpine Meadow) are identified. [References, Negi et al, 2001, Negi 2003, Negi 2005, Negi 2010, Negi 2010a, 2010b & 2010c, Negi 2012]. Uttarakhand Biodiversity Board has selected 13 Sacred Natural Landscape Sites fit to promote as ecotourism sites to improve the economy and conditions of community people. Out of which 4 are underway for approval from the states forest department. These 4 forests include Tadkeshwar in Pauri Garwal, Saim Mukhim in Tehri, Dhurka Devi in Almora and Thal Kedar in Pithoragarh. As the villagers are mostly apprehensive about outside interference in their sacred groves, NGO's are approached for these projects. These sacred grooves are managed by a committee which provides finances to be used judiciously for maintenance of forests.

Some of the best conserved sacred groves- (Clock-wise from top right, apart from those finally selected for developing into Biodiversity Heritage Sites, Chapter 10) – Ghandhura, Syang-Se, Nakuleshwar, Byandhura, Vishnu, Jhakar Sem, Se-Rong (Tedang), and Bhujaani.

Some Sacred Groves, Uttarakhand

Some of the best conserved sacred water bodies- (clock-wise from top right)-
 Bedini Kund, Balchand Kund, Nandi Kund (enroute Namik glacier), Nandi Kund,
 Kadar Kund, Kakroul Kund, Thamri Kund and Jyolingkong (Parvati Sarovar).

Some Sacred Water Bodies, Uttarakhand

Threats

There may be many benefits of ecotourism; excess activities can always be a threat. Ecotourism is listed as the second major threat to these natural landscapes sites as this gives rise to human-wildlife conflict. It is becoming threat to wildlife, as to meet the tourism needs, resource extraction mainly fuel wood and water is increasing and degrading the habitat quality of the region. For instance, Nanda Devi biosphere Reserve in Uttarakhand had to be closed due to high environment degradation caused due to ecotourism activities. Mushrooming of tourist facilities around protected areas has led to the exploitation and disturbance of these conserved ecosystems. Also due to commercialization of private tour operators, as they do not follow the prescribed guidelines for Ecotourism and not involving local people has led to economic leakages that have reduced the availability of funds for local people and the protected sacred groves.

While preamble of ecotourism is to imply on environmentally responsible tourism, ecotourism itself has become an unsustainable practice, today. Instead, ecotourism is creating negative impact on the tourist areas. Carelessly, planned or poorly implemented ecotourism projects results in projecting negative impacts. Unplanned tourism in such landscapes can cause destruction of the environment whereas that is the major source of attracting such tourism.

Approach:

There is a need to move towards a model of tourism that is compatible in these landscapes.

Success depends on careful planning and management. As per UNWTO (United Nations World Tourism Organization), sustainability principles refer to the environmental, socio-cultural aspects of tourism development along with creating suitable balance between these three dimensions. Tourism infrastructure must conform to environment –friendly low impact architecture, renewable including solar energy, rain water harvesting, water cycle recycling, natural cross ventilation, no use of asbestos, controlled sewage disposal and merging with the surrounding landscape.

For a sustainable Ecotourism:

In Uttarakhand, the culture still survives and keeps holding up very strong. This state is rich in its nature and culture.

- Activities involved in ecotourism should be undertaken in a sustainable manner. It is possible only if it is well planned and runs on a set of guiding principles as per UNWTO

- Sustainable tourism planning is the one concept that significantly contributes the environmental knowledge into planning. It involves planning
 1. From the site selection
 2. Site evaluation
 3. Appropriate implementation of the planning concepts
 4. Monitoring
- Environmental management system plans should be implemented.
- Environmentally sensitive construction techniques should be used.
- Solid Waste Management Plan, should be implemented with proper solid waste management or suitable way to transport to other disposal sites.
- The visitor's carrying capacity should not be exceeded. It should be closely monitored.
- Designing a sustainable community model, that will connect to the community.

Sustainable Community model:

Benefits:

- This will give local people employment opportunities that will in return improve quality of life, while still preserving their culture.
- This will be a positive contribution to the village that suffers the effects of rural migration. If the quality of life is improved, their migration can be decreased to a certain extent.
- It will be a tool, linking bio diversity conservation with community development.
- Involving Community to participate in the design and construction process.
- Careful use of sustainable materials.
- Fixing a maximum share of the Sacred Grove income as an honorarium to the local people for conducting various activities in the environmental conservation so that fixed amount is used for maintenance and development of sacred grove to a ecotourism site.

Environmentally sensitive Construction Techniques:

Minimizing site disturbance caused by the development and construction process is the foremost concern when establishing a ecosystem site. Priority concerns also include natural hydrology, social stability and quality of vegetation around the site. Damage to natural vegetation should be minimal and controlled. Views and qualities of the site should be considered in priority.

Developing a Sustainable Model:

Energy:

- Main power supply is solar energy.
- Plan in such a manner that allows thermal performance during winters and shading during summers.
- Cross flow ventilation so that prevailing breezes facilitates the residents.
- Use of passive solar design, solar hot water and energy conservation principles should be adopted.
- For winter heating-long sides of the house face N and S. Low winter sun from S heats the floor and stores heat for reradiating at night. Insulated roof and wall aid retention of heat.
- For summer cooling, shading the S-Facing windows in summer. Operable windows allow for effective cooling because of cross ventilation.

Water:

- Main water source is supplied by rainwater collected in small existing water bodies or tanks from roof water.

Waste:

- There are many ways of treating the sewage.
- Clivus Multrum Dry Composting system can be installed.
- Waste water is removed from the system and passed through a digester where it is further filtered through a fine weave material healed with bacteria and passed into a transpiration trench, where it evaporates. Solid waste is recycled.
- Environ cycle septic system can also be relied upon.
- It is an aerobic waste treatment system that reticulates clean nutrient rich water into surrounding landscape.

Building Materials:

- Material should be light weight and simple construction techniques should be implied.
- Wastage should be minimized by using limited number of materials.
- Other building materials can include color bond steel for roofing and compressed fiber cement for wall cladding.
- Materials should be selected primarily for passive thermal performance, durability and aesthetic values.
- Recyclable and reusable materials should be brought to use.

Connected with Landscape:

- Very strong connection should be established with landscape.
- Uninterrupted views to the forests
- Design should ensure a full experience of weather, climate while still affording necessary protection and privacy.
- Open Plan Design and floor to ceiling windows provide maximized indoor/ outdoor views 'brings the outside in' giving the feeling of living amongst the trees.
- Overall sense of the interior space is peace, isolation and appreciation for nature.

Fire Protection Consideration:

- Installation of a dedicated rain water tank for the use of fire.

- Use of Protective building materials such as laminated glass, aluminum windows and colorbond steel.
- Evacuation plan has to be established.

Conclusion:

Ecotourism focuses on protection of natural and cultural spaces. To achieve the goal, ecotourism should be conducted in a planned and sustainable manner to reap the economic gains without affecting the environment. Inappropriate tourism development and practices degrade the natural landscapes, deplete the natural resources and generate the pollution. A social –cultural and economical issue has prevailed for decades, since relationship has not yet been established between local community and tourists. With the use of the Sustainable model, a new relationship can be developed between tourists and community; between eco village and eco-tourism, between sustainable architecture and ecotourism.

An approach to this issue is through sustainable architecture and development using sustainable building techniques and through educating the local people by involving them in construction process. In this way, the sustainability of well beings of human cultures that exhibit these environments is sustained and tourists get an opportunity to get engaged with community through interaction. It can promote awareness and support for the conservation of local culture, creating economic opportunities for communities. To make ecotourism become a real, it must be based on a new significant, ideological and moral development that takes a success for Ecotourism.

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Promotions of Obscured Tourist Destinations through Digital Marketing

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Abstract

Tourism is one of the most demanding, progressive and exciting industries. Part of the visitor economy, tourism is also big business and it impacts on almost every other industry. These days promotion and selling of products to customers is a major issue to various tourism organisations. To reach to a larger segment of society and making them aware about their product and services matters a lot therefore, these days various tourism organisations are majorly depending upon digital marketing techniques so that they can widely cover their customer and sell their products to them. Technology is growing at a faster pace these days and people are also becoming tech savvy therefore, digital marketing is playing a major role in the awareness of people about the product and services. If you are non-technical the world of digital marketing may seem a bit daunting at first. All that technology seems to be really complicated but not necessary. One of the key things to remember is this: Digital marketing is not about understanding the underlying technology, but rather about understanding people, how they're using that technology, and how you can leverage that to engage with them more effectively. Being user friendly in nature this technology is helping organisations to create their own niche in the market. These days it's important for all businesses to have a strong mark of online presence. Maintaining an effective website and implementing strong Internet marketing techniques, including social media, are great ways to bring in more leads and make your website work for your organisations. This is even more significant for tourism industry, where customers have many options and may not know the area and want to get the detail about the tourist destinations, recreational services and other services and for all these things the role of digital marketing comes in.

Implementing a well-thought social media program is essential in the tourism industry. By having a page on social sites such as facebook, twitter etc. helps a lot in the enhancement of the business. Simultaneously, organisations need to hire a IT professional for their company who can update

special offers, and deals, share valuable information about the organization and market their products and services and keeps on updating website. A Twitter account is a great way to manage customer service issues. Visit relevant blogs and post a comment with a link to your site below other's postings. Or create your own blog for your company and link it to your website. Also, take advantage of YouTube by uploading your videos and commercials. This is a great place to store virtual tours as well. Business owners have faced many obstacles while trying to "become a player" in the social media arena however with the passage of time they have becoming more used to and able to work with this new technology in a friendly way which is overall helping them to expand their business and become available at the nook and corner of the nation.

Key words: Digital Marketing, destination, tourist, tourism

Introduction

Advertising is an essential component in the marketing of any business, has been around for the long time. People have been trying to influence other people since the dawn of human existence, utilizing whatever means and media they had at their disposal at the time. The human voice and word of mouth, of course came first.

The development of printing during the 15th and 16th centuries heralded a significant milestone in advertising, marketing it more cost-effective for marketers to reach a much wider audience. In the 17th century, adverts globe. The first form of mass-media advertising was born.

The 18th and 19th centuries saw a future in newspaper advertising and alongside it the birth of mail-order advertising, which would evolve into the massive direct mail/direct response industry that has been utterly disrupted by the internet but still exists today.

The 20th century saw the dawn of another new medium through which advertisers could reach out to prospective customers. Then came television, which shifted the advertising landscape yet again, and towards the end of the century a new force-the internet-began moving out of the realm of 'techies' and early adopters to become a valuable business and communication tool for the masses. The era of digital marketing was born.

Technological advances have punched the evolution of advertising throughout history, each fundamentally altering the way that business could communicate with their customers, however none of these ground-breaking developments suppress those that came before. Developments in

technology and the evolution of marketing are inextricably intertwined. Technology has underpinned major milestones in the history of marketing since its inception. Technology has the ability to open up completely new markets and to radically shake up existing ones. The mainstream adoption of digital technology – the internet, the software applications that run on it, and the devices that allow people to connect both to the network and to each other whenever, wherever and however they want to – promises to dwarf all that has come before it. It heralds the single most disruptive development in the history of marketing. Whether that disruption represents an opportunity or a threat to you as a marketer depends largely on your perspective.

Digital Marketing

Technology merely affords the marketer new and existing platform that allow them to connect with people in increasingly diverse and relevant ways.

For marketer's evolution of the marketplace, and the shift in consumer mindset that it heralds, presents a plethora of new challenges. As consumers increasingly embrace new ways of communicating, take greater ownership of the information and entertainment they consume, and aggregate in increasingly specialized niche online communities, marketers must engage in new ways and shift their approach if they want to connect with them. And the first step on their journey is to understand what digital marketing is.

If you are non-technical the world of digital marketing may seem a bit daunting at first. All that technology seems to be really complicated but not necessary. One of the key things to remember is this: Digital marketing is not about understanding the underlying technology, but rather about understanding people, how they're using that technology, and how you can leverage that to engage with them more effectively.

People are embracing digital technology to communicate in ways that would have been inconceivable just a few short years ago. Digital technologies are no longer the preserve of tech-savvy early adopters, and today ordinary people are integrating them seamlessly into their everyday lives. One should learn to use the tools at his disposal – but understanding people is the real key to unlocking the potential of digital marketing.

Whether you are running a home based business or business at large scale, customers prefer to choose online channels for products information, research and purchasing needs. Now these days,

target market comes to rely on these online channels. Obviously, the more the target market, the more critical digital marketing will become to the ongoing success of business.

Review of Literature

- The concept of a destinations' image is closely linked to Urry's (1990) seminal work on the "tourist gaze", where he argues that tourists are, "directed towards features of the landscape that separate them off from everyday experiences". Turner, et al, (2005) argues that this gaze is manipulated so that "the gaze falls upon what the gazer expects to see". Ibrahim and Gill (2005) linked this tourist gaze to a destinations image, arguing that before a tourist engages with a destination, they already have preconceived ideas of what they expect to see, which are based on a destination image, but how and where does the tourist source such images?
- Crompton (1979) argues that destination image is composed of a mixture of beliefs, ideas and impressions that a person holds about a certain destination, while Buhalis (2000) stated that destination image is made up of, "a set of expectations and perceptions a prospective traveller has of a destination".
- In terms of destination image, there is empirical evidence, to suggest a strong link
- between destination image and tourists' buying behaviour. Sirgy and Su (2000) found that, "consumer research has shown that a consumer's attitude towards a product (and product purchase) is influenced by matching a product's user image with the consumer's self concept". This can be tested and applied to a tourists' attitude towards a destination, as tourists have stereotypic images of different destinations.
- Franklin and Chang (2001) argue that tourists are, "seeking to be doing something in the places they visit rather than being endlessly spectatorially passive". New technology has given the tourist the power to plan their own itinerary and to go to places beyond the gaze. As MacCannell (1989) argues, "touristic consciousness is motivated by its desire for authentic experiences, and the tourist may believe that he is moving in this direction, but often it is very difficult to know for sure if the experience is in fact authentic".
- Fyall and Garrod (2005) argue that the tourist is now an active partner in the marketing process, and in order for destinations to succeed, they must "be able to provide them with

the types of information and experience they are increasingly able to demand”. King (2002) argues that marketers should look to establish ongoing, two-way communication channels with their clients, and that greater emphasis should be placed on the creation and the promotion of vacation experiences, that link key brand values and assets with the desires of the customer. Consumers are becoming better informed, better connected, more communicative, and more in control than ever’, highlights Julian Smith, an analyst with Jupiter Research writing for the Clicks network. ‘They are better informed through the increased ability to access and sift an abundance of information anytime, anywhere. They are better connected through the ability to instantaneously communicate with others across time zones and social strata. They are more communicative through the ability to publish and share their ideas and opinions. They are more in control through the ability not only to personalize their information and entertainment consumption, marketing messages, and the products and services they buy, but also to gain satisfaction on demand’.

- Analysts at Jupiter Research identified seven key ways in which the increasingly widespread adoption of technology is influencing consumer behaviour.

Objectives

The aim of this paper is to investigate the different ways of Digital Marketing and the use of it as a tourism-marketing tool from the viewpoint of tourism organizations and tourists.

- To Study different ways of digital marketing: Digital media plays a vital role in Digital marketing.
- To determine the need of Digital Marketing in tourism industry.
- How Digital Marketing helps in tourists’ destinations promotion: DM helps you to keep your business ahead of the pack. Helps in increasing the revenue of the business.
- Problems faced by business people or marketers for adopting Digital Marketing.
- To identify its effect on the relationship between their business or brand, and their customers and prospects.

Research Methodology

This is a descriptive paper based on review of literature. Primary data is limited to personal interviews of executives and Managers in the Hospitality & Tourism industry. Secondary data sources comprising of articles, research papers, books and journals of the contributions in this area by the experts.

Research Methodology

In research design an arrangement was made for collection and analysis of data in a manner that aims to combine relevance to the research purpose. For the present study, we required a sample of those who are working in the various destinations of the tourism industry and guests who are tech savy and using various modes of technology for exploring various tourists' destinations. The study was conducted by collecting first hand data through getting questionnaires filled. During the time of collecting information it has been tried to gather data in such a manner so that respondents of different categories such as service providers and guests who are availing the digital marketing services provided by the service providers.

Techniques for Data Collection

In the present study, interviews were conducted of the various executives and Managers in the Hospitality & Tourism industry and guests who are availing services of digital marketing keeping in view different objectives of the study respondent's interviews were conducted.

Analysis and Interpretation

- **To Determine The Need Of Digital Marketing In Tourism Industry:**

Earlier, it was very difficult to contact people who were living at faraway places due to lack of commutation and communication but with the help of digital channels person can transcend traditional constraints such as geography and time zones to connect with a much wider audience. At the same time, digital technology allows to hone your marketing message with laser like precision in order to target specific niche segments within that wider market. Implemented effectively it can be an incredibly powerful combination.

Digital marketing helps to grab the opportunity and prevents to lose business. It future-proofs business by helping to understand the origins of digital marketing and the trends that are shaping its future. It provides a concept of the scale of the online marketplace, the

unfolding opportunities and the digital service providers who will help business to capitalize on them. And therein lies the crux of our need for a cohesive digital marketing strategy. If we are going to harness the power of digital marketing to drive our online business to dizzying new heights, we need a thorough understanding of our market, how our customers are using digital technology, and how our business can best utilize that same technology to build enduring and mutually rewarding relationships with them.

- **To Analyze Different Ways Of Digital Marketing**

Digital media plays a vital role in Digital marketing. Digital media helps to do digital marketing and keeps it alive and well. The world of digital media is changing at a phenomenal pace. Its constantly evolving technologies, and the way people are using them, are transforming not just how we access our information, but how we interact and communicate with one another on a global scale. It's also changing the way we choose and buy our products and services.

Digital media is the mass market of tomorrow, and for business people and marketers the challenge is to become fluent in this new digital language so that they can talk effectively to their target customers. Digital marketers have always been interested in new geographical markets but the need to understand new customer is paramount.

Digital media has a power that can achieve amazing things. The printing press, radio, television and now the internet are all examples of major breakthroughs in technology that ultimately altered the relationships between marketers and consumers for ever, and did so on a global scale. But, of course, marketing isn't about technology; it's about people: technology is only interesting, from a marketing perspective, when it connects people with other people more effectively.

Internet

To understand the explosive growth of the internet we need to look back at how early communications technology evolved into the global network of interconnected computers that today we call the internet. The story of electronic communication begins with the wired telegraph – a network that grew explosively to cover the globe, connected people across vast distances in a way that seemed almost magical, and changed the world for ever. In the developed world internet

access is becoming practically ubiquitous, and the widespread availability of always-on broadband connections means that people are now going online daily to do everything. Unlike conventional forms of mass media marketing, the internet is unique in its capacity to both broaden the scope of your marketing reach and narrow its focus at the same time. It's often stated that the internet puts consumers in control as never before. But it's also important to remember that the internet also delivers an unprecedented suite of tools, techniques and tactics that allow marketers to reach out and engage with those same consumers.

E-mail:

E-mail one of the internet's most widely used applications, and one of the most critical for internet marketers.

Website

When it comes to getting your business and brand out in front of online consumers, there are a number of tools you can use. First and foremost, of course, you can and should use your own website as a vehicle to make your PR-related content available to both media professionals and consumers. It's perhaps the only place online where you have direct control over every aspect of your content: how it looks, how it's presented and how people interact with it. Your site is also the ideal place to host added value content that supports your broader off-site PR campaign, enticing people to click back to your own online real estate, where you can track and measure their engagement.

People could suddenly find what they were looking for online – could get access to what they wanted, when they wanted it – without having to go through the frustrating rigmarole of a dial-up connection. It transformed the online experience, turning it from a passing curiosity into a useful everyday tool for a much wider demographic of users. And the more people used the internet, the more indispensable it became. Provide practical, real-world examples of digital marketing successes-including leading brands that have become household names in a relatively short space of time.

- **How Digital Marketing Helps In Tourists Destinations Promotion**

Helps to keep you focused: Ultimately, digital marketing gives the tool need to harness the power of the internet in order to take business wherever businessmen want it to go. It helps businessmen or business to choose online advertising and marketing channels that will get

their ideas, products and services to a massive and ever expanding markets. It provides elusive competitive edge that will keep them ahead of the pack and also help them in increasing the revenue of the business.

Grab the Opportunities

Digital Marketing helps to grab the opportunities without this marketer would miss prospect and lose business. In truth, there are very few businesses today that would not benefit from at least some degree of digital marketing- even if it is just providing a basic online brochure telling people what you do, and sending out the occasional update to existing customers via an e-mail newsletter or RSS (Really Simple Syndication – a way to retrieve updated posts or articles from a website automatically) feed.

Decision Making

Formulating a digital marketing strategy will help them to make informed decisions about their foray into the digital marketing arena, and ensure that your efforts are focused on the elements of digital marketing that are most relevant to their business.

Research & Choose: It doesn't matter what business you are in, it is a fairly safe bet that an increasing number of your target market rely on digital technology every day to research, evaluate and purchase the products and services they consume.

If your customers use digital technology to research and/or purchase the products and services you provide, then you absolutely need to embrace digital marketing now in order to engage with them and retain them. If they don't, then you don't. It really is that simple.

Some products and services are obviously more suited to online purchase and fulfillment than others (digital files, such as e-books or music, spring to mind), you will also find being marketed effectively through digital channels plenty of times that few people would ever dream of actually purchasing over the internet. Consumers go online to research, evaluate and compare their choices.

- **Problems faced by business people or marketers for adopting Digital Marketing:**

The basic problem faced by business people is whether their audience is online or not or is it going to be online in future. If customers do not use digital technology to research and/or purchase the products and services you provide, in that case digital marketing becomes tedious.

Installing modern technology requires financial investment and training as result it is an important aspect for the marketer or businessman to evaluate the market and their product thoroughly so they he should be able to get benefit in future by adopting digital media in their business.

Are my products/services/brands suited to digital marketing? This can be a tricky one-but the answer is usually yes. Typically it doesn't matter what your product, service or brand is: as long as you have established that there is a viable online audience for it, if you do not have in that case it is just wastage of time and energy. Sometimes customers do not get the full or right information when an online booking is made as result he feels deceived.

Digital marketing of products and services also demands customers' access to computers as result people who do not have access to modern technology they feel deprived of getting information from this kind of marketing and their access to new and different products and services also becomes limited.

- **How it affects the relationship between their business and their customers and prospects**

Digital Marketing is a crucial first step towards understanding how the constantly evolving digital marketplace relates to marketer, and how it influences the relationship between their business and their customers and prospects. Digital marketing not only changes the way that the user interacts with it, but often also asks users to embrace new behaviors. It has been determined that the wide spread adoption of technology is influencing product buying ability of the consumers and puts him at ease by providing him below mentioned services or facilities.

Interconnectivity

Networked digital technology is enabling consumers to connect with each other more readily, be it through e-mail, instant messaging (IM), mobile messaging, or web-based social networking platforms. Consumers are interacting with like-minded people around the world, paying scant regard to trifling concerns like time zones or geography. Peer-to-peer interaction is reinforcing social networks and building new virtual communities.

Information

Technology is leveling the information playing field: With digital technology content can be created, published, accessed and consumed quickly and easily. As a result the scope of news, opinion and information available to consumers is broader and deeper than ever. Consumers can conduct their own unbiased research, comparing and contrasting products and services before they buy. Knowledge is power, and digital technology is shifting the balance of power in favour of the consumer.

Relevance filtering is increasing

With such a glut of information available to them, digital consumers are, through necessity, learning to filter out items relevant to them and to ignore anything they perceive as irrelevant. Increasingly digital consumers look to have their information aggregated, categorized and delivered (whether through e-mail or RSS feeds). They use personalization features to block out irrelevant content and increasingly employ software solutions to exclude unsolicited commercial messages.

Niche aggregation is growing

The abundance and diversity of online content allow consumers to participate in and indulge their specialist interests and hobbies. Aggregations of like-minded individuals congregate online; the homogeneous mass consumer population is fragmenting into ever-smaller niche groups, with increasingly individual requirements.

Micropublishing of personal content is blossoming: Digital media's interactive and interconnected nature allows consumers to express themselves online. Publishing your own content costs little more than a bit of time and imagination, whether through discussion forums, message boards, feedback forms, voting platforms, personal photo galleries, or blogs. Users are posting their opinions online for all to see and are consulting the opinion of their online peers before making purchasing decisions.

Rise of the 'prosumer'

Online consumers are getting increasingly involved in the creation of the products and services they purchase, shifting the balance of power from producer to consumer. They're letting producers know what they want in no uncertain terms: the level of interaction between producer and

consumer is unprecedented. Individuals are more involved in specifying, creating and customizing products to suit their requirements, and are able to shape and mould the experiences and communications they receive from producers. Traditional mass-production and mass-marketing concepts are rapidly becoming a thing of the past.

On demand; any time, any place, anywhere

As digital technology becomes more ubiquitous in people's lives, the corresponding acceleration of business processes means that consumers can satisfy their needs more quickly, more easily and with fewer barriers. In the digital economy, trifling concerns like time, geography, location and physical store space are becoming irrelevant. It's a world of almost instant gratification, and the more consumers get of it the more they want it – now, now, now!

Summary & Conclusion

The marketing of tourists' destinations and tourism products are rapidly changing as the needs, wants and expectations of the tourist become more demanding. Through the use of internet, the power relationship between the individual tourist and the tourism sector is changing, to the benefit of the consumer. In order to maximize the chances of attracting new consumers, marketers are under pressure to engage with their potential consumers as early as possible in the decision-making process through the provision of much more pre-decision information about a destination or product. There is no doubt that technology is changing the way tourism destinations/products are presented to the consumer. Tourism marketers can and do promote a specific destination images in order to maximize patronage.

We are in full mobile revolution and there are increased opportunities for personalized marketing through digital platforms. Customers are continuing to spend more hours a day on a mobile device, still wanting connection, context, and convenience. In order to keep pace with their expectations, there is a real need of investing in Digital marketing, in online distribution channels, being on a continuous test-and-learn loop, attracting online shoppers, increasing conversion rates, and having data mining tools to assess customer choices and understand the customer's preferences and booking patterns.

As digital channels continue to broaden the scope available to us as marketers, so they add to the potential complexity of any digital marketing campaign. Having a clearly defined strategy will help to keep us focused, ensure that our marketing activities are always aligned with our business

goals and, crucially, ensure that we are targeting the right people. Without a coherent strategy of engagement and retention through digital channels tourism business is at best missing a golden opportunity, and at worst could be left behind, watching its competitors pull away across an ever-widening digital divide. Therein lays the crux of our need for a cohesive digital marketing strategy. Just bear in mind that as the next generation of consumers start to become your new customers, they are likely to demand more digital interaction from business. If we are not in a position to deliver that, they could well choose to spend their money elsewhere.

Limitations

Although the research has reached its aims, there were some unavoidable limitations.

- The research limitations of this study include: the randomization of the sample, the rigor in which sample is selected.
- The busy schedule of respondents also makes the collection of information a difficult one.
- Lack of information related to new technology among people affect the study to get information from them.
- Time was big constraint so more time could not be devoted to individual respondents.
- Due to the unwillingness of providing any information, the respondents filled the questionnaire casually which might have affected the conclusion.

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Fascinating Principles of Prasadam of Hindu Gods

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Abstract

In Hinduism, food plays an important role in rituals and worship, and the food offered to the gods is called prasada. The Sanskrit word "prasada" or "prasadam" means "mercy," or the divine grace of God. We can make the preparing of food, the offering of food to God, and the eating of the food offered, into a powerful devotional meditation. If, as a meditative discipline, we can offer our food to God with devotion before eating it, not only are we not implicated in the karma involved in acquiring the food, but we can actually make spiritual progress by eating the offered food. It is emphasized in the texts to remind us about the meaning of existence. Anna is called Brahmin, the way bhasha is called Brahmin. God resides in food; the one who eats is god, what you are eating is also god. The concept that "god is life and life is food" is repeated constantly in mantras and other texts so that we don't forget the importance of food. Our devotion, and God's grace, subtly transforms the food offered from material nutrition to spiritual mercy or prasada. This paper will be an attempt to envisage the channel for how food was given importance in the concept Food as Prasada of Hindu Gods

Key Words: Prasada, Food, God, and Divinity, Tales

Govt Approved List Of Temples In India

- Tamil Nadu—34,000 temples
- Andhra Pradesh—43,000 temples
- Karnataka—34, 000 temples
- Kerala—28,000
- Maharashtra—45,00- 0 temples
- Mathura Brindhavan area—5000 temples
- Himachal Pradesh—over 2000 temples and sacred places

Prasadam at Lord Vishnu Temples

Indeed, sacrifice was the central feature of the religious life of the Aryan-speaking tribes. For primitive societies, all growth and evolution depended on sacrifices and ritual activity, precisely because of the close bond between human beings and nature in the tribal organization. Without sacrifice, it was believed, all cosmic processes would cease and chaos would prevail. Around the sixth century A.D. the image emerged as the centre of worship, although a sacrificial offering was still the pivotal point in the ritual. Although blood sacrifice persisted in some regions, purificatory rites assumed importance with the rise of the Brahmans as power group. These rites far outlived the sacrificial practice in the country as whole. Of all the Hindu rites, puja as we know it to performed today is a non-violent version of the blood sacrifice of the Vedic age. Influenced by Buddhist teachings, the Brahmans began to substitute harmless rice-cakes in the place of human beings or animal offered in sacrifice. These cakes were supposed to symbolically represent the real bodies of living creatures by means of the spiritual manipulation the priest. Our ancient ancestor's great sages' due to their constant quest for the Ultimate creator had attained a great treasure of divine knowledge. They shared their wisdom with mankind though Agama ritual and Vedic verses. Their aim had always been global peace, non-violence, health of the planet and protection of all creation.

Our Enlightened ancestors, the maharishis, blessed us with the Agama Shasta that prescribes the performance of various rituals. As a sugar-coated capsule of medicine is given to a patient to keep him healthy, our ancestors prescribed the rituals, festivals and celebrations by keeping the Temple as the centre of a town, village or a city. A layman may follow these instruction in blind faith with due respect subtle purpose of rituals, we arrive at the love and affection that our ancestors had towards the entire creation, the human race , our planes, its environment and finally, our safe future.

The ritual of offering food to the deity in the temple is one such act. Food offerings require good harvests m which, in turn, require high agricultural activity .The food , after it is offered to God, is distributed among assembled devotees irrespective of caste, creed, gender, age and social status. The cared food or prasadam is, in fact, happy event of daily feeding the community to take care of each other as human beings with divine guidance. The purpose of our ancestors in setting up this

beautiful ritual is, thus, achieved when the devotee gets the blessing of God in the form the Prasadam.

The Measurement Units of Prasadam

The measurements for making prasadam have an ancient origin. Although they have been detailed in texts that are thousands of years old, these measurements are followed precisely in important temples of modern times today. The rules for temples of Lord Vishnu are laid down in the Agama Shastra and strictly followed for making and offering the prasadam to God. For food offerings to be made in Lord Vishnu temples, Maharishi Arti elaborated the measurements in the ancient text of Prakeerna Adhikaram based on Vaikhanasa Agama. The measurements are as given below:

One Sukti	250 Paddy seeds
One Tilam	2 Sukti
One Prakuncham	2 Tilam
One Prashruti	2 Prakuncham
One Kudumbam	2 Prashruti
One Anjali	2 Kudumbam
One Praatham.	2 Anjali
One Aadhakam	2 Pratham
One Dronam	4 Aadhakam
one Bhaaram	2 Khari

Quantitative Measurement Unit for Prasadam

- Quantitatively, food offerings are of two kinds those that are made in terms of volume, like rice prasadam, and those that made in number of pieces, like Dosa, Vada, Appam, Etc. Both kinds are measured in Sola (approximately equivalent to 25 Kgs), which is the common measurement for all prasadam. The food offerings prepared in pieces are making to the set number of 51 pieces which is called “Padi”. The Padi remains the same number whatever may be total volume of the prasadam in Sola measurement. That means, the Sola measurement might vary among full (25 Kg) half (12.5 Kgs) and quarter (6.4Kgs), and a Padi or fifty-one pieces of food offering can be made

from the different sola measurements. The Padi units used mainly for food offerings made with jiggery/sugar, and for prasadam that are salty.

• For liquid prasadam, one unit is 15 liters. This base measurement is never multiplied and remains the same for all occasions. This unit is used for all liquid forms of food offerings that may be cooked or uncooked.

Distinctions of Prasadam Based On Measurements

Maha Havis	Prasadam Made with the measurement of more than 8 Dronam
Best of Best(uttamo-uttamam)	Prasadam made with the measurement of 8 Dronam
Excellence	Prasadam made with 6 Dronam
Excellence in decreasing order by	5 Draonam , 1 Dronam,
Prasadam for Goddesses in Vishnu Temple	- Half measure of Aadhakam

The Rules to be followed about the kind of food that is not fit to be offered to God

- The sacred food should not be smell of smoke
- The Prasadam should never be burnt
- The food offering should not be overcooked
- The sacred food should not be cold
- Care should be taken so that no hair may fall in the food
- Caution should be taken to keep the food free from impurities and foreign objects , like insects

Classification of food prasadams offered to God on four broad categories

- Offerings make with Rice – Rice Prasadams
- Offerings made with jiggery or Sugar – Sweet Prasadams
- Offerings made with salt- Salty Prasadams
- Offerings that are uncooked – Apakwa Prasadams

Rice Prasadams

Rice prasadam are offerings to God prepared with rice as the main ingredient and these forms a majority of all the sacred food offerings. There are a range of preparations with rice that are offered as prasadam and the most important among them are:

The term used in temples for different kinds of Rice prasadam	Culinary terms
Pongal	Ghee Rice
Pulihora	Tamarind Rice
Dadhodhanam	Curd Rice
Kesari Bhaat	Saffron Rice
Sakkari Baath	Sweet Rice
Malahora	Black Pepper Rice
Kadambam	Kadambam
Bakala Baath	Spicy Curd Rice
Matra-Annam	Butter Rice

Sweet Prasadams

Food prepared with jiggery or sugar constitutes another important category of prasadam that are offered to God. These sweet food offerings can accompany other offerings or could be offered separately, and they can be made with rice or pulses. Sweet prasadam that are offered to God. These sweet food offerings can accompany other offerings or could be offered separately, and they can be made with rice or pulses. Sweet prasadam like laddu are very popular among devotees for several reasons. First, Laddus from Tirumala temple are famous across the world for their distinctive taste and are considered a blessing of the God. Second, laddus are made in a manner that there is minimum damage to their shape or quality despite time and the distance they may travel..As devotees of God are spread across the country and the globe, laddus are easily transported. Third, ‘the Tirupati laddu’ is unique because of its large size, representing the generous nature of the God’s blessings. This is another reason why the laddu is so widely sought after by the devotees and ordinary people. Fourth, the Temple makes the laddus available for all

devotees, unlike other prasadam, which are mostly consumed among the devotees present inside the Temple after each darshan or sacred viewing of the deity. There are many sweet food offerings made to God, of which the main ones are:

The term used in temples for different kinds of sweet prasadam	Culinary terms
Payasam	Milk Rice
Kesarai	Suji halwa
Laddu	Sphere-shaped sweet
Appam	Sweet Pancake
Jalebi	Coiled flour cake with sugar syrup
Manhoharam	Jaggery Laddu
Poli	Jaggery Pancake
Sukhiyam	Stuffed Laddu
Bellapu Dosa	Jaggery Dosa
Amruta Kalasam	Jar of Nectar

Salty Prasadam (Offerings Made With Salt)

Offerings of food prepared with salt are their category of prasadam offered to the God. Along with the foods made with rice or with jiggery or sugar, the prasadam made with salt complete the spectrum of the variety of foods that are made at the Temple every day for sacred offerings. Some of the salt-based preparations are famous dishes of South India relished across the world. At the Temple, each dish is made with ingredients specially grown or procured and carefully selected for the preparation of the particular food offering. Most of these food offerings are available to the devotees only during the time of darshan or sacred viewing. The main prasadam made with salt are

Different kinds of Salty prasadam	Culinary Terms
Vada	Blackgram Doughnut
Dosa	Rice Pancake

Ghee Dosa	Clarified Butter Pancake
Murukku	Crisp Flour Loops
Sundal	Salty Soaked Pulses
Vada Pappu	Green gram Coconut Mix

Apakwa Prasadams (Uncooked Food)

The uncooked food might be the simplest form of food offered to God and, therefore, the purest. The ingredients remixed together in careful proportions to provide the perfect taste and complete nutrition. There are no spices added to such food preparations and not even salt is introduced to change the taste of the natural ingredients. None of the foods are introduced to fire or heat and remain unaltered from their original form. There are mainly two kinds of uncooked food, liquid and solid.

Liquid Uncooked Food Offerings

Among the uncooked foods, Jaggery Water is a liquid prasadam, which is made in the measured unit of 15 liters.

Solid Uncooked Food Offerings

There are a number of uncooked foods that are offered to God at different times of the day and with different pujas performed before the deity in the Temple. Some of these are as follows, Cow's Milk ,Fresh Butter, Fresh fruits, Dry fruits, Betel Leaves with Betel Nuts ,Cashew Nuts,Badaam , Raisins ,Rock Candy,Cardomom,Cloves,Dry Coconut ,Nutmeg

Myths behind Prasadams of God (Lord Shiva)

Bhang

It is an ancient Indian drink which is believed to be the 'nectar of the Gods'. Bhang is often stigmatized because of its marijuana content. However, according to the ancient Hindu texts, Bhang is one of the most effective, natural medicines available to mankind. It has known to be the cure for many nervous disorders, skin diseases and wounds. According to the Vedas, when the ocean was churned by the Gods and the demons for acquiring the nectar, a drop of the nectar fell on Mount Madra. A plant sprouted out from the drop and the drink made from the leaves of the

plant became a favourite of all Gods, including Lord Shiva. After that Lord Shiva brought the cannabis down from the Himalayas for the pleasure of mankind.

Rice Annabishekam

During The seventh month in the calendar is the holy (Aadi) month. According to astrology Sun resides in the house / rasi Libra. The harvesting of paddy in Tamil Nadu would have got completed by this time. People are more interested in thanking Lord Siva with Annam (cooked fragrant rice). They believe that Lord Siva has only created annam (cooked rice) and He alone offer His grace and protect His subjects with annam (cooked rice).

Milk, Curd, Ghee, Honey

Abhishekam: Abhishekam is the process of bathing the deity. According to Siva Agamas (pooja rules) abhishekam is considered as one part of the shodashopachara pooja. Lord Siva will be pleased by the process of bathing with the prescribed eleven ingredients like water, milk, curd, ghee, honey etc. If you pour a drop of water on the 'Linga form' you will the blessings of Lord Siva. He will remove all your difficulties and will grace with happiness and joy.

Nector Amirtham

The Devas and Asuras got together to churn the ocean. They used Mandramalai to churn the ocean. Vaasuki, the snake agreed to form the rope for churning, in return for some amirtham. They started churning with Lord Vishnu and the Devas on one side (tail end) and the asuras on the other side (head end). But soon, the Mandramalai started sinking due to its great weight. Lord Vishnu took the form of a tortoise (Kurmam-tortoise) to form the base and to hold up the Mandramalai, preventing it from sinking. As they continued to churn the ocean, Vaasuki the snake began to tire and started spewing its poison. The Asuras who were on the head side of the snake, suffered the most and they ran away in fear. The Devas prayed to Lord Siva for help. Siva came and consumed all the poison. Goddess Parvati rushed and held his neck so that the poison would not spread to the whole of his body. Thus Siva became blue up to his throat and is also known by the namavali "Neelakandan" (neela-blue colour from poison, kandam-throat).

Mahaprasad

Mahaprasad in Oriya and the one at the Jagannath Temple in Puri consists of up to 56 different types of cooked and uncooked items.

It is first offered to Lord Jagannath, and later to Maa Vimala (Lord Jagannath's companion) before it is declared as Mahaprasad. The food is steamed in traditional earthenware. It is said that the food is tasteless while it is being offered to the Lord, but somehow all the flavours seep in when it is being served to the devotees. Each and every dish has a unique flavour, don't miss the Payas, Gajja (dry prasad), Kheera (rabri with paneer), Kanika (sweet rice) and Abhoda (rice- dal- sabzi).

Modaka-Kozhukattai

Laddu, Modaka, and Sanskrit. Here is an interesting tidbit about modaka. This goes beyond the history of laddu and instead dwells on mythology.

Lord Krishna's mother had made an offering of modaka (steamed rice flour dumpling stuffed with jaggery/sugar and coconut shavings) for a Ganesha idol. Wary of her son's thieving ways, she tied Krishna's hands. Lord Ganesha did not like this at all! Apparently, the idol came to life and lifted the sweet with his trunk and fed baby Krishna!

Beaten Rice Poho Rice

While studying at Sandipani ashram with Krishna, Sudama had and eaten his as well Krishna's share of the beaten rice given to him. This tied Sudama to reap the result and live in poverty till he has done full repentance to satiate the destiny associated with him. By this, Krishna tells the world that every person in this world is equal in front of him and is bound to Destiny carved out by man's own deeds.

MILK: As Lord Vishnu Lies On

Kshir sagar, an ocean of milk. So, nature prakriti, is visualised as ocean of milk. whatever you get from nature is like milk

Coconut

Hindu religious rituals have a lot symbolic import. Breaking of the coconut represents the breaking of ego, which is a prerequisite for the attainment of wisdom. Breaking of the ego results in your mind become as white as the broken coconut and the water within is the nectar of Divine Knowledge.

Coconut (Shripal)

Shri is lakshmi, phal is fruit , it is a fruit that you get around the year and one which is easily available , symbolize endless wealth and affluence

Bhog –Rice in Ramayana

In Ayodhya, there's a place known as Sita's kitchen. Sita was a very good cook. And Draupadi was famous for her generosity. Nobody went hungry from her kitchen. During their stay in the forest, after being exiled from the palace, the Pandavas don't have anything. Draupadi feels bad that she won't be able to feed whoever comes to her door. To tease her, Duryodhana sends Durvasa and some other rishis to her. They ask her for food. She requests them to go and bathe in the river, while she prepares a meal for them. Once they depart, she goes inside and starts weeping in despair. It is then that Krishna arrives. He says there must be something that she can offer the rishis. Dismayed, Draupadi shows him the empty vessels, saying that she'd fed her husband's and then eaten whatever little remained. Krishna picks up one leftover grain of rice and eats it. He is satiated and because of that, so are the rishis. They, in turn, feel they will end up disrespecting Draupadi if they don't eat anything she offers, so they make a hasty exit. This is how Krishna protects Draupadi's dignity. However, Krishna tells Draupadi to pray to Surya, the sun god, for a solution to her problem. Draupadi does so and Surya gives her a thali, plate. There's a phrase "Draupadi ki thali", which is similar to the concept of "mataji ka bhandar", implying that there will always be food in the kitchen. Each day, Draupadi's thali stayed full until she ate. She would feed hundreds of people and be the last to eat. But once she had eaten, there would be no more food till the next day.

Milk and Curd

At the age 25-year-old Tenali Rama who is an ultimate procrastinator and too lazy to pursue his dreams, but at the same time he also wants to become rich and famous. An honored saint asks him to go to the village temple and recite a powerful mantra. Tenali does the same and manages to impress Goddess Kali played by Barkha Bisht. Goddess Kali appears in front of him with a bowl of milk and a bowl of curd. She asks him to pick one but Tenali ends up gulping both which leaves Kali fuming. The very astute Tenali reasons by explaining that there is no use of one without the other. She gets impressed by his wit and blesses him saying that he will become a Vaikatavi, a jesting poet in Krishnadevaraya's court.

Conclusion

As with most Hindu God worshipping, the prasadam and its fascinating principles along with some its myths are presented in a somewhat condensed form. Such limited discussions are focused how Prasadam of Hindu gods facilitate a personal dialogue with God that takes place within as food offerings during worshipping. This paper seeks to connect the two and bridge the gap between thought and action, the eternal question and interim answer.

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Guru Ka Langar as Parsad Embracing "Sarve Dharm Sambhaw"

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Abstract:

The Food which is offered to Hindu deity is known as Parsad. This food after offering to deity is distributed among devotees as offering of God. There are few rules in India for preparing the food as Parsad. The whole research paper revolves around the idea behind the langar, as per the Sikh faith, is for people of all castes and religions to eat together before visiting the Guru¹ every human being is equal. 'The concept of equality is visible everywhere, from the place where people stay around the Gurudwara complex to the 'langar' (a concept of free dining for every one). Skin color fades in front of goodness, and religion does not matter in the sea of humanity here². In the Gurudwara it is carrying out the sewa for the overall welfare of people -- irrespective of religion, caste, colour, gender or creed. Not only we citizens of India believe this system of serving people but also Canadian president³ Trudeau and his family members first went to the "Langar Hall", where thousands of devotees partake langar (community food) and also do "sewa" (voluntary service). The Golden Temple's Langar Hall is the biggest community kitchen in the world. Langar is the main meal which is served all afternoon to every visitor, irrespective of their social standing or religious affiliation. In the earlier time Guru Nanak Dev Ji wanted to stress the idea that everyone is equal. Everyone shares the tasks of preparation, cooking, serving and cleaning. He said that⁴ this community kitchen is meant for providing food to all devotees, pilgrims and visitors. It is a symbol of equality, fraternity and brotherhood. It is here that the high and the low, the rich and the poor, the learned and the illiterate, the kings and the paupers, all share the same food sitting together in one row⁵.

Key words: Langar, community food, sangat, pangat, community kitchen, parsad.

Introduction

In the Sikhism culture the Langar or Communal Kitchen was firstly started by the first Sikh Guru, Guru Nanak Dev Ji in the year 1481. Guru ka Langar is a community kitchen which runs in the name of God, it is usually a small room which is attached to the Gurudwara. The word 'Langar' in Sanskrit term means 'anagarh' i.e. 'cooking room' and in the Persian term it means 'an almshouse' i.e. 'an asylum for the poor'. He introduced this institution in which all people would sit together and they will share food as a symbol of equality removing all the barriers of caste, creed, religion, gender, age or social status i.e. all the people rich or poor, high or low, female or male will sit in the same row to eat which has given a term of 'Pangat'. The feeling behind serving people from all religions, caste was true 'Sewa' to humanity. This institution served people in so many ways that in Langar all men, women and children's participate in the activities of preparation of meal, serving meal to the people sitting in 'sangat' (a term which means company or association). The institution teaches people the etiquettes of sitting together, eating together with the people belonging to different communities and creating different communities situation. In the langar people freely volunteers (sewadars) to serve other people weekly as there are so many people who need to be fed and to serve them is a very generous thing to do as the caterers are not allowed. Langars can be organised daily or weekly or on special occasions like any festivals Guru Nanak Jayanti, Vaisakhi etc.

Research Objectives:

The main aim of the present study is to present the cultural thoughts of Sri Guru Nanak Dev Ji and to see the relevance of these concepts in the present time.

- To study the working of 'langar system' or the 'communal kitchen' i.e. how these langar systems are helping people to preserve the culture of Sikhism that was started earlier by the Guru Ji.
- To analyse that whether this system was designed to maintain the equality between different religions, cultures, caste, creed and so on.
- It is to look after that the food served in the langar system is hygienic, vegetarian and of good quality.

To study that if there is any differences in the above mentioned points based on' Sarve Dharm Sambhaw'.

Literature reviews:

- On normal days, over 50,000 people partake langar served selflessly at the complex to people from various religions, cultures, castes, countries and gender⁷.
- It is designed to uphold the principle of equality between all people of the world regardless of religion, caste, colour, creed, age, gender or social status. In addition to the ideals of equality, the tradition of Langar expresses the ethics of sharing, community, inclusiveness and oneness of all humankind. “The Light of God is in all hearts.”Guruji designed an institution in which all people would sit on the floor together, as equals, to eat the same simple food. It is here that all people high or low, rich or poor, male or female, all sit in the same pangat (literally "row" or "line") to share and enjoy the food together.
"This is the true 'Sewa' to humanity" Sher M, Illinois, USA⁸
- Community service: At the Guru Ka Langar in Golden Temple Amritsar free meals are provided to visitors belonging to all religions⁹.
- Sikhism offers a simple straight path to eternal bliss and spreads a message of love and universal brotherhood¹⁰.
- Langar (community Kitchen): Close to the principles of social work based on worth of an individual, acceptance and equality is the philosophy behind the Langar (Guru's kitchen-cum-eating-house).
- Langar is the common kitchen room in the Gurudwara where everyone irrespective of their caste, class, creed, religion and sex sit together and eat from the common kitchen. It is not for the person only.
- Sikh community organizes inter-faith langar at mosque : On October 8, volunteers of Sikh Press Association and Basics of Sikhi organized a langar at the historic Jama Masjid in Amritsar. Close to 400 people including madrassa students, Sikhs, Christians, and labourers of various faiths were served food that was prepared in the community kitchen on the rooftop of the mosque¹¹.

- In an attempt to spread the message of love and peace, an interfaith langar (community kitchen) was organized at Jama Masjid in Ludhiana. To set an example of solidarity over the recent incidents, Muslims, Sikhs, Christians and Hindus came together to serve and eat under one roof¹².

Significance:

The main aim of Guru Nanak Ji behind starting this 'community kitchen' was to remove the barriers of Hindu caste system where the people belongs to different caste does not sit together or eat together. He said that all people are human beings they share the same light, same air, same soil then why to have discrimination amongst them. The basic concept of 'equality' can be seen everywhere in the Gurudwara complex from serving meal to people to eating meal with people. It has some other objectives:

- To offer free meal to the people from all over the country or world.
- To offer 'Sewa' for the overall welfare of the people irrespective of caste, creed, religion, colour, gender or social status.
- To provide a society which is free from old rituals, traditions and customs?
- To integrate the society as a whole.
- To offer food which is voluntarily prepared by the people of any religion i.e. one not need to be a Sikh.
- To offer pure vegetarian and simple food so that no religion or caste system feels offended.
- To make people learn the etiquettes of sitting together and eating together.
- Canadian elements of this food-centered marker of Sikh religious life, including internal community building and outreach activities¹³.

Straight facts & figures

- The Foundation of the Golden Temple was laid down by a Muslim saint Mian Mir (The contributor of the entry¹⁴ E. Nicholls, (Secretary, Municipal Committee, Amritsar)
- Its 'four door' symbolizes openness of the Sikhs towards all religion of people.
- Around 35% of the pilgrims who visit Golden Temple are non – Sikhs.

- In the UK, homeless people are getting free meals, all thanks to the centuries-old Sikh tradition.
- In Canada, the Seva Food Bank serves food to low-income families.
- Langar Aid, an extension of Khalsa Aid, set up a community kitchen in the ISIS territory to feeds Yazids.

Voluntary & selfless service:

The service in the 'langar system' is performed by people voluntarily without the intention of getting any rewards, recognition or personal benefit. This service is also known as 'sewa; which means 'selfless service'. In the Punjabi language the person performing such service is called a 'sevadar'. When people engaged in the communal service it enhances the relationships of communities and also works for moral upliftment of the society. People are encouraged from all over the world to perform this selfless service which are cleaning dishes, cooking food, serving food, cleaning floors and so on for many people this activity forms an essential part of their life, providing spiritual fulfillment and practical benefits. People do this voluntary service to other people without seeking their religion, caste, gender or social status¹⁵.

Steps that converts an ordinary food ‘as Parsad’:

In the ‘Community kitchen’ every volunteer has to follow a process when preparing the food or serving the food in langar which converts an ordinary food as Parsad i.e. what are the essentials in the community kitchen which make a simple and vegetarian food so important for people that it carries huge crowd from all over the world removing all the barriers of religion, caste etc

1. Take bath and enter the kitchen with clean clothes and freshly washed hands.

2. During preparation and serving ‘parsad’ the mind should be occupied with good thoughts, holy scriptures, with the name of god not with gossip.

3. Avoid creating unnecessary rush in the kitchen.

4. Do not taste salt, sugar or anything while cooking the Parsad.

5. No portion of parsad is taken out for any other purpose before offering it to the guru.

Discussion & Interpretation:

After going through this research paper, we have gone through different articles, blogs, references of different links and it is discussed that the major hub for Sikh religion serving ‘langar’ is Golden Temple in Amritsar where around 100,000 people have Parsad as a communal meal everyday 24/7 throughout the year. While discussing about the Sikh religion we have founded that there are several ‘langars’ are going on throughout the world with only one purpose that is the ‘selfless service’ or voluntary service. In the earlier tradition just like Sikhs in the Hindu religion also there is also a system of serving people called as ‘bhandara’ in which people from different religion eats together. Every persons follow the same instructions in the Gurudwara complex like when one person whether a female or male enters into the gurudwara they have to cover their heads with scarves or handkerchief whichever suits to a person of any religion. While interpreting it is discussed that people from all over the world come to serve ‘langar’ in different parts of the world and carries only one feeling with them that is to serve to do ‘sewa’. When doing different activities in the Gurudwara complex like preparing meal, serving meal they believe that ‘God is the creator of all beings’. Every person rich or poor, low caste or high caste devotes their share of time and money for feeding people as there soul is sanctified i.e. if a person having low income share their time in serving people or else a person having no time but money donates their money for purchasing pulses, rice, milk, ghee etc. In the research paper we have discussed that Sikh religion follows the principles of ‘Sarve Dharm Sambhaw’ i.e. to serve people they buy food from every

religion or caste without discriminating them from others. Examples can be they buy vegetables from farmer buy pulses from Jain person, buy milk from muslim person without actually knowing their religion or caste.

Conclusion

From the above points that we have discussed in this research paper it is to be concluded that after analyzing this topic of ‘sarve dharm sambhaw’ in Sikh religion it is proven with different points which the researcher has founded .Sikh religion is one of those religion which has assures the acceptance worldwide, this Sikh religion is organising langars in 46 places in 11 countries along with India with the help of all the devotees of Guru Nanak Ji around the world which means that people from all over the world are sanctioned with the pure feeling of serving people from different parts of the world without discriminating them on the basis of religion,caste,creed,gender or social status.’Langar is organising for people on an inter-faith basis muslims,christians,hindu all participates actively in the activities of this system.

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Ethno-medicinal and Foods Folklore of *Jaunsari* Tribe and its impact on Tourism Promotion

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Abstract

The present work has been carried out on the ethno-medicinal and nutritional folk-lore of Jaunsari tribe inhabitants in the Uttarakhand state of India particularly in the district of Dehradun and explorations of possibilities of Tourism Promotion. Lots of Food substances have been related with religion, recuperating, love, mortality, status and excellence. Look through any old writing; we have enlightening records of different foods and their "otherworldly" powers on the brain, soul, and body known to foods folklore. The folk-medicine and wellness foods particularly as ethnomedicinal plants used by *Jaunsari* tribe in *Jaunsar-Bhawar* region have great medicinal plant-lore. There are more than 150 plant species used as medicine for the treatment of various diseases and disorders by the tribal community. The scientific name of the plants along with their vernacular names, medicinal uses, parts used, by the tribal people in the study area, is presented. The *Jaunsari* tribal people use a total of 169 plant species belonging to 72 families for curing different ailments. Various food folklores were observed among Jaunsari tribes. There are insufficient research data on evaluation and validation of folk medicinal wisdom and wellness foods folklore of various tribe groups. Jaunsar-Bhawar area is as yet not perceived and preferred as one of the vital Cultural tourist destination. By legitimate planning, usage and by the shared co-task Jaunsar-Bhawar can develop as one of important Cultural tourist destinations in future and can have the accompanying future favorable circumstances and will be helpful in economic steadiness to neighborhood individuals.

Keywords: Ethno-Medicine, Foods Folklore, *Jaunsari* Tribe, Cultural Tourism

Introduction

Various Food substances have been related with religion, recuperating, love, mortality, status and excellence. Look through any old writing; we have enlightening records of different foods and their "otherworldly" powers on the brain, soul, and body known to foods folklore. Accordingly, it is nothing unexpected that a considerable lot of these myths and legends assume an imperative part in our own nourishment decisions, today. A significant number of these claims go back to similarly as 2000 B.C. Regardless of whether there is any precision to these references, nobody can truly say. While a ton of these records can't be demonstrated, one thing is sure: these folk foods are of incredible dietary significance. Jaunsaris offered food to eat which could only satisfy their spirit but not their hunger.

The local Jaunsari have private information of eatable and noxious mushrooms; other than this they utilize a few mushrooms therapeutic purposes or for some religious ceremonies [1].

Conventional foods are an imperative segment of a country's legacy and accordingly are a piece of the setting of folklores. Folklores may record any part of a country's past legacy including customary sustenance. Foods are a fundamental piece of our lives from birth to death. At one outrageous it is vital for our reality and at the other an extravagance to be delighted in on uncommon events. It has been an ever display subject through the old stories of any country and ought to be a basic piece of folklore contemplates. Aside from extraordinary occasions, foods have a part in regular day to day existence, showing a man's status, individual inclinations and desires. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated that perhaps 80% of the world's population relies on herbs for its primary healthcare and nutritional needs. There are some traditional medical practices [2], viz. *Ayurveda* and *Siddha* in India, Chinese medicine in China, *Unani* medicine in Islamic countries, etc. where herbal medicine is widely used for therapeutics. It is also observed that more than 35,000 plant species are being used around the world for medicinal purposes in ethno-medicinal, nutritional [3] and ethno-botanical practices [4, 5].

Jaunsaris are renowned for their vivid garments, celebrations and nourishments fables. Critical parts of their way of life are the celebrations, sanctuaries, society moves and tunes. A portion of the imperative social attractions for tourists in the Jaunsar-Bhawar are;

The celebrations like Megh Mela, Bissu Mela, Lakhawar Mela and presentations of various cultures and local food-lore.

Lakhamandal, Hanoi sanctuary worked in the Huna architectural style, *Ashoka* edict.

The folk dances and songs, ethno-medicine associated with the festivals like Baradi Nati, Harul, Mandawana.

These social attractions are very common among the tribes dwelling in the Jaunsar-Bhawar region. Subsequently these social attractions can possibly be advanced for the visitors who are dependably in the chase of investigating new culture and in this way helping Jaunsar-Bhawar to rise as an essential folk tourist destination.

This paper is an outcome of extensive study among the *Jaunsari* tribes and is an attempt to enlist various plant-lore and their folk claims.

Material and methods

The present work has been carried out on the ethno-medicinal and nutritional folk-lore of Jaunsari tribe inhabitants in the Uttarakhand state of India particularly in the district of Dehradun and explorations of possibilities of Tourism Promotion. The region is under the *Shivalik* and *Himalayan* mountainous chain. Medicinal plants and data of their folk claims was recorded involving interviews, semi-structured meetings, group discussions and reviews of various research literatures published.

The data presented in the present communication delineated with botanical name, family, local name, uses etc. The research work towards enumeration of plants is based on earlier published data along with documentations and communications under present studies.

Results and discussion

The folk-medicine and wellness foods particularly as ethnomedicinal plants used by *Jaunsari* tribe in *Jaunsar-Bhawar* region have great medicinal plant-lore. There are more than 150 plant species used as medicine for the treatment of various diseases and disorders by the tribal community [Table 1]. The scientific name of the plants along with their vernacular names, medicinal uses, parts used, by the tribal people in the study area, is presented. The *Jaunsari* tribal people use a total of 169 plant species [6] belonging to 72 families for curing different ailments.

In the Jaunsar-Bhawar forests various ethno-medicinal plants enhances the importance, notwithstanding the types of trees which are of financial and mechanical significance and valuable for development fill in and in addition a wellspring of income. Other than providing fuel, feed, bamboos and therapeutic herbs, they likewise yield an assortment of items like nectar, lac, gum,

exudates, catechu, wax and horns. Forest resource utilization statistics [7] of the region is presented in **Table- 2 and Figure- 2.**

Table: 2. Forest Resource Utilization pattern (%) in Jaunsar-Bhawar

S. No.	Particulars	Utilization %
1	Food Plants	32.12%
2	Fodder	12.73%
3	Medicinal Plants	42.42%
4	Fibre	1.21%
5	Fuel	6.06%
6	Others	5.45%

There are a large number of scientific studies are being carried out by various scholars on folk-lore and ethno-medicinal status of various communities including *Jaunsari* tribes [9-11].

Food Folklore: Various food folklores were observed among Jaunsari tribe like;

1. Arabi leaves moves arranged to steam-prepare as a healthy green vegetable,
2. Muda bukaono - produced using wheat grains by delicate simmering on tawa and valuable as healthy snacks starter,
3. Chuloda - a cake produced using mash of Chuloo Fruit of apricot family. This makes an exceptionally classy Chutney including suitable masala,
4. Doroti made of Masur dal, a decision delectable Sweet or Sour flavor,

5. Khendadi cooked in high temp water and presented with ghee making a little well at the inside,
6. Pinunwe - another steam prepared dished taken with ghee,
7. Uluwe - a steam prepared dish eaten with Ghee,

Jaunsari tribes have their own way of life as far as food folklore, society cures, moves, tunes, celebrations, sanctuaries and landmarks which are very famous among themselves, however for whatever is left of the world these social wisdoms are obscure and that is the reason these can possibly be advanced for the travelers who are dependably in the chase of investigating new societies.

Cultural Tourism has an exceptional place in Jaunsar-Bhawar in view of its past human progress. Those social attractions should be misused so the household and also outside vacationers could have a chance to taste the folk foods and experience the mending practices of folk healers.

Conclusion

There are insufficient research data on evaluation and validation of folk medicinal wisdom and wellness foods folklore of various tribe groups. Jaunsar-Bhawar area is as yet not perceived and preferred as one of the vital Cultural tourist destination .The celebrations of Jaunsar-Bhawar locale like Magh Mela, Bissau and so on society moves and folk healing, folk foods and so on are not famous among the household and additionally international tourists and these are not advanced by the Uttarakhand Tourism Department. Cultural Tourism today is on the blast as more tourists are occupied with understanding the way of life of various regions and teaching them. Thus by legitimate planning , usage and by the shared co-task Jaunsar-Bhawar can develop as one of important Cultural tourist destinations in future and can have the accompanying future favorable circumstances and will be helpful in economic steadiness to neighborhood individuals.

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Role of communication and soft skills to enhance tourism through customer satisfaction: an empirical study on employees in selected hotels of mussoorie, Uttarakhand

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Abstract

Travel and Tourism is a dynamic engine of economic development and job creation throughout the world with some countries dependent on tourism as a catalyst for growth and development. In 2017, it directly contributed US\$2.6 trillion and nearly 119 million jobs worldwide. The sector contributed US\$8.3 trillion to the global economy and supported 313 million jobs in 2017. This was equal to 10.4% of the world's GDP, and approximately 1 in 10 of all jobs. India ranks 7th position in the list of world's largest tourism economy in terms of GDP. (World Travel & Tourism, 2018).

The paper traces as the prime objective, the role and importance of communication in hospitality industry employees which helps them to fill-up those communication gaps which may hamper the service delivery and guest satisfaction leading to lesser guest retention. Data was collected from selected hotels of Mussoorie, Uttarakhand through questionnaire over eight week period through 108 respondents between January and February 2018. The sample was made up of the star category hotels' employees hailing from different levels of management. This research was mainly undertaken to investigate on the significance of communication skills including soft skills. The findings suggested the emphasis should be given on the usage of a blend of traditional and contemporary tools both to enable the employees to be more communicative and hence result oriented.

Key words - Hospitality industry, skill-sets, communication skills, levels of management, soft skills, result oriented.

Introduction

Hospitality industry has always been considered of paramount importance to national economic growth. Uttarakhand is no exception. To boost the state's attractions for tourists, the government has been endeavouring to attract more tourists. Hotels and restaurants sector faces a number of employment and labour related challenges such as high skills shortages, staff turnover, lack of training, and a growing demand for flexibility and multi-skilling. Also, global trends such as the increased cross-cultural tourism, awareness of healthy lifestyle, individualisation in customer demands, environmental concerns, globalization of travel and tourism products and services and digitalization of information and communication systems will challenge the Hotels and restaurants sector, making the discussion of skills needs and emerging competencies even more relevant than ever.

In view of the expected increasing demand of capacity to accommodate the growing number of tourists, there emerges a need for qualified hotel employees with required proficiency to handle guests and provide best accommodation experience. As the demand for hospitality personnel trained to deliver high-quality guest service continues to grow, such proficiency cannot be promoted without first analyzing carefully what are the needs for workplace. Further and unavoidably linked questions are whether or not these perceived needs mesh with actual performance and whether or not there are gaps between performance and needs. (Wenyuh Shieh, 2012) [1]

The hospitality industry is one of the oldest branches of tourism, yet despite its modernization and technical development, its main resource remains the multi-skilled human resource, and which may lead to high employee turnover which remains one of the industry's major problems, reason being skill-gaps. (Shosh Shahrabani et al, 2015) [2]

Employees must be culturally intelligent to understand the basic variations in work ethics, behaviours, communication styles, and the way of managing interpersonal relationships. Employees in high-context nations including Japan, South Korea, and China tend to rely on non-verbal gestures. Conversely, people from low-context countries including Germany and Great Britain prefer to communicate directly. Shazeb Ali (2017)[3]

Customers' personal care and assistance is an important criterion for the customers. The marketer is supposed to have good and neat behaviour and attitude towards its customers. An employee

must understand the problems and needs of the customers who use their products and services and use that information to create a competitive advantage. Ritwik Anand et al (2017). [4]

Effective communication and soft skills are required for success in the workplace—such as how to interact with customers, how to work in teams, how to act professionally, and even how to properly represent themselves in job interviews in the first place. Soft skills may enhance employment prospects by providing better skills and confidence making the employees more productive. Matthew Groh et al (2016). [5]

Research problem

Communication and soft skills are critical in today's service industry and they can cause a differentiation between excellence and mediocrity. Those communication gaps may hamper the service delivery. Organisations consider these competencies as important criteria during staff recruitment and also started linking soft skills into their employee appraisals and reward packages. Thus, to fill the skill-gaps is the major point of concern for the employers as well for the employees and aspirants of the hospitality industry also.

Objective of the study

1. To identify communications and soft skill sets important in hospitality organizations.
2. To analyse relationship between communications and soft skill and employees' performance.
3. To identify factors behind the development of soft skills.
4. To analyse soft skills as a criterion for employees' selection.
5. To suggest intervention strategies for improving the 'soft skill' in hospitality organisations
6. Development of hypotheses
7. On the basis of the above-mentioned objectives, the hypothesis is as follows:
8. H.0:1. There is no significant relationship between soft skills and employees' performance.
9. H.0:1. There is significant relationship between soft skills and employees' performance.
10. H.0:2. There is no significant relationship between soft skills and employees' selection.
11. H.0:2. There is significant relationship between soft skills and employees' selection.

Study area

According to the statistics of the Ministry of Tourism, Government of India, in 2015, Uttarakhand state witnessed a footfall of 225 lakh domestic tourists and 1.1 lakh foreign tourists. Uttarakhand's hotel and tourism industry, having a turnover of nearly Rs 1,398 crore, contributes 1.5% to the nation's economy, said the report that also mentions that there is a huge potential waiting to be exploited. (Indian Tourism Statistics, Ministry of Tourism, 2016). In view of this tourism has placed a higher demand for the quality hotels in the state as more affluent travellers travel to the tourist places of this area. The present study is based upon Mussoorie which attracts significant percentage of recreationist for summer vacations and for fun and visiting scenic attractions.

Mussoorie as a place enjoys tourist visits for leisure and recreational purposes and saturated with the number of hotel properties including the hotel units of internationally recognized branded hotel chains. Mussoorie hosts mainly vacation hotels that are influenced by the seasonality of tourism. The main areas of study will be the star categorised hotels of Mussoorie recognized by the FHRAI (Federation of Hotels and Restaurants Association of India) and HRACC (Hotels and Restaurants Approval Classification committee) governed by the Department of Tourism, India. The population of the study is composed of 108 employees (both male and female) hailing from different levels of management from various hospitality organizations of the city. A structured questionnaire as a survey instrument is developed to measure the responses. In order to obtain detailed information, semi-structured interviews are carried out. In the questionnaire, the first section of the questionnaire includes questions on demographics (age, gender, education, current position and work experience). The second section includes the communication and soft skills required and rated by the respondents on the Likert scale of 5.

Research methodology

To achieve the above mentioned objectives, the research is exploratory and descriptive in nature. It is aimed to find out the required communication and soft skills competencies in effective and efficient service delivery.

Basis of sample selection

Population: The population consisted of a blend of employees hailing from the top, middle and lower level of management. The ratio of the respondents is directly dependent on the factors like

type of hierarchy or organization structure of the organization and the number of employees working at different levels of management.

Sample design

1. **Sample frame:** Employees of the top, middle and lower level of management of various government approved and above 3 star categorization chain hotels of Mussoorie.
2. **Sample size:** Sample size consists of 108 respondents from more than 06 chain hotels (government approved and above 3 star categorization) from Mussoorie for the proposed study.
3. **Sample technique:** Sample of employees from different departments of various hotels working under different levels of management will be selected on the basis of convenient sampling.

Ethical considerations

It implies issues of harm, consent, deception, privacy and the confidentiality of data that will be recognized. Academic objective of the study is communicated to the respondents. Individual names, address, hotel's name are not be used in the study.

Types of instruments and methods used for research

1. Data collection through Questionnaires with employees hailing from different levels of management.
2. Respondents Core and functional competencies regarding communication and soft skills are recorded in questionnaire.

Data Analysis Tools

1. Development of Hypothesis
2. For analysis of data, descriptive statistics is used.

Literature review

- Gary Lynn (2017) has centred on 'four communication pillars' of emotional intelligence; viz. Listening, Questioning, Empathy and Rapport to effectively equip with the intrapersonal and interpersonal abilities required. Many similarities can be seen to exist between these socially constructed models from the capacity to listen and co-operate; to conflict resolution, self-control, and awareness. [6]

- Dr. Abdurezak Mohammed et al (2017) aimed at awaken each and every individual's leadership potential and develop the necessary skills like competence and confidence to perform job roles effectively. Trainings provide soft skills for effectively leading the team and empower leaders to maintain good relations with the team members; as well as customers and clients. [7]
- David Rivera Jr et al (2016) referred communication and soft skills as the attributes exhibited by an individual that display his/her ability to interact with others. Two types of soft skills that are often discussed within the hospitality industry are diversity awareness and emotional intelligence. Studies have suggested that individuals who display higher levels of positive soft skills or personality traits have an increased chance for successful career development. Two specific areas of professional development that have been mentioned as important soft skills to display and develop in order to advance one's career include diversity consciousness/cultural intelligence and emotional intelligence. [8]
- Razak Roshita Abdul et al, (2016) stated that the most essential competencies for hospitality graduates are associated with soft skills namely the communication skills whether oral communication or professional writing skills. Professional grooming and appearance of graduates are also crucial as hospitality industry deals with customers; therefore good appearance will provide good impression for the hotel's guest. [9]
- Simon Caruanaa et al (2015) listed good interpersonal and communication skills, problem solving, self-management, knowledge of the business, ability to use own initiative but also to follow instruction, team working, leadership, decision making, communication, creativity and others as being essential for entrepreneurial success and maximising human capital in organisations. Such skills shortages jeopardise economic recovery, growth and competitiveness. [10]
- Sarkodie Noble Amoako et al, (2015) pin point communication skills, multi lingual, operational skills and skills in computing as the most prominent skills. Professional appearance and poise, communication skills in both writing and orally, positive customer relations, managing guests' problem with understanding and

sensitivity are also important. In addition to these skills, moral skills, customer relationship, leadership skills, personal skills, and problem solving skills need attention in hospitality and tourism industry. [11]

- Gurel Cetina et al (2014) advocated that the employees should be selected on their attitudes and personality rather than solely on their industry experience and technical skills. Creativity and interpersonal communication skills are also crucial in creating experiences. Employees should be empowered and independent after making sure they are trained to make decisions needed to create desired experiences. They should also be given authority to decide on corrective action. [12]
- K Rajesh Kumar et al, (2014) emphasized upon interpersonal and soft skills like ability to listen to the guests, problem solving and conflict resolution, negotiation, effective communication, well behaving and team membership skills. He also pin point personal qualities like dealing and selling with guests, adapting to the situation, honesty, commitment and integrity towards the roles and responsibilities. [13]
- V Jaykumar, (2014) quoted that the hotel managers believed that personality is the most important factor to possess as an employee in the hotel industry. They think that if the personality is suitable for hotel work and with good positive attitudes to work well, hotel industry knowledge and experience, the hotel industry will be a suitable work place for them. Also, communication skills along with Commitment, willingness to learn, pointed to be the important skills for employees' career development. [14]
- Rok Marija, (2013) emphasized the importance of practical utilization and demonstration of the knowledge gained; with skills of tangible and immediate value and the potential to perform difficult tasks in future (possess soft skills). Positive attitude, the ability to work with others in a team, the ability to organize oneself, openness to change, reliability, goal orientedness, problem solving, work commitment, verbal communication skills, etc. [15]

- J Krishnaveni, (2013) mentioned relationship management, communication, task proficiency and leadership and adaptability of the employees of great importance. The leadership skills of the employees the organisation are developed by encouraging them to participate in personality development programmes and simulation training conducted within and outside the organisation. [16]
- Shruti Ahuja, (2012) affirmed that managers seek to hire someone who can be an effective time leader or who has demonstrated great active listening skills. Alternately, they may need someone who enjoys taking initiative or someone who is very good at taking direction. Team structure, leadership, decision-making, key attributes (knowledge, skills, and behavior attributes) that are required to perform effectively in a job classification. [17]
- Kamau Sarah W et al, (2012) asserted that the hospitality industry expects the employees to be competent in communication skills, specific technical skills, conflict resolution, computer skills, good work habits, information technology, customer service, sales and marketing, good interpersonal skills, multi-skilled, self-initiative, self-discipline, self-motivation and understanding the level of service. [18]
- Prachanant Nawamin, (2012) stated that English, which is associated with host-guest interaction in the service business, should be termed as the “language of hospitality” which refers to all linguistic expressions related to and represented in hospitality concerns. This increases the importance of communication skills as an essential competency. The language of hospitality is often formal, though it very much depends on the level of acquaintance among the participants themselves. [19]
- Daniela Wilks et al (2011) focuses on the crucial importance of soft skills in the hospitality industry. Good manners, civility, and proper speech, in addition to technical and conceptual skills and hospitality sector along with personal qualities and soft competencies, whereas vocational/technical competencies are viewed as comparatively less important. People learn from one another through observation and imitation (modeling), reproducing given behaviours. Close contact, imitation of seniors, understanding the concepts and role model behavior. [20]

- Lan Sun, (2011) stated that the competencies represent the personality, ability, knowledge and the skills factors. Hotel emphasize on personalized services by providing sufficient resources, the hotel's management ensures that the staffs are not overstrained so that the high level of customer care expected from them is not compromised. Staffs are motivated and encouraged to interact with guests in order to get to know each guest's preferences and needs, so as to deliver personalized services. [21]
- Cathy A. Enz, (2011) said that it is extremely difficult to sustain a competitive advantage, hotels work to create advantages through the development of resources and capabilities i.e. both tangible resources (such as the physical property or financial assets) and intangible resources (such as brand or organizational culture, and human, innovation, and reputation resources). Offering training programs helps employees by creating an environment that is favourable to both learning and change and then rewarding employees for their productivity improvements. [22]
- Jennifer Kim Lian Chan (2010) referred soft skills to "those attributes that enable effective teamwork, communication, presentation, leaderships, customer services and innovative problem solving. They are not jobspecific but are valued across a variety of jobs, fields and organisations regardless of position or title. [23]
- Misty Johanson et al, (2010) emphasized upon communication skills, the ability to speak on one's feet to customers, employees, managers, suppliers, and partnering agencies is a skill needed and used on a daily basis. Furthermore, being able to communicate ideas to lead, instruct, motivate, train, and coordinate often involves writing skills. Guest satisfaction and conflict resolution by resolving customer problems, manage guest problems with understanding and sensitivity, and solve customer problems. [24]
- Blayney Candace, (2009) addressed that highly rated competency are soft skills, interpersonal relationship with and among employees, adapting to changing circumstances, enhancing socialization marketing analysis techniques and identifying and defining problems of operations, and maintaining consistent service quality and developing innovative ways of work. [25]

- Kong Hai-yan et al (2006) emphasized that communication within the operating business, plays the role of the “brain” in the hotel. Language, communications, emotional and wider generic skills are necessary for effective work in the contemporary hospitality industry. [26]

Data analysis

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Demographic Characteristics		No of Respondents	%
Age	21-30 years	49	45.37
	31-40 years	31	28.70
	41-50 years	19	17.59
	51 and above	09	8.33
Gender	Male	80	74.07
	Female	28	25.92
Education	Graduate	22	20.37
	Graduate (HM)	41	37.96
	Post graduate	16	14.81
	Diploma	22	20.37
	Others	07	6.48
Experience	< 5 years	46	42.59
	5-10 years	28	25.92
	10-15 years	22	20.37
	15-20 years	07	6.48
	>20 years	05	4.62

Total Number of Respondents	108	100%
Number of Hotels	06	

Table 1, shows the demographical characteristics of respondents. 49 (45.37%) of respondents were from age group of 21-30 years and 31(28.70%) were from age group of 31-40 years while, 19 (17.59%) were from 41–50 years. 09 (8.33%) were from age group of 51–60 years. This shows that there is a balance of young and aged workforce in the hotel industry from Mussoorie. The percentage of the male as respondents is 74.07% while rest of 25.92% constitutes by the females. The highest number of the respondents 41 (37.96%) indicated they had a professional degree in hotel management; 22(20.37%) had a diploma in hotel management. Only 22 (20.37%) of all respondents had graduation degree. 28 (25.92%) respondents had working experience in the hospitality field for 5-10 years; 22 (20.37%) respondents had 10-15 years working experience in this field. There is a considerable number of respondents 46 (46.66%) working experience less than five years, which depicts the trend of freshers in the hospitality industry. The table also indicates there is a balance between samples which are relatively fresher and experienced in hospitality operations in Mussoorie. Respondent are selected from various departments of the hotels i.e. front office, housekeeping, food and beverage production, food and beverage service, human resource etc.

Data analysis and interpretation

Table No.1- English proficiency and Multi lingual skills

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	7	6.48
Disagree	8	7.40
Neutral	29	26.85
Agree	39	36.11
Strongly Agree	25	23.14
Total	108	100.00

Table No.2- Non-verbal communication

Response	Frequency	Percentage
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Strongly disagree	5	4.62
Disagree	6	5.55
Neutral	29	26.85
Agree	46	42.59
Strongly Agree	22	20.37
Total	108	100.00

Table No.3- Interpersonal communication and people skills

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	7	6.481
Disagree	7	6.481
Neutral	30	27.77
Agree	37	34.25
Strongly Agree	27	25
Total	108	100.00

Table No.4- Emotional and Cultural intelligence

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	2	1.85
Disagree	10	9.25
Neutral	26	24.07
Agree	45	41.66
Strongly Agree	25	23.14
Total	108	100.00

Table No.5- Leadership and initiative skills

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	5	4.62
Disagree	9	8.33
Neutral	27	25
Agree	38	35.18
Strongly Agree	29	26.85
Total	108	100.00

Table No.6- Grooming and Physical Appearance

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	3	2.77
Neutral	11	10.18
Agree	41	37.96
Strongly Agree	53	49.07
Total	108	100.00

Table No.7-Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	0	0
Disagree	8	7.40
Neutral	15	13.88
Agree	50	46.29
Strongly Agree	35	32.40
Total	108	100.00

Table No.8-Conflict resolution and analytical skills

Response	Frequency	Percentage
Strongly disagree	3	2.77
Disagree	8	7.40
Neutral	32	29.62
Agree	39	36.11
Strongly Agree	26	24.07
Total	108	100.00

Findings and results

The information collected for the purpose of this research led to some important findings in addition to helping testing of hypothesis through the analysis carried out. The replies to questionnaire have, after careful analysis also led to some suggestion and recommendations.

Graph no. 1. Strongly agreed respondents (in %)

Maximum respondents i.e. 53 (49.07%) strongly agreed upon the importance of Grooming and physical appearance of the employees followed by 35 (32.40%) the requirement of the essential components of a workplace Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics. Respondents also gave importance to Leadership and initiative skills 29 (26.85%) followed by Conflict resolution and analytical skills 26 (24.07%). One-fourth i.e. 27 (25%) of the respondents strongly agreed upon the role of interpersonal communication and people skills at workplace while, Emotional and Cultural intelligence along with English proficiency and Multi lingual skills were rated similar i.e. 25 (23.14%) by the respondents. Least respondents i.e. 22 (20.37%) strongly agreed upon Non-verbal communication.

Graph no. 2. Agreed respondents (in %)

Maximum respondents i.e. 50 (46.29%) agreed upon the requirement of the essential components of a workplace Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics followed by Non-verbal communication 46 (42.59%). Emotional and Cultural intelligence was agreed upon by 45 (41.66%) respondents followed by Grooming and physical appearance of the employee 41 (37.96%). Conflict resolution

and analytical skills along with English proficiency and Multi lingual skills were rated similar i.e. 39 (36.11%) by the respondents.

Respondents rated Leadership and initiative skills 38 (35.18%) followed by the role of interpersonal communication and people skills at workplace 37 (34.25%).

Graph no. 3. Respondents remained neutral (in%)

Maximum respondents i.e. 32 (29.26%) remained neutral for Conflict resolution and analytical skills followed by the role of interpersonal communication and people skills at workplace 30 (27.77%). Non verbal communication along with English proficiency and Multi lingual skills were rated similar i.e. 29 (26.85%) by the respondents. One fourth i.e. 27 (25%) respondents remained neutral for Leadership and initiative skills followed by 26 (24.07%) for Emotional and Cultural intelligence. For Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics along with Grooming and physical appearance of the employee least employees remained neutral with 15 (13.88%) and 11 (10.18%) respectively.

Graph no. 4. Disagreed respondents (in %)

Maximum respondents i.e. 10 (9.25%) disagreed upon the necessity of Emotional and Cultural intelligence followed by Leadership and initiative skills 9 (8.33%). Conflict resolution and analytical skills, Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics along with English proficiency and Multi lingual skills were rated similar i.e. 8 (7.40%). The role of interpersonal communication and people skills at workplace was disagreed by 7 (6.48%) respondents. For Non verbal communication followed by Grooming and physical appearance least employees disagreed with 6 (5.55%) and 3 (2.77%) respectively.

Graph no. 5. Strongly disagreed respondents (in %)

Maximum respondents i.e. 7 (6.48%) strongly disagreed upon the necessity of interpersonal communication and people skills at workplace and English proficiency and Multi lingual skills as well. Leadership and initiative skills along with Non-verbal communication were strongly disagreed upon by 5 (4.62%) respondents. Conflict resolution and analytical skills and Emotional and Cultural intelligence were strongly disagreed by 3 (2.77%) and 2 (1.85%) respondents respectively. Not even a single respondent denied the importance of Grooming and physical appearance and Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics.

Discussion

It is widely acknowledged that tourist destinations are becoming more competitive and hotels must catch up with effective and efficient staff equipped with contemporary traits in order to remain into existence and be competitive. As majority of staff members out of 108 randomly selected respondents with age group 21-40 years and with experience 0-10 years comprises of 80 (74.07%) and 74 (68.51%) respectively affirmed i.e. strongly agreed or agreed only on the importance of skills like 53 (49.07%) strongly agreed upon the importance of Grooming and physical appearance

of the employees followed by 35 (32.40%) on the requirement of the essential components of a workplace Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics. Also, 29 (26.85%) respondents also gave importance by being strongly agreed to Leadership and initiative skills. While, 50 (46.29%) agreed upon the requirement of Dedication, Co-operation and Work ethics followed by Non verbal communication 46 (42.59%). Emotional and Cultural intelligence was agreed upon by 45 (41.66%) respondents.

The present study shows enough evidence towards inclination of majority of the respondents towards such crucial skills which is not only required to carry out the daily operations effectively and efficiently but also helps the business i.e. hotels to increase customer satisfaction, leading to repeat business and increase in the number of tourists in a particular destination also.

Nowadays, hotels face many challenges with regard to improving the profitability of operations and exploiting the new opportunities that have arisen due to the growth in the economy and the changing nature of tourism in India. To cope up with this challenge, employees must be given proper training and exposure in order to brush up their communication and soft skills and deliver the things with great perfection on consistent basis. As it is also evident that these skills are the major decisive factors in future prospects with the hotel industry, this will definitely lead to fill-in those skills-gaps and will also help in communicating and understanding well between the employees and the customers.

Conclusion

The research reported in this paper provides an understanding that communication coupled with soft skills plays a vital role in effective and efficient service delivery. From the study, it can be concluded that the perception of employees towards such key skills is positive and they rated the same as per their requirements and with great logical ability. Also, from the customers' point of view, with the help of these skills a better understanding is established between the service providers and customers. Such experience will surge the customers to provide repeat business to the hotels and augment the tourism potential of the destination as well.

Limitations and scope for future research

The industry population surveyed represents employees in some selected hotels of Mussoorie; therefore it is not appropriate for this study to make the claim that the findings are applicable to the hospitality industry in the whole state and outside Uttarakhand also. However, it is hoped that

the study can be reproduced to test the extent of the applicability of the findings. On the other hand, this limitation may provide an opportunity for future research on such competencies. The future research could use a larger sample to enable a test for skills required by the hospitality industry and cause-and-effect relationships between employees perception and the impact of those skills.

Due to the fact that it being the busiest industry, the employees remain occupied with their operations which was a limiting factor for accepting an interview. Therefore, the method that was employed to obtain the primary data was the questionnaire survey.

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“Rice” The Travel Food Connecting India (North, West, South, East and Central India)

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Abstract

Rice is majorly the staple food which is grown and consumed widely all over the world but especially in Asian region. Rice is a type of cereal which is consumed by most of the Indians. People of south majorly prefer rice in their food there three times meal includes something or the other made of rice. But when people of southern India travel to other parts like north, east, west or central part of India they didn't get to eat rice in that much quantity but still there is some amount of rice included in their food. Speaking of eastern India people there love to have rice in their meals but with some chapattis on other hand people of northern India like chapatti more over rice but still they include rice in one meal in a whole day. Rice is grown over almost 75 percent of the land area and is the country's most important crop. Two-thirds of this land area is now covered by MV technology after a rapid expansion over the past 15 years. The adoption process has been driven by the subsistence demands of households rather than by systematic agricultural extension efforts^[1]. Including rice in our diet also helps our body in prevention for illness like promotes good regulation of heart and nervous system and also prevents cardiovascular diseases. As we know golden rice is grown and consumed in central also helps in promoting better health it is a genetically modified variety of rice rich in the orange or red plant pigment beta-carotene, a substance important in the human diet as a precursor of vitamin A^[1]. Rice is also easy to carry food which people prefer to take while travelling. Whenever the people of either part of India travel to any other part of India they find rice as a familiar element in the food they are served in other part this makes them feel home like even after being in any other part of India.

Key words: Rice, Food, Connecting, People, Health, Meal, Travel

Introduction

Rice is growing as the staple food for millions of people in India. Rice is basically the seed of the grass species *Oryza sativa*^[1]. It is a type of cereal grain which is widely consumed in most part of world but especially in Asia and that to majorly in India and nearby country. Due to this wide consumption there is essential need to increase the production of rice from 680 million tons in 2015 to 771 million tons in 2030 to feed increasing population of 8.27 billion^[1] India is basically divided in five major parts that are north, west, south, east & central India. All these five parts of India are somewhere connected through rice when we speak of food. There are several dishes which may differ by name and method of preparation but one ingredient is common among them that is rice^[1]. Like in North India Tudkiya Bhath , Kashmiri pulao , Fara , Mithe chawal etc. are dishes which are loved by north Indian peoples and are made up of rice. Now for Western India Gatte Ki Khichdi , Handvo , Khichu , Pohe^[1] are some major dishes prepared from rice. Now as we come to the downward part of India that is Southern India they prepare dishes like Pulihara, Dosa , Idli , Uttapam which are majorly prepared from rice flour. The Eastern part of India prepares dishes like Dal Peetha , Patishapa , Kanika , Pilaf from rice or rice flour. In the last we came to the Central part of India in which dishes like Muhia , Chila , Poha Jalebi , Chusela^[1] are some delicious dishes prepared using rice flour. The production of White rice, Brown rice, Palakkadan matta rice, Small grain rice, Black rice is most in Southern part of India. Sticky rice is majorly produced and consumed in North East India. Basmati rice is widely consumed in Western and Northern part of India. Parboiled rice is generally produced through method of soaking, pressure steaming and drying in Eastern part of India. So from this we can make out that rice is the connecting element in between the five major part of India. Whenever the people of either part of India travel to any other part of India they find rice as a familiar element in the food they are served in other part this makes them feel home like even after being in any other part of India.

Objective of the research

The main objectives of this research paper are mentioned in following points: -

- To show that the “RICE” is a connecting element of food among five different parts of India.

- To show that rice is used either in its original form or in flour form in different part (North, South, East, West & Central India) of India to prepare dishes.
- To show that rice can be part of food which tourist can get in each part of India
- To show the different variety of “RICE” that is produced in five different parts of India.
- Different parts of India use “RICE” as the part of their daily routine food.

Need of the study

The reason to study this topic is mentioned in the following point: -

- To represent “RICE” as a connecting food of India.
- To increase the utilization of rice as a handy food used while travelling.
- To increase the future consumption of RICE.
- To develop a better quality of RICE through which better health can be promoted.

Models Representing Rice Used In Different Parts Of India As Connecting Food

fig1.1

Production And Consumption Of Type Of Rice In Diferent Part Of India

Explanation of the Flow Chart

From the two flow chart mentioned above we can make out that what are the different type of dishes that are prepared in different parts of India. According to FIG1.2 as we take the northern part of India they produce white rice and basmati rice and using these varieties of rice they prepare some delicious dishes such as Tudkiya Bhath , Kashmiri pulao, Fara , Mithe chawal ect. as shown in FIG1.1. Now for the western part of India as shown in FIG1.2 production of white rice and basmati rice is done which is similar to that of northern india but the dishes prepared using these

variety of rice are much different such as Gatte Ki Khichdi , Handvo , Khichu , Pohey etc. as per FIG1.1. Coming to the downward part of India that is in southern India production of rice such as White rice , Brown rice , Palakkadan matta rice , Small grain rice , Black rice are widely done as per FIG1.2 in this part rice is majorly used in preparation of several dishes such as Pulihara , Dosa , Idli , Uttapam etc. as per FIG1.1. In eastern part of India different variety of rice is produced through the process of soaking, pressure steaming and drying as shown in FIG1.2 and dishes prepared using rice in this part of India are Dal Peetha, Patishapa, Kanika, Pilaf etc. as shown in FIG1.1. In last the central part of India produces Bamleshwari rice, Swarna rice, Brown rice etc. as per figure 1.2 and dishes prepared from rice are Muhia , Chila , Poha Jalebi , Chusela etc. as in FIG1.2.

Discussion and interpretation

Through the study of this paper we can prove that rice actually connects tourist of different parts and they find rice as a handy element of food which they can get in North, South, West, East & Central India. They can easily carry rice while travelling and can have it any time and in any parts of India. This can be proved by following testimonials:-

- In the North Eastern part of India rice is actually an important element of food and people there prefer eating rice twice in a day but when the travel to other parts of India they actually get rice as an element of food.

- SHIVAM KUMAR
(Assam)

- Western side of India easily get to eat rice in different parts of India. As and when they travel they just find slight difference in the quality of rice of western part to the other parts of India.

- VINA DONODE
(Maharashtra)

- Rice is actually an element of food she gets in other region too but she finds that the quality of rice in central India is much better than of north India and in central India people get to eat rice in many different dishes as a part of their daily food routine but when they travels they just get boiled rice.

- TEJSWINI CHANDRA

(Chhattisgarh)

- Firstly due to the change of place from eastern side to northern side they prefer rice over chapatti but they didn't get rice in that much proportion as they get in eastern part but still they get connected to rice as a part of food they get in other parts of India.

- SHRUTI RAY NANDAN

(West Bengal)

- Rice which is used in eastern part is quite thick but rice in northern part is of finer quality and in eastern side people prefers more of rice over chapatti and when they travel yes they get connected to rice of other parts of India.

- VIDAYARANYA SHUBHAM

(Bihar)

- People of northern India connect to rice as an element of food when they travel to different part of India they generally eat rice once in a day but when they travel they can adjust by having three to two time of rice a day.

- SAKSHI KRISHNA

(Uttar Pradesh)

- People from south India Includes rice as main course in their food the prefer eating dosa, idli, uttapam etc. which are generally prepared using rice flour but when they travel to north, east, west and central part they didn't get rice as their main course but they get rice there also in some proportion.

- LAKSHMI SHIVA

(Bangalore)

- People of south majorly prefer rice in each meal they have in day without rice food is not completed in south India and even when this people travel to different part of India rice is the first element what they look for in a food. They don't get rice in that much majority but they get rice in some other form which helps them in getting comfortable with that food.

- HARI PRASAD

(Chennai)

- Though Gujarati people are less fond of rice but still they take rice at least once in a day and due to this habit they search for rice while travelling to different parts of India. Therefore they find rice as a connecting element.

- POOJA PATEL
(Gujarat)

Reference from Veda

“RICE” is mentioned in Rig-Veda but it received more attention when it got mentioned in “YAJURVEDA”. According to Arthasashtra Sanskrit has given different word for variety of rice, barley and wheat which is known as “VRIHI”^[□]. There is no road map demonstrating the origin of rice cultivation of India. In India word “ARICI” is used for rice with slight regional variation. Sanskrit accepted the word “VRIHI” instead of the regional word for denoting “RICE”^[□]. Word “TANDULA” is used for paddy grains of rice, “AKSHAT” is used for unbroken rice, words like “NIVAR”, “NAMBA” and “VRIHI” is used for transplanted rice^[□]. Akshat is generally used in religious ceremonies by mixing it with “HONAM”. The tamil word “ARICI” is much similar and shows more affinity to the words used for rice in Greek and Latin language^[□].

Health benefit of rice

Till this we only got to hear that rice contains high carbohydrates which results in obesity and bad health but now we would like to introduce the healthy side of rice and how rice promotes better health in following points:-

- Basmati rice is generally rich in amylase and amylopectin. Amylase helps in slowing down the digestion of starch which promotes better health^[□].
- Manganese is a mineral found in rice which is essential for metabolism and helps in growth and development of a body^[□].
- Thiamine which is also known as B1 is found in rice which promotes better function of heart, muscles and nervous system^[□].
- Ferulic acid is a strong antioxidant which is found in rice bran which protects the body against chronic diseases such as CANCER, diabetes and cardiovascular diseases^[□].

Conclusion

From the facts and points mentioned above in this research we came to a conclusion that as per our topic “Rice the travel food connecting India” rice is actually the connecting element of food in northern, southern, western, eastern and central part of India. People from different part of India are having different dishes and different consumption and production quantity of rice. Even the quality of rice is also changing with movement from north to south or east to west. Rice also has its mention in Rig-Veda and Yajurveda. There are also some spiritual importances of rice in Hindu religion as “akshat” in which unbroken rice is mixed with honam and used in performing different spiritual ceremonies. Rice is also produced on different levels in all parts of India due to which tourist while travelling to different parts of India find rice as an connecting element on the food. Rice has also become handy food which tourist can easily carry with them while travelling and for proving our point we had taken the views of people belonging to different states of India.

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Healthy combo Meals in Educational Institutes- Need of the Hour

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Abstract

Background: Provision of adequate diet for the school aged children enhance the learning capacity as well as prevent them from childhood diseases. Understanding the importance of providing healthy food to the growing children helps their mental and physical growth, providing them with different meal combinations keeping in mind the nutritive value and the financial condition of the organizations. The eating pattern of the young generation has changed over the years. Combo meal is one of the upcoming options which most of the children prefer for their consumption. This study will outshine the benefits of choosing combo meals especially in terms of nutritional, financial and social responsibility. The National Programme of Nutritional Support to Primary Education (NP-NSPE) was launched as a Centrally Sponsored Scheme on 15th August 1995, initially in 2408 blocks in the country. By the year 1997-98 the NP-NSPE was introduced in all blocks of the country to provide adequate meals to the children in classes I –V. Meal with a minimum content of 300 calories of energy and 8-12 gram protein per day is the recommendation by the Government of India.

Objective: To enlist combo meals served in educational institutions and to analyse the cost effectiveness of combo meals. Methodology: Different schools and institutes will be observed for the meals served. A comparative analysis of the combo meals will be done with the existing Government norms. Results: Combo meals variations served will be enlisted and comparison of cost analysed according to Government norms. Conclusion: Combo meals will be a good choice as these are cost effective and provide variety to the students.

Keywords - Combo meals, nutritional value, food pattern.

Introduction

Consuming a healthy diet throughout the life course helps prevent malnutrition in all its forms as well as a range of noncommunicable diseases and conditions. But the increased production of processed food, rapid urbanization and changing lifestyles have led to a shift in dietary patterns. People are now consuming more foods high in energy, fats, free sugars or salt/sodium, and many do not eat enough fruit, vegetables and dietary fibre such as whole grains.

The exact make-up of a diversified, balanced and healthy diet will vary depending on individual needs (e.g. age, gender, lifestyle, degree of physical activity), cultural context, locally available foods and dietary customs. But basic principles of what constitute a healthy diet remain the same (Healthy diet, Fact sheet N°394, September 2015)

Children should eat food high in fruit and vegetables, high in complex (brown) carbohydrates, low in fat and sugar with a medium amount of protein. Free school meals will at last offer the chance for these young children to have at least one nutritionally sound meal a day.

Children should have a varied diet, not only so they have the best chance of getting the nutrients they need but also so they try new foods, see food as interesting or different and also avoid getting picky or rigid about what they will and will not eat.

We want our children to eat a nutritionally sound diet in order have long and healthy lives. But we also want them to have a healthy approach to food to make these lives happy ones.

The regularity of the school dinner routine means children learn to feel and live with hunger (without reaching for a snack), then learn that meals are nicer if you are hungry. They also learn that eating a meal makes the hunger go away for longer. Let's put the 'school' back into free school meals and teach the importance of healthy habits. (<https://theconversation.com/lets-put-the-school-back-into-free-school-meals-and-teach-the-importance-of-healthy-habits-31124>)

Past scenario

Children's food preferences are strongly associated with their consumption patterns. Identifying the factors that influence preferences is therefore crucial to the development of effective interventions to improve children's diets. Perhaps the most important determinant of a child's liking for a particular food is the extent to which it is familiar. Put simply, children like what they know and they eat what they like. From the very earliest age, children's experiences with food influence

both preferences and intake, and research suggests that the earlier and broader that experience, the healthier the child's diet. L. Cooke (2007)

Mid-Day Meal in schools has had a long history in India. In 1925, a mid-Day Meal Programme was introduced for disadvantaged children in Madras Municipal Corporation. By the mid-1980s three States viz. Gujarat, Kerala and Tamil Nadu and the UT of Pondicherry had universalized a cooked Mid-Day Meal Programme with their own resources for children studying at the primary stage by 1990-91 the number of States implementing the mid-day meal programme with their own resources on a universal or a large scale had increased to twelve states. (About the Mid-Day Meal Scheme).

Present scenario

Every 5 years since 1980, a new edition of the Dietary Guidelines for Americans has been published. Its goal is to make recommendations about the components of a healthy and nutritionally adequate diet to help promote health and prevent chronic disease for current and future generations. Although many of its recommendations have remained relatively consistent over time, the Dietary Guidelines has evolved as scientific knowledge has grown. These advancements have provided a greater understanding of, and focus on, the importance of healthy eating patterns as a whole, and how foods and beverages act synergistically to affect health. The Dietary Guidelines is designed for professionals to help all individuals ages 2 years and older and their families consume a healthy, nutritionally adequate diet.

The information in the Dietary Guidelines is used in developing Federal food, nutrition, and health policies and programs. It also is the basis for Federal nutrition education materials designed for the public and for the nutrition education components of HHS and USDA food programs. It is developed for use by policymakers and nutrition and health professionals. Additional audiences who may use Dietary Guidelines information to develop programs, policies, and communication for the general public include businesses, schools, community groups, media, the food industry, and State and local governments.

Previous editions of the Dietary Guidelines focused primarily on individual dietary components such as food groups and nutrients. However, people do not eat food groups and nutrients in isolation but rather in combination, and the totality of the diet forms an overall eating pattern. The components of the eating pattern can have interactive and potentially cumulative effects on health.

These patterns can be tailored to an individual's personal preferences, enabling Americans to choose the diet that is right for them.

A growing body of research has examined the relationship between overall eating patterns, health, and risk of chronic disease, and findings on these relationships are sufficiently well established to support dietary guidance.

As a result, eating patterns and their food and nutrient characteristics are a focus of the recommendations in the 2015-2020 Dietary Guidelines for Americans issued by Department of Health and Human Services, United States.

Diet evolves over time, being influenced by many factors and complex interactions. Income, food prices (which will affect the availability and affordability of healthy foods), individual preferences and beliefs, cultural traditions, as well as geographical, environmental, social and economic factors all interact in a complex manner to shape individual dietary patterns.

Therefore, promoting a healthy food environment, including food systems which promote a diversified, balanced and healthy diet, requires involvement across multiple sectors and stakeholders, including government, and the public and private sector.

A study found that young consumers are more highly involved in sustainable food consumption than any other sector. Sustainable food products are perceived by many consumers to be better with regard to taste, quality, safety, and freshness. If companies can make their products desirable, consumers want to buy them, regardless of the possible higher price than a non-sustainable food product. (Vermeir and Verbeke, 2004)

A Mid Day Meal (MDM) is an important instrument for combating class room hunger and promoting better learning. MDM is effective in improving physical and psycho-social health for disadvantaged school children in lower income and higher income countries. It increased the school attendance in lower income countries and increased the height of younger children in both lower and higher income countries.

Combo meals like mithe chawal, roti sabji, kadichawalrajma chawal, khichri and dal chawal during different days of a week. Midday meals include combo meals which are cost effective and provide required amount of nutrients to children (ICMR2010).

The Government of Punjab started cooked meal for all students of primary classes in Government and Government aided schools of the state from September, 2004. All the schools of total twenty

districts are covered under this scheme. The meal is cooked and served in the school premises. Under the scheme, school children are being provided combo food viz. Mithechawal, roti sabji, kadichawal and dal chawal during different days of the week.(news.mit.edu/2012/sustainable-approaches-to-reducing-food-waste-in-India)

Cooking cost (excluding the labour and administrative charges) has been revised from Rs.1.68 to Rs. 2.50 for primary and from Rs. 2.20 to Rs. 3.75 for upper primary children from 1.12.2009 to facilitate serving meal to eligible children in prescribed quantity and of good quality. The cooking cost for primary is Rs. 2.69 per child per day and Rs. 4.03 for upper primary children from 1.4.2010. The cooking cost will be revised with prior approval of competent authority by 7.5% every financial year from 1.4.2011.

The scheme guidelines envisage providing cooked mid-day meal with 450 calories and 12 g of protein to every child at primary level and 700 calories and 20 g of protein at upper primary level. This energy and protein requirement for a primary child comes from cooking 100 g of rice/flour, 20 g pulses and 50 g vegetables and 5 g oil, and for an upper primary child it comes from 150 g of rice/flour, 30 g of pulses and 75 g of vegetables and 7.5 g of oil. (<http://mdm.nic.in/>)

Revised Cooking cost per child per school day w.e.f. 1.07.2016

Stage	Total Cost (in Rs)
Primary	4.13
Upper Primary	6.18

Governments have a central role in creating a healthy food environment that enables people to adopt and maintain healthy dietary practices.

Effective actions by policy-makers to create a healthy food environment include:

(1) Creating coherence in national policies and investment plans, including trade, food and agricultural policies, to promote a healthy diet and protect public health:

- Increase incentives for producers and retailers to grow, use and sell fresh fruits and vegetables;
- Reduce incentives for the food industry to continue or increase production of processed foods with saturated fats and free sugars;

- Encourage reformulation of food products to reduce the contents of salt, fats (i.e. saturated fats and trans fats) and free sugars;
- Implement the WHO recommendations on the marketing of foods and non-alcoholic beverages to children;
- Establish standards to foster healthy dietary practices through ensuring the availability of healthy, safe and affordable food in pre-schools, schools, other public institutions, and in the workplace;
- Explore regulatory and voluntary instruments, such as marketing and food labelling policies, economic incentives or disincentives (i.e. taxation, subsidies), to promote a healthy diet; and
- Encourage transnational, national and local food services and catering outlets to improve the nutritional quality of their food, ensure the availability and affordability of healthy choices, and review portion size and price.

2. Encouraging consumer demand for healthy foods and meals:

- promote consumer awareness of a healthy diet,
- develop school policies and programmes that encourage children to adopt and maintain a healthy diet;
- educate children, adolescents and adults about nutrition and healthy dietary practices;
- encourage culinary skills, including in schools;
- support point-of-sale information, including through food labelling that ensures accurate, standardized and comprehensible information on nutrient contents in food in line with the Codex Alimentarius Commission guidelines; and
- provide nutrition and dietary counselling at primary health care facilities.

3. Promoting appropriate infant and young child feeding practices:

- implement the International Code of Marketing of Breast-milk Substitutes and subsequent relevant World Health Assembly resolutions;
- implement policies and practices to promote protection of working mothers; and

- promote, protect and support breastfeeding in health services and the community, including through the Baby-friendly Hospital Initiative.

WHO response: The “WHO Global Strategy on Diet, Physical Activity and Health” (12) was adopted in 2004 by the World Health Assembly (WHA). It called on governments, WHO, international partners, the private sector and civil society to take action at global, regional and local levels to support healthy diets and physical activity.

In 2010, the WHA endorsed a set of recommendations on the marketing of foods and non-alcoholic beverages to children (13). These recommendations guide countries in designing new policies and improving existing ones to reduce the impact on children of the marketing of unhealthy food. WHO is also helping to develop a nutrient profile model that countries can use as a tool to implement the marketing recommendations.

In 2012, the WHA adopted a “Comprehensive Implementation Plan on Maternal, Infant and Young Child Nutrition” and 6 global nutrition targets to be achieved by 2025, including the reduction of stunting, wasting and overweight in children, the improvement of breastfeeding and the reduction of anaemia and low birth weight (7).

In 2013, the WHA agreed to 9 global voluntary targets for the prevention and control of NCDs, which include a halt to the rise in diabetes and obesity and a 30% relative reduction in the intake of salt by 2025. The “Global Action Plan for the Prevention and Control of Noncommunicable Diseases 2013–2020” (8) provides guidance and policy options for Member States, WHO and other UN agencies to achieve the targets.

With many countries now seeing a rapid rise in obesity among infants and children, in May 2014 WHO set up the Commission on Ending Childhood Obesity. The Commission is developing a report specifying which approaches and actions are likely to be most effective in different contexts around the world.

In November 2014, WHO organized, jointly with the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO), the Second International Conference on Nutrition (ICN2). ICN2 adopted the Rome Declaration on Nutrition (14) and the Framework for Action (15), which recommends a set of policy options and strategies to promote diversified, safe and healthy diets at all stages of

life. WHO is helping countries to implement the commitments made at ICN2. (Healthy diet, Fact sheet N°394, September 2015)

School nutrition services provide access to a variety of nutritious foods that promote students' health and their capacity to attend to academic tasks. About 94% of schools in the United States, both private and public, participate in the National School Lunch Program (NSLP). Schools are therefore uniquely positioned to promote healthy eating behaviours and attitudes toward food among the vast majority of American children.

The availability of nutritious foods as part of school meals increases children's consumption of whole grains, fruits, vegetables, and low-fat milk. (Katherine B. et al.)

Methodology

Locale: For the current study, different combo meals were selected from various schools' and colleges' mess. Various schools and educational institutes were visited for the survey. The mess incharges of various government schools were contacted and an unstructured, informal interview was conducted.

For this study, two meals were selected from faculties' restaurant of Institute of hotel management, catering and nutrition, Pusa, New Delhi, while other four meals are taken from different government schools. Different combo meals included gate kisabji, parantha and moong dal kahalwa; kahal biryani, burhaniraita and rasmalai; aloo, poori and aatekahalwa, kadi, rice and kheer; aloo matar, roti and zarda; chane ki dal, rice and aloo baigan.

Portion size: No of Portion served differs with different institutions. The no of portion served per meal are as follows:

Como meals	No. Of Portion served
Gatte ki Sabji, parantha and moong dal kahalwa	25
Kahal biryani, burhanirayta and rasmalai	25
Aloo, poori and aatekahalwa	50
Kadi, rice and kheer	50
Aloo matar, roti and zarda	50
Chane ki dal, rice and aloo baigan	50

Results

Different combo meals served in the educational institutions are enlisted below:

- Gatte ki sabji, parantha and moong dal kahalwa
- Kathal biryani, burhani raita and rasmalai
- Aloo, poori and aatekahalwa, kadi, rice
- Kheer; aloo matar, roti and zarda
- Chaneki dal, rice and aloo baigan.
- Shahi Paneer, roti and ice cream
- Poorichholey and halwa
- Aloo parantha and coondiraayta
- Uttapam and chutney
- Masoor dal, aloo gobhi and roti.

Different combo meals were selected from different schools and colleges and their cost is analysed on the basis of rates provided by institute.

The cost of meals is calculated as per the no of portion served and then cost for 1 portion is calculated.

Costing of combo meals is as follows:

Combo meals	No. Of Portions served	Total Cost	Cost for 1 portion
GattekiSabji, parantha and moong dal kahalwa	25	770.72	30.82
Kathal biryani, burhaniraita and rasmalai	25	685.5	27.42
Aloo, poori and aatekahalwa	50	189.87	3.79
Kadi, rice and kheer	50	282.65	5.65
Aloo matar, roti and zarda	50	172.8	3.45
Chane ki dal, rice and aloo baigan	50	246.50	4.93

It was found that the raw material for most of the schools was bought from the KendriyaBhandar, that is the Government food distribution system on the nominal prices.

Hence the price per meal was coming out to be low for them.

Conclusion

During the course of the research, several findings came to the light, adding to the knowledge gathered during the interviews with the staff members at different schools. Although it is believed that mid-day meal initiative should be encouraged for a proper physical and mental growth of children at the school level. The educational authorities along with the caterers and the meal preparation team have performed cyclic meals keeping in mind that proper nutrition is provided to every meal served to them. The cost band provided by the government is too low and some of the schools find it difficult to meet the nutritive requirement within that range. Hence, many schools do not take initiative in serving mid day meal due to costing, staff crunch and other problems. Hence, there is a need for the government to encourage the schools to serve mid-day meal by launching schemes that are beneficial for schools, students and parents.

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The Effect of Mindful Eating on Body Image and Self Esteem between Vegetarian and Non-Vegetarian College Students

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Abstract

Mindfulness is defined as an astute, non-judgmental awareness of the present moment (Kabat-Zinn et al 1985). Mindful eating” describes a non-judgmental awareness of physical and emotional sensations associated with eating (Framson et al 2009). The prevalence of eating disorders is higher among vegetarian adolescents who experience frequent binge eating and caloric restrictions due to their concerns about their physical appearance (Klopp, heiss and Smith, 2003). Body image is the way of our perception about our body, how we see our body and think about our body. Our body image can be influenced by our beliefs. Abnormal eating attitudes and low self esteem was found in Turkish vegetarian adolescences (Bas, Karabudak, Kiziltan 2005). Self esteem is the opinion of the individual regarding his/her self. Self esteem is most important because it affects the way how you think, act and even how you relate yourself with others.

ObjectiveThe current study aims to assess the relationship among Mindful eating, body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non-vegetarian on male and female college students.

Method

This is a descriptive study using cross sectional study design. The sample comprises of 50 Vegetarian and 50 Non-Vegetarian college students (both male and female) from Amity

University, Madhya Pradesh and the samples are selected using random sampling method. The students are assessed for Mindful eating, body image and self esteem using the measures “Mindful Eating Questionnaire” (Framson, et al 2009), “Body Shape Questionnaire-16 (Evans & Dolan 1993) and “Self Esteem Scale” (Rosenberg 1965). Data was analyzed using SPSS 16.0 version, Independent sample t test was used to analyze the difference between the group and Pearson

Moment Correlation was used to find the relationship between Mindful eating, body image and self esteem. **Findings** The result showed that, the present study didn't find any significant difference in mindful eating, body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non-vegetarian students. Also we couldn't find any significant relationship among Mindful eating, body image and self esteem in both the groups.

Key words - Mindful Eating, Body Shape, Self Esteem, Vegetarian, Non Vegetarian

Introduction

Mindfulness is maintaining a non judgmental, non deliberately awareness about the thoughts and perception of self. Mindfulness teaches the individual to live in the present (Lofgren, 2015). The goal of the mindfulness is to enhance the awareness regarding the present moment and reduce the “automatic pilot” state (Lofgren, 2015). Mindful eating is very helpful for the individual to control the weight gaining. It is an emerging approach to addressing the eating disorder (Lofgren, 2015). Mindfulness eating encourages the individual to understand the urge for eating. Because of the mindful eating we can understand whether we are physically hungry or not. If we are physically hungry then we will be paying attention to the food and our mind will think about the food, smell of the food, appearance and taste of the food (Laor, 2003). Mindful eating affects the body image and self esteem. Many research studies showed the correlation between the mindful eating and self esteem. Taylor, Daiss & Krietsch, (2015) found in their study that there is a positive relationship between self-compassion and mindful eating. They suggest that people who have high self-compassion may engage in more mindful eating because both component mindful eating and self compassion is associated to the awareness, curiosity and openness. Some research studies showed that psychological distress is associated to the eating behavior and the mental health professional may help the individual with eating disturbance with the mindfulness eating intervention. According to the Harter (1999) an adult has a positive attitude towards the body image and his/her body image also associated to the self esteem. Muth & Cash (1997) explained body image in two ways satisfaction and dissatisfaction with one's physical appearance and body shape. Body image affect the psychological well being at different phase of life and it is highly correlated to the self esteem and this relationship is much stronger during the adolescence period of life (Carroll, Tiggemann, & Wade, 1999). Koyuncu et. al (2010) reported that the individuals

who were satisfied with their physical appearance have higher self esteem and low social physique anxiety. They also showed a positive relationship between self esteem and body image satisfaction. According to West & Sweeting (1997), females have more concern towards their physical appearance and because of this females have low self esteem in comparison of the males. Nnaemeka & Solomon (2014) observed that body image and self esteem both are related to each other. Furthermore, females showed more concern toward the body image and want to reduce the body weight.

Methodology

Aim

To measure the effect of mindful eating on body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non-vegetarian college students.

Objective

- To find the difference in mindful eating, body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non vegetarian college students.
- To assess the relationship among Mindful eating, body image and self esteem in vegetarian college students
- To assess the relationship among Mindful eating, body image and self esteem in non vegetarian college students

Hypothesis

- There will be no significant difference in mindful eating, body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non-vegetarian college students
- There will be no significant relationship between body image and self-esteem in vegetarian students
- There will be no significant relationship between mindful eating and body image in vegetarian students

- There will be no significant relationship between mindful eating and self-esteem in vegetarian students
- There will be no significant relationship between body image and self-esteem in non-vegetarian students
- There will be no significant relationship between mindful eating and body image in non-vegetarian students
- There will be no significant relationship between mindful eating and self-esteem in non-vegetarian students

Materials and Methods

Subjects

This descriptive, cross sectional study consists of 100 colleges students in which 50 were vegetarian students and 50 were non vegetarian students. The subject were selected from Amity University, Madhya Pradesh using random sampling method.

Measures

- Mindful eating questionnaire (Framson et. al 2009)
- The scale consists of 28 items and measures five domains of mindful eating such as disinhibition, awareness, external cues, emotional response, and distraction. Each item rated on a 4 point Likert scale ranging from 1(rarely/never) to 4 (usual/always). The higher indicates that the person eat mindfully most of the meal time.
- Body Shape Questionnaire 16 (Evans & Dolan 1993)
- This 16 item scale measures the body image and each item score range from 1 to 6 with 1(never) and 6(always). If the total scores are below 38 then it shows no concern with body image and if the total scores are above 66 it indicates marked concern with body image.
- Self Esteem Scale (Rosenberg 1965).
- It consists of 10 items which measures the self esteem of the individual. Each item is scored with 4 point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree

(SD). Item numbers 2, 5, 6, 8 and 9 are required the reverse scoring. Higher the score higher the self esteem.

Data Analysis

The statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 16.0 was used to analyze the data. Descriptive statistics were done for socio demographic data. Parametric test was used since the sample was found to be uniformly distributed. Independent sample t test was used to see the difference between the group and Pearson Moment Correlation was used to find the relationship between mindful eating, body image and self esteem.

Procedure

After explaining the aim and objective of the study. The investigator took consent from each student, subsequently socio demographic data sheet, Mindful Eating Questionnaire, Body Shape Questionnaire and Self Esteem Scale were administered on both the groups

Result Table 1: shows the distribution of socio demographic variables of undergraduate college students

Variable		Mean±SD/n(%)
Gender	Male	55 (55.0)
	Female	45(45.0)
Age	Veg	21.56±2.31
	Non Veg	21.18±1.87

Table 2: shows the comparison of MEQ, BSQ and self esteem between vegetarian and non vegetarian undergraduate college students

Variables	Mean±S.D VEG (N=50)	Mean±S.D NON-VEG (N=50)	t	Df	P
MEQ	2.11±0.26	2.14±0.32	-0.562	98	0.575
BSQ	38.76±16.65	35.16±16.65	1.090	98	0.279
Self esteem	20.28±3.46	19.32±3.00	1.480	98	0.960

Table 2: shows the comparison of MEQ, BSQ and self esteem of between vegetarian and non vegetarian undergraduate college students. The mean of MEQ in Veg-students is 2.11 ± 0.26 and the mean of non-Veg students is 2.14 ± 0.32 . Similarly, the mean of BSQ in Veg-Students is 38.76 ± 16.65 and the mean of non-Veg students is 35.16 ± 16.65 . Furthermore the mean of Self esteem in Veg-Students is 20.28 ± 3.46 and the mean of non-Veg students is 19.32 ± 3.00 . Overall there is no significant difference between the groups.

Table 3: shows the correlation between MEQ and BSQ in vegetarian students:

Variables	BSQ
MEQ	0.091

Table 3: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and BSQ and found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Table 4: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and Self esteem in vegetarian students:

Variables	Self esteem
MEQ	-0.035

Table 4: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and Self esteem and found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Table 5: shows the Pearson correlation between Self esteem and BSQ in vegetarian students:

Variables	BSQ
Self esteem	-0.126

Table 5: shows the Pearson correlation between Self esteem and BSQ found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Table 6: shows the correlation between MEQ and BSQ in non- vegetarian students:

Variables	BSQ
MEQ	0.077

Table 6: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and BSQ and found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Table 7: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and Self esteem in non-vegetarian students:

Variables	Self esteem
MEQ	0.135

Table 7: shows the Pearson correlation between MEQ and Self esteem and found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Table 8: shows the Pearson correlation between Self esteem and BSQ in non-vegetarian students:

Variables	BSQ
Self esteem	-0.003

Table 8: shows the Pearson correlation between Self esteem and BSQ found to have no significant relationship between the variables

Discussion

The present study didn't find any significant difference in mindful eating between vegetarian and non vegetarian students. This finding is in agreement with the previous study by Janelle and Barr (1995). Furthermore, the present study didn't find any significant difference in mindful eating between vegetarian and non vegetarian students. In contrast a previous study by Bas, Karabudak and Kiziltan (2005) examined 1205 students and reported that low self esteem in Turkish vegetarian students than non-vegetarian. Similarly, the current research didn't find any association between mindful eating and body image in vegetarian students. We have found a contrast previous research by Hatanka (2015) reported there is a positive relationship between mindful eating and organic food in vegetarian students. Similarly, Plante (2014) also reported a significant relationship between the Mindful eating intervention and the reduction of fat. Nevertheless, the current study didn't find any significant relationship between mindful eating and self esteem. However, Pepping et. al (2013) found that the individuals who eat mindfully have high self esteem. Also the current study showed no significant relationship between self esteem and body image. In one of the earlier study by Strickland (2004) documented that, the females who have the negative body image have low self esteem and the females who have positive body image have the high self esteem.

Conclusion

The present study didn't find any significant difference in mindful eating, body image and self esteem between vegetarian and non vegetarian students. Also we couldn't find any significant relationship among mindful eating, body image and self esteem in both the groups.

Limitations

The study was done on mostly hostel students, so hostel food may affect the eating pattern.

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“Mental Health in Yoga, Culture and Tourism”

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Abstract

Yoga is a Hindu technique discovered 5000 years ago in India that relatively recently came to the attention of western nations for its role in improving mental health.

The word yoga comes from Sanskrit “yuj” meaning to yoke/ union, meaning union of body, mind and spirit. There are several different types of yoga and in the west the most common form is hatha yoga. Yoga combines a variety of postures and relaxation breathing techniques.

There is no domain of life where yoga has not made its contribution it changes our attitude towards work. It makes us aware of the so far unseen challenges in our work. It awakens our creativity. It enriches our relationships with others. In the light of Yoga nothing remains mundane; everything gets a touch of the sublime. We all long and strive for success. And what is success? Success is the result of tireless striving towards the goal with a positive attitude of confidence in oneself and others leading to a fruitful culmination. This is self development.

In Yoga, when we learn to perform Asana and Pranayama, our breathing becomes long and deep. We learn to focus our attention on a particular spot. When this focused mind is applied to studies, it grasps the ideas and concepts better. It can retain the matter effectively. In other words, Yoga improves our learning and memory. When we appear for examination, our mind is cool and composed. An unexpected question does not disturb us. Even if we study very hard sometimes we do not get the expected results and our mind gets clouded by anxiety and depression. Regular practice of Yoga frees us from depression. In a country like Japan, where meritocracy prevails, the percentage of suicides among youth is alarming. Yoga teaches us to do our best and leave the rest in hands of the Lord

Yogic Practices are isometric exercises:

1. Effect of Yoga on Human Relationships:
2. Effect of yoga on work:

3. Effect of yoga on attitudes, thinking and behaving
4. Let us out complain about our environment.
5. Self development and yoga
6. Let us train the body first.
7. Let us train our mind
8. Let us train our intellect
9. Therapeutic importance of yogic practices.
10. Pranayama
11. Bandhas and mudras
12. Shatakarama
13. Meditation
14. Yogic diet
15. conclusion

Yogic practices are isometric exercises

As against isotonic exercises of aerobics, gym exercises which help to build muscles which reduce the flexibility & become blockers over a period of time (aerobics are useful to exercise the heart) Increases absorption of oxygen into the hemoglobin by creation inhale pressure in lungs for osmosis E.g. Ujjai breath Increases the removal of carbon dioxide from the blood plasma by creating exhale pressure in lungs for osmoses E.s. Bastrika pranayam increases oxidation and liberation of energy in every cell of the body Air filter analogy in automobiles Stimulates nerve tips in llungs which have connection to the brain area (hypothalamus) where Pituitary Gland is situated Pituitary Gland is the master gland in the endocrine system and has a strong influence on rest of the endocrine glands

Breathing is the key voluntary And involuntary function clue(entry point) to explore the internal world – what ancient Rishi's discovered Meditation Takes the brain to Alpha state: electrical impulses of 8 to 14 cycles per second At dep meditation level(Samadhi state brain goes to Theta state: electrical impulses of 4 to 7 cycles per second Leads to deep relaxation.

Many western scholars too realized the utility of Yoga and made efforts to study its significance from scientific point of view. They made some longitudinal studies in their area and their research

findings are available to us for further work in this area. Swami Kuvalyananda reported sub-atmospheric pressure in the various internal cavities during Uddian Bandha and its extension of Nauli.

He also took X-rays to demonstrate the movements of the diaphragm during Uddiyana Bandha. A pupil of his, Behanana, undertook further research leading to a doctoral thesis of Yale University in 1937. He estimated the oxygen consumption during Pranayama practice and reported an increase during Ujjai, Bhastrika and Kapapbhati. He also brought different types of Pranayama on to kymographic record. The ability of Yogis to voluntarily stop the beating of the heart was considered- a fascinating feat, and aroused the interest of scientists in India and elsewhere. Bagchi and Wenger (1957) studied practitioners of RajYoga in India. They found a lower respiratory rate and raised G.S.R(Galvanic Skin Resistance) with no consistent alterations in heart rate or blood pressure during meditation.

During Meditation, the EEG showed an increase in alpha wave amplitude and activity and in some of the Yogis there was a loss of the alpha blocking response to all external stimuli. Yoga even emphasizes that mind influences the body more than the body influences the mind.

Effect of Yoga on Human Relationships

Our relationship with the person around brings to us joy and pain together. We are constantly seeking fulfillment through our friends, or family members and people at our work-place. When we practice Yoga, co-operation takes the place of competition. Instead of making constant and unreasonable demands from others we learn to give selfless love to others. While making friends, we learn to give greater importance to the inner qualities than to outer appearances. The sage Patanjali gives importance advice regarding our reaction in relationship. He says, ‘ Form friendship with those who are awake to the higher values of life and try to put them into practice. There is less likelihood of friction and misunderstandings in their company. For those who are in misery, we must have compassion. We should not be self-centered. We should feel happy in the progress and prosperity of others. There should be no shadow of envy or rivalry in our minds. Towards the wicked we should have indifference. It is not worth spending your precious energy – mental or emotional on their bad works. Being intolerant towards others and getting irritable unnecessarily spoils our mind, If we can be aware of our reactions towards others and develop a habit of giving positive response to even a negative situation, that is emotional development.

Effect of Yoga on Work

Work or employment should be seen as a joyous opportunity for self expression and growth. What do we see in the offices? Boredom, clock watching, politics, fights between workers and management! Our work should be seen in terms of what we can give to it rather than what we get from it. Good posture, deep breathing and gently stretching will help you to keep relaxed at work-place. Pausing for a moment and watching your breath immediately makes you relaxed. It is good to be creative in you work. Geeta says that he art of doing work in excellent way without expecting fruit is Yoga.

Effect of Yoga on attitudes, thinking and behaving

Everybody feels that he or she should become a happy and successful person. Yoga assures us that our dream can be fulfilled provided that we acquire certain attitudes and habits of thinking and living. The ancient wisdom can be tuned into some practical hints for joyous and effective living. Some of them are as follows:-

Let us out complain about our environment

Some people are not happy with their parents, their financial status, and social status.They are not happy about our physique, looks and brains. They always look at others,envy them and feel sad! Then think, Only if I had a mother like that... ‘or’ Had I been in the place of that scholar or that scholar or that champion! It is not healthy to complain about what we have got; it is good to think as to how can we make the best of it. Many great persons in the world fought against physical disabilities and adverse circumstances and became successful. Everyone of us is gifted in some way or the other. Let us find out our gift. It may not be academic intelligence, it may be social or other types of intelligence.

Self Development and Yoga

With books but we may be very good with machines, which is equally valuable. We may have a potential to become a singer, a painter or a stage- actor. Les us have a goal and decide steps to move towards it. Yogic techniques make our. Body, mind and intellect strong.

Let us train the body first

Yogasananas and surya namaskaras shake off our lethary and idleness. They bring fresh vigor to our body. They free us from tensions and diseases, so that we van focus our attention totally on our

goal. How do we train the body? Let us take care of our food. Let us avoid eating very less or eating unnecessarily. Select the food that agrees with us and brings harmony to our body.

Digestion of food, its assimilation in the body and excretion of unwanted stuff, must be regular.

Let us train our mind

Self education is very important in yoga. If we train our mind to become strong it will be strong. If we let it be weak like a pampered child, it will become weak and brittle. It would collapse at the smallest shock. Swami Vivekanand said that he wanted young men of iron muscles and steel nerves. Let us avoid all kinds of negative thoughts like envy, jealousy and narrow mindedness.

Some students do not exchange notes because they feel that somebody would 'steal' their knowledge! They forget that the more we give, the more our knowledge grows! Also, let us give up the ideas of dependence. There is no person or thing in the world without whom or without which it is impossible for us to live. Nothing is indispensable. There are persons, communities and nations who have rebuilt life from ashes.

Let us train our intellect

If we don't give challenging work to our intellect, it gets rusted, it loses its capacity to do mighty things. In fact we do not use our brain to the fullest extent if brain does not get enough exercise, it gets tired easily. Seeing dreams and exerting all our energies to fulfill them makes our intellect strong. Let us teach our intellect taking wise decision-making and staying firm with our decisions. Clarity in thinking and grit to stick to our decision is self-development. This way we build up our character. There is a beautiful saying : Watch your words. They form your thoughts. Watch your thoughts, they form your habits . Watch your destiny.

Therapeutic importance of Yogic practices

Asanas

Asanas can be used for release of physical stress resulted from day-to-day negative emotions of behavioral pattern. This will help to avoid Psychosomatic or psychological disorders like hypertension, gastric acidity , depression neurosis etc. The regular correct practice of Asanas also help to prevent constipation, arthritis, asthma, diabetes, obesity etc.

Pranayama

These are practices to control respiratory impulses which one of the main channels of the flow of the autonomic nerve currents. Pranayama have important role in prevention of the diseases. The various diseases caused by disturbed homeostatic state of autonomic nervous system like obesity. Hypertension, hyperthyroidism, diabetes, gastric acidity etc. Can be prevented by Nadishodhan Pranayama, Bhastrika Pranayama etc. The imbalanced State of Doshas caused Suryabhedan and Bhastrika Pranayamas. The intensity of psychosomatic ailments can be prevented by restoring the normal I rhythmic breathing.

Bandhas and Mudras

In these practices one tries to consciously control certain semi-voluntary and involuntary muscles in the body. These influence the activity of the autonomic nervous system which functions as a chole. These tones up the internal organs, decongest them and stimulate their health functioning.

Shatakarama

These are purificatory Processes usually classified into six divisions, each of which consists of many sub-sections. They bring in control over the autonomic nervous system.

Neti is an important means to develop resistance against environmental offending factors like temperature, dust , pollen grains, humidity and other particles to prevent the respiratory disorder , for example, the Neti in the evening by the laborer working at flour mills, cotton textiles mills, cotton textiles mills mines, busy roads, harvesting rains in the fields, libraries etc. can wash out the inhaled particles and thereby preventing their decay and decomposition in nasal passage and Pharynx for viral and bacterial infection . The use of nei helps also in development of resistance against seasonal change by using water of different temperature in Neti lota during the period of change of season as it would increase the adaptability of inner lining of nasal passage for vasoconstriction and dilution in response to temperature variation of environment. Similarly, one can prevent digestive disorders by the use of Shankhprakhshalana at time of start of new season, Basti once in a month , daily practice of Nauli etc. Case of dyspepsia, the Vaman Dhouti/Vyaghra Dhouti will be useful to prevent intensity of digestive disorder. The regular practice of Tratak and Kapalbhata can be used to prevent the eye and respiratory disorders respectively.

Meditation

It involves mental practice from initial withdrawal of the senses to the complete oblivion of the external environment. There are innumerable states and practices which could be included under this head. Meditation is a great tranquillizer. The regular practice of meditation by any of the various techniques, the inherent defense mechanism to fight with external physical, mental, emotional and environmental factors for causation of diseases can be developed. The meditation provides physical and mental resting pause to restore and revitalize the bodily organs for their normal functioning. Meditation practices have been widely used to counteract the day-today stress and strains of modern life. Therefore, the Meditation can be used for prevention of psychological and psychosomatic disorders like depression anxiety, neurosis, hypertension, asthma, arthritis, angina etc.

Yogic diet

According to the yogic concept of nutrition, food has been categorized as Sattvic (pure) , Rajadic (over-stimulating) and Tama sic (dull) with respect to its effect on the body and mind. Modern science emphasizes the importance of diet rich in micronutrients and low in fats and cholesterol for grater health attributes. The present investigation was carried out to examine how far the two concepts are similar and also their effects on physical and mental health. A database of nutrient contents of 110 cooked food items was cross-classified with their gunas as Sattvic, Rajasic and Tamasic, and their micronutrient density or fat density. Observations on daily diet by 24-h recall, blood levels of haemoglobin, lipids, superoxide dismutase (SOD), lipid peroxidation as MDA, and anxiety, patience and stess scores were recorded for 109 apparently healthy individuals. A significant correlation of yogic classification was found with micronutrient density ($r=0.533$, $P=0.0001$)

And fat density of food ($r=-0.51$, $P=0.0001$). In adults, dietary intake of micronutrients showed significant positive correlation ($r=0.31-0.7$) with Sattvic food intake. However, Rajasic food intake was correlated with only thiamin ($r=0.47$) and Tamsic food intake only with zinc ($r=0.23$) and iron ($r=0.3$). Correlation between Tamsic food intake and anxiety was statistically significant ($r=0.37$, $P=0.004$). Thus, Sattvic food was high in micronutrient density and low in fat content, while Tamasic food was low in micronutrient density and high in fat content. Diet showed significant impact on mental status of adults, supporting the diet-mind inter-relationship concept of yoga.

Laughter yoga

- What could be best possible medicine than ‘Laughter’! All over the world Laughter Yoga is becoming known and sought after. The fun and the health benefits are amazing, plus we all know that laughter just feels great! It’s easy to lead, anyone can do it, all ages, and all walks of life. Laughter is nature’s stressbuster. It lifts our spirits with a happy high that makes us feel good and improves our behavior towards others. Laughter therapy is gentle exercise. It fills your lungs and body with oxygen, deep-clears our breathing passages and exercises our lungs.
- When we laugh our bodies release a cocktail of hormones & chemicals that have startling positive effects on our system. Stress is reduced, blood pressure drops, depression is lifted, and our immune system is boosted. This laughter practice moves progressively from the ho ho, ha ha exercise to other types of simulated laughter. It is called as ‘laughter cocktail. This “cocktail” includes hearty laughter, greeting laughter, open-mouthed silent laughter, humming laughter, lion laughter (an adaptation of Lion Pose), and swinging laughter, with arm movement. Each laughter is sustained for up to 45 seconds, and followed with deep breathing exercises. Laughter exercises almost always lead to real laughter, especially when practiced in a group. Laughter yoga is one of the best stress management known so far.
- Many people might be surprised to think of laughter as a form of meditation. Not only is laughing meditation one of the simplest forms of meditation, but also it is a very powerful one. The physical act of laughing is one of the few actions involving the body, emotions, and the soul. When we laugh, we give ourselves over to the immediacy of the present moment. Practiced in the morning, laughing meditation can lend a joyful quality to the entire day. Practiced in the evening, laughing meditation is a potent relaxant that has been known to inspire pleasant dreams. Laughter also can help open our eyes to previously unnoticed absurdities that can make life seem less serious. At one point or the other everybody suffers from stress. Relationship demands, physical as well as mental health problems, pressure at workplaces, traffic snarls, meeting deadlines, growing-up tensions-

all of these conditions and situations are valid causes of stress. People have their own methods of stress management. In some people, stress-induced adverse feeling and anxieties tend to persist and intensify. Every one of us needs to master the art of fighting stress, and what could be best possible medicine than 'Laughter'. Humans were designed to laugh. Laughter is nature's stressbuster. It lifts our spirits with a happy high that makes us feel good and improves our behavior others. Just a few generations ago happy healthy humans spent 20 minutes a day or more in laughter. Now adult daily laughtime is down to 5 minutes or less in many countries. This is one of the worst aspects of 'modern life'.

- We all know that laughter makes us feel good. A regular 20 minute laughter session can have a profound impact on our health and wellbeing. Laughter therapy is gentle. It fills your lungs and body with oxygen, deep-clears your breathing passages and exercises your lungs. This is really is really important for people who don't get regular aerobic exercise.
- When we laugh our bodies release a cocktail of hormones & chemicals that have starting positive effects on our system. Stress is reduced, blood pressure drops, depression is lifted, your immune system is boosted & more. Western science is just starting to discover the great affects of laughter. Laughter Yoga combines laughter exercises and yoga breathing to give you the health benefits of hearty laughter. Laughter exercises almost always lead to real laughter, especially when practiced in a group. Laughter Yoga is one of the best stress management known so far.

Conclusion

- Indian tradition, Scientific research and clinical experience all point out that Yoga practices are probably the most important and effective self-help tools available to man. It appears that the Indian practitioners of psychotherapy, who have been looking for a conceptual framework and a set of procedures which are not alien but intimate to the Indian mind would definitely find an alternative in Yoga.
- The importance of Yoga is coming into light in the west in the comparative analysis of different systems by psychologists to find out meaningful answers to some problems of life. We seem to be very close to a behavior technology and self reliance in the domain of Yoga. The main principle of Yoga therapy is that it seems to establish the homeostasis in

the organism as a whole. As yet, however, it has not been established exactly how this is accomplished.

- But when proper investigation along scientific lines has been set up in several places throughout the world, Yoga therapy will be properly recognized as a valid form of treatment. The doors of Yoga therapy have already been knocked and opened up. Only earnest research and therapeutic pursuits by scientists and clinicians may perfect the ages old Yoga and make it more and more refined and suitable to people all over the world.

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To Study the Effect of Nada-Yoga Practice on Anxiety Level of Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to explore the effect of Nada yoga practice on the anxiety level of students. The nada yoga intervention spread for 60 days scheduled one session each day in the evening, for 15 minutes. The practice of nada yoga consisted of an integral approach of different type of Indian classical musical instruments played with the help of an Audio aid. A sample of 60 students selected through accidental sampling age ranged from 18-25 yrs who have similar level of anxiety divided into two group one experimental group and other control group each group consists of 30 subjects respectively. The pre-measurement of anxiety has been taken by both the group **for the similarities between the groups**, after this, researcher intervened nada yoga practice to the experimental group and control group did not perform any kind of this practice. After 60 days completion of the nada yoga for experimental and control groups post data for anxiety level has been taken with the help of same method. Result revealed a statistically significance difference between the experimental and control group anxiety level of the subjects. The finding suggests the beneficial effects of nada yoga practices for the management of anxiety level of the students.

Key words: Nada yoga, Anxiety, Musical Instruments

Introduction

The world is changing with incredible rapidly and established customs, tradition and values are changing with it. The major problem is the continuing adjustment that individual and groups must make to the rapid social change whether we like it or not. A great majority of people in metropolitan cities experience high anxiety. Every rich and successful person has to pay the price

for it as it affects not only their mental health but also their, physical health scenario. Our era has been called the Age of anxiety and anxiety manifestations are certainly widespread and protean” (*Cattell and Scheir, 1957*). In its usual sense, anxiety means that emotional state of the mind where an apprehension of danger or less or suffering is a prominent feature. About 18% Americans are affected by anxiety disorder. Anxiety is a physiological state characterized by cognitive, somatic, emotional and behavioral components (*Seligman, Walker and Rosenha, 2001*). Anxiety is often accompanied by physical sensations, such as heart palpation, nausea and chest pain, shortness of breath, stomach aches, or headache.

Nada yoga

Nada yoga is an Indian Healing Technique the most ancient and primitive human societies across the worked have recognized the power of sound vibrations as they affect the mind and the body.

fpRrkuUnrnkftRoklgtkuUnlEHkoA

nks'knq[k tjko;kf/k {kq/kkfunzkfooftZrAA -Swatmaram(2001)

In flouncing from Nada Sound get victory over fluctuation of mind. It arise bliss of mind and soul. Soul becomes free from Vatta, Pitta, Kapha and also form hunger, thirst, sleep, and form old age disorders, at the time of Nada in heart region. People who have full of pranic energy, because have very divine beauty. He becomes brave and his body spread divine smell everywhere and that yogi because free form all disease. The nada yoga sadhana is appropriate in the present era every one can do this practice in any condition. There are no barriers of cast, religion, sex, age, health etc. in practice. There are no need of rules and regulations. In modern life, which is fast, hectic and demanding, this nada yoga practice is most appropriate and useful. This practicea does not require any particular time it can be done whenever, an individual can do it. *Delmonte (2012)* reviewed the literature on meditation and anxiety reduction, and concluded that those who practice meditation regularly tend to show significant decreases in anxiety, although meditation does not appear to be more effective than other types of intervention, such as hypnosis. *Thompson, S. A. (2011)* found that the impact of group music therapy on anxiety, depression, quality of life and coping with women with breast cancer: a mixed method study. *Stern (2008)* completed his study with trait Anxiety Scale of spiel Berger's state-trait Anxiety Inventory was administered to an experimental group of thirty-seven subjects practicing the TM techniques and to a control group

of fifteen subjects not practicing TM. The mediators were found to be significantly less anxious. *Usry, J. (2006)* study shows the effect of music therapy relaxation techniques on the Stress and Anxiety Level of music and music therapy students and music and music Therapy Professionals. *KulshreshthaAsim (2006)* study shows the effect of nada yoga sadhana on psychological well-being and self-confidence the sample consist of 40 students, 20 girls & 20 boys from DevSanskritiVishvidyalaya, Gayatrikunj, Haridwar selected by quota sampling pre-post design. Result show that the positive affect of nada yoga on psychological well-being & self-confidence.

Due to anxiety many psychosomatic disorder evolved in which hypertension is most common disease. Somatically the body prepares the organic to deal with threat. Blood pressure and heart rate are increased. Our body system is directly and indirectly related form emotions and blood pressure is affect by emotions, such as fear or anger, but the effect tends to be short lived. When a person leads a life that is full of tensions anxiety, worry etc. Recent study shows that gives complete curative as well as preventive message for all psychosomatic disorder. In yogic service, there are many technique used for improving mental as well as physical health. In present study I have chosen the technique of Nada Yoga a technique of meditation.

Research methodology

- **Research Design-** In the present study experimental-control research design has been used.
- **Sample and Sampling method-**
- A sample of 60 students selected through accidental age ranged from 18-25 yrs who have similar level of anxiety divided into two group one experimental group and other control group each group consists of 30 subjects respectively.
- **Variables-**
- **Independent variable-**Nada yoga practice
- **Dependent Variable-**Anxiety level
- **Tools used-**

Anxiety Measurement Scale-

The scale is used in the present study is a popular anxiety measurement scale SCAT (Sinha's Comprehensive Test) constructed by A.K.P.Sinha and L.N.K.Sinha in 1973.

Technique used for nada yoga in the study

The technique used in the present study is a nada yoga practice which has been prepared by AkhilVishwaGayatriPariwar, Shantikunj, Haridwar in an audio form. The practice of nada yoga started with the blowing of sea shell (Shankh) after this voice there are some instructions related with the nada yoga in the voice of founder patron of this institution Mata Bhagwatidevi for the maximum benefits of nada yoga. After this the voice of different classical instruments begins at different levels of rhythms. With different rhythms of the voice of the instruments there are effects occurs at the level of physiological and psychological levels of the practioners.

Hypothesis

The null hypothesis has been form for the study

1- There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety among Nada yoga practitioners and non-practitioners.

Result and interpretation of the result

Hypothesis 1:“There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety of naad yoga practitioners and non- practitioners”.

Table -1 Showing of anxiety result

Group	Mean	S.D.	N		SE _D	t-value	Df	Sig. level
			N1	N2				
Nada yoga practitioner	56.74	5.1	30	30	0.803	13.39	58	0.01
Nada yoga non-practitioner	72	3.59						

Table- 1 depicts the t-value 13.39 is significant at 0.01 level of confidence this indicates that the null hypothesis, “There is no significant difference in the level of anxiety of naad yoga practitioners and non- practitioners” has been rejected hence there is difference between anxiety level of nada yoga practitioners and non-practitioners.

Interpretation and discussion

The obtained data shows that Nada Yoga significantly reduces Anxiety level of the students who were practicing the practice of nada yoga. Result shows a significant difference between the two means at the 0.01 level of significance. Throughout the ages, sound and music, originally a highly developed science in the ancient mystery schools, have been used as vehicles for healing. This healing was based on concepts of life that recognized vibration as the fundamental creative force. “Nada Yoga” is the classical term for the Yoga of Sound in the Hindu tradition. It is a stream of sacred sound that embraces Hatha Yoga, the occult linguistics of Tantra, and the spirituality of classical Indian music. By including the non-linguistic element of music, Nada Brahman augments the Shabda-Brahman of the Vedic tradition, as well as the differentiation of energy in the chakras discovered by the Tantrics. “Certain studies have also found unique patterns of blood hormone level and blood flow to a number of organ including brain (*Jevning& O Halloran 1984*) increased level of gamma amino butyric acid (**GABA**), melatonin, and dehydroepiandrosterone sulfate (**DHEAs**) have been reported (**Glaser et al. 1992, Elias & Wilson 1995**)”. Hypothesize that meditation produces its anxious tic effects by promoting GABA action in specific areas of the brain. So in the conclusion it may be conclude that the nada yoga practice is effective tool to reduce the level of anxiety for the students.

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A Pilot Study of the Effect of Yajna on the Level of Stress and Anxiety

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Abstract

Yajna is the most ancient ritual connecting human beings with the divine essence. It is not merely a fire sacrifice, but a combination of esoteric and exoteric elements to propitiate the cosmic energies. The spirit inherent in Yajna is service and sacrifice as a way of life. Yagyopathy is an ancient Indian ritual moulded according to modern era needs, which helps in the management of holistic health. It's a therapeutic approach helpful in mental disorders. A study conducted on 4 subjects for 30 days on the levels of stress and anxiety showed significant improvement. Their stress and anxiety levels were reduced to normal.

Keywords - Yajna healing, Yagyopathy

Introduction

The Bhopal Tragedy of December 2, 1984, caused by the leak of Methyl Isocyanide poisonous gas from the union Carbide factory killed 16000 and maimed and incapacitated many more. In the midst of this horrendous occurrence, a miracle happened which made the researchers all over the world sit up and think. Among the population of the city four or five families living near the railway station remained unaffected by the pernicious gas. Investigations were done and it came to the conclusion that the surviving families were in the habit of practicing Yajna in the form of 'agnihotra'.

It is a common experience that if an individual eats a red chilly then that person alone would be sneezing under its influence. But if the same chilly is put in the fire then the resultant air can cause many hundred people to sneeze. Similar is the principle of Yagyopathy. Also, it is a well-known fact that the substances when taken in their vapor or gaseous form through the nostrils have much greater efficacy – many hundred times more. And, the same quantity of substance can benefit a much larger population. The sublimated vital elements and herbal medicines inhaled in

Yagyopathy it has a direct healing effect on brain-born (neurological and psychological) diseases and complexities.

Previous research

Yagyopathy has been done previously on diseases like Pulmonary Tuberculosis by Meenakshi Raghuvanshi who found significant improvement of Yagyopathic Herbal Treatment. Moreover, there are many mental health benefits of Yagyopathy.

Data and methods

With the help of accidental sampling method 4 subjects were taken and their stress and anxiety levels are measured with the help of GSR (Biofeedback) and Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety Test respectively. The subjects were performed Yagyopathy daily during sunrise for continuous 30 days.

(Sinha's Comprehensive Anxiety Test)

Names/Score	PRE	POST
1.ROSHNI BANSAL	25	18
2.PAYAL SINGHAL	53	23
3.RAJURAM	18	2
4.HARSHADEEP DEWANGAN	15	10

Galvanic Skin Response (GSR) readings of actual and basal value before and after the Yagyopathy.

PERIOD	PRE			POST		
	Basal value	Actual Value	Difference (actual-basal)	Basal value	Actual Value	Difference (actual-basal)
1.ROSHNI BANSAL	173	253	80	173	250	77
2.PAYAL SINGHAL	173	343	170	171	208	37

3.RAJURAM	173	430	257	175	300	125
4.HARSHADEEP DEWANGAN	173	509	336	177	476	299

Procedure

- Pavitrakarāṇam: Some water is taken on left palm and cover it with the right one. After the mantra has been chanted sprinkle this water on your head and all over yourself.
- Âchamanam: For a yajna, unison of speech, mind and anatahkaraṇa are essential. With the pronouncing of each mantra one acamana is taken.

om amratopastaraṇamasi svaha ||1||

om amritapidhanamasi svaha ||2||

om satya yasah sīrmayi, sirhih sīrayatam svaha ||3||

Chandanadharaṇam: Sandalwood paste is applied on the forehead as a reminder of the constant need of keeping our minds and thoughts cool, calm and fragrant.and the sandalwood paste should be applied together

- Worshipping the Kalaia: The kalaia is a symbol of the entire universe. All the gods in their microcosmic and macrocosmic forms are present in this symbolic form of the universe. with the folded hand kalash is worshipped

- Deepa Pujanam: Deepak is lighten while chanting the mantras. Devavahanam(Invocation of Gods): All deities all prayed to guide us to the righteous path through this yajna therapy.

- Agnisthapanam: The yajna-fire is considered to represent Brahma and with this belief, the fire is placed on the dais and life is infused in it through the medium of mantras and with the same feelings the act of igniting the fire is accomplished.

- Âjyahuti: At the beginning of the yajna, 7 offerings of ghee are given to the fire together with the chanting of seven mantras.

- Mantrahutih

oSuryagayatri mantrahuti(12 times)

oChandragayatri mantrahuti(12 times)

oMahamritynjay mantrahuti(3)

- Svistakrita–homa: In this act some sweetmeat is offered. This indicates a soft and sweet personality.
- Purñahuti: Taking a bit of ‘s³magr^o’ in the hand, everyone should stand up and with the utterance of the word ‘sv³h³’ should offer it to the fire together with two resolutions each for giving up a bad habit and inculcating a good one.
- Ghiatavaghrañam: The drops of ghee which are put in the vessel of water after each offering of ghee get coagulated in the water. This vessel should be taken around amongst the gathering and each one should dip the fingers of his right hand in this coagulated ghee and rub it in both palms. While saying the mantra both hands should be so placed near the yajóá kuòÃa as if they are warmed by the fire. This receiving of the ghee is a symbol of the blessing of gods for those who wish to create an atmosphere where in their lives are totally encompassed by the yajóá message, those whose eyes are filled with it, whose ears are always resounding with its voice, whose tongues are forever speaking about it and whose nose can always get the smell of divinity of the sacred ritual.
- Bhasmadharañam: The ashes of the yajna-fire are smeared on the back of the vessel and taken with the middle finger and put wherever indicated by the mantra.
- Kshama Prarthana: The ritual of asking forgiveness at the end of a yajóá is done leads to a habit of such behaviour and attitude
- Subhakamana: This mantra invokes the blessings of the gods for the well-being of all and wishes that we should have no ill-feelings towards anyone nor wish anyone any harm.

sarve bhavantu sukhinah, sarve santu niramayah I
sarve bhadrañi pasyantu, ma kaïcid dukkhamapnuyat II

- Shanti – Abhisinchanam: The water of the kalash should be sprinkled on all those present in the chamber
- Suryarghyadanam: The devotee prays in this ritual that may his negative thoughts come in contact with the sun god and be purified. While facing the Sun, the water of the kalaïa should slowly be let out like a stream and be collected in a vessel kept below.

- Visarjanam: Together with folded hands, farewell is given to all the deities there with chanting mantra which means that we may receive such grace and blessings of gods over and over again.
- Pranayama: Deep inhalation and exhalation is done with the feeling positive thoughts and giving out negative thoughts while exhalation.

Results

Anxiety

P value and statistical significance

The two-tailed P value equals 0.0842

By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not quite statistically significant.

Confidence interval

The mean of Pre minus Post equals 14.50

95% confidence interval of this difference: From -3.62 to 32.62

Intermediate values used in calculations:

$$t = 2.5467$$

$$df = 3$$

$$\text{standard error of difference} = 5.694$$

Significant between 0.05 and 0.025

Group	Pre	Post
Mean	27.75	13.25
SD	17.35	9.22
SEM	8.67	4.61
N	4	4

STRESS

P value and statistical significance

The two-tailed P value equals 0.1054

By conventional criteria, this difference is considered to be not statistically significant.

Confidence interval:

The mean of Pre minus Post equals 76.25

95% confidence interval of this difference: From -29.44 to 181.94

Intermediate values used in calculations:

$t = 2.2960$

$df = 3$

standard error of difference = 33.210

Group	Pre	Post
Mean	210.75	134.50
SD	110.43	115.42
SEM	55.21	57.71
N	4	4

Significant between 0.10 and 0.05

The subjects show changes in the anxiety level after 30 days of Yagyopathy therapy. This signifies that the deep breathing during the Yagyopathy therapy helped the subjects to overcome their anxiety level.

The deep inhalation and positive affirmation during each step of the Yajna therapy or Yagyopathy helped the subjects to enhance mental health. There were no side-effects seen in between the Therapy. Moreover, this can equivalently be treated on individual as well as group. The duration of therapy was almost 30-35minutes in each session.

The Galvanic Skin Response was also reduced after the completion of the therapy. This proves the hypotheses that Yagyopathy is beneficial for reducing stress and anxiety.

Conclusion

Yagyopathy is a very effective drugless therapy with no side effects. This therapy can be applied on any kind of disease whether somatic or psychic or somatopsychic or psychosomatic. Also, It is easy to perform anywhere in a closed room. The Yagyopathy treatment was done following the procedures helped the subjects to be positive and the sublimated herbs helped to restructure the wires of mind leading to improved mental health. Yagyopathy , therefore , with mantra, timing and havan samagri acts as an holistic approach to be healthy.

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Psychology behind the Indian Desserts – A Conceptual Study

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Abstract

Desserts have a special room in festivals, celebrations, occasions, gatherings, and events. It may be a personal or professional achievement that is cherished with sharing of various desserts. In India, the dessert is not just an appetizer or sweet tastes but a sign of pleasant feeling that includes joy, care, love, affection, compassion, and so on. It is being shared among family, friends, relatives, neighbors, near and dear ones to mark almost every aspect of life like Childbirth, Birthday, Anniversary, Ritual, Worship, Festival, etc. Although, there are hundreds of desserts but has a special recognition as per the festive. Therefore, the connectivity of Indian desserts with positive emotions is worth considering.

Keywords: Indian desserts, Pleasant feeling, Positive emotions

India is the land of rich heritage with multiple religions, culture, and traditions. The Vedic system, Spirituality, Hospitality, Monuments, Carvings, Dance, Music, Arts, Language, Clothing, Cuisine, Festivals, Tours, add a unique feature. Indians are known for their exceptional attributes. The greeting to the guest, “*Atithi Devo Bhava*” that means "Guest is God". This generosity is put forwarded through many ways, but the foremost is by presenting food. Sharing of food is assumed as a sense of care to the person. ‘Annadaan’ (Donation of food) is meant to be one of the biggest donations in Indian culture. In western countries, people don’t feel like having food together (workplace) or exchange their foodstuff whereas, in India presenting and exchange of food is a part of their habit. At the times where a person is not acquainted, a new friend, new neighbor, a new colleague, they are welcomed by offering home cooked food along with the dessert (Higgs, 2008; Settembre, 2017). This is concerned with the influence of senses that is smell, vision, audition, and touch on taste. This concept and sense of contentment make food psychology enormously fascinating.

Dessert is a mandatory part of Indian cuisine. In most of the families, it is been in taken on daily basis. It is not eaten to satisfy one's taste buds but as a symbol of warm feeling. A study reports that people who like sweets are more likely to be enjoyable, amiable, helpful and kindhearted (noble feelings) than people who prefer other tastes, like salty, bitter or spicy foods. Another study suggests that there is a robust link between sweet tastes and pro-social behavior. The findings reveal that metaphors lead to exclusive and provocative predictions about people's behaviors and personality traits (Robinson et al, 2013).

The chief ingredients in dessert are sugar as the symbol of sweetness in life, dry fruits as happiness, and saffron as purity. Thus in temples sweets are offered to Gods and Goddesses and that is distributed among the devotees as *Prashad* to rebuild the divine qualities. There are some prominent 56 desserts (*Chappan Bhog*) that are offered with dedication. In ancient times people use to have meals sitting on the ground with crossed legs (At homes and parties too) with a change of phase, now in modern times people have their party foodstuff in buffets. The sitting and serving stalls have revised but the unchanged habit is sharing sweets. Even though desserts are plated along with the other menu but it is very commonly seen is the person serving self handedly and presenting it additionally. This is extra love and compassion for one another. It is said as *Manuhar* (delight) dear ones.

Indian desserts are appreciated in the worldwide. The huge variety of sweets is only seen here when compared to other countries, as they have only cakes and puddings. In any event, people in the west have an option with various flavors into it. On the other side, in India there are sweetstuffs for each festival, the festival of colors (Holi) bring *Gujia*, Birthday of Lord Ganesha (Ganesh Utsav) get *Modak*, the festival of kites (Sankranti) provide *Tilli laddu*, the festival of lights (Diwali) bring *Burfi* and so on. Even there are special desserts for each season like Halwa for winters, and Kulfi for summers. This brings joyous vibes all around.

Each state of India has its own specification in the varieties of desserts. Khapse of Arunachal Pradesh, Narikol of Assam, Chakhao Kheer of Manipur, Shufta of Jammu & Kashmir, Pukhleim of Meghalaya, Koat Pitha of Nagaland, Chhangban Leh Kurtai of Mizoram, Bal Mithai of Uttarakhand, Sandesh and Rosagulla of West Bengal, Ghewar and Churma of Rajasthan, Shrikhand and Mohnthaal of Gujrat, Besan Laddu and Balushahi of Uttar Pradesh, Gond ke ladoo of Haryana, Babroo of Himachal Pradesh, Pinni of Punjab, Thekua and Khaja of Bihar, Anarsa of

Jharkhand, Chhena Poda of Odisha, Khoya Jalebi and Mawa Bati of Madhya Pradesh, Bebinca of Goa, Santra Burfi and Puran Poli of Maharashtra, Payasam and Paniyaram of Telangana State, Kozhakattai, Pongal and Senni Mittai of Tamilnadu, Khubani ka meetha and Kajikayalu of Andhra Pradesh, Obbattu of Karnataka, Ilayappam of Kerala (Chaudhary, 2015; Sharell, 2018). It may be diverse states and dissimilar desserts but one thing common i.e. Love, Joy, Care, Empathy, Kindness, Compassion, Gratitude (positive emotions) attached to it (Rom & Parrot, 1996). The craze for desserts is also shown in many of the Bollywood films. The blockbuster film Jodha Akbar sets the best example for the hospitality of Royal Rajasthan (A State in North India) with the dialogues: “*Lo sa, Jimo sa*”, “*hum baati baatkar khate hai*”, “*Navratna se thaal sajayo pitodo ko saag rachayo, ghewar laadu our churma...*”

Conclusion

Desserts cover a wide range of importance in Indian cuisine and offered to please someone soon. These are the indication of Love, Joy, Care, Empathy, Kindness, Compassion, Gratitude (positive emotions) (Rom & Parrot, 1996). Advertisement in Indian television “*Achi shuruat ke liye kuch meetha ho jaaye*” that means “*For a good start lets have some sweet dish*” shows the psychology of foodstuff among the Indian population.

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Traditional Herbal Recipe for New Mothers

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Abstract

Traditional herbal recipe for new moms that purpose more than enough health profits in compression of medicine. Baby takes everything it need from its mother via the placenta it is healthy a better option. after a normal delivery to rebuild their strength and also to pass on healthy nutrients to the infant through nursing mother. It relief from pain and provide relaxes. Sonth and gond ke ladoo recipe it is useful in cold and cuff, strong bone it also relief joint pain increase hemoglobin in human body. it gives heat and energy to the body they include essential spacial ingredient and antioxidant. These sources play an important role to get healthy muscle and tissues, enhance immunity level as well as it useful in minimizing the risk of heart disease.

Key Words - Herbal recipe, New Mothers, Gond Laddu

Introduction

Traditional recipe for new mother it helps to recover body after delivery. Ayurvedic recipe for post delivery care and nursing mother. New mother need spacial nutrients to recover from birth and build up their reserves, especially if nurse their baby. Because baby takes everything it needs from its mother Via the placenta.

Homemade herbal traditional recipe so much beneficial for recovery health after child birth. this type of recipe used in rural areas mostly women used recipe or include daily part of diet. Fibers helps your poor traumatized internal system recover more quickly and get things back to normal. Because pulse, it does burn calories, for those of us insecure about losing the baby weight. So don't have feel guilty about not exercising for a while healthy diet and hydration also helps keep you healthy.

This type of recipe made by the older women like the grandmothers, mother in-laws used to give this recipe to mother after a normal delivery to rebuild their strength and also pass on healthy nutrition to the infant through nursing mother.

Objective

The main objective of herbal and traditional recipe is to improve the immuno – modulatory activities. To provide the better lactation for new born. Also, to enhance the complete healthy state of a new mother. And the main thing is that, it is free from side effects and harmful effects of supplements provide pharmaceutical companies.

Need of the study

- In the modern time, we are running for western world. Our society is not following our traditional recipe. There is a intense need to be aware of our traditions and culture. In ancient era the indian traditional recipe had a beneficially effect on health of everyone.
- All the recipe which I have mentioned in this article are used in our villages by the our for-father. These all recipes include the complete health supplements for new born and the mother.
- The supplements prescribed by doctors are mostly made up of waste and harmful material Ex - mostly prescribed during pregnancy by gyanecolo gist is made up of ground nute peel extracted waste.
- And our families spend a lot on these so humble request to all to make aware about these not only to woman's but the whole society. Move towards traditional recipe to maintain health as well as wealth.

Names of the Herbal dishes

- South and gond ke ladoo
- Achwani
- Panjiri

- Ajwain ladoo
- Haldi ka Halwa
- Fenugreek seeds halwa

Why new mother need these food

Need of this type of food its helps regain the energy levels and passes the nutrients to the baby through mother milk. Nutrients help fight postpartum depression. Boosts immunity and helps keep away the cold in winter. relief back pain maintain bone density also help to buildup stamina in mothers. All the hubs work to induce milk production (lactation). Ajwain helps to bring the complete outflow of menses.

- Cumin seeds help an easy lactation periods I.e, it is used in most preparations for new mothers.
- Turmeric is the best healer. It is work to fight against pain, bodyache, and small internal wounds. Also act as antibacterial, anti fungal so it is the best to give a newly mother.
- Gond (gum) it is the best and authentic hub to treat women aliment. It work as pain killer in mother body. As after delivery there is excess back pain bodyache, menstrual weakness. On which gum- resins act as a medicine. And helps to recover fast.
- Jaggery after delivery there is huge blood loss which will lead to anemic, jaggery has very good property to increase hemoglobin and blood level in body. So it is used in many preparations and which are given to a newly mother.
- Almonds are a very good sources of vitamin A, E and folic acids. It is also given even during pregnancy to avoid heart burn. Also increase the bone developed and memory of new born too.
- Dry dates rich sources of vitamin A, b₁, b₂, and fiber. It also gives calcium, amino acids, iron, sulfur, magnesium, manganese, copper, phosphorous and potassium. So it is widely used as food for new mother.

- Makhana good source of protein carbohydrates, fiber, magnesium, potassium, phosphorous, zinc. It enhances immuno-modulatory activities and also acts as antioxidants. Which helps the mother skin to recover and glow.
- Dry ginger powder also known as sonth; take with food. Ginger offers health benefits, including anti-inflammation effects, and can also be found in health food stores.

Real Experience Testimonies:

- Practically I have used this recipe it is very useful for our body during after pregnancy. It cures full bodyache it also improves lactation. Achwani is traditional recipe for new moms that purpose more than enough health profits in compression of medicine it is healthy a better option. It relieves from pain and provides relaxation. (Mrs Mamta Devi Aurangabad, Bihar)
- Practically I have used this sonth and gond ke ladoo recipe it is useful in cold and cough, strong bones it also relieves joint pain increases hemoglobin in human body. It gives heat and energy to the body they include essential spices ingredients and antioxidants. These sources play an important role to get healthy muscles and tissues, enhance immunity level as well as it is useful in minimizing the risk of heart disease. (Mrs Ranjita Sahu Nawapara, Raipur)
- It has no side effect on body it is used in practical life. It provides energy to body after delivery it should be taken for one week or recover the losses from the body during delivery. Herbal recipe essential after pregnancy can help body to concentrate, fight against diseases even help to maintain a fit body and balance weight. (Mrs Rita Gupta Sumbhalpur Odisha)
- The herbal traditional recipe used in practical life. It provides better lactation for newborn baby makes their bones strong, it also relieves joint pain and protects both mother or child from the harmful diseases. (Mrs Anita Devi Aurangabad Bihar)

Sonth Ke Ladoo Recipe

A healthy and long lasting ladoo recipe that is prepared with whole wheat flour, dry ginger powder, gond, ghee, jaggery and assorted nuts- Makes a great mid morning snack

Sweets can be indulgent and healthy at the same time. That is the best part of some Indian sweets and Whole Wheat Sonth Ke Ladoo falls under that category. Made from dry ginger powder (sonth), whole wheat , mastic gum(gond), desi ghee(clarified butter), jaggery, nuts and dried coconut, these ladoos are packed with flavours and nutrients.

This ladoo can be given to new mothers to help them with bringing their energy levels back up and assists the mother with lactating better.

Whole Wheat Sonth Ke Ladoos are usually made and eaten during the winter season to provide warmth to the body.

Ingredients

- 1 cup Whole Wheat Flour
- 1/4 cup Dry ginger powder, (sonth)
- 3/4 cup Jaggery
- 1/3 cup Gond (natural gum)
- 1/2 cup Dry coconut (kopra), grated
- 1/2 cup Mixed nuts, almonds, cashews and pistachios
- 1/3 cup ghee

How to make Sonth Ka Ladoo Recipe

- To begin with Whole Wheat Sonth Ke Ladoo, heat 1 tablespoon ghee in a heavy pan add gond and fry it on low flame until it puffs up and turns slightly brown in colour.
- Remove from pan and transfer to a plate.
- Add remaining ghee into the same pan. Roast vivatta whole wheat flour on low flame until a nice aroma from the flour is released and ghee separates from the flour. Remove it into a wide bowl.
- Add ginger powder and roast for about a minute or until the powder releases nice aroma. Remove from pan and add into the bowl containing whole wheat flour.
- Next dry roast grated dry coconut for a minute and then transfer into the wheat flour bowl.

- Add the broken jaggery pieces into the same pan and heat it until melted. Once fully melted filter it to remove any impurities. Pour the filtered jaggery syrup into the whole wheat flour bowl.
- Grind almonds and cashews into coarse powder and chop the pistachios. Add all the nuts into the bowl.
- Crush roasted gond (mastic gum) into very small pieces. Add it to the bowl as well.
- Mix all the ingredients well. Wait until heat reduces to bearable amount to touch. Make lemon sized balls and shape them into round shapes.
- Store Sonth Ke Ladoo Recipe in airtight container, as they stay good for about 3 to 4 months.

Fenugreek seeds halwa :

This is one traditionally prepared delicacy, which is enjoyed by new mothers but also other family members, due to its yummy taste and nutritional values. Usually the utter name of fenugreek seeds makes people frown due to its bitter taste, but I bet on this you are just going to love this.

Ingredients:

1. Fenugreek seeds – 100 gms
2. Jaggery – 250 gms
3. Freshly grated coconut – 1 big coconut
4. Ahaliv (Garden cress) – 2tbsp
5. Cardamom powder – 1/2tsp
6. Roasted chopped almonds – 10-12
7. Poppy seeds roasted – 1 tbsp
8. Ghee – 1tbsp

Preparation:

Soak Fenugreek seeds in water for a day, drain the excess water and allow it to sprout. once sprouted, cook them well in minimal water, make sure that water is evaporated completely. Now

add jaggery, ghee and grated coconut to it. stir occasionally to avoid sticking to pan till the mixture becomes dry and starts leaving ghee on its side. Now add chopped almonds, cardamom powder, ahaliv seeds and roasted poppy seeds and mix well. You can also add black currants to it.

Fenugreek halwa apart from being tasty, is very nutritious. It is good for lactation, strengthens bones, good for backache especially after delivery. It also helps to regain the normal size of the uterus, pacifies vata dosha. Normal individuals can enjoy this halwa in winters to strengthen the bones.

Achwani is suitable for new mother post pregnancy after normal delivery.

Ingredients:-

Sugar -1/2 kg

Pure Desi Ghee (Clarified Butter) - 1/2 kg

Chaar Maghaz (Mixed Melon seed) 250 gm

Chaar Maghaz is a combination of four nuts/seeds: Cucumber seeds, Cantaloupe Seeds, Water melon seeds and Pumpkin seeds in equal quantities.

Dried coconut -155 gm

Raisins 125

Almonds 250 gm

Munaqqa/Munakka (Dried Grapes/Sultanas) 125 gm

Ilaichi (Green Cardamoms) 10

Milk - 1 cup

Drinking Water -1/2 glass

Cooking Method:

- Wash Munaqqa/Munakka thoroughly. Make a slit in each munaqqa and pit them by taking the seed out of it. Discard the seeds. Set the pitted Munaqqa aside.
- Dice the dry coconut or chop finely.

- In a grinder, pour half a glass of drinking water. Add Almonds, Chaar Maghaz and Munaqqa and grind in to a smooth paste.
- In a separate saucepan, heat the desi ghee (clarified butter) on medium-low flame. Pop open the ilaichi (Green Cardamom) pods and add to the ghee. Fry until light golden brown and take them out on an absorbing paper.
- After taking out the ilaichi, add your ground paste into the ghee. Cook on low flame for five minutes.
- Add raisins and dried coconut to the sauce pan and slowly cook on low flame until all the water has evaporated. Keep stirring every few minutes so that it doesn't stick to the bottom of the pan (we don't wanna burn anything).
- When all the water has dried up, add all the sugar and cook until all the water of the sugar also evaporates.
- It will start to look like a halwa. And your achwani is ready.
- Store in an air tight clean/sterilized jar. You can refrigerate it for 2 weeks.

Directions (How to Use): Take 1 cup of warm milk and add 1 tablespoon of Achwani to it. Mix well and consume once every day.

Caution: Achwani may not be taken after a cesarean/ c-section unfortunately. Discuss with your doctor first before starting anything.

Conclusion - Over all the data interpretations proof herbal recipe trends in Indian culture are used in practical and important for new mother because beneficially for body, it helps to fight against diseases, better lactation for new born baby. It is free from side effect and harmful effects. It helps to promote circulatory and lymphatic flow in the body. Traditional recipe had a positive impact on health of everyone.

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The Concept of Diet & Spiritual Evolution in Ayurveda & Shrimadbhagwadgeeta

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Abstract

According to Ayurveda; the knowledge of life, life is a journey and our vehicle is equipped with forces of the body, mind and soul, which carries us towards the ultimate goal of life. The diet plays an important role to go through this journey successfully. According to Brihadayagnavalkya Smriti, that food which comes in front should be considered as the very ambrosia of the gods and then eaten, as if an oblation is done to the fire of life (within oneself). This would remove all diseases and sins.

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Even in Ayurveda, Acharya Charaka explains very lucidly that , Whatever is beneficial to worldly life, whatever pertains to the vedic practices leading to heaven and whatever action leads to spiritual salvation- all of these are said to be established ultimately in food.

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The present paper is an attempt to explain how the awareness full approach regarding diet is having foremost importance for maintaining health at physical and mental level for the balanced approach in life and also for the evolution of human consciousness in Ayurveda and Shrimadbhagwadgeeta.

Keywords: Ayurveda, Spirituality, Shrimadbhagwadgeeta, diet, mental health, spiritual evolution.

Introduction: Diet (from Greek – the manner of living) is what we eat. Diet provides us with nutrition. Nutrition is the process by which body utilizes food for growth, maintenance and repair. Proper diet can treat diseases – food is medicine when consumed properly. Food choices make a huge impact on how you feel today, tomorrow and what the future holds in terms of promoting and maintaining good health. If improper, diet can cause diseases. The build-up of digestive toxins is the root cause of most disorders. What you choose to eat, and what you choose not to eat, are factors in warding off many leading chronic illnesses and diseases. So it is undeniable that a well-balanced diet goes hand in hand with a healthy lifestyle.

The ancient science of life : Ayurveda , having the purpose of health preservation and disease elimination , has given very prime importance to three pillars of life : Ahaar: food, Nindra: Sleep, Brahamcharya: .

The diet is the root of a living being.

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The key to proper digestion and metabolism of food lies in simple sutra of “*Jeerne hitam mitamβ¼/4 th.ksZ fgre fera½/2-* This means for proper food assimilation we have to follow three simple rules:

1. Food should be taken after digestion of previous meal.
2. Only beneficial food should be taken. 3. Only limited quantity of food should be taken.

The state of mind towards the food has also mentioned in Charak Samhita for the maintenance of health.

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Means. One should not consume food either with lustfulness or ignorance. One should scrutinize it well and then eat what is wholesome as body originates from the food.

The Ayurveda concept of Food and Spiritual evolution :

The lot of importance is attached to food and diet as it is the root cause of health. Food and water are like *Samidha* (holy firewood) offered in a Yajna to internal fire.

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The life of all living beings is food hence the whole world is dependent on food and running after food. The complexion, gracefulness, good voice, long life, understanding, happiness, growth, strength, intelligence, are all established in food. Whatever is beneficial to worldly life, whatever pertains to the vedic practices leading to heaven and whatever action leads to spiritual salvation- all of these are said to be established ultimately in food.

THE FOOD: HOLISTIC AYURVEDA APPROACH

This sutra explains very clearly that all the dimensions of physical, mental and spiritual health have their roots in creation of awareness about the food.

Rules of Diet and Dietetics in Ayurveda:

The Ayurveda has explained very clearly about the rules of diet and dietary habits for the preservation of health. One should be very vigilant about the quality, quantity, proportion, purity, timing, environment etc. Lust and ignorance about the diet is harmful for the body.

- **Quality:** The food should contains all kinds of tastes, soothing, compatible,uncontaminated, unadulterated, warm, fresh, acceptable and healthy.(Su. Chi. 46/459)
- **Quantity:** It should depend upon the intensity of Agni in the form of Hunger. Hunger indicates that the previously ingested food is digested. Heavy things should not be consumed further on feeling of half fullness of stomach. 1/3 of stomach should be filled with solid food, 1/3 with liquids and 1/3 should be left empty.(A. H. Su. 8/2)
- **Proportion:** Proportion of different Rasas and preparations is indicated according to the seasonal variations, the profession of the individual and geographical situation.
- **Timing :**The interval between the intake of food should not be less than three hours. Meals should be earlier in the winter months and later in the summer months.
- **Environment:** Food should be taken with clean hands, in clean vessels and quiet atmosphere with solemn mind. It should be warm and compatible. The same should be consumed with concentration, but never hurried or lazily. Food should never be criticised. It should be prepared and served by people who maintain cleanliness and have affinity. Before taking food one should see that other persons at home and pets also consumed food.
- So, Ayurveda takes cooking and eating as a very auspicious and significant activity of our life and explains that diet should be nurturing in quality, quantity and timing. The proportion should vary according to the Agni: the digestive capacity. It should be healthy,clean and consumed in congenial environment.

The Shrimadbhagwadgeeta concept of Food and Spiritual evolution : Trigunas, and diet

In the philosophy of Yoga, all matter in the universe arises from the fundamental “substance” called Prakriti. Prakriti is beginningless and endless, from which the three primary gunas (qualities) emerge creating the essential aspects of all nature in the universe. These three gunas are called tamas (darkness), rajas (activity), and sattva (beingness). All the three gunas are inherent in all living and non-living beings and surroundings, but vary in their relative quantities. Humans have the unique ability to consciously alter the levels of the gunas in our bodies and minds. The gunas

cannot be separated or removed in oneself, but can be consciously affected so that they would increase or decrease in amount. A guna can be affected in amount through the complex influence of external environment, lifestyle, thoughts and actions. Since food consumed has a major effect on the body and the mind, depending on which guna food adheres to, diet can either promote healthy mind that is pure and calm or cause an agitated mind. A clear, pure, and reflective mind is essential to self-enquiry, which leads to Self-Realization, while an agitated person will find it difficult to sit quietly and meditate.

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Threefold is the faith of the embodied, which is inherent in their nature—the Sattwic (pure), the Rajasic (passionate), and the Tamasic (dark). (17-2)

Tamas is a state of darkness, inertia, inactivity and evil. Tamas is caused by ignorance and deludes all beings from their spiritual truths. To reduce tamas avoid tamasic foods, over sleeping, over eating, inactivity, passivity and fearful situations. Tamasic foods include heavy meats, and foods that are spoiled, chemically treated, processed or refined.

That which is stale, tasteless, putrid, rotten and impure refuse, is the food liked by the Tamasic. (17-10)

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Rajas is a state of energy, passion, action, change and movement. The nature of rajas is of attraction, longing and attachment. Rajas strongly binds us to the fruits of our work. To reduce rajas avoid rajasic foods, over exercising, over work, loud music, excessive thinking and consuming excessive material goods. Rajasic foods include fried foods, spicy foods, and stimulants.

dV~oEyyo.k vR;q".k rh{k #k fonkfgu%|

vkgkjk jktLL;s''Vk nq%[k'kksdke;çnk ||¼Jh enHkxon~xhrc f%o/<½

The foods that are bitter, sour, saline, excessively hot, dry, pungent and burning, are liked by the Rajasic and are productive of pain, grief and disease.

(17-9)

Sattva is a state of harmony, balance, joy and intelligence. Sattva is the guna that yogis aspire to, as it reduces rajas and tamas and thus makes liberation possible. To increase sattva reduce both rajas and tamas, eat sattvic foods and enjoy activities and environments that produce joy and positive thoughts. Our human physiology is a reflection of the laws of the universe, and the more in tune our lives are with nature, the healthier we are likely to be! Our bodies possess the natural intelligence to process the foods that are closest to nature, such as fresh whole grains and organically-grown fruits and vegetables. Sattvic foods include whole grains and legumes and fresh fruits and vegetables that grow above the ground.

vk;q% IROcykjsX; lq[kfçrhfoo/kZuk% |

jL;k% fLuX/kk% fLFkj% ân;k vkgkj% lkfRodç;k% ¼Jh enHkxon~xhvk f%o/Š½

Foods which increase life, purity, strength, health, joy and cheerfulness, which are oleaginous and savoury, substantial and agreeable, are dear to the Sattvic people. (17-8)

THE FOOD NUTRITION : SHRIMADWAGWADGEETA TRIGUNA APPROACH

Gunās of the mind are highly unstable, they “fight” each other trying to take a dominant position. The predominate guna of the mind acts as a lens that effects our perspective of the world around us and, therefore, our thoughts and behaviour. As said previously, there is a natural tendency of guna to always replace each other, so it is very difficult to make one Sattvaguna a predominant one most of the time. Rather, one need to learn awareness of their guna state, so that they do not control him. Since there is already a natural challenge not to be a slave of the “game of gunas”, one can increase awareness of their gunastate through auspicious diet instead of letting their diet to be controlled by guna. By controlling diet it becomes easier to control the mind and make it work in auspicious direction.

All gunas create attachment and thus bind one’s self to the ego. Although it is necessary to encourage sattva, the ultimate goal is to transcend the misidentification of the self with the gunas and to be unattached to both the good and the bad. Therefore, auspicious diet isa helping tool at the beginning to develop Sattva as a means to reach the final goal. Body is an inseparable part of human, and there dwells a healthy spirit in a healthy body. Body is like a foundation of our being, and if we make the foundation pure and strong, then all our endeavors, including yogic ones, will be much more successful.

गुणानेतानतितय त्रीन्देही देहसमुद्भवान्।

जन्ममृत्युजरादुखेविमुक्तो अमृतमश्नुते)।।श्री मदभगवद्गीता १४/२०(

“When one rises above the three gunas that originate in the body; one is freed from birth, old age, disease, and death; and attains enlightenment”. (14-20)

Conclusion

We can see and conclude very clearly that diet and holistic health at all the dimensions right from physical to spiritual levels , are essential part of a human lifestyle and wellbeing. All the ancient sciences of Ayurveda, Shrimad bhagavad Geeta and yoga provides yogic explanation and methods to sustain healthy diet and mental state to reach ultimate goal of being in human life. The tree of spiritual evolution have there roots in proper diet and one should make choices about right food by creating more and more inner awareness in accordance with environment. As manu said that: The food that is worshipped confers strength and vitality constantly. If unworshipped means taken without awareness , it destroys strength and vitality.

iwftre g;k'ue fuR;a cYHkwtZe p ;pNgfr|

viwftra rq HkqäeqHk;a uk'k;sfne|| ¼euq½References :

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A Study on the Health Aspect of Mandua (Koda): A Cultural Icon of Garhwal Himalaya

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Abstract

Uttarakhand is well known to the world for its mesmerizing natural beauty. The rich natural diversity mixed with the distinct climatic conditions produce edible medicinal & herbal plants and spices that are unique to the region. The Garhwal Himalaya represents a traditional agricultural background where more than 74% population depends on the cultivation of cereal & millet crops to run their livelihood. Mandua (Koda) is one of the small millets grown widely in Garhwal. Apart from being a source of food, it is used as fodder for cattle also. Mandua is generally consumed during the cold and harsh winters. As a food, it accounts a high nutritional profile therefore, most definitely qualifies as a Super Food. It has the amazing properties of being suitable for 0 to 90 age groups. The protein of Mandua is said to be as complete as milk protein, which makes it an ideal substitute for lactose resistant people. Its Glycemic index is low which makes it suitable for diabetic patient also. Like other millets, it is gluten free and its flour is ideal for those with gluten allergy. Since the authors are the inhabitants of the region, through this paper an attempt has been made to investigate the health aspect and sustainable nutritional security of Mandua millet in the foothills of Garhwal Himalaya.

Keywords: Garhwal Himalaya, agriculture, millet crops, livelihood

Socio-economic and Environmental background of the Study Area

India is the largest producer of many kinds of millets, which are often referred as coarse cereals. Realizing the nutrient richness of these millets they are now considered as 'nutria-cereals'. In different parts of India it is also known as Nachni, Ragi, Mandua, and so on. This hardy grain grows in the fields in diverse eco-zones; from the hills of Garhwal to the Deccan Plateau or the

Jharkhand plains. The Garhwal is located in Indian Central Himalayan Region which is a part of Uttarakhand Himalaya. It constitutes one of the most fragile ecosystems. The geography of the region constitutes four eminent features i.e. highlands, valleys, mid-altitudes and snow-covered area. Garhwal Himalaya possesses varying degree of climatic character ranging from subtropical to temperate, alpine, and frigid. The Ganga, Yamuna and numerous tributaries originate from this region of Himalaya.

Garhwal is one of the divisions of Uttarakhand. It comprises 07 districts Haridwar, Dehradun, Tehri, Uttarkashi, Pauri, Chamoli and Rudraprayag. The main occupation of the people of Garhwal is Agriculture. Around 70% population is depended on agriculture practices for their livelihood. Agricultural development holds the key to provide livelihood to a significant segment of population and the overall development of the region by way of creating employment, generating income, and ensuring food security to the rural people. In this region of Himalaya agriculture is characterized by low yield due to traditionally cultivating cereals, inadequate capital formation, low investment, inadequate irrigation facility, and uneconomic size of the holdings (Sati, V. P., 2012). Low agricultural yield reflects the small size and scattered land holdings, difficult terrain, unfavourable climatic conditions for some crops, inadequate availability of improved inputs and technology, and lack of credit and marketing facilities (Dewan & Bahadur, 2005). It is an economically underdeveloped and ecologically fragile region of the state. Here, small millets are grown up to an altitude of 3000 mtr above sea level under shifting cultivation. The Cropping pattern is dominated by the traditional agriculture practices. There is a minimum scope of increasing employment through industrialization because of the sensitive landscapes & poor infrastructure. However, the region is blessed with certain climatic advantages which provide opportunities for the production of variety of high value crops.

Profile of Mandua (Koda)/Finger Millet

Mandua is considered one of the most nutritious cereals, grown extensively in various regions of India. Its scientific name is *Eleusine coracana*. It ranks sixth in production after wheat, rice, maize, sorghum and Bajra in India. It requires very little care and can grow even in drought conditions. It is also resistant to pests and diseases. Mandua hold a significant place in the agriculture of the Garhwal. The inhabitants of Uttarakhand have been growing Mandua (Koda) since long time.

Terrace farming is widely practised in Uttarakhand and the Madua crop is easily grown there. It can also be grown as a support crop or inter-cropped with other crops, like rice, wheat and so on.

- English: Finger Millet
- Garhwali: Koda, Mandua
- Bengali: Marwa
- Gujarati: Nagli, Bavto
- Hindi: Ragi, Mandika, Marwah
- Kannada: Ragi
- Marathi: Nagli, Nachni
- Odiya: Mandia
- Punjabi: Mandhuka, Mandhal
- Tamil: Keppai, Ragi, Kelvaragu
- Telugu: Ragi Chodi

It is higher in protein and minerals in comparison to other cereals and millets. Mandua contains about 5–8% protein, 1–2% ether extractives, 65–75% carbohydrates, 15–20% dietary fiber and 2.5–3.5% minerals. Of all the cereals and millets, finger millet has the highest amount of calcium and potassium. Finger millet contains important amino acids like isoleucine, leucine, methionine and phenyl alanine.

Climate requirement and cropping system

Mandua is a short-day plant with a growing optimum twelve hours of daylight for most varieties. Its main growing area ranges from 20° N to 20° S, meaning mainly the semiarid to arid tropics. Nevertheless, Mandua is found to be grown at 30° N in the Himalayan region. It is generally considered as a drought tolerant crop. It prefers moderate rainfall (≥ 500 mm annually). It is a typical Rabi (dry season) crop. Relatively to other millet species (pearl millet and sorghum) finger millet has a higher tolerance to cool temperatures. It is grown from about 500 meters above sea level up to about 3000 meters above sea level. By that, it can be cultivated on higher elevations than most tropical crops. Mandua can grow on various soils, including highly weathered tropical lateritic soil. Furthermore, it can tolerate soil salinity up to a certain extent. Mandua can tolerate moderately acidic soils (pH 5) but also moderately alkaline soils (pH 8.2).

Terrace farming is widely practised in Uttarakhand and the Mandua crop is easily grown there. It can also be grown as a support crop or inter-cropped with other crops like rice, wheat and so on. Mandua can be easily cultivated using the organic farming as it require very little fertilizers and is less attacked by borers, insects and plant moulds. Maturity of crop is between 3 to 6 months depending on the variety and growing conditions. The crop is adapted to fairly reliable rainfall conditions and has an extensive but shallow root system. Most common Mandua intercropping system in Garhwal is as follows:

With legumes: Mandua/pigeon pea, Mandua/black gram

Country	5-year average (met. tons)
India	9,041,765
Nigeria	4,299,211
Niger	1,733,793
China	1,116,505
Burkina Faso	856,337
Mali	701,701
Sudan	560,548
Uganda	408,137
Senegal	347,989
Chad	296,119
Russian	280,941
Ethiopia	259,490
Nepal	251,027
Myanmar	137,759
Tanzania	136,409
Ghana	117,955

With cereals: Mandua/maize, Mandua/foxtail millet, Mandua/Jowar

With other species: Mandua/mustard

Top Millet consumers in the World

Source: Millet Network of India, FIAN, India

Nutritional Importance of Mandua (Koda)

Among different varieties of Mandua like red, brown, yellow, white, tan, only the red colour varieties are cultivated extensively throughout India. The five layered testa in Mandua makes it unique compared to other millets such as pearl millet, kodo millet and foxtail millet. It is one of the possible reasons for the higher dietary fiber content in Mandua.

Table 1: Nutritional composition of Mandua with other millets and cereals

Protein (%)	Fat (%)	Starch (%)	Ash (%)	Crude fiber (%)	Total dietary fiber/100 g	Total phenol (mg/100 g)	Carbohydrates (g)	
Mandua/Finger millet	7.3	1.3	59.0	3	3.6	19.1	102	72.6

Pearl millet	14.5	5.1	60.5	2	2	7	51.4	67.5
Proso millet	11	3.5	56.1	3.6	9	8.5	0.10	70.4
Foxtail millet	11.7	3.9	59.1	3	7	19.11	106	60.9
Kodo millet	8.3	1.4	72.0	3.6	9	37.8	368	65.9
Little millet	7.7	4.7	60.9	6.9	7.6	–	21.2	67
Barnyard millet	6.2	4.8	60.3	4	13.6	13	26.7	65.5
Wheat	14.4	2.3	64	1.8	2.9	12.1	20.5	71.2
Rice	7.5	2.4	77.2	4.7	10.2	3.7	2.51	78.2
Maize	12.1	4.6	62.3	1.8	2.3	12.8	2.91	66.2
Sorghum	11	3.2	73.8	1.8	2.7	11.8	43.1	72.6
Barley	11.5	2.2	58.5	2.9	5.6	15.4	16.4	80.7
Oats	17.1	6.4	52.8	3.2	11.3	12.5	1.2	69.8
Rye	13.4	1.8	68.3	2	2.1	16.1	13.2	80.1

Source: D. Chandra et al. (2016)

Table 2: Mineral & Vitamin composition of Mandua with other millets and cereals (mg/100g)

Ca	P	Fe	Mg	Na	K	Cu	Mn	Zn	Thiamine	Riboflavin	Niacin	
Mandua/Finger millet	344	283	3.9	137	11	408	0.47	5.49	2.3	0.42	0.19	1.1
Pearl millet	42	240	11	137	10	390	1.06	1.15	3.1	0.38	0.21	2.8
Proso millet	8	206	2.9	114	5	195	0.8	1.6	1.7	0.41	0.28	4.5
Foxtail millet	31	290	2.8	143	1.3	364	0.59	1.16	3.51	0.59	0.11	3.2
Kodo millet	35	188	1.7	110	4.8	141	1.60	1.10	0.7	0.15	0.09	2
Little millet	17	220	9.3	61	7.9	126	0.05	0.68	3.7	0.30	0.09	3.2
Barnyard millet	22	280	18	82	-	-	0.60	0.96	3	0.33	0.1	4.2
Wheat	41	306	3.9	120	3	363	0.9	13.3	1	0.41	5.46	5.5
Rice	10	160	0.5	32	6	130	0.25	1.1	1.2	0.41	0.0149	1.62

Maize	10	89	2.3	0.163	37	270	0.22	0.163	0.46	0.155	0.055	1.77
Sorghum	13	289	3.4	165	2	363	1.7	1.6	1.7	0.33	0.1	3.7
Barley	29	221	2.5	79	9	280	2.13	1.32	2.13	0.191	0.114	4.6
Oats	54	523	5	177	2	429	4	4.9	4	0.763	0.139	0.961
Rye	33	374	2.6	110	6	264	0.45	2.6	3.73	0.3	0.3	4.3

Source: D. Chandra et al. (2016)

Table 3: Essential amino acid profile of Mandua with other millets and cereals (g/100g)

Arginine	Histidine	Lysine	Tryptophan	Phenylalanine	Tyrosine	Methionine	
Mandua/Finger millet	0.300	0.130	0.220	0.100	0.310	0.220	0.210
Pearl millet	0.300	0.140	0.190	0.110	0.290	0.200	0.150
Proso millet	0.290	0.110	0.190	0.050	0.310	–	0.160
Foxtail millet	0.220	0.130	0.140	0.060	0.420	–	0.180
Kodo millet	0.270	0.120	0.150	0.050	0.430	–	0.180
Little millet	0.250	0.120	0.110	0.060	0.330	–	0.180
Barnyard millet	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
Wheat	0.480	0.130	0.230	0.080	0.280	0.290	0.150
Rice	0.290	0.130	0.170	0.070	0.280	0.180	0.090
Maize	0.131	0.089	0.137	0.023	0.150	0.123	0.067
Sorghum	0.355	0.246	0.229	0.124	0.546	0.321	0.169
Barley	0.496	0.223	0.369	0.165	0.556	0.284	0.190
Oats	1.192	0.405	0.701	0.234	0.895	0.573	0.312
Rye	0.500	0.400	0.600	0.100	0.400	0.200	0.200

Source: D. Chandra et al. (2016)

The nutritional value of Mandua lies in its high content of calcium (0.38%), protein (6% –13%), dietary fiber (18%), carbohydrates (65-75%), minerals (2.5% 3.5%), phytates (0.48%), tannins (0.61%) and phenolic compound. Mandua has been perceived as a potential “super cereal” by the United States National Academies being one of the most nutritious among all major cereals

(National Research Council, 1996). Mandua is known for its beneficial health effects, such as anti-diabetic, anti-diarrheal, antiulcer, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. From the nutritional perspective, Mandua is considerably rich in minerals and its micronutrient density is higher than that of the world's major cereal grains; rice and wheat (Antony & Chandra, 1998; Vadivoo et al. 1998).

Health benefits of Mandua Millet

Mandua is usually milled with the testa (seed coat) which is rich in dietary fiber and nutrients to make flour. The flour is used to prepare different traditional dishes such as Kode (Kode) ki Roti, Thag Roti, Halwa and so on. On daily consumption of whole grain of finger millet and its products can protect against the risk of cardiovascular disease, type II diabetes, and gastrointestinal cancers and other health issues (D. Chandra et al. 2016). No other cereal comes close to Mandua when it comes to calcium content. Calcium is a significant element when it comes to bone development and prevention of osteoporosis. Replacing calcium pills with Mandua and including it in the diet of growing children is a good way to reap its benefits. The natural unsaturated fat content in Mandua is lower than all other cereals. Therefore, it could be a substitute for wheat and rice for the people trying to lose their weight. It also contains an amino acid called tryptophan which reduces appetite.

As compared to rice, Mandua contains higher amounts of dietary fibre. Hence, it aids digestion, prevents over-eating and makes you feel full for a longer span of time. The amino acids lecithin and methionine help in decreasing the cholesterol levels of body by getting rid of the excess fat in the liver. The high polyphenols and fibre content has another perk. Diabetic patients can eat Mandua to create a restrained build in glucose level. Mandua is an excellent source of natural Iron. Patients of anaemia and low haemoglobin levels can include Mandua in their diets as a domestic remedy. The ample amount of amino acids and antioxidants in Mandua help the body relax naturally. Common disorders like anxiety, insomnia, headaches and depression can be battled with Mandua. The amino acid called Tryptophan is a major contributor to the relaxing effects of Mandua. In the early stages of growth of Mandua, when it is still green can help to prevent high blood pressure. The cholesterol levels in blood can be regulated too. As a result the risk for hypertension and stroke goes down significantly. In South India, Mandua is widely consumed, babies as old as 28 days are fed Mandua porridge at their christening. It is believed that Mandua

promotes better digestion. The high calcium and iron content is useful for the overall development of the infants.

Mandua in Food industry

Composite flour technology is initially referred to process of mixing wheat flour with cereal and legume flour for making bread and biscuits. However, the term can also be used with regard to mixing of non-wheat flours, roots and tubers or other raw materials (Dendy, 1992). Composite flour technology makes it possible to blend, mix or fortify one food material with others so that the resulting fortified mix has not only better nutritional quality but also the necessary attributes for consumer acceptance (Lupien, 1990). Fortification of finger millet in chapattis not only improves the taste but also helpful in controlling glucose levels in diabetic patients very efficiently (Kang et al., 2008). Due to the changing food habits of people, a good market of noodles has been created nowadays in India. The demand of the noodles made of Mandua is growing due to awareness of its nutritional properties. Noodles can be prepared in different combinations such as noodles made of Mandua, Mandua and wheat in the ratio of 1:1 and Mandua blended with wheat and soya flour in the ratio of 5:4:1 (Thapliyal V, 2015).

Extrusion technology is a process of transforming ingredients into value added products. Extruded products prepared from different grains are very popular nowadays among all age groups. Kurkure is one of the examples of extrusion product which is very popular among children. Mandua exhibits good extrusion characteristics. Mandua flour has already been incorporated in bakery preparations. Many confectionary brands now proudly promote Mandua (Ragi) biscuits. More importantly, at the artisanal level, Mandua biscuits, muffins and cakes have been developed. Manufacturers have introduced biscuits, breads & muffins made of Mandua flour. The use of this millet in bakery preparations will be superior in terms of fiber content, nutrients. In a recent study, attempts have been made to improve the nutritional quality of cakes with respect to the minerals and fiber content by supplementing with malted finger millet flour (Desai et al., 2010).

Few popular preparations of Mandua Millet

1. Mandua ki Roti
2. Mandua Poori
3. Mandua Dark chocolate Cake
4. Mandua Coconut Barfi

Conclusion

- The Mandua has started its journey by being considered a coarse grain, especially from the colonial times, to becoming today, in post-colonial times, a grain duly recognized for all it has to offer ecologically, nutritionally and gastronomically, as a true blue Super Food, which packs in a powerful punch in its tiny grains. It possesses excellent nutritional value, ability to tolerate various abiotic stresses and resist pathogens. The experts have recognized the Mandua millet to have a bright future in the nutraceutical industry.
- In spite of rich nutrient profile, the consumption of Mandua among urban Indians is lower. Unhealthy foods have increasingly become a part of the food choices made by youth. Obesity has become a matter of health concern. Large populations of children in the country are malnourished and are deficient in calcium and protein.
- The millet Mandua then could be the answer to all the above problems relating to nutrient deficiencies. 'Mandua' is truly a wonder cereal grain and should be incorporated in the diets. Combination of millets with other sources of protein would compensate the deficiency of certain amino acids such as lysine. The regular use of Mandua millet as a nutrient and its products helps in managing different disorders of body by maintaining blood glucose homeostasis.
- The whole meal-based Mandua products may be preferred due to the protective role of seed coat, which has health enhancing benefits.

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Nutraceutical & Pharmaceutical Potential of Plants in Agrotourism: a mini Review

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Abstract

Aim of this study was to review the potential of plants as Nutraceutical and Pharmaceutical agent in enhancement of Agrotourism in biodiversity hotspot areas (mainly Uttarakhand and North-East states). Contribution of agriculture sector is decreasing in GDP of our country. Innovative income generating activity for farmers, tribals and local/ rural people is a milestone that needs to be achieved. Agrotourism centre (service sector) development in hilly areas where accessibility of conventional medical facilities is poor through the application of alternative remedies (plant based ethno medicines, ayurvedic-Siddha, Unani-tibbi etc) for curing number of body disorders and disease. It will help in conservation of traditional knowledge and sustainable development of rural/ local, tribals, poor people.

Keywords – Nutraceutical, Pharmaceutical, Agrotourism, Alternative remedies

Introduction

Our mother earth is endowed with more than 3.9 lacs plants including sea plants wealth and some minor groups of land races. The World Health Organisation (WHO) has recently compiled a list of 28,187 plant species used as medicinal plants in different parts of the world. 4,478 plant species which are more reputed as herbal medicines, even then the plants which could be brought under realistic cultivation web stand about 1.9% and remaining plants for Nutraceutical/ Pharmaceutical purpose are still extracted from forest/ wild resources(98.10%). A mini review of Agrotourism in India along with its 'Nutraceutical' and 'Pharmaceutical' aspects is of great concern. 'Nutraceuticals' are plants derived food items having capability to provide health or medical benefits in addition to its basic nutritional values. 'Pharmaceuticals' are the plants derived or

synthetically derived medicinal drugs for the purpose of curing various ailments of human body or animals. India is emerging country with wide scope for growth in various sectors. Biodiversity of India is very rich, distributed across the twenty one (21) different Agro-climatic zones. An “Agro-Climatic Zone” is a land unit in terms of major climates, suitable for a certain range of crops and cultivars. We need to explore our potential of rich flora so that we may overcome our poverty in sustainable manner. The global market for the medicinal plants is estimated to be worth US\$ 900 billion a year. According to WHO, people of developing countries depends up on the herbal medicines for primary healthcare. Contribution of agriculture sector is decreasing in GDP of our country. Innovative income generating activity for farmers, tribals and local/ rural people is a milestone that need to be achieved. Generation of additional sources of income apart from exclusive agricultural practices is need of the hour. Uttarakhand and North-eastern states are biodiversity hotspot of the country. ‘Agritourism’ is termed as an instrument for employment generation, poverty alleviation and socio-cultural development of the people. Tourism on the farms enables farmers to diversify their activities while enhancing the value of their products and property.

In Agri-tourism venture, following factors play a major role:

Meals for tourists (Nutraceuticals)

Derived from various parts of the plant such as Fruits, flowers, leaves, stem, tubers, corms, rhizome etc. Fruits (ripened ovary) are good source of nutrients. Fruits are rich sources of fibres, proteins, vitamins, flavonoids, carbohydrates, lipids, pectins, antioxidants and other secondary metabolites. Fruits are found in nature either in Wild/ Semi-domesticated or Cultivation web.

Medical facilities (Alternative remedies/ Ethnomedicines)

Primitive healthcare practices need to be followed for general body disorders so that ethno medicinal knowledge imbibed in form of their cultural practices may be conserved and sustained. Medicinal and aromatic plants are biosynthetic laboratories for various acute and chronic diseases and disorders.

Miscellaneous facilities (Spa & massage)

Aromatic plants have flavonoids and antioxidants that help to combat the anxiety and stress of day to day life. Aromatic oil induces sound sleep and to alleviate restlessness in hypertensive

patients. Medicinal and Aromatic Plants (MAPs) based livelihood systems are often mediated by the market forces, and/ or related directly to employment/ income of the poor. Proper and optimum utilization of those resources will help in employment generation and economic development of the rural people. Cultivation of MAPs species have now become a popular and economically viable commodity. Cultivation at microlevel/ cottage industrial level should be promoted for sustainable utilization and conservation of these wild resources.

Some important medicinal and aromatic plants are given as under:

Rosemary (*Rosmarinus officinalis*)

Family-Labiatae

Uses – Oil is mainly used in perfumery industry, and is frequently used in aromatherapy. Rosemary extract is employed in cosmetology, because of its antioxidant activity it is used to restoring the healthy status of the skin.

Geranium (*Pelargonium graveolens*)

Family – Geraniaceae

Uses – Oil is mainly used in perfumery industry. It's oil has rose like odour. Hence, used in soaps and cosmetic items. Antioxidant activity it is used to restoring the healthy status of the skin.

Vetiver (*Vetiveria zizanioides*)

Family – Gramineae

Uses – It is used as stimulant, refrigerant, flavouring agent, aromatic, stomachic and in the treatment of prickly heat or itches. It is also used in preparation of nutraceuticals and cosmeceutical items.

These factors will help in establishing more 'Agrotourism Centres' in different zones of the country where conventional healthcare facilities are poor or unavailable. The alternative therapies (plant based ethno medicines, Ayurvedic-Siddha, Unani-Tibbi etc) may play a vital role for providing treatment in short span of time. Medicinal plants offer alternative remedies for various ailments in safe and efficient way. Extra sources of income through service sector (Agrotourism) may prove as boon to them and will check the migration of the rural/tribal people. It will also help in raising per capita national income of our country.

Table 1: Some Wild/ Semi-domesticated Medi-food Plants of India

S.N.	Local Name	Botanical Name	Family	Climatic Zone/ Geographical Source	Therapeutic uses
1	Hisalu	Rubus ellipticus	Rosaceae	Sub tropical & Tropical Climate (Uttarakhand & Northern estates)	Renal tonic and antidiuretic
2	Pilu	Salvadora oleoides	Salvadoraceae	Arid Hot climate	Carminative, analgesic, astringent, antibacterial, antimycotic and anticonvulsant
3	Bel	Aegle marmelos	Rutaceae	Dry forest in Indian peninsula, Indo-China, South-East Asia	Diarrhoea, dysentery, dyspepsia, GI disorders and good source of Vitamin-A & C
4	Carambola	Averrhoa carambola	Oxalidaceae	Indian Subcontinents, and South-East Asia	Antimicrobial activity and good source of antioxidants, potassium and Vit-C
5	Tendu	Diospyros melanoxylon	Ebenaceae	Tropical and sub-tropical climate (Chhatisgarh, Jharkhand, Assam)	Anti-haemorrhoid, Controls diabetes, Stregthens cardiac muscles, Good Source of fibre

Summary & Conclusion

India is emerging country. Biodiversity of India is very rich, distributed across the twenty one (21) different Agro-climatic zones. Contribution of agriculture sector is decreasing in GDP of our country. Innovative income generating activity for farmers, tribals and local/ rural people is a milestone that need to be achieved. According to WHO, people of developing countries depends up on the herbal medicines for primary healthcare. Uttarakhand and North-eastern states are biodiversity hotspot of the country. Some Wild/ Semi-domesticated Medi-Food of India are Hisalu (Rubus ellipticus), Pilu (Salvadora oleoides), Bel (Aegle marmelos), Camabola (Averrhoa carambola) and Tendu (Diospyros melanoxylon). Additional sources for income generation through service sector is need of the hour. 'Agritourism' is termed as an instrument for employment generation, poverty alleviation and socio-cultural development of the people. In Agri-tourism venture- Meals for tourists (Nutraceuticals), Medical facilities (Alternative remedies/ Ethnomedicines), Miscellaneous facilities (Spa & massage) plays a major role. Nutraceuticals are derived from various parts of the plant such as Fruits, flowers, leaves, stem, tubers, corms, rhizome etc. Primitive healthcare practices need to be followed for general body disorders so that ethnomedicinal knowledge imbibed in form of their cultural practices may be conserved and sustained along with conservation of wild/ threatened medicinal and aromatic plants. Aromatic plants have flavonoids and antioxidants that help to combat the anxiety and stress of day to day life. Aromatic oil induces sound sleep and to alleviate restlessness in hypertensive patients. Some important medicinal and aromatic plants that are helpful in aromatherapy are Rosemary (Rosmarinus officinalis), Geranium (Pelargonium graveolens) and Vetiver (Vetiveria zizanioides) etc.

Conflict of Interest

There is no conflict of interest.

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Art of Eating in Special Reference to Bhagavad-Gita

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Abstract

This research paper is an attempt to explore and understand the concept of Eating according to the Bhagavad-Gita including scientific discourses of Food and Mood. BhagavadGita is known to be a renowned Yogic Scripture and well accepted text book of management which teaches us how to live our Life with grace. In this particular paper researcher has tried to uncover the Dietary concepts, types of food, reflection of food on individual disposition from Bhagavad-Gita. Bhagwadgeeta's sutras has been explained with an scientific approach taking the help of various scientific studies done earlier in especial context of food and art of eating which clearly reveals the importance of one vegetarian diet and different aspects of nutrition to have good physical and mental health.

Keyword – Satvik, Rajasik, Tamasik, Gyan yoga, Mood

Introduction

The Bhagavad-Gita is one of the most ancient religious scriptures of the world. It contains the direct message of God. It is a dialogue between God(Krishna) and his closest devotee(Arjuna). Bhagavad-Gita truly known as Raj Yogic scripture comprises 700 sutra and 18 chapters which tell about the Discipline of Karma Yoga (Art of Doing Good:-Selfless work), Bhakti Yoga(Art of Being Kind:-Devotion to mankind and nature) and Gyan Yoga(Being Good:-Acquiring knowledge of Shiksha(Science) and Vidhya (Spirituality) (Acharya, 2013). Apparently BhagawatGita known to as Art of Living text which includes the Art of Eating under the Gyan yogic concept. Food comes as the main component of our core necessity, and should be pure enough. We know well from an old saying "You are what you eat". The food people eat influences their nature and vice versa. The Chhāndogya Upaniṣhad explains that the coarsest part of the food we eat passes out as

feces; the subtler part becomes flesh; and the subtlest part becomes the mind (6.5.1). Again, it states: āhāraśuddhau sattva śuddhiḥ (7.26.2) “By eating pure food, the mind becomes pure.” The reverse is also true—people with pure minds prefer pure foods.

Objective

The main aim of the present study is to bring the knowledge of BhagawatGita over the food habits, an art of eating into light. In this process, the study analyzes the concept of Bhagavad-Gita over food, its types and personality it reflects in reference to scientific study. And to give direction about food habits and its core impact on individual disposition.

Methodology

The work is done entirely on the basis of secondary sources that include review of books, journals, research article, reports and other secondary sources.

ScientificdiscoursesoffoodandMood: Food as ‘Feeding the Mind’

Foods are represented as having a long-term influence on mood and wellbeing “...because of the impact they have on the structure and function of the brain” (Cornah, 2006, 6). Not only does food impact on mood and general wellbeing, but it also contributes to the prevention and management of specific mental health disorders. Early work on the relationship between food and mood indicated a link between reduced fat consumption and increased anger (Wells 1998). Subsequent work has shown an affirmative link between consumption of omega-3 fatty acids and positive mood (Appleton et. al. 2007, Beezhold et. al. 2010). Fish in particular, with its high levels of omega-3 fatty acids, has been recognized as beneficial to health, potentially contributing to low levels of depression, memory loss and anxiety (Maddock et. al. 1999, Appleton et. al. 2007, The Economist, 2010). Rodgers (2001) also supports this but suggests that the relationship between diet and depression needs further exploration. Whatsoever (2002) found an association between high consumption of sugars and depression while Appleton (2007) noted links between low income and the exclusion of mental health promoting food products that can magnify the relationship between eating certain foods and depression.

Interestingly, Beezhold et. al.’s (2010) research found that, despite a diet low in omega-3, strict vegetarians do not suffer from high levels of depression. This they attribute to the inclusion of other nutrients in their diet that, in simple terms, have an anti-inflammatory effect similar to omega-3 fatty acids. The sample group’s emphasis on healthy diet and lifestyle was also

recognized as contributing to lower levels of depressive illness. Gould et. al. (2008) identified a range of foods purporting to have mental health benefits; foliates and B vitamins are linked to feelings of well-being, balancing carbohydrate, sugar and fat consumption contributes to the control of depression and fatty acids found in fish, shellfish, fruit and berries offer positive benefits to children's cognitive functions and reduce levels of anxiety.

Recent research has further clarified the relationship between food consumption and how we feel. In a study focusing on a wide range of healthy and non-healthy food groups, Akbaralyet. al. (2009) found direct links between diet and mental wellbeing. The study, conducted over 5 years by food scientists and psychologists in France and the UK, found evidence of a direct link between the consumption of junk food i.e. processed food that is high in sugars and fats, and subsequent levels of depression. They found that the group of respondents who consumed healthy foods, that were not highly processed and which had relatively low levels of sugars and fats, experienced much lower of levels of depression (Akbaraly et. al. 2009). This finding is not new but it represents a more direct linkage between a diet of healthy foods, relatively unprocessed and low in sugars and fats, and mood than previous studies had proposed. However, while it is acknowledged that the physiological and nutritional benefits of food influence mood, consumer understanding of food is much more multi-faceted and influenced by other discourses beyond science. (Dr Sarah Maddock, 2016)

Bhagavad-Gita & Art of Eating

To acquire health and happiness, one needs to live a balanced life. This typically comes from Bhagwad-Gita chapter 6 Shloka 17 where Krishna says to Arjuna "Yukaharaviharasyayuktachestasyakarmasu. Yuktasvapnavabodhasya yoga bhavatiduhkhaha". It means "the one, whose diet and movements are balanced, whose actions are proper., whose hours of sleeping and waking up are regular, and who follows the path of meditation, is the destroyer of pain or unhappiness." The message is relevant even today, validated by modern scientific research and analysisofdata. Moderation and variety is the mantra of the present day concept of dieticians. Moderation in diet, as well as moderation in thinking, recreation and actions is the secret to healthy living. Lord Krishna further clarifies this (chapter 6 shloka 16) by saying that, eating too much food or starving, and sleeping too much or remaining awake all the time is not health friendly. Such people cannot concentrate or do sadhana.

Every person is distinct as his or her personality depends upon three attributes called satva, rajas and tamas. The food one eats and one's personality are related (shloka 17.7). People with predominant satwa eat food which is greasy, nourishing, appealing and succulent (shloka 17.8). People with predominant rajas eat food which is bitter, sour, salty, hot, pungent, dry and burning. Excess amount of these foods makes one miserable and sick (17.9). People with predominant tamas in the body prefer to eat half cooked food which is dry, bad-smelling, stale, defiled and impure.(Aggarwal, 2015)

Satvic Food	Rajasic Food	Tamasic Food
Sattvic foods are those which purify the body and calm the mind	They stimulate the body and mind into action. In excess, these foods can cause hyperactivity, restlessness, anger, irritability, and sleeplessness	Tamasic food are those which dull the mind and bring about inertia, confusion and disorientation
Cooked food that is consumed within 3-4 hours can be considered sattvic	Overly tasty foods are Rajasic	Stale or reheated food, oily or heavy food and food containing artificial preservatives fall under this category
Examples - Fresh fruits, green leafy vegetables, nuts, grains, fresh milk , certain spices	Examples – Spicy food, onion, garlic, tea, coffee, fried food	Example – Non vegetarian diet, stale food, excessive intake of fats, oil, sugary food

Examples - Fresh fruits, green leafy vegetables, nuts, grains, fresh milk, certain spices

Examples – Spicy food, onion, garlic, tea, coffee, fried food Example – Non-vegetarian diet, stale food, excessive intake of fats, oil, sugary food

The Bhagavad-Gita also explains how to eat: "while eating, one should concentrate only on eating as the food is served to one's consciousness" (9.27). Lord Krishna says that even eating leaves, fruits, and water suffice to keep us healthy". During the last minutes of life, a person's mind remains under the influence of his/her dominant attributes and this determines our next birth. People who die with dominant satvaguna, take rebirth as people who are pure in their mind (14.14). On the contrary, dying people with predominant rajas guna will be reborn in families devoted to action, and if a person's soul departs when the tamasguna is growing, the soul takes rebirth in people who are stupid.(Aggarwal, 2015)

Way of living & choice of food: Reflection of individual disposition

Foods in the mode of goodness are pure, illuminating, and serene, and create a sense of happiness and satisfaction. Such foods promote longevity and bestow good health, virtue, happiness, and satisfaction. They are juicy, naturally tasteful, mild, and beneficial. These include grains, pulses, beans, fruits, vegetables, milk, and other vegetarian foods. Hence, a vegetarian diet is beneficial for cultivating the qualities of the mode of goodness that are conducive for spiritual life.

When vegetarian foods are cooked with excessive chilies, sugar, salt, etc. they become rājasic. Such foods are very bitter, very sour, very salty, very hot, very pungent, very dry, very spicy, etc. They produce ill-health, agitation, and despair. Persons in the mode of passion find such foods attractive, but those in the mode of goodness find them disgusting. The purpose of eating is not to relish bliss through the palate, but to keep the body healthy and strong. As the old adage states: “Eat to live; do not live to eat.” Thus, the wise partake of foods that are conducive to good health, and have a peaceable impact upon the mind i.e., sāttvic foods.

Cooked foods that have remained for more than one yām (three hours) are classified in the mode of ignorance. Foods that are impure, have bad taste, or possess foul smells come in the same category. Impure foods also include all kinds of meat products.

The mind and body impact

Although we might like to have junk, oily and spicy food, it is not good for our health and invariably causes illness. To curb the tāmasic and rājasic nature of our mind and to follow a sāttvic regime is the only way to have healthy body and mind. “The pleasures that arise from contact with the sense objects, though appearing as enjoyable to worldly-minded people, are verily a source of misery. And such pleasures have a beginning and an end, and so the wise do not delight in them.” (Bhagavad-Gita 5.22)

Therefore, we should be in constant check of what we eat as it has direct effect on our body and our mind. To eat sāttvic food (as much as possible), not only aids healthy body and mind but is essential for spiritual health as well. How food effects spiritual health is a topic for some other day.

Discussion & Interpretation

In the present times, satvik food has become rare and tamasik and rajasik food have got proliferated everywhere. Most food products available today are prepared to please taste buds; there is no consideration given to how unhealthy they may be for people who consume them. The markets and hotels are inundated with food products which are instilled with ingredients to augment taste. Even foreign companies are now investing huge amounts of money in food industry. These products are extremely attractive to look at and are very tasty as well but are harmful for health. Food has also become a matter of prestige now. People like to show off their wealth by consuming only branded foods. These food products get a lot of publicity through advertisements on TV which entices the viewers to get addicted to these. In the Encyclopedia of Junk Food and Fast Food Andrew Smith has described junk foods as the products which are basically created for commercial purposes and are very low on nutrition. These products are high on calories and have excessive fat, sugar and salt content. The latter are added to enhance taste. Candies, fried bakery items, pastries, cakes, different types of namkeens, ice-creams and drinks are some of the popular junk foods. These also are very low on nutrition and contain excessive fine flour (Maida), due to which they stick into intestines and create constipation. And, Ayurveda says that constipations the genesis of all kinds of diseases. These modern foods have become very popular, but people are totally unaware of the harmful effects they have on our body. A latest scientific study has found that excess of junk food causes a great damage to neurons in our brains. These brain cells once damaged cannot be replenished and their destruction creates a number of diseases related to the brain. Excessive consumption of junk food leads to loss of memory, headache, heaviness in the eyes, fatigue, obesity, constipation, acidity etc. A research study was published in American Journal of Clinical Nutrition in 2011 related to junk foods. In this study healthy people were given junk food for 5 days and were subjected to tests thereafter. It was found that there was a clear reduction in their cognitive abilities like memory and attention. In order to make junk food tasty, several specific chemicals are added and these affect the hippocampus region of our brain. Since hippocampus is related to memory and attention, it gets severely affected by such food products. In a research study conducted by Brown University it was found that junk foods contain excessive amounts of fats and sugar. Both these reduce the activities of Brain Derived Neurotrophic Factors (BDNF), alternatively known as brain peptides. These peptides play an important role in the ability

of brain to learn and remember. Since junk foods affect these peptides, learning and memorizing functions of the brain are adversely affected. Professor Suzanne deal Monte, a famous neurologist at Brown University also conducted a study to understand the effects of junk food. She has found that eating junk foods is a very strong causative factor for diabetes and also results in the Alzheimer's disease. They also cause other mental ailments like depression, stress etc. (Pandya, 2018)

Foods to be eaten according to the Bhagavad-Gita

In Bhagavad-Gita, Sri Krishna states, "If one offers Me with love and devotion a leaf, a flower, fruit, or water, I will accept it." (Bg.9.26). To me this seems to suggest that Sri Krishna is sanctioning a diet based on leaves and fruits and water as the best one for spiritual growth. I am no scholar on the Bhagavad-Gita, but my liberal interpretation of this verse would be that the Satvic diet is generally plant based and includes all or most vegetables, fruits, legumes, grains, nuts, seeds, etc.

Because Sri Krishna gave cows sacred status similar to that of a human mother and favored raw butter for personal consumption as a child, one could reasonably argue that dairy products (such as yogurt, milk, kefir, lassi, sour cream, etc.) belong to the Satvic food category.

Many yogis hold the view, however, that dairy products can only be considered Satvic if these are obtained respecting the cows and goats who are shown kindness, love, and humane treatment. According to the principle of Ahimsa (nonviolence), any food procured through violence to living beings cannot be considered Satvic. (K. Luthar, 2007)

Yogic Sattvic Diets

Some yogis that I have met favor a completely raw vegetarian diet with a primary focus on sprouted grains and beans (such as Garbanzo, Black-eyed peas, etc.) along with raw fruits and vegetables. Their diet is essentially vegan and contains no animal products. However, modern science teaches us that since vitamin B12 is missing from a purely vegan diet, supplementation is necessary. A number of medical and scholarly references can be found on this issue on the web. Other yogis have felt that a raw vegetarian diet is too limiting and include cooked foods as well as dairy products (milk, yogurt, lassi, etc.) in their diet. This diet, known as the lacto-vegetarian diet, is probably the most wide spread among Indian Hindus and Jains. A few well known yogis have also traditionally included not only dairy but also eggs and egg products in their otherwise

vegetarian diet. This is known as the lacto-ovo vegetarian diet. Although very few Indian yogis include any kind of fish, fowl, or meat in their food, there are exceptions. Buddhist yogis, for example Dalai Lama, do eat meat. A few Hindu yogis also eat meat pointing out that some ancient scriptures sanction meat eating for certain religious rituals. For most Hindu and Jain yogis, however, there is no convincing argument for eating meat if one wishes to uphold the supreme principle of Ahimsa and follow the philosophy of nonviolence.

Best Satvic Diet

The general answer from my study is that foods which cause the body to gain health and for the mind to be calm and peaceful constitute the Sattvic diet. To some extent, this requires knowing the needs of one's own body and being sensitive to the effects of various foods on our system. Foods which are very suitable and nutritious for one person may not be right for another. Common sense and wisdom are the essential ingredients to find the best Satvic diet for yourself. In terms of particular foods to be eaten, the yogis and sages have answered this question, but the answers have different variations. One common element of a yogic Satvic diet is that it is primarily vegetarian. This is true at least for Hindu and Jain yogis. Within the broad framework of vegetarianism, a number of dietary systems are possible where certain foods are included and some are excluded. In the most liberal vegetarian diets, eggs and dairy products are included. Some people include dairy in their vegetarian diet but not eggs. Some include eggs but not dairy. In the most strict vegetarian diet, eggs and milk are excluded. Supplementation through certain vitamins is needed in such diets, according to modern medical opinion. (K.Luthar, 2007)

So what does it all mean and what are the lessons from Bhagavad-Gita and our discussion of the Satvic diet? Here is what I think some of the lessons are.

- Whatsoever you eat, eat in moderation.
- Educate yourself on proper nutrition, be sensitive to your body, and see what foods work for you.
- Emphasize fresh vegetables and fruits and eat a diet which is mostly plant-based.
- Do not eat foods which are too salty, bitter, or have gone stale and putrid.
- Regardless of the food being eaten, eat with gratitude, prayerful attitude, and with mental poise.
- Chew the food carefully and taste it deeply without rushing. (K.Luthar, 2007)

Conclusion

We all repose our faith somewhere or the other. Where we decide to place our faith and what we choose to believe in, practically shapes the direction of our life. Nature of our faith is also echoed in our lifestyle and the choice of food we like to eat.

Bhagavad-Gita says, “Every human being is born with innate faith, which can be of three kinds—sātvic (mode of goodness), rājasic(mode of passion), or tāmasic (mode of ignorance).” (Bhagavad Gita 17.2) And the quality of our faith is decided by the nature of our mind. “The faith of all humans conforms to the nature of their mind. All people possess faith, and whatever the nature of their faith, that is verily what they are.” (Bhagavad Gita 17.3)

It is said that the good are drawn to the good and the bad to the bad. Those in tamoguṇa are drawn toward the evil. Those who are rājasic get drawn towards power, wealth, sensual enjoyment, revenge, and wrath. Those who are imbued with sattva guṇa become attracted to qualities of goodness.

But even when some action might seem to suggest that one is engaging in good deeds and hence is sātvic, it might not be the case all together. “Some people perform stern austerities that are not enjoined by the scriptures, but rather motivated by hypocrisy and egotism. Impelled by desire and attachment, they torment not only the elements of their body, but also I who dwell within them as the Supreme Soul. Know these senseless people to be of demoniacal resolves.” (Bhagavad-Gita 17.5/6)

Polluted foods are the main reasons for reduction of our life spans. Our eating habits too are in disarray. If our food is good, our brain will develop well and mind will get steady and balanced. Our Rishis of yore had given this sutra – May you live for hundred years. And they said not just stay alive, they added – may your eyes see for hundred years, you ears hear and your voice speak for hundred years, may you maintain good health for hundred years. This is possible only when our eating habits and life styles are refined and balanced. Our kitchens are amazing chemical laboratories to try out various experiments. In this laboratory we prepare many nutritious food items rich in medicinal values as well. We must cook foods here that satiate our hunger, give us good health, increase our lifespan, and calm our minds. It has been proven that homes where pure and good satvik food is prepared regularly and family members feel happy after eating, in such homes fights are infrequent and love grows steadily. A hungry and dissatisfied person remains

disturbed and also troubles others. He gets angry easily and remains irritated, but when he gets good food he becomes calm and balanced. So we must eat food that increases our life expectancy, gives us a balanced mind, gives energy, nutrition, health, and increases happiness and love. Such foods are the best. In this regard, PujyaGurudev(Pt. Shreeram Sharma Acharya) has given us a right advice [1]: In order to maintain good health, there is need to consciously make it a practice to (1) select proper eatables (2) eat in a proper way (3) do appropriate physical exercise and (4) manage the daily routine properly. If the mind is kept alert and the routine is practiced carefully, it will become a habit; and once a person becomes habitual of these four activities, it should be considered that she / he has conquered her / his health.(Pandya, 2018)

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Food and identity of Indian peoples

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Abstract

Food is necessity of every creature for his existence in this universe, as well as all human beings. Food is considered as basic need and first level in Maslow's need hierarchy. All other things are secondary necessity to have life span. People around the world from different cultures have their special needs and availability of food differed on various climatic and geographical conditions. People always consider food primarily which is easily available in their region and can be easily grown. For instant Bengali and south Indian has rice or cuisines made by rice are prefer to have in their plates while desert people from Rajasthan prefer millets. Food is showcase of culture and social habits as well as personal and psychological characteristics. Apart from this food can be studied in relation with many fields of diverse nature i.e. humanities & social science.

Introduction

Food is not only a necessary element to function human body and life cycle it also reveals about various aspects of human life like views, passions, education, socio-cultural customs, rituals etc. Food in an individual's plat indicates various serious aspects of his personality, his assumptions, observations and exploration through his life spans. For instant if we evaluate food in a highly educated and well designated person and a person who is lesser educated and daily wages earner due to difference working ambience and sensitivity of outputs we found a huge difference in their food habits. First type persons aware about impacts of food over body, hygiene, rather than second type people.

Authors as academicians try to throw light above aspects related to food. This paper focused on a theme that "we are what we eat". Your emotions, feelings, backgrounds, observations, social status reveal about your food habits or vice versa. Food habits provide information about families, societies, their resettling struggles and development over the time.

The author introduces the concept of food studies and explores the relationship of food to the human experience. In this paper as authors we try to examine how food habits around the globe influence cultural and social Identity of local people and how they react when a tourist visit distinct cultural sites and tourism destinations out of their regions. People try to recognize and set assumptions by food habits and cuisines which they have in their routine life.

Through food studies, one examines the relationships people have with food, and analyzes how this association discloses an enormous amount of information about them. The food choices made by people, either as individuals or as a group, can reveal views, passions, background knowledge, assumptions and personalities. Food has been found to be associated with people and delivers huge information about a group of persons. Eating habits disclose valuable characteristics of a culture or an individual.

Food and Identity

A famous saying that characterizes the idea of food and identity is, “You are what you eat.” Or very famous Indian thought that “ Jaisa Khao Anna, Waisa hoga Man” mean Food you eat drive your thoughts. This expression addresses two of the questions considered in the research: What does the food on my plate signify? And how do food practices contribute to personal identity? Both questions are have a strong bond to each- others. For instance if a person is very health conscious, aware and active always incline toward nutritious and healthy food.

Cultural & Religious perspectives of food

Globally it is found that food habits are bound somehow with religion. Any religion cannot deny its association with any mythological food, may be it happens occasionally. Food choices are driven somehow by religious faith can be studied in various religion of world. In every religion some food are praised and suggested according spiritual rituals and some are restricted.

For instance main food practices in Islam involve specific ritual slaughtering procedures for animals of consumption (haram practices), fasting during the month of Ramadan, the avoidance of pork and of intoxicating liquor. Foods are categorized as halal (those than may be eaten) and haram (those that should be avoided), as are other aspects of life. Most foods are halal while the list of haram foods includes pork, alcohol and any products that may contain emulsifiers made from animal fats (such as gelatins and margarines).

Buddhism considers living beings to be sacred, a belief that has translated into widely practiced vegetarianism and veganism. Violence towards animals is considered to translate into human aggression; hence most Buddhists will keep to the principle of ahimsa (non-violence or harmlessness) and avoid all foods related to processes where harm was done. Some Buddhists avoid meat and dairy products while others avoid only meat. Buddhists also avoid the consumption of alcohol.

There are some special foods from different religions which are symbolic to respective religion:

Baklava – The 33 layers of dough in this sweet pastry are supposed to signify Christ in life.

Bread – For Christians, bread is associated with Christ's body.

Cattern cake – These are prepared on 25th of November to commemorate St. Catherine since time of Tudor. It is flavored with caraway seeds.

Easter biscuit – These biscuits are cassia flavored to symbolize the importance of cassia as it was used in Christ's last rites, prepared on the day of Ester.

Dates – Muslims believe that prophet Mohammad ate dates to conclude his fasting. Hence, dates are the first to be eaten after the fast of Ramadan.

Ketupat – It is related to Id-ul-Fitar, especially in South-East Asian continents. In this rice are prepared in palm tree leaf.

Charoset – is associated with the Passover Seder. It is a sweet paste which symbolizes the mortar prepared by the Jews in Egyptian slavery.

Tilkutta – famous among Hindus, is a simple sweet dish made by pounding jiggery and sesame seeds together during the festival celebration of Makar Sakranti.

If we see above listed dishes in anybody's plate we easily describe his or her religious background and faiths. So, it is applicable fact that food in plate also shows a person's religious aspects.

Personal Identity

Food is reflection of an individual's personality. The way how an individual cook, eat, choice of places, selection of typology of restaurants, treat of people who are invited for feast ect pure and clear indication of his behavior and personality. People from higher and rich society always want to feed themselves in costly restaurants. They always want to maintain their social status.

Food in plates in highly educated and highly paid people always show preference for nutritious and healthy food because they are very health conscious. Similarly people working in

Multinational companies maintain a diet plan to be prone future problem. Nutritious and healthy food choice is clear view of a person's identity that he is health conscious.

Social and Psychological Identity

Food choices are immensely affected by social faiths and customs. Ambience in which you are grown up leads a person's food habits. Each and every social segment has some inherent effects by generations and followed by next generations without any immense argument.

Kids always attracted foods which are consumed or praised by their favorite fictional character. For instance a kid who is fussy about milk but after watching a campaign driven by any his fictional character that based on importance of milk that kid immediately show his interest in milk. And by passing time he makes having milk his habit. So it is clearly observed that your social ambience somewhere play a vital role for your food habits.

Rural parts of India always eager to have dairy products like butter or Ghee while same thing in urban areas have lesser important due to their different aspect and preferences of health.

Local cuisine reveal about geographical Identity

From the different part of world people have distinct food and cuisines. Geographical and climatic conditions drive always regional food habits. Around the globe people have their regional food and local cuisines. Crops grown and availability of raw food material always influence food habits. For instant south Indian people have different cuisine then Rajsthani people. If we examine daily plates of both we will find south Indian people prefer fish and rice made cuisines while Rajsthani love to have millet and wheat.

Cultural Identity

Throughout our life we met different people with diverse cultural identities. It is quite natural for human to question their new neighbors and environments. Cultures are built over a long period of time through. Common culture denotes the phenomenon where we share certain traditions, customs, beliefs and values through various cultural practices which have become meaningful and important to that society. It contributes to how we see ourselves and the groups with which we associate ourselves. Ethnic foods offer a rich set of metaphors through which individuals can express their cultures. Food is one custom that strongly connects people to their traditions. For example a person from Kerala always like to have Uttapam, Idali, Sambar in his breakfast, we can

easily guess about other aspect of south Indian culture like their language, Costumes, rituals etc. And compare about his own cultural aspects.

Conclusion

After discussing over so many aspects of how food is related with social, cultural, personal and geographical elements it is author's opinion that food is not only an element to drive life, it has so many significances which contribute in comparison and observation of a person's identity .

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consume-identity-through-food/

Travelling Journalism- Current Scenario & its scope

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Abstract

The practice of travel journalism is still largely neglected as a field of inquiry for communication and journalism scholars, despite the fact that news media are increasingly focusing on softer news. Need for research into the field has been identified before, very little actual investigation of travel journalism has been forthcoming. This paper reviews the current state of research by reviewing what studies have been conducted into the production, content and reception of travel journalism. It argues that while there does now exist a very small number of studies, these have often been conducted in isolation and with significant limitations, and much remains to be done to sufficiently explore this sub-field of journalism.

Globalization has affected our lives in every possible way. The highly advanced mode of communications has changed the way people interact with each other and faster means of transportation have made traveling a common experience. Food markets of the world are also not excluded from the effects of globalization. This has happened because of the increased trade among countries and introduction of different local food products in the global markets. Travel journalism's location at the intersection between information and entertainment, journalism and advertising. By reviewing existing research about travel journalism and examining in detail the special exigencies that constrain it, the paper suggests a number of possibilities in each area on how we can advance this knowledge. These dimensions include travel journalism's role in mediating cultures, its market orientation, motivational aspects and its ethical standards. Above all, the practice of travel journalism needs to be taken seriously.

Key Words: Travel Journalism, Travel & Tourism, Photography, Writing

Authenticating the past

- In considering how travel journalism presents the Middle East as other and exotic, as well as ancient and traditional, what is apparent is that it tends to make use of representational strategies that have their origins in 19th century European travel writing.
- In particular, variations of two specific representational strategies can be found in the selection of material sampled here. These two strategies are deployed as a means of conveying what is presented as two key aspects of the Middle East travel experience: the people, principally, the Bedouin, and the landscape, principally, the desert. It is significant to note that these representational constructs have a long, established history in European travel writing on the Middle East (Cocker, 1992; Tidrick, 1989). By the mid-late 1800s these representational motifs began to take hold with the emergence of a specific genre of travel writing on the Arabian peninsula.⁵ This cohered around the publication of Richard Burton's Personal Narrative of a Pilgrimage to Al-Madinah and Mecca (1856), the Cradle of the Arab . Race (1879) and Charles Montagu Doughty's Arabia Deserta (1888).

What is Travel Journalism?

Travel journalism is travel writing, it can be travel blogging. Travel journalism is a writing form all its own. Even though journalism is often dubbed as a lesser form of journalism, it is indeed an important medium of information, especially as our world shrinks with globalization. Travel journalism must stay factual and the authors must strive to be non-biased. It helps readers understand the culture and importance of a place they visit. Travel journalist must go beyond writing reviews of a festivals, museum or hotel travel writing. Travel journalists must explain what each of these things means to a culture. Travel writing appeals to tourists, while travel journalism appeals to travelers. Those who want to authentically understand other cultures.

What Does A Travel Writer Do?

At its most basic, travel writers do only two things: They travel and they write. While going places and writing reviews about each destination is how the job of a travel writer is described in a nutshell, it isn't actually as easy as it sounds. Travel writers have to genuinely love traveling and

be able to find their way in very unfamiliar places. A genuine love for traveling encompasses a lot of things, too. It means that they should be comfortable in riding whatever accommodation that will take to get to their destination—from taxis to buses to airplanes to motorcycles to bicycles to camels and other animals. It also means that they should be willing to stay in various accommodations—from the cheapest hostels to the most expensive five-star hotels and resorts. Travel writers need to have the inherent knack for being able to get around unfamiliar places among people who don't even speak English. This is one of the challenges that travel writers constantly meet on the job.

Aside from covering accommodations, travel writers may also be tasked to cover celebrations and festivals. To be able to give an accurate picture of the activity, the writer must be present and experience the revelry in all its fullness. While they are enjoying the action, they should still be alert enough to note the various issues that travelers should watch out for. These include safety concerns, the food that can be tried and others.

Travel writers also include the actual travel experience in various modes of transport that get them to their destination. They will reveal practical tips such as where the traveler should get their ticket and how much they should pay for it, what stop to get off at in order to arrive at a particular destination and if there are other safety issues that travelers should watch out for when they ride public transportation.

After experiencing a destination, travel writers then record their reviews and observations about it. They also choose the pictures or video that would accompany their write-up. They would then send the articles to their editor who will do the final edits before putting it to print. The length of time that travel writers are given to submit their articles to their editors vary depending on how in-depth the coverage is. There are some travel guide publishers that commission a travel writer to write one whole guidebook for an entire country.

Information about traveling is important; there are few magazines in India.

Various magazines in field of travelling:

- **Outlook Traveler:** Outlook Traveler is India's No.1 travel magazine. This magazine is recognized for its quirky, stylish, and elegant reading. The contributors travel far, wide, and deep to bring fabulous and honest tales for their readers.
- **Lonely Planet:** Lonely Planet India written by Indian authors, is able to provide authentic and independent information especially based on Indian Travelers need. The magazine ensures a better travel planning as well as a memorable holiday to share.
- **Travel Plus:** Travel Plus presents the Indian states deeply. It gives the articles straight from a Traveler's heart.
- **Discover India:** Discover India reflects diverse aspects of India. It deals with India's philosophy, history, culture, architecture, fashion, art, and folklore in both ancient and modern context.

Travel blogs

In the 21st century, travel literature became a genre of social media in the form of travel blogs, with travel bloggers using outlets like personal blogs, Pinterest, Twitter, and Instagram to convey information about their adventures, and provide advice for navigating particular countries, or for traveling generally. Travel blogs were among the first instances of blogging, which began in the mid 1990s.

Travel journals

Goethe's Italian Journey between September 1786 and May 1788

A travel journal, also called road journal, is a record made by a Traveler, sometimes in diary form, of the traveler's experiences, written during the course of the journey and later edited for publication. This is a long-established literary format; an early example is the writing of Pausanias (2nd century AD) who produced his *Description of Greece* based on his own observations. James Boswell published his *The Journal of a Tour to the Hebrides* in 1786 and Goethe published his *Italian Journey*, based on diaries, in 1816. Fannie Calderón de la Barca, the Scottish-born wife of

the Spanish ambassador to Mexico 1839–1842, wrote *Life in Mexico*, an important travel narrative of her time there, with many observations of local life. A British traveler, Mrs Alec Tweedie, published a number of travelogues, ranging from Denmark (1895) and Finland (1897), to the U.S. (1913). A more recent example is Che Guevara's *The Motorcycle Diaries*.

Types of travel writing

When we're talking about travel writing, there are a couple of distinctions to be made. There are:

- **Travelogues** (journal/itinerary style, actual reports about someone's trip)
- **Travel stories** (a realistic narration about a journey, meant for a wider audience and usually with a certain literary value to it)
- **Travel guides** (publication with practical information and tips/advice about a certain destination, meant for people that want to visit that place).

In all travel writing, the focus lies on accounts of real or imaginary places. It may range from documentary to the evocative, from literary to journalistic and from humorous to serious. You can find it in books, magazines and nowadays more and more online. You don't need to be a professional-level writer to start with. Try starting a blog, and you might find that it becomes rather popular. The reason for this is that those with your cultural background or a similar one will find the blog and know that the information within it is interesting and relevant to their interests.

Top 8 Indian travel journalists

- **Lakshmi Sharath:** She started her journey as a media professional but then she was also a Traveler, travel writer and a photographer. She has been an active blogger and shares some of the best travelling experiences. Her blog 'A travel blog of an Indian Backpacker' has interesting stories about her amazing experiences in India.
- **Shivya Nath:** Her travel blog 'The Shooting Star' has captured a lot of attention for the adventures she has come across. Be it her captivating travel stories or marvellous shots.
- **Mridula Dwivedi:** **Mridula Dwivedi**, an Indian travel writer. Her blog 'Travel Tales from India & Abroad' have some of the best travel stories. She has very recently featured in Via.com.

- **Venkat Ganesh:** When it comes to a road trip on a bike I am sure Venkat Ganesh's blog will leave your eyes wide open. Known for his amazing solo bike trip.
- His blog 'India Backpack Motorbike' chronicles some of his amazing travel experiences.
- **Prasad Np:** His blog has a lot to tell you about the majestic beauty of India. From holy temples to various religious places his blog has it all. Prasad is truly an inspiration for the upcoming travel junkies. He loves to write a lot about the Wildlife, Nature, and conservation. His blogs also include interesting tales from the countries he has visited especially US, Thailand, Singapore, Jordan etc.
- **Dheeraj Sharma:** A night dreamer and a passionate lover of the Himalayas.
- His blog 'Devil on Wheel' carries a lot of travel stories.
- **Rachel Jones:** Currently residing in Goa, Rachel's blog 'Hippie in Heels' shares a lot of amazing stories of different places around the globe.
- Photography is an integral part of travel journalism, as visual are the best methods of portraying emotions and telling story.

Top 5 travel photographers

- **Sourabh Gandhi:** Can one be a good engineer, traveler, and photographer all at once? Well, only if you're Sabby! Forget pictures, his entire Instagram account is a masterpiece in itself, featuring a diverse range of photographs that mostly cater to travel and experiences.
- **Subhash Chandra:** Among the best Indian travel photographers, Subhash loves to travel to different parts of India for his pictures, specially Himalayas. An avid traveler and trekking enthusiast, Subhash brings something new and unique to the concept of photography every time his Instagram profile is blessed with a new picture!
- **George Koruth:** Describing himself as an avid "Documentary & Travel Photographer" George strives to share the glorious stories & colours of India. A peek at his gallery will reveal a profound glimpse at India and will totally beguile you! Apart from the subject, he makes sure his compositions have intriguing backdrops and well-placed elements.

- **Siddhartha Joshi:** Though he usually focuses on portraits, his travel photography too is mind blowing. He uses different angles and dimensions to click his subjects, be it people, landscapes, or monuments, and that is what adds that unmistakable charm to his work and keeps viewers glued to his profile.
- **Aakash Naresh:** The first thing people usually utter post a look at his work is ‘WOW’. The awe is then followed by a deep feeling of jealousy at the amount of time this talented photographer spends amid scenic hills and snowy mountains. The perfect mixture of colours, composition, and the most mind boggling backdrops, his pictures make viewers fall in love with them each time!

Becoming a travel journalist (Scope)

- Choose the right course of study. You can go for a four-year general journalism degree at a top journalism school, which will certainly open doors, or consider an online course specifically for travel journalism (as well as travel photography).

While a degree is not necessary if you plan to remain a freelancer, if you are looking for a steady-paycheck type of job, it can make a difference.

- Sometimes the best way into a staff job at a media outlet is to start as an intern, and although interns are often selected from an applicant pool filled with journalism or communications students, it’s not always the case – sometimes those with good writing skills, a passion for the job, and a positive and enthusiastic mindset will get the internship. It’s a great way to learn the ropes and build a network (see below) of industry contacts.
- Develop a network of other writers, editors, and publishers. The best way to do this is to attend workshops and conferences where you can continue your education, learn to improve your writing, and make new professional contacts.
- Get started! Start small, with your local paper or a local magazine.

Job Opportunities in Travel journalism:

- There are many options you can opt for. You can look for a travel magazine or write for newspapers covering the travel news. Otherwise, you can get into web writing and work for the various travel websites like

- Makemytrip.com,*yatra.com,*travelguru.com

Job opportunities

- Travel Bloggers, Tour Guides, Photographers, Travel Journalists, Writers, Video Jockey, Commercial pilots, Food columnists , Vloggers, Travel shows on platform like YouTube, Freelancing is the correct way for Travel Journalists, Travel Journalism has quite a scope in the Print Media. Not generally in Newspapers but in Various lifestyles Magazines that are published throughout.

Conclusion

Travel & Tourism sector is growing gradually in India whether is it through professional journalism, freelancing or by tourism agencies. Various varieties of traveling are growing day by day in India like health tourism, spiritual tourism, business tourism etc. India being the fastest growing economy has adopted several methods of growing tourism as it is a boon to Indian economy. Earlier people in India were not aware about travelling as recreation and enjoyment but gradually it has adopted such culture. Keeping this in mind government of India has taken initiatives for tourism growth through advertisement. People are also adopting freelancing methods of writing, blogging and vlogging. Foreign countries have already adopted various courses in the field of travel journalism. They have respected media houses and broadcasting channels and shows. Travelling journalism in India is also growing very fast and becoming popular specially among youth. Youth in India aspires to make career in the field of journalism along with travelling, keeping this in mind India has created many job opportunities for aspiring new comers. Several Tv shows such as Yatra, Musafir hu yaaron, Highway on my plate, Humsafar etc. OMG! Yeh mera India are few examples of growth of travel journalism in India.

So it is concluded that there is need from scholars, practitioners and researchers to show interest in travelling journalism help in growing this sector in various ways.

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Food for thoughts (reading for pleasure): an innovative medium for enhancing self-efficacy of students

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Abstract

This study has been conducted to study the impact of reading for pleasure on self-efficacy of adolescent girls. Samples of 100 girls from Shri Ram Collage Muzaffernagar (U.P.), who are studying in first year of graduation, were selected from accidental sampling method. Sample was divided in to two groups, 50 in experimental group and 50 in control group. Reading for pleasure was selected as the independent variable, which was applied for 5 days a week 3 months where girls used to read holistic books written by Shantikunj Publications. Self-efficacy of girls was assessed using the „self-efficacy scale“. Statistical analysis of the data was performed using the SPSS software (version 18) the result indicated that there was a significant difference between experimental and control group on the level of self-efficacy of adolescent girls. The findings of this study indicate that reading for pleasure significantly improved the level of self-efficacy of adolescent girls, and it is good method as food for thoughts.

Keywords: reading for pleasure, self-efficacy

Introduction

Reading for pleasure is a form of play that allows us to experience other worlds and roles in our imagination. Reading can represent an interaction with text in a variety of formats for a variety of purposes. Research from the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2002) showed that reading enjoyment is more important for children’s educational success than their family’s socio-economic status. Reading for pleasure could therefore be one important way to help combat social exclusion and raise educational standards. According to Cunningham and Stanovich (1998) Correlational studies have also consistently shown that those who read more are better readers. Indeed, reading amount and

reading achievements are thought to be reciprocally related to each other—as reading amount increases, reading achievement increases, which in turn increases reading amount and according to Pressley (2000), “the frequent admonition for children to „Read, read, read“ makes sense in that extensive reading promotes fluency, vocabulary, and background knowledge.” Events focusing on reading for pleasure can also promote or enhance social skills in children (e.g. Allan, Ellis and Pearson, 2005; The Reading Agency, 2006). It has also been shown to combat feelings of loneliness in adults (Rane-Szostak and Herth, 1995). Overall, when individuals read for pleasure frequently, “they experience the value of reading as efferent and aesthetic processes. Thus, they are more likely to read with a sense of purpose, which further supports their developing reading habit” (Sanacore, 2002).

According to Benton and Fox (1985) stories provide the possibility of educating the feelings and can offer their readers potential growth points for the development of a more subtle awareness of human behavior. Wynne and Ryan (1993): children need to hear moral stories in order to develop moral literacy and moral character.

Dependent variable for the present study is self-efficacy. During the past two decades, self-efficacy has emerged as a highly effective predictor of students’ motivation and learning. Bandura (1997) notes it is possible conceptually to have high self-efficacy about a capability that one does not particularly esteem as well as the reverse. As a performance-based measure of perceived capability, self-efficacy differs conceptually and psychometrically from related motivational constructs, such as outcome expectations, self-concept, or locus of control. Researchers have succeeded in verifying its discriminant validity as well as convergent validity in predicting common motivational outcomes, such as students’ activity choices, effort, persistence, and emotional reactions.

Self-efficacy beliefs have been found to be sensitive to subtle changes in students’ performance context, to interact with self-regulated learning processes, and to mediate students’ academic achievement. According to Bandura (1997) that self-efficacious students participate more readily, work harder, persist longer, and have fewer adverse emotional reactions when they encounter difficulties than do those who doubt their capabilities.

Objectives of the study

The objective of the present research is to study the impact of reading for pleasure writing on student's self-efficacy.

Statement of study

To study the impact of reading for pleasure on self-efficacy of adolescent girls.

Hypothesis

There is no significant difference between self-efficacy of pre-mid and post conditions of experimental group.

There no significant difference between self-efficacy of pre-mid and post conditions of control and experimental group.

Limitation of the Study

The study is confined to the district of Muzaffernagar of Uttar Pradesh.

Only one college of district Muzaffernagar is included in the present study.

The study is confined to adolescent girls only.

The study is confined to graduate students only.

Methodology

Sample and Sampling

Total sample size of 100 students was selected from Shri Ram Group of Colleges from district Muzaffernagar from Uttar Pradesh. Accidental sampling method was used in the study. Accidental sampling is also known as convenience sampling in which a researcher includes people who are easy to reach or a targeted population or convenience population.

Inclusive criteria-

only adolescent girls of age range- 16-18 years, who are regularly attending college after successfully their 12th standard, were selected in this study.

Tool used-

Self-efficacy scale developed by sonali sood was used. In this scale total 10 items are included and this scale is standardized for 22 years below students.

Research design-

In this study, experimental and control groups design was used. This design comprises of two groups, out of which one group was given the treatment and the data was gathered at the pre-condition stage before starting the intervention and post-condition after completing the intervention schedule. The control group received no treatment, over the same period of time, but underwent exactly the same tests. From this method researcher can compare pre-post test result between experimental and control groups.

Procedure

In order to collect data, the experimental method was used. The sample of the study consisted of 100 adolescent students. Only female students of graduation first year were taken from the Shri Ram Group of Colleges. All the students were divided equally into two groups" namely experimental group and control group. Each group comprised of 50 students each. Before starting the experiment base-line data of self-efficacy was collected from both the groups using the self-efficacy scale. Then the experimental group was asked to read Akhand Jyoti and Panchatantra book. It was continued for 5 days per week for a period of three months. Meanwhile, the control group was not asked to do anything. 45 days later, both the groups were assessed for mid condition data and again after 3 months both the groups were assessed for post-condition data using the same scales. In order to statistically analyze the collected data and test the research hypothesis, the investigator applied ANOVA (analysis of variance) using SPSS software version 18.

Result analysis

In order to test the hypothesis, the investigator applied ANOVA (analysis of variance) through SPSS version 18 and used multiple comparison and tukey for result analysis.

Experimental and control group design table

Table-1: Data analysis of Means, Standard Deviation and std. error of self-efficacy of pre, mid, and post condition of experimental group.

Table-1
Descriptive

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error
Pre-test	50	22.40	5.19	.73
Mid-test	50	28.84	3.71	.52
Post-test	50	33.56	4.07	.57

From **Table-2** we can see that, the significance value of our experimental group is .000, which is below 0.01 levels. And therefore, there is a satisfactory difference in the means between the pre-mid and post condition of experimental group.

Table-2
ANOVA
Self-Efficacy

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	3138.29	2	1569.147	81.94	.000
Within Groups	2815.04	147	19.150		
	5953.33				
Total		149			

From the result so far, we know that there is statistically significant difference between the groups as a whole. Now the multiple comparison table shows which groups are different from each other. We can see from **Table-3** that there is statistically significant difference between pre-test and mid-test condition of experiment group (mean difference=-6.44, p. value is=.000) as well as between the pre-test and post-test results of experimental group (mean difference =-11.16, p value=.000,) and between mid-test and post-test condition also (mean difference= -4.72, p value is=.000) .

Table -3
Multiple Comparison

(i)condition	(j)condition	Mean Difference (i-j)	Std. Error	Sig.
Pre-test of self-	Mid-test of self-	-6.44	.87	.000

efficacy	efficacy			
Pre-test of self-	Post-test of self-	-11.16	.87	.000
efficacy	efficacy			
Mid-test of self-	Post-test of self-	-4.72	.87	.000
efficacy	efficacy			

*. The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table-4: test analysis of Means, Standard Deviation and std. error of self-efficacy of pre, mid and post condition of control group.

Table-4
Descriptive

	N	Mean	Std.Deviation	Std.Error
Pre-test	50	28.60	5.12	.72
Mid-test	50	29.64	5.18	.73
Post-test	50	29.42	4.63	.65

From the table -5 we can see that, the significant value of experimental group is .60, which is above 0.05 levels. Which is not proven statistically satisfactory difference in the means between the pre-mid and post condition of control group.

Table-5
ANOVA
Self-efficacy

Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.						
Between Groups	30.04	2	15.02							
					Within Groups	3657.70	147	24.88	.60	.54
	3687.74	149								
Total										

We can see from the table-6 that there is not statistically significant difference between pre-test and mid-test condition of control group (mean difference=-1.04, p. value is=.55)as well as between

the pre-test and post-test results of control group(mean difference =-.82, p value=.59,) and between mid-test and post-test condition also (mean difference= -.22, p value is=.97) .

Table-6
Multiple Comparisons

(i)condition (j)condition Mean Diffrence (i-j)
Std.Error Sig.
Pre-test of self-efficacy Mid-test of selfefficacy
-1.04 .99 .55
Pre-test of self-efficacy Post-test of selfefficacy
-.82 .99 .59
Mid-test of selfefficacy
Post-test of selfefficacy
.22 .99 .97

Result

It was found in this study that reading for pleasure significantly affects girl’s self-efficacy. The higher mean in favor of post- test of experimental group indicates that reading practice significantly enhances self-efficacy of girls as compared to control group.

Conclusion

These findings are as according to previous research reviews as According to According to Guthrie and Wigfield (2000), reading motivation is a multifaceted construct that includes reading goals, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, and self-efficacy and social motivation for reading. Krashen (1993) said that it is a major proponent of the value of reading for pleasure: When children read for pleasure, when they get “hooked on books”, they acquire, involuntarily and without conscious effort, nearly all of the so-called “language skills” many people are so concerned about: they will become adequate readers, acquire a large vocabulary, develop the ability to understand and use complex grammatical constructions, develop a good writing style, and become good (but not necessarily perfect) spellers. Although free voluntary reading alone will not ensure attainment of the highest levels of literacy, it will at least ensure an acceptable level. And this process enhances automatically student’s self-efficacy. facing at present.

A study on interrelation approach of Environment and Culture for Sustainable Development

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Abstract

Environment is everything that is around us. It can be living or non-living things. It includes physical, chemical, and other natural forces. In the environment, there are different interaction between animals, plants, soil, water, and other living and non-living things. It is usual to find the term “culture” used without further explanation or classification. Culture itself evolved with humans and thus plays a role even at that level, including insight into how human environment evolved.

So, the researcher has tried to inculcate the topics in the research paper to enlighten the thoughts and mind of person as by culture, Environment, proportionality of environment and culture, impact of environment on culture, modern scenario, culture and environmental degradation, causes of environment and cultural degradation, mitigation, interpretation and discussion and at last conclusion.

As the developing modern era and existence of scientific and modern life, affect the culture as well as environment thereby affecting the sustainability. Culture and Environment are directly proportional to each other. They work for each other and that’s why preserving culture is actually sustaining the Environment & at the same time protecting Environment is being taught in our Culture as our prior duty towards Sustainability. Through this research paper, researcher wants to bring the importance and Indian ethical privilege of culture and environment, its interrelation along with the impact of culture on environment and impact of environment on culture for making sustainable mother Nature which is only. Ultimately one can easily sustain its culture to sustain environment or sustain environment to establish its culture.

Keywords: Culture, Environment, Sustainability, and development. INTRODUCTION

The word ‘culture’ derives from a French term which in turn derives from the Latin ‘colere’ which means tend to the earth and grow or cultivate and nurture. “It shows its etymology with a number of other words related to actively fostering growth”.

We have heard about different types of culture like Western culture, Eastern culture, Latin culture, Middle east culture, African culture. etc but in real sense Culture, is the art of working. Culture means to follow our norms, values, and ethics in a sustainable manner. Culture is the precious heritage to remold, rejuvenate, the sum of purity, piety and integrity with happiness. Culture means to sustain the utilities and explore of the needs and nature with goods. Culture is the most ancient art or we can say the most precious response of humans towards the society and nature. Culture plays a very important role in sustaining environment. It contains lots of religious, ethical, and normative values in it.

Our culture, The Indian culture is the world’s most vast and exploring culture with the history of warm blooded leaders, beauty of nature, essence of scriptures and having the variance and adaptability and religions with their respect towards the God and Environment. Culture is a word for peoples ‘way of life’ meaning the way groups do things. Different group of people may have different cultures. A culture is passed on to the next generation by learning, whereas genetics are passed on by heredity. The concept of culture is very complicated and the word has many meanings. The word ‘culture’ is most commonly used in three ways:

- Excellence of taste in the fine arts and humanities, also known as high culture.
- An integral pattern of human knowledge, belief, and behaviour
- The outlook, attitudes, values, morals, goals and custom shared by a society.

Culture is the characteristic and knowledge of a particular group of people, encompassing language, religion, cuisine, social habits and music arts. Culture is made of 4-inter-related parts: Physical environment, level of technology, social organization, system of symbols.

Environment (“THE GAURDIAN”): The natural world as a whole or in a particular geographical area, especially as affected by human activity.

Environment is everything that is around us. It can be living or non-living organism or things. It includes physical, chemical, and other natural forces. Living things live in their environment. They constantly interact with it and adapt themselves to conditions in their environment. A person’s environment is the event and culture that the person lived in. A person's belief and action depends

on his environment. The sum total of all surroundings of a living organism, including natural forces and other living things, which provides conditions for development and growth as well as danger and damage. In general theory of system, an environment is a complex of external factors that act on a system and determine their way of existence. An environment could be considered a superset in which the given system is a subset. It can consist of one or more parameters, physical or other nature. The atmosphere of a given system must necessarily interact with living beings. The environment is not anything other than the middle, precisely the place or space in which different life related processes are carried out. The biggest problem that present in the environment today is one that has to do with the damage that man has been causing him to it in recent centuries. In this sense, we must say that the environment may present changes or natural disturbances that have to do with the physical space or even the action of different plant and animal's species (such as for example when generating a phenomenon known as plague)

Proportionality of Environment and Culture

This topic within the broader context of Environment Behaviour Relationship (EBR). In this way, the role of culture can be seen in light of other aspects of this set of relationship. It is therefore not claimed that culture is the only relevant consideration although it is claimed that it is a central and inescapable one. Major emphasis is placed on clarifying the concepts used and making the concepts and the relationship among them more operational. This is essential in order to make it possible to use these concepts in both analysis and design. A major goal here is to make the topic more concrete, specific and manageable since at the moment it is rather vague. It is like the weather: everyone talks about it but no one does anything about it mainly because they do not know how. At the same time the discussion is kept general to make it applicable to all cultures, all types of environment, and all types of problems and so on. Over the past few years culture – environment relationship has been among the most active and lively areas of Environment Behavior Studies (EBS) not only has this topic been prominent at meetings of the Environmental Design Research Association (EDRA), but there are two series of conference aerated specifically to this topic. This is also the case in other fields where the role and effects of culture, previously unrecognized, neglected or minimized, have been influential. This is the case in areas as diverse as developmental disorders, sports, employment, development policies, language development, medicines and medical practices and psychology (with cross cultural psychology as a major field). One also finds the concept of culture and cultural approaches being applied to institutions, as in the use of 'cooperative culture' in office studies and to profession (including architecture). The reason for these development have to do with the inescapable and central role that culture plays in

all aspects of human behaviour, cognition, affect , preference , and meaning .

Operationalizing the concept of culture

The first concern the nature of statement about the relation between culture and environment. These tend to assume implicitly that culture and designed environments are equivalent units, in the sense that they are equal in “scale”.

Culture is vast domain; built form is a small part of it and also a subset of it. The latter is, as it were, embedded in the former. This makes the nature of relationship between them, and the nature of the translation process of one into the other rather difficult to grasp. Without resolving either the nature of the relationship or the translocation process, it is essential that this difficulty be born in mind.

Impact of Environment on culture

It is virtually impossible to link culture to build environment, it is feasible to relate them to family and recreational institutions, sex, and other roles, social networks, or status hierarchies. It should be emphasized that “culture” is a theoretical construct, it exists by definition and is a conceptual summary shorthand for particular conjunctions of a great variety of human phenomenon. No one has ever seen or ever will see or observe culture, only its effect, expression, or products. One in this making inference about an unobservable entity, that presents no instrument able problems if the nature of the entity is borne in mind. The reason concerns the impossibility of wind the “culture”. It can be suggested that culture is both too abstract and too general to be useful. It is often useful to clarify excessively broad and abstract concepts by “dismantling” them and then studying the components and the ways in which the other variables (eg, components of built environment) over the years I have developed two complementary ways of responding to twin problems of excessive abstractness and excessive generality. Life styles leads to activities and activity system, the specific of which began to explain the diversity of environment and hence their links with culture. Together, life styles and activities are extremely useful in analysing and designing environments. Lifestyles groups are extremely useful since most other criteria for groups membership such as age, sex, ethnicity, religion, caste, occupation, tribe, and ideology historically used to define groups, can be expressed in terms of lifestyle.

The Environment as Cultural Landscape

It is important to note that people do not live just in buildings, to outdoor settings, both built and “natural”. The result is that they use the cultural and landscape that they use the cultural and landscape that is the subject matter of study and of environmental design. The term comes from geography and refers to any part of the surface of the earth that has been modified by human’s action. But by now the whole earth has been transformed by such action, including the most remote and natural looking rainforest they have been modified, ranging from those least modified (which we call natural) to settlements which have been most modified.

Modern scenario: “Development is the need of living”

No matter what culture of a people are part of, one thing is for certain, it will change. Culture appears to have become key in our interconnected world, which is made up of so many ethnically diverse societies, but also riddle by conflicts association with religion, ethnicity, ethical beliefs , and essentially the elements which make up culture. But culture is no longer fixed, it in eve was. It is emotionally fluid and constantly in motion. This makes it so that it is difficult to define any culture in only one way.

While change is inevitable, the past should also be respected and presented. The United Nations has created a group called The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) to identify culture and natural heritage and to conserve and protect its monuments, buildings, and silts are covered by the groups protection, according to internationally treaty. The convention concerning the protection of the world cultural and natural heritage. This treaty has adopted by UNESCO in1972.

Need of sustainability:

- Sustainability is the ability to continue a defined behaviour indefinitely.
- Environment sustainability is the ability to maintain rates of renewable resources harvest, pollution creation and non-renewable resources depletion that can be continued indefinitely.
- Social sustainability is the ability of a social system such as a country to function at a defined level of social well-being indefinitely.
- "Sustainability is we are making the future the cause of our present"
- Environment and Cultural Degradation: “over use of anything causes degradation”

As a defining attribute is an inescapable aspect of any human phenomenon including how people shape environment, use them and interact with them. It also involves the meanings they give to environmental elements, their preferences and notion of environmental quality, image, ideals and schemata. People has the greatest impact on the environment in the ways that they exploit natural resources and dispose of waste. Different human cultures have had varying effect in their environment. Some cultures particularly hunter gathered small scale agricultural societies, have little environmental impact.

How Does Environment Affects Agriculture?

Culture is greatly affected by environment. As ‘Rolland B.Dixon’ said in his book “The Building of Culture” , culture leans most heavily upon environment (Dixon 12) The three parts of culture that affects culture are as stated by Dixon: “Topography”, climate and nitrobacterial and that are component may tend to influence culture in an direction of development ,another in another (Dixon13).This means that each of these components of environment changes in its own way. Climate is a huge factor in different cultures. If a group of people live in cold place, they will most likely wear thicker clothes, opposed to these clothes worn by people in warm places. Also, the climate affects crops that can be grown, animals living in an area, what houses look like and so on. Topography affects culture also. For e.g. People living nears lakes will be more into trading and fishing than people living in prairie, who will be more dependent on forming and hunting. Second, if people live on flat land and they will most likely grow crops, whereas in mountain region the people will be more relevant on hunting (mountain culture). Lastly topography affects housing in some countries, such as Indonesia, the people there built their house on stilts to avoid marshes and flooding. Lastly, raw material affects culture, if an area is full of trees; people are more likely to build houses out of wood rather than stone or concrete.

Causes of Cultural practices and Environmental Degradation

Cultural practices lead to many rituals and ethical values, related to the earth and environment in the ethical concept and norms values. Which sometimes leads to environmental degradation, due to its over exploitation and uses.

It leads to

- Environmental pollution (Air, water, soil)
- Agricultural destruction

- Over exploitation of pilgrimage uses
- Degradation and over use of natural heritage and natural era. Most importantly, in the modern era or today's aspect mental pollution and environmental pollution causes the cultural as well as environmental degradation. [11]
[SEP]

Mental pollution: Today mental pollution can be defined as arrogance is a barrier that stops people to understand each other. The pollution of man's mind by such pollutants as selfishness, jealousy, greed, anger, and lust is responsible for the disequilibrium apparent in all aspects of today's world the greatest danger lies in the fact that humanity does not recognize that a polluted mind manifests itself by making the atmosphere dense and viscous. Mental pollution has spoiled the socio-economic atmosphere and political climate everywhere and has made man fight man, nation prepare itself militarily against nation, and allowed one person to exploit many others by subjecting them monetarily, politically, militarily, sexually and in other ways. Mental pollution is a global problem because every man is affected in one many or another.

Environmental Pollution:

Agricultural Destruction: The destruction of the rainforest for agricultural use is due to two groups; poor farmers with cattle ranches and agricultural companies converting the rain forest in mono cultural land for animal grazing. The farmers use the slash and burn technique to clean patches of forest for short term use. They move on to clear a new patch of forest after a few years because the soil gets exhausted of nutrients. Some cultural aspects also sometimes degrade the agriculture fields, due to set of norms and values. while these are made for its crop yield and more plantation offering and practicing ethical values. but because of its over exploitation agriculture is destructing.

Over exploitation of pilgrimage uses: Large scale movement of visitors during pilgrimage has a high potential to influence the environmental effects are governed by seasonality and are limited over time and space.

Degradation and Over Use of natural heritage (Deterioration of our cultural heritage); over cultural heritage is being destroyed faster today than at any time in the past. An understanding of the basic processes causing, deterioration of ancient artefacts is urgently needed.

Mitigation: AS we studied further how environment and culture are directly proportional to each other, but one step can make them inversely proportional to each other, but one step can make

them inversely proportional in the damage or loss and deterioration. we need some steps of concerning over our culture as well as over our environment. so, how can it be mitigated shown below:

- By conceptualizing the concept of 3 R's; in both the aspects of culture and environment, because over of everything is dangerous. 3R's; Reduce, Reuse, Recycle.
- By the acceptance of all casts, religion, culture, people, and all as the child of mother earth
- By following laws, rules, acts and principles or norms related to environment, culture and self.
- To be aware at each step and at working at individual level.
- Stop thinking start acting $\left[\begin{array}{c} \text{I} \\ \text{SEP} \end{array} \right]$

Interpretation and Discussion:

By the means of this research paper, researcher tried to enlighten or focus on the modern scenario and conditions in relevance to Culture and its impact on the environment, or we can say the environment and its impact on the culture. Both the things are interdisciplinary, as both are complementary to each other. Today, the things are so much changed with modernization as well as for the ethical values concern which affects over the realm of the nation and its cultural values. As both the topics which are precious and complementary to each other, shows the existence of human and presence of human on this planet Earth. Researcher tried to cover all the topics which are degrading the root of culture and environment and how it can be mitigated. Much scientific development and much human inhabited development lead to destruction of the comprehensive values. As, the development of anything is considered to be beneficial , at an extent , while the implementation of cultural values and ethics has been made to make the human society or we can say the sociality can be under a boundary of positive limitations , same as environment is the over explored gift of nature , which has no boundaries to protect human as well as living society , while other hand ,the culture is made to protect , to offer the prayer to that environment as on the behalf of living God . By following all the norms, values, ethics, and rules. Culture can be sustained and it can sustain the human life with nature's respect.

Conclusion:

The effect of environment on culture, is the realistic principle relates to human life ,by the means of this research paper , it is a medium to show the reality of life and human ,that how they change the pre-existing era and the utilities provided by the nature and culture .It is concluded that the culture makes the realm of human behaviour , character and thought rather than the environment builds up the existence and presence of distance of human in the society and on the earth. As, environment and culture are interdisciplinary and complementary to each other, this shows that the pre-existence or inculcation and creation of God is present till now in an architectural form, with complete management; but there is a lack of one concern towards the meet of one's self with himself . To know itself, it's cultural values and environmental offerings. Today people are on the way of high speedy development ,with change in its thoughts ,values ,and individual nature which pulled back the cultural values and environment so far away from him , and although such development leads to success , economy and many more , but it also pretends to hazardous degradation and destruction for upcoming generation thereby questioning sustainability, as in the aspect of pollution ,land degradation ,forest degradation ,water scarcity ,global warming and many more with , died human nature ,ethical values and over whelming of negative values on human , leads to increasing crimes , murder, caste ,family destruction , biodiversity loss , sacred gross deterioration ,loss of sacred plants , and destruction of human values. So Each one of us should focus on sustainable development if we really want to leave something productive for our future., Environment & Culture both should be preserved, conserved & sustained all together.

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A Study on Patalkot ki rasoi - new venture of tribal food for promoting tribal culture and tourism with reference of Tamia, Madhya Pradesh

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Abstract

Tribal food, tribal culture and tribal tourism are emerging trend and major research area in the field of tourism. This paper discusses the tribal food, Patalkot tourism, Patalkot ki Rasoi - tribal traditional food culture and its role in tribal tourism with specific reference to Tamia, Madhya Pradesh which have majority of tribal populations respectively. This study aims to make a valuable contribution to tribal tourism by a new venture of tribal food and Patalkot ki rasoi. There are specific key themes for this study as 'Tribal', 'culture', 'food' and 'tourism'. This study used convenience purposive techniques for collecting primary and secondary data. Tribal food and culture has many possibilities to promote tourism in tribal territory. Presently various aspects of tribal food, tribal culture and tribal tourism are still to be explored.

Keywords: Patalkot ki rasoi, tribal, culture, food, tourism.

Introduction

Tourism is an extensively growing sector in India. There are many categories of tourism one of them is tribal tourism. We have focused on Tamia tehsil in Madhya Pradesh. Tamia is a completely surrounded by dense forests. We also focused on the Patalkot. The meaning of 'Patalkot' is the land away from surface. Patal is a Sanskrit word which mean is very deep. It is situated in the Tamia

block of the Chindwara district. Pataalkot valley is known for its flora, fauna and tribal culture. Pataalkot spread around the hills which depth is 2750 to 3250 feet. Looking down from the top of the valley at Pataalkot, the place takes the shape of a horse shoe. The deep and dense forests also make Tamia a place of vast ecological and botanic diversity. Tamia is a well-maintained block from the British time. Tamia is one of the hidden treasures of Madhya Pradesh.

Tribal are main inhabitants of this district in rural areas (B. P. Singh & N. Kanungo, 2017). The tribal community is the oldest residential people of this place and also they are following their unique culture in present days. “Gonds and Bharias mainly constitute the population of Pataalkot. It is said that Bharias have been living here for more than 500 years. Tribal men, women and children wear traditional dresses during their festive times and enjoy it (Mona Dwivedi & Anita Sakalle, 2014). One of them is Bharia; Bharia is a tribal community who is living there since hundreds of years. The natives Bharia women, who live there know how to collect and grow the plants that’s they needed for food, clothing and building their homes. More than 2,000 natives live. Cohen, E., & Avieli, N. (2004) believed that food in tourism is an important aspect. Pataalkot ki rasoi is a concept which is developed by Mr. Pavan Shrivastava, director of the tribscapes a tourism center. Pataalkot ki rasoi means a concept of Pataalkot where they provide various healthy food made by local natural resources. The location Map of Tamia is shown in Fig. 1

Review of Literature

- Smith, V. L. (1996) is examined tribal tourism “In terms of the four criteria of tribal or ethnic tourism development is that Habitat, Heritage, History and Handicrafts.”
- Subhash Chandra (2017) Visited Tamia and written down “this visit of Tamia area has been an experience, which is extraordinary and I learnt a lot on Nature and what it has been giving to mankind. Through it is also a known fact that mankind has grossly organized it”
- Sebastian, L. M., & Rajagopalan, P. (2009). Said about development and sustainability “tourism as a development strategy in Kerala, tourism's contributions to the development processes and the sustainability of tourism activities remain unexplored.”
- Erik Cohen & Nir Avieli (2004) according to him “The common perception of food as a mere attraction in tourism is challenged by stressing the complications and impediments experienced by tourists in the local culinary sphere in unfamiliar destinations, even when

attracted to the local cuisine. Hygiene standards, health considerations, communication gaps, and the limited knowledge of tourists concerning the local cuisine are discussed, while the role of ethnic restaurants at home in preparing tourists for the food abroad is questioned.”

- S. Prasad, s. D. Singh and v. Kumari (2013) highlighted “ecotourism is one among the fastest growing segment of tourism Industry. Ecotourism both at conceptual and empirical levels is significant in a number of respects. Traditionally it encapsulates scientific, aesthetic, and philosophical approaches which reflect the structure and function of the society.”
- Govt. of Madhya Pradesh, started a project named “Madhya Pradesh tourism board” (2017) with the help of this initiative they introduced Tamia as “It is a picturesque forest destination that offers scenic and breath-taking views of dense forests and mountains. Untouched and unexplored, Tamia is the perfect location to disconnect from the world and experience absolute tranquility. A few houses on the hill top offer panoramic views of the steep hills, vast greenery and deep valleys. Inaccessible for a very long time, Tamia has stayed away from any form of commercialization, and makes for the perfect monsoon getaway. The experience is akin to visiting the forests depicted in your childhood books and cartoons!”

3. Research objectives

- The goal of this paper is to determine the role of Patalkot ki rasoi in tribal tourism. To achieve this goal the following objectives are defined:
 - To introduce the untouched tribal food;
 - To study the Patalkot ki rasoi - new venture of tourism;
 - To explore the possibilities for tourism of Patalkot;

4. Tribal Food and Tourism

Chowdhary, A., & Singh, V. (2009) Commented on Pachmarhi, “Pachmarhi is a queen of the satpura (satpura is a vast forest region of Madhya Pradesh).” Tamia is located very near by Panchmarhi. The beautiful Tamia surrounded by steep hills, vast greenery and deep valley states

mostly have tribal's, who have their own distinct methods of cooking and food habits. The tribal people of Tamia has so far managed to preserve their ancient rituals, customs and culture even in today's modern world. Besides the modern cuisine; tribals are using traditional food habits. Wild fruits, roots and tubers, leafy vegetables, spinach, and honey is main food items. Grains, vegetables and mushroom are collected by the tribes during summer and monsoon and preserved for future use. Arhar, tuar, mung, masur some pulses exclusive consume by them. Tribals are mostly depending on forest produce. Tamia is a tourist place because of there are many sight seen to visit as Patakot, Satdhara, Geological formations, geological heritage, Richness of biodiversity of flora and fauna, pleasant climate, beauty of landscape, Sunrise and sunset point, Bhura Bhagat, Anthoni (Badi and Chhoti), Chhota Mahadeo, Lal Pahadi, Bander Kudani, Vulture point, Gwal garh etc.

Main Ingredients

Biswas, S. N. (2014) focused on the tribal food, "Grains and vegetables are the main food of tribes." Rice, corn, pulse, honey and green leafy vegetables are an important part of the cuisine. As well as mahuaa, Phoolo ki bhaji (Boiled leafs), Roti (Chapati) made by Wheat, Aam ka pana (boilded mango juice), Cow Milk, Mattha, Aawla, Awla ki chironjii, Jaamun, Jaamun ka sirka Behda, Rural Rice (Kutki).

List of some food items, vegetables and grains

Tribal name	English name
Bhejra	Tomato
Bhata	Brinjal
Kumba, Bhamodi	Forest masroom
Meva Kaddu	Pumpkin
Saag	Pea greens
Aalu ka saag	Potato greens
Popat Ballahar	Indian bean
Guniya	Arbi
Non	Salt

Antmul	Herbal tea
Palak	Spinach
Podina	Mint
Samar	Coriander
Mithi Neem Patta	Curry leaf
Gobhi	Cabbage
Phulgobhi	Cauliflower
Kuti	Wheat
Bhat	Rice
Mirach	Chili
Bihi	Gavava
Kera	Banana

5. Patakot ki Rasoi - Tribal Traditional Consonants

Patakot ki Rasoi is a unique initiative to promote tribal sustainable tourism where they provide food of tribes from Patakot and introduce tribal culture among the tourist. They establish a stall in the various occasions like festivals, functions, events and provide all type of tribal food. All major food prepared by Grain - rice, pulse, corn, wheat and Green vegetables - pumpkin, Spinach, cauliflower, tomato etc. There are different varieties of grain and vegetables which are used for different dishes, most widely used being peja (made by wheat), kachariya (made by mango) and kheer (made by rice and pumpkin). Grain is eaten in different ways such as roasted, grounded, boiled or just soaked. The Boiled broken wheat called peja, it is an important breakfast meal for many which is generally had with milk. Water mixed with honey and sugar is also a traditional breakfast.

Specialty of Patakot Tribal Food

- Food with oil and spices.
- Combination of different grain.

- Mainly to the use of herbs, fruits and vegetables.
- Prepared by grains and vegetables.
- Common use of cow based products.
- Honey is used widely in the food.

Types of Foods at Patalkot ki Rasoi

- Peja - It is a high quality of food made by boiled broken wheat.
- Kheer - Rice and Pumpkin kheer is a commonly family sweet dish make in almost all festivals.
- Deshi Bada – Deshi Bada is a recipe made by different pulse. It is one the most liked by guest and tourist.
- Pakode - Kevkand, made by besan (gram flour), rice flour, garam masala (blend of spices), coriander powder, turmeric, cumin seeds, ajwan seeds and salt.
- Papad - It is a thin, crisp, round-shaped, plain food. Made by gram flour, potato, rice, pulse, either fried or cooked with dry heat.
- Ghungri – The wheat is soaked overnight and it is used as breakfast in the morning.
- Shahad - Natural honey bee is provided by Patalkot ki rasoi.
- Awala Murabba - It is a sweet dish. It is traditionally prepared with amla, sugar, and spices and can be preserve for long time.
- Roti - Called it chapati. It is made by wheat, corn, Mix and Jowar-Bajra.
- Kutki Bhat, Mahua (butter tree) Puri (Small chapatti fryed in oil), Barbati Saag, Bhejra Chatni, different soup, herbs etc. are the most liked food by tourist in Patalkot ki rasoi.

6. Patalkot Tourism

Government and local people are trying to establish Patalkot as a destination for tourist. Patalkot tourism is based on five A's. First one is attractions; there are many attraction points nearby Tamia. These are Patalkot, Viewpoint, Chintipur, Rated, Satpura Mountains, Gayani and Dudhi rivers, Rajakhoh, Tamia, Chota mahdev, Tamia view point, Rest House, Lal Pahadi (Tamia valley),

Girjamai Temple, Jhingria Water Fall, Pratapghar mountain – mystery mountain, Vulture point, Rock Painting, Anhoni (Hot water spring) Second A is Activities – Tour and travel agencies are providing various activities for patalkote tourism. These are Village visit, Nature trails, trekking, jungle safari, camping, Bird watching, Tribal interactions, Adventure sports etc. Third A is Amenities – Tamia is a block level place so here very few facilities are available. Like Restaurants, Dhabas, Local Guide, Public toilet, Drinking water, only one Travel agency, Reservations ect., Fourth A is Accommodation - There are few facilities to stay here. Some of them is M.P. Tourism - Motel, Wild welly resort, Forest rest house, Lodge etc. Fifth A is Accessibility - Tourist can reach there By road, train and air. Akare, D. S., & Singh, B. P. (2015) shows the path how to reach Tamia, By Bus: By road Tamia is 58 km from Chhindwara, 220 km from Bhopal, frequently luxury and local bus service available from Bhopal, Indore and Chhindwara. By Train: By train tourist can reach Parasiya and Parasiya is 30 km far from Tamia. Jabalpur, Itarsi and Nagpur are the nearest railway Junction. By Air: Nagpur, Dr. Babasaheb Ambedkar International Airport, Bhopal, Raja Bhoj Airport and Jabalpur, Dumna airport are near from Tamia.

7. Conclusion

Based on observations, discussion, interview, book review, article and research papers of the tribal food and culture we found that tribal people has unique life style, culture and food. The tribal journeys of Patalkot are most refreshing and energizing. There are many possibilities to develop and promote tribal tourism in Patalkot region. Patalkot valley in which they live celebrates their festivals there are no any public toilet, lack of drinking water, lack of awareness, lack of infrastructure, building and lack of other amenities. As a result, few tourists are reaching there. Apart from this also tourist can still get the glimpse of rich tribal culture, traditions and food. Tribal food like Patalkot ki rasoi is also an exclusive concept and initiative where tourist get tribal food and an unforgettable experience.

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वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म का सम्प्रत्यय एवं स्वरूप

असीम कुलश्रेष्ठ

।पेजंदज च्त्वमिवतए व्मचजण वल्वहं दक भ्मंसजीए व्मअँदोतपजप टर्षूअपकलंसंलंए ळंलंजतपानदरए भ्तकूतए न्जजंतींदक
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षोध-सार

आध्यात्मिक अनुशासन व्यक्ति को मर्यादाओं में बाधित रखते थे परन्तु कालक्रम में जुड़ी रहस्यवादी घटनाओं और परम्पराओं ने उसे विकृत रूप दे दिया और जन साधारण ने अध्यात्म के वास्तविक स्वरूप को न पहचानकर उसके विकृत रूप को गृहण किया जिससे अध्यात्म के सम्बंध में अविश्वास उत्पन्न हो गया। वह आध्यात्मिक मान्यताओं को अस्वीकार करने लगे। आज जन साधारण की मनोभूमि किसी भी विषय को बुद्धिसंगत ढंग से समझने की है। आज तर्क, तथ्य, प्रमाण, उदाहरण को विज्ञान माना जाता है। इन बदली हुई परिस्थिति में अध्यात्म को उसी पृष्ठभूमि में प्रतिपादित करना पड़ेगा। सही आधार पर किए गए प्रतिपादन जब मनुष्य के अन्तःकरण में बैठ जाते हैं तो उनके अनुसार वे आचरण भी करते हैं। यदि अध्यात्मवादी मान्यताओं का आज विज्ञान, तर्क और प्रमाणों के आधार पर प्रतिपादन कर सकते हैं तो निस्संदेह जन साधारण को उसे स्वीकार करने में कोई आपत्ति न होगी। आज घटनाओं के रूप में कार्य तो है, पर उसका कारण नहीं ज्ञात है, उसका बपमदबम विकसित नहीं है। हम आध्यात्मिक घटनाओं की पुनरावृत्ति नहीं कर सकते क्योंकि हम उसका कार्य-कारण का सिद्धान्त नहीं जानते, उसके विज्ञान को नहीं जानते। आज के विद्वान अध्यात्म को इसलिए अवैज्ञानिक मानते हैं क्योंकि वहां कार्य तो है परन्तु उस कार्य को पीछे से संचालित करने वाला कारण अदृश्य एवं अस्पष्ट है। इसलिए अध्यात्म को रहस्यमयी घोषित किया गया। अध्यात्म की वैज्ञानिक प्रकृति उसका प्रारूप और तकनीक का अध्ययन ही वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म है। प्रस्तुत षोध-पत्र में वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म के सम्प्रत्यय को षोधकर्ता ने स्पष्ट करने का प्रयास किया है।

कूट षब्द- अध्यात्म, वैज्ञानिक, वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्मए अन्तःकरण।

प्रस्तावना-

'वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म' वर्तमान समय में सबसे प्रचलित प्रत्यय है। यह विज्ञान और अध्यात्म के समन्वय को, सम्मिलन को दर्शाने वाला प्रत्यय है। अध्यात्म जिसे कभी कोरा अंधविश्वास और दार्शनिक कल्पना माना जाता था, वह आज जिज्ञासा के साथ वैज्ञानिक अनुसंधान का विषय बन गया है। लैववए ळववहसम जैसे सर्च इंजन पर अध्यात्म की खोज करने पर इस विषय पर अनेकों पृष्ठ आपके सामने होंगे जो इस विषय की मान्यता के प्रति वैज्ञानिक समुदाय में बढ़ते विश्वास को दर्शाता है। पश्चिम में विज्ञान के उदय ने धर्मानुयाइयों को संषय में डाल दिया था, जब निकोलस कॉपरनिकस ने बताया कि धरती सूर्य की परिक्रमा करती है। प्रचलित मान्यता को ठेस लगी और रूढ़िवादियों ने विज्ञान द्वारा उदित हुए सत्य को अस्वीकार कर दिया गया। पर सत्य की उपेक्षा अधिक दिनों तक नहीं की जा सकी और विज्ञान के सिद्धान्तों के प्रतिपादन का सिलसिला धर्म की अंधमान्यताओं के लिए एक दयनीय कुठार बन गया और विज्ञान की चरम प्रगति ने घोषणा की कि धर्म-अध्यात्म एक दिन मात्र चर्चा का विषय बनकर रह जायेगा; लेकिन धर्म और अध्यात्म दोनों ही आज जीवन्त है। विज्ञान ने धर्म के अंधविश्वासों को ठेस पहुँचाई, न कि उसके सत्यों को। धर्म में प्रचलित धार्मिक कर्मकाण्डों, मान्यताओं, विश्वासों में भी विज्ञान निहित है, जिसे कल न देखा

जा सका, उसे आज देखा जा रहा है। सर्वाधिक ध्यान देने योग्य तथ्य है कि अध्यात्म और धर्म को सामान्यतः लोग एक जैसा समझते हैं; पर वस्तुतः दोनों भिन्न हैं। ब्रह्माण्ड के सभी मनुष्यों के धर्म या धार्मिक मान्यताएँ भिन्न-भिन्न हो सकते हैं, पर 'अध्यात्म' सभी मनुष्यों में एक है। इस संदर्भ में संत विनोबा ने कहा है, "अध्यात्म धर्मपंथ से अलग चीज है। धर्म हर जमाने में, हर कौम के लिए और हर समय के लिए एक नहीं होता, पर अध्यात्म एक होता है। जैसे प्यार करना, सच बोलना, रहम रखना अध्यात्म है। वैसे ही ईश्वर की भक्ति करना भी अध्यात्म है। लेकिन ईश्वर की उपासना के लिए घुटने टेकना, पूर्व या पश्चिम की तरफ मुंह करना, यह सब धर्म है। ईश्वर के लिए दिल में भक्ति रखो, ईश्वर को हमेशा याद करो, ईश्वर की फिक्र रखो— यह अध्यात्म है।" श्रीअरविन्द के अनुसार, "प्रत्येक वस्तु का अपना धर्म अर्थात् अपने जीवन का विधान होता है जो उसकी प्रकृति के द्वारा उस पर लादा जाता है; परन्तु मनुष्य के लिए धर्म है, अपने सभी अंगों पर आदर्श जीवन यापन के नियम को सचेतन रूप में लाकर करना।" धर्म का उद्देश्य, आत्मा के शुद्ध स्वरूप का दर्शन कराना है। अर्थात् धर्म अध्यात्म प्राप्ति का एक साधन है।

वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म का अर्थ—

अध्यात्म का अर्थ है— 'आत्मनः सम्बद्धम्' अर्थात् आत्मा का व्यक्ति से संबंध रखने वाला। यह ब्रह्मवाचक है। अध्यात्म—ज्ञान आत्मा—परमात्मा संबंधी ज्ञान है। अमरकोश के तानर्थवर्ग में 144वें प्लोक के अनुसार, अध्यात्म शब्द का अर्थ सूक्ष्म भी है। यहाँ कहा गया है, 'सूक्ष्ममह्यात्ममपि'। यह सूक्ष्म शब्द पाणिनि व्याकरण के अनुसार, 'सूच पैषून्ये' धातु से उणादिगण के 'सूचेः स्मन्' (सूत्र 4/177) से बनता है। मेदिनी कोश में इसका अर्थ दिया है, 'सूक्ष्मं स्यात् कैतवे ध्यात्मे'। इस तरह अध्यात्म शब्द सूक्ष्म का पर्यायवाची शब्द है। अतएव इसे रहस्यमय भी कहा जा सकता है। आत्मा और रहस्यमयता अध्यात्म के दोनों ही अर्थ परस्पर घुले-मिले हैं। दोनों ही एक-दूसरे का बोध कराते हैं और यह बोध व्याकरण के ज्ञान से नहीं तप-साधना से ही सम्भव है। 'आत्मा' अध्यात्म का मुख्य विषय है। 'आत्मा' शब्द की व्युत्पत्ति के विषय में पंकराचार्य ने एक प्राचीन प्लोक उद्धृत किया है— आत्मा जगत् के सारे पदार्थों में व्याप्त रहता है (आप्नोति), सारे पदार्थों को ग्रहण कर लेता है (आदत्ते), सारे पदार्थों का अनुभव करता है (अत्ति) और इसकी सत्ता निरन्तर बनी रहती है, इसलिए इसे 'आत्मा' कहा जाता है। 'आत्मा' का यह अर्थ अतिव्यापक है। आत्मा की अतिव्यापकता व मैकेनिज्म के संदर्भ में ऐलिस ए. बैले ने बताया है कि आत्मा एक अखण्ड अमूर्तिक चेतनतत्त्व है, जो शरीर में भी व्याप्त है और शरीर के बाहर निखिल ब्रह्माण्ड में भी। इसलिए वह शरीर को ही नहीं जानता, षाष्वत जगत में जो कुछ हो रहा है, जो कुछ भी होने वाला है, वह सब जानता है; यदि उस पर पाप और मलिनता का परदा और इच्छा तथा आसक्ति की चादर न पड़ी हो।

साधारणतः 'अध्यात्म' शब्द पर विचार करे तो हम पाते हैं कि यह दो शब्दों से मिलकर बना है। 'अधि'+ 'आत्म', जिसका तात्पर्य है, 'अपनी आत्मा का, अपने अंतर का अध्ययन करना।' इस आधुनिक युग में अंतर के विधि-विज्ञान को जब अध्यात्म वैज्ञानिक रूप से खोजता है तो 'वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म' कहा जाता है। दूसरे शब्दों में कहा जाए तो अध्यात्म की वैज्ञानिक प्रकृति उसका प्रारूप और तकनीक का अध्ययन ही वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म है; बपमदबजपपिबैचपतपजनंसपजलद्ध है।

वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म के सम्प्रत्यय की उपादेयता—

दर्शन का मानव के लिए वास्तविक महत्व है कि उसको अपने अस्तित्व की प्रकृति के विषय में प्रकाश दे, उसके मनोविज्ञान के सिद्धान्त विषय और ईश्वर के उसके संबंध, उसके भविष्य की महान संभावनाओं की निश्चित रूपरेखा को स्पष्ट करे। दार्शनिक ज्ञान की यही खासियत, जो उसको मानवीय ज्ञान की अन्य शाखाओं से अलग और विषेशताओं से भरा— पूरा साबित करती है वहीं परिपूर्ण सत्य की अनुभूति को देने वाली है।

जीवन बोध के इस षास्त्र का लक्ष्य है— ज्ञान का समग्र अनुभव, सत्य का सम्पूर्णता में साक्षात्कार। दर्शन षास्त्र का सदा से यही काम रहा है। मैथ्यू अर्नाल्ड ने कवि सोफोक्लीज के संबंध में कहा है कि उन्होंने जीवन को सुस्थिर और पूर्ण रूप से देखा था। इस सारगर्भित कथन में दर्शन के ध्येय और उसकी प्रणाली दोनों का समावेश है। ध्येय है, जीवन को पूर्ण रूप से देखना न कि व्यापारी, कलाकार, कवि या उपदेशक और विष्वविधालय के प्राचार्य के दृष्टिकोण से अथवा किसी अन्य दृष्टि से देखना, वरन इस दृष्टि से देखना जिस तरह उसे “षाष्वत काल और पूर्ण सत्ता का द्रष्टा” देखेगा। और प्रणाली है उसे सुस्थिर दृष्टि से देखने, अनुभव करने की, जिसमें न तो पक्षपात हो, न कोई विशेष झुकाव और न अर्धज्ञान।

प्रणाली की सार्थकता सत्य को पूरी तरह अनुभव कर लेना भर नहीं है। उस अनुभव को बुद्धि ग्राह्य और तर्क सम्मत भाशा में कहना भी आना चाहिए। इसकी आवष्यकता पर बल देते हुए श्री अरविन्द कहते हैं— “आध्यात्मिक और दार्शनिक दोनों का ही ज्ञान में षब्दों के प्रयोग में स्पष्ट और यथार्थ होना आवष्यक है, ताकि विचार और अनुभव की क्रमहीनता से बचा जा सके, जो कि उन षब्दों की अव्यवस्था के कारण होती है, जिनको हम उन्हें प्रकट करने में प्रयोग करते हैं। इसके आभाव में अनुभव को दूसरों तक पहुँचाया नहीं जा सकता। फिर तो दर्शन सार्वभौमिक होने से वंचित रह जायगा। और ‘लोग प्रकाषपूर्ण विचारधारा के अभाव में वर्तमान कूप मण्डूकता और क्षुद्रता के कीचड़ में पड़े हुए कीड़ों के तरह ही बुलबुलाते रहेंगे, उन्हें ऊँचे उठने की न तो प्रेरणा मिलेगी न दिषा।’ जबकि ‘यह एक सुनिश्चित तथ्य है कि यदि कोई सारगर्भित विचारधारा, हृदसग्राही, बुद्धिसंगत और तथ्य—तर्क के साथ प्रतिपादित की जाय— उस प्रतिपादन के पीछे समर्थ व्यक्तित्व और सक्रिय अनुभव जुड़ा हुआ हो, तो उसका प्रभाव पड़े बिना रह नहीं सकता।’ यह प्रभाव ही दर्शन को सर्वजनीन और सर्वव्यापक होने की गरिमा प्रदान करता है। अतएव “एक ऐसी भाशा उत्पन्न करनी है जो कि संवेगात्मक और स्पष्ट इंगितों के वाहन के रूप में, विशेष और जीवित प्रतिभाओं को लेते हुए एक साथ ही संबोधि रूप से आध्यात्मिक एवं तत्वदर्शी रूप से कवित्वमय हो।” अतः ज्ञान के अन्वेशक के सम्मुख अनिवार्य काम है— समग्र सत्य को अनुभव करने और उसकी व्याख्या कर सकने योग्य भाशा का विकास। यह प्रणाली अपने आप में ज्ञान की प्रकृति की ओर संकेत है। क्योंकि “जिस ज्ञान की ओर हम जाना चाहते हैं, उसकी स्थिति का वर्णन उस साधन का वर्णन करता है, जिसे हम प्रयोग करेंगे।”

वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म की सर्वांगपूर्ण प्रणाली का सम्प्रत्यय —

आज विचारों की समग्रता नष्ट प्रायः है, मनुष्य के खण्ड — खण्ड का चिन्तन — विश्लेषण चल रहा है। उसके अस्तित्व के एक भाग को समग्र शास्त्र का रूप दे दिया गया है। ये सब हैं तो उपयोगी, पर समग्र मानव को समझे बिना उसकी मूल प्रकृति और प्रवृत्ति पर ध्यान दिये बिना एकांगी आंशिक समाधानों से कुछ बनेगा नहीं। उस महाविद्या की ओर से क्यों उदासी है? जिसे समग्र मानव का विज्ञान कहा जा सके।

युग दृष्टा अर्थात् काल पर चेतनता के साथ दृष्टि रखने वाले आचार्य प. श्रीराम शर्मा ने 1947 में अपनी कृति वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्मवाद में कहा है कि विज्ञान भौतिकता को बढ़ावा देता है और अध्यात्म आत्मिकता को। व्यक्ति का संबंध इन दोनों छोरों से रहता है। अतः आने वाला समय विज्ञान और अध्यात्म के समन्वय का होगा।

पिछले दो सौ वर्षों में इतने अधिक शास्त्र — ज्ञान, विज्ञान की धाराएँ ढूँढ़ निकाली गई हैं जितनी पहले कभी न थी। इसके बाद भी उदासी के बादल छँटे नहीं, गहराते ही गए, कारण उपर्युक्त सवाल के समाधान में बरती गयी उदासीनता है। ज्ञान के खोजियों, जीवन के मीमांसकों और अन्वेषित प्रणालियों का पर्यावलोकन करें तो पाएँगे कि इनके मुख्यतः तीन वर्ग हैं —

एक जिनने जीवन का बाह्य परिवेश देखा — केन्द्र से दूर रहकर परिधि की ओर उन्मुख रहे। इस परम्परा ने व्यक्ति को आत्म—गरिमा से हीन भारवाहक श्रमिक बना दिया। आज जिसे विज्ञान कहते हैं, वह इसी परम्परा का अनुयायी है। इन्द्रोडक्शन

ऑफ फिलासॉफी के लेखक जी.टी. डब्ल्यू पेट्रिक के शब्दों में, विज्ञान मूल्यों, जीवन तथा मानवीय आचरण – जैसे अनिवार्य प्रश्नों के समाधान की चेष्टा नहीं करता जो हमारे लिए बहुत महत्वपूर्ण हैं।

इसके विपरीत जिन्होंने सोचा उन्होंने क्रिया की निस्सारता मान ली। मनोसंकल्पनाओं से घिरे रहने के कारण वस्तु जगत को झुठलाने के प्रयास में ही अपने कर्तव्य और पुरुषार्थ की इतिश्री समझ ली। बेकन की भाषा में, स्वयं को दार्शनिक समझने वाला जीव अपने ही बुने तन्तुजाल में फँसता— उलझता, उलझाता रहता है। क्योंकि उसने मान रखा है, दर्शन सोचने की पद्धति है, करने की नहीं। भावना और क्रिया से विलग रहकर वह स्वयं को मानवता का कितना भी हित साधक कहे। पर उसने स्वयं का भी कितना हित साधन किया है – इस पर भी समय ने अमित प्रश्न चिन्ह लगा दिया है।

इस प्रश्न का हल खोजने वालों ने मानवी अस्तित्व के नये केन्द्र का स्पर्श किया। उसी को सब कुछ मान जीवन की प्रश्नावली के नये समाधान खोजने शुरू किये। उनका कार्य स्तुत्य होते हुए भी समग्रता के अभाव में मनुष्य का कुछ अधिक हित नहीं कर सकता। भावनाएँ उत्तम हैं, पर क्रिया का अभाव उन्हें पंगु बना देता है। चिन्तन न होने पर ये कोरी भावुकता होकर रह जाती हैं। बौद्धिक विवेचना से पल्ला छुड़ा बैठने के कारण ही इस पक्ष के अनुयायी रहस्यवादी कहलाए।

क्रिया, चिन्तन और संवेदना – जीवन के तीन पक्ष अपने एकाकीपन में मनुष्य जाति को जीवन का अर्थ नहीं दे सकते। वह कला नहीं सिखा सकते, जिससे अनगढ़ता— भद्दापन मिट सकें। इस कला का अभाव ही है, जिसके कारण समृद्धियों के ढेर में दबा—बौद्धिक भार से लदा मनुष्य करुण विलाप कर रहा है।

धर्म, दर्शन और विज्ञान, मानवीय अस्तित्व से उपजी तीन प्रबल विचार शक्तियाँ हैं। किन्तु इनका अलगाव— आपसी टकराव मानव—जीवन में वरदानों की सृष्टि न कर सका। जब संवेदना— चिन्तन और कर्म ही आपस में टकराते रहेंगे, तब परिणाम संहार के अतिरिक्त क्या होगा? उज्ज्वल भविष्य की संसिद्धि का सिर्फ एक उपाय है – इनका सामंजस्य। 'वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म' के रूप में यही है। इस नये तत्त्वदर्शन के अनुसार क्रिया और चिन्तन दोनों जहाँ मिल सकते हैं, वह स्थान संवेदना है। इस मिलन बिन्दु को अपने मूल स्रोत के रूप में पहचानना, स्वीकारना ही वह उपाय है, जिससे मनुष्य का अब तक के अपने विकास को बरकरार रख संभावनाओं के नए द्वार खोल सकता है।

वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्मवादवादों के ढेर में नए प्रकार की सर्जना नहीं, बल्कि ऐसा कुछ है जहाँ सभी वाद समा जाते हैं। जहाँ सबको उसका स्थान मिल जाता है। 'समुद्र मायः प्रविशन्ति यद्वत्' – समुद्र नदी नहीं है, परन्तु सभी नदियाँ समुद्र में अपना स्थान ग्रहण करती हैं। इसी भांति इस चिन्तन प्रणाली से जीवन के सभी अंग—उपांग अपने चरम विकास की कला सीखते हैं। अभी यह मानते रहे हैं कि विज्ञान वह है जो दृश्य माध्यमों को आधार बनाकर हमें प्रत्यक्ष रूप से यह समझाता है कि कोई भी घटनाक्रम या क्रिया – प्रतिक्रिया किस कारण होती है, जबकि अध्यात्म मूलतः चेतना विज्ञान को प्रगति की दिशा देने वाली एक परोक्ष विधा है, उसे विज्ञान का प्रत्यक्षीकरण का जामा नहीं पहनाया जा सकता। किन्तु श्रद्धा – भावना— संवेदना भी विज्ञान है, जिसे आध्यात्मिक प्रयोगों द्वारा प्राप्त किया जा सकता है।

पं. श्रीराम शर्मा ने कहा है, अध्यात्मवाद वह महाविज्ञान है जिसकी जानकारी के बिना भूतल के समस्त वैभव निरर्थक और जिसके थोड़ा सा भी प्राप्त होने पर जीवन आनन्द से ओत—प्रोत हो जाता है। संसार में सीखने और जानने योग्य अनेकों वस्तुएँ हैं पर सबसे पहले जिसे जानने और हृदयंगम करने आवश्यकता है वह – वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्मवाद ही है। आज युग की मांग भी यही है। विज्ञान सत्य का अनुसंधान करता है, परन्तु इस अनुसंधान का आधार पदार्थ है। विज्ञान की सीमाएँ हैं तर्क और तथ्य पर आधारित पदार्थ की वास्तविकता का ज्ञान करना परन्तु पदार्थ के समाप्त होते ही विज्ञान भी सीमित हो जाता है, वहीं से चेतना की यात्रा प्रारम्भ होती है।

श्रीअरविन्द के अनुसार, अतिभौतिक प्रकृति के नियम और संभावनाओं को जाने बिना विज्ञान का वास्तविक अनुसंधन पूर्ण नहीं हो सकेगा। अतः अनुसंधन एवं अन्वेषण की पूर्णता के लिए तर्कबुद्धि के साथ अंतर्प्रज्ञा का समावेश आवश्यक है, तभी वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म रूपी नवीन युग का सूत्रपात हो सकेगा। तर्क एवं प्रमाण की अपनी उपयोगिता है। विज्ञान ने अपना सतत विकास इसी आधार पर किया है। परीक्षण की कसौटियों पर कसने के बाद उसने अपना वर्चस्व सिद्ध किया है। उसकी प्रत्यक्षवादी मान्यताएँ परीक्षण किए जाने के बाद ही प्रमाणिकता प्रस्तुत कर सकी हैं।

उपसंहार—

मात्र कर्मकाण्डों का अनुसंधन करते, श्रद्धा, विश्वास के नाम पर मान्यताएँ अपनाने को आज का बौद्धिक वर्ग तैयार न होगा। इन कर्मकाण्डों के साथ जीवन के सूत्र – सिद्धान्तों का दार्शनिक क्रम भी होना चाहिए। ऋषि प्रणीत ग्रन्थों में न केवल ज्ञान – विज्ञान की विभिन्न धाराओं का समावेश मिलता है वरन् ये ग्रन्थ उदात्त जीवन और आध्यात्मिक दृष्टिकोण के उच्च आयामी मूल्यों का निर्धारण भी करते हैं। दर्शन ही विचार और आचरण का मूल आधार है। इसलिए ईश्वर, आत्मा, धर्म, स्वभाव, कर्मफल आदि के दार्शनिक सिद्धान्तों का सही ढंग से प्रतिपादन करना ही वैज्ञानिक अध्यात्म के सम्प्रत्यय का उद्देश्य है। इस सम्प्रत्यय के आधार पर दार्शनिक सिद्धान्तों का विज्ञान, तर्क, प्रमाणों के आधार पर प्रतिपादन कर सके तो निस्संदेह जनमानस को पुनः उसी प्रकार सोचने और करते रहने को तत्पर किया जा सकता है, जिस पर आरुढ़ रहकर भारतीय जनता लाखों वर्षों से समस्त विश्व का प्रकाशपूर्ण मार्गदर्शन करती रही है।

भारतीय संस्कृति एवं साहित्य में लोक प्रशासन

अश्वनी कुमार, डॉ० चिन्मय पण्ड्या

शोधार्थी, प्राच्य अध्ययन विभाग (लोक प्रशासन), देव संस्कृति विश्वविद्यालय, गायत्रीकंज-शांतिकुंज, हरिद्वार-249411।

प्रति-कुलपति, देव संस्कृति विश्वविद्यालय, गायत्रीकंज-शांतिकुंज, हरिद्वार-249411।

शोध सार

भारतीय संस्कृति विश्व की प्रधान संस्कृति है, यह कोई गर्वोक्ति नहीं, बल्कि वास्तविकता है। भारतीय संस्कृति का आधार स्रोत वैदिक संस्कृति से सम्बन्धित है। वेद समस्त विषयों के आदि स्रोत हैं। अपने मूल रूप में अविभक्त तथा मिश्रित वेदमन्त्र अनेक ऋषि-महर्षियों द्वारा समय-समय पर संकलित तथा सम्पादित होकर वर्तमान संहिता के रूप में वर्गीकृत तथा व्यवस्थित हुए। प्रत्येक वेद की अपनी अलग-अलग संहितायें हैं। प्राचीन ग्रन्थों में एक वेद की अनेक संहिताओं का उल्लेख मिलता है, किन्तु उनमें से कुछ संहिताओं में लोक प्रशासन के संदर्भ में विस्तृत वर्णन प्राप्त होता है और ऐसा प्रतीत होता है कि भारतीय संस्कृति के रूप में वेद लोक प्रशासन हेतु विभिन्न लोकाचार के नियम, दण्ड प्रणाली, न्याय प्रणाली, सुरक्षा के नियम, परराष्ट्र नीति, अर्थ एवं कर व्यवस्था आदि का वर्णन सूत्रों के रूप में किया गया है, जिससे यह प्रतीत होता है कि आदिकाल में भी लोक प्रशासन से सम्बन्धित व्यवस्थाएँ थी।

लोक प्रशासन के पाठ्यक्रम के अन्तर्गत जिन विषयों का अध्ययन किया जाता है, उनमें अधिकांश का वर्णन वेदों में प्राप्त होता है। लोक प्रशासन विषय के अन्तर्गत संगठन सम्बन्धी सिद्धान्त की अभिप्रेरणा, समन्वय, संचार आदि का अध्ययन किया जाता है। इन तत्त्वों का उल्लेख ऋग्वेद में भी प्राप्त होता है। प्रस्तुत लेख में शोधकर्ता का उद्देश्य भारतीय संस्कृति के मूल स्रोत एवं आधार केन्द्र वेद रूपी वैदिक साहित्य में वर्णित लोक प्रशासन के स्वरूप को स्पष्ट करना है।

कूट शब्द . संस्कृति, वैदिक साहित्य, लोकाचार, दण्ड प्रणाली, न्याय प्रणाली एवं लोकप्रशासन

परिचय-

प्रशासन का अर्थ है व्यवस्था करना। यह व्यवस्था परिवार से लेकर विश्व स्तर तक व्याप्त है। यदि प्रशासन का अभाव हो जाए तो जीवन संकट में पड़ जाता है। पारिवारिक स्तर पर गृहस्वामी, ग्राम स्तर पर ग्राम-प्रमुख, जिला स्तर पर जिलाधिकारी राज्य स्तर पर मुख्यमंत्री, देश स्तर पर प्रधानमंत्री तथा प्राकृतिक स्तर पर देवता विश्व व्यवस्था के नियामक होते हैं।

प्रशासन एक व्यापक प्रक्रिया है जो सभी सामूहिक कार्यों के बारे में चाहे वे सार्वजनिक हों अथवा व्यक्तिगत, नागरिक हों अथवा सैनिक, बड़े कार्य हों अथवा छोटे सभी के सम्बन्ध में लागू होता है। यह एक सहयोगी कार्य है जो सुनिश्चित उद्देश्य के लिए किए जाने वाले सभी प्रकार के प्रयत्नों की तुलना में प्रशासन आधुनिक युग की ही विशेषता नहीं है, अपितु इसकी झलक सभ्यता के विकास के आरम्भ में ही भली-भाँति दिखायी देने लगी थी। आदिम काल के गुहा-स्वामी तक के लिए यह महत्त्व की वस्तु थी। मित्र देश के पिरामिडों का निर्माण आश्चर्यजनक प्रशासकीय सफलता थी और यही बात सिन्धु घाटी की सभ्यता के बारे में की जा सकती है।

परन्तु यहाँ पर हम उस ब्रह्माण्ड या विश्व प्रशासन अथवा प्राकृतिक प्रशासन की बात कर रहे हैं जिसके द्रष्टा, रचियता हमारे ऋषि थे। उन्होंने ऐसे मन्त्रों से हमें अवगत कराया जिसके अनुशीलन से प्राकृतिक प्रशासन, विश्व प्रशासन, राष्ट्र प्रशासन तथा ग्राम प्रशासन की जानकारी प्राप्त होती है।

लोक प्रशासन का सम्बन्ध उन सभी कार्यों से है जिनका प्रयोजन सार्वजनिक नीति अथवा उद्देश्य को जनहित के सन्दर्भ में पूरा करना अथवा उसे क्रियान्वित करना होता है। कहा जाता है कि लोक प्रशासन एक क्रिया भी है साथ ही एक पाठ्य-विषय भी। एक क्रिया के रूप में प्रशासन बहुत प्राचीन है परन्तु पाठ्य विषय के रूप में इसका उद्भव वर्ष 1887 में वुडरो-विल्सन रचित लेख '।'जनकल व।कउपदपेजतंजपवद' से माना जाता है।

परन्तु लोक प्रशासन के बीज वेद में देखने को मिलते हैं, जहाँ लोक प्रशासन अपने वृहद् रूप में उपस्थित है। वेदों में ब्रह्माण्ड प्रशासन का वर्णन मिलता है जिसका उद्देश्य विश्व कल्याण है। ठीक उसी प्रकार जैसे लोक प्रशासन का उद्देश्य जनकल्याण है।

समस्त भारतीय वाङ्मय में यहाँ तक कि शेष तीनों मन्त्र संहिताओं की अपेक्षा ऋग्वेद संहिता का अनेक दृष्टियों में महत्त्व है। उसमें इतिहास, भूगोल, राजनीति, समाजशास्त्र, अर्थशास्त्र और सम्पूर्ण कलाओं तथा विद्याओं का उल्लेख मिलता है। ऋग्वेद का प्रधान विषय किसी दिव्य शक्ति की स्तुति है, किन्तु उनका अर्थ प्रतीकात्मक है। वे सृष्टि-विषयक गूढतम रहस्यों की ओर संकेत करते हैं। ऋग्वेद इस प्रकार विश्व-कोश है जिसमें भारतीय जनजीवन से सम्बद्ध प्रत्येक विषय का उद्गम देखने को मिलता है। अथर्ववेद में लौकिक जीवन से सम्बन्धित सभी बातों का उल्लेख है। वेदों में वर्णित लोक प्रशासन सम्बन्धित जो विभिन्न पद एवं कार्यों का वर्णन है उसका विस्तृत विवरण इस प्रकार है—

1. कार्य विभाजन अथवा विभागीकरण

ऋग्वेद के प्रत्येक सूक्त में किसी देवता की स्तुति वर्णित है। इन स्तुति मन्त्रों से सृष्टि विषयक प्रबन्ध की जानकारी प्राप्त होती है। प्रत्येक देवता किसी विशेष विभाग का प्रतिनिधि होता है। इन्द्र सैन्य-विभाग का प्रतिनिधि है।¹ अग्नि ऊर्जा विभाग का, वरुण समन्वयकर्ता की भूमिका निभाता है। वह विश्व का नियामक और शासक हैं, सोम वनस्पति विभाग का प्रतिनिधि, पूषन् को पशु-विभाग का और विष्णु को विश्व के संरक्षक और पालनकर्ता के रूप में माना जाता है, जो प्रधानमन्त्री के सदृश प्रतीत होता है।² इस प्रकार देवों के मध्य कार्यविभाजन, विभागीकरण तथा पदसोपानीकरण को देखा जा सकता है।

2. नेतृत्व

नेतृत्व सम्बन्धी विचारधारा का उल्लेख भी ऋग्वेद में प्राप्त होता है। वरुण के नेतृत्वकर्ता अभिहित किया गया है—

“कदा क्षत्रश्रियं नरमा वरुणं करामहे।।”³

3. नीति व नियम

लोक प्रशासन में निर्णय, नीति तथा नियमों के निर्माण का अध्ययन किया जाता है। ऋग्वेद के अनुशीलन से यह विदित होता है कि वरुण प्रमुख नीति निर्माता है। वरुण सूक्त में कहा गया है कि — हे वरुण देव! जिस प्रकार संसार में प्रजाजन कभी प्रमाद करते हैं उसी प्रकार हम भी आपके नियमों का जो कुछ भी प्रतिदिन प्रमाद से उल्लंघन करते हैं, हमारे प्रमादों का परिमार्जन करके उन नियमों को पूर्ण बनाइये।⁴ इसी प्रकार अन्यत्र कहा गया — ‘अपने स्वीकृत नियमों का पालने करने वाले श्रेष्ठ कर्मों को करने वाले वरुण देवता प्रजा के साम्राज्य की सिद्धि के लिए दिव्य प्रजाओं में आकर अधिष्ठित हुए हैं।’⁵

लोक प्रशासन के पाठ्यक्रम के अन्तर्गत केन्द्रीय प्रशासन में राष्ट्रपति, प्रधानमन्त्री तथा मन्त्रियों की नियुक्ति, निर्वाचन, उनके कर्तव्य, लोकसभा, राज्यसभा का गठन, प्रशासन तथा जनता के मध्य सम्बन्ध संविधान इत्यादि का अध्ययन करते हैं, जिसकी झलक हमें वेद में भी देखने को मिलती है।

4. राजा का निर्वाचन व उसके कर्त्तव्य

राज्य का प्रमुख राजा अथवा राष्ट्राध्यक्ष कहलाता है जो लोककल्याण हेतु विभिन्न प्रशासनिक क्रियायें करता है सम्प्रति राष्ट्रपति तथा प्रधानमंत्री का निर्वाचन होता है। भारत में यह प्रथा वैदिक काल में भी विद्यमान रही होगी, क्योंकि ऋग्वेद और अथर्ववेद के कई सूक्तों में प्रजा के द्वारा राजा के निर्वाचन का उल्लेख है। अथर्ववेद से ज्ञात होता है कि राजा के निर्वाचन के लिए सभी प्रतिनिधि एकत्र होते थे और वे सर्वसम्मति से राजा का निर्वाचन करते थे। राजा की नियुक्ति का कार्य समिति करती थी। वही राजा स्थायित्व प्रदान करती थी।⁶ राजा की इस नियुक्ति के साथ राजा से यह आशा की जाती थी कि वह लोकप्रिय होकर रहे जिससे जनता उसको पसन्द करे। वह ऐसा कोई काम न करे जिससे वह पदच्युत हो जाए।⁷

अथर्ववेद में उल्लिखित है कि प्रजा को प्रसन्न करने के कारण राजन्य या राजा हुआ – “सो•रज्यत, ततो राजन्यो•जायत”⁸ राजा का प्रमुख का कर्त्तव्य है – प्रजा का पालन, रक्षण और संवर्धन। प्रजापालन राजा का कर्त्तव्य है।⁹ यजुर्वेद में उद्धृत है कि राजा का अभिषेक प्रजा के कल्याण और उनके विकास के लिए होता है। क्षेम और पोष शब्दों के द्वारा प्रजा की कुशलता और उनके भौतिक सुख-साधनों में वृद्धि का निर्देश दिया गया है।¹⁰

5. प्रशासन और जनता के मध्य सम्बन्ध

कुशल प्रशासन के लिए अति आवश्यक है कि प्रशासन को जनता का सहयोग मिले इसीलिए विकास प्रशासन में नागरिक सहभागिता पर बल दिया गया है। वेदों में भी राज और प्रजा के मध्य सम्बन्धों को अभिव्यक्त किया गया है। यजुर्वेद में उल्लिखित है कि राजा और प्रजा का अंग हैं।¹¹ प्रजा राजा को पूर्ण सहयोग दे और राजा प्रजा को सभी प्रकार से संरक्षण दे।¹²

6. अनुशासन तथा निरीक्षण

संगठन में कार्यरत कार्मिकों के कार्यों के मूल्यांकन के लिए निरीक्षण अपरिहार्य है। हेनरी फयोल द्वारा प्रतिपादि संगठन के 14 सिद्धान्तों में निरीक्षण तथा अनुशासन भी परिगणित हैं। ऋग्वेद में उद्धृत है कि अनुशासन और निरीक्षण से ही राज अधिराज होता है। यदि कठोर अनुशासन नहीं होगा तो प्रजा में अव्यवस्था फैलेगी।¹³

7. प्रशासन का उद्देश्य जनकल्याण

लोक प्रशासन का एकमात्र उद्देश्य जनकल्याण है। प्रजा के हितार्थ समस्त सार्वजनिक क्रियायें सम्पन्न की जाती हैं। वेदों के कई मन्त्रों में राजा का ध्यान प्रजा की उन्नति और विकास के कार्यों की ओर आकृष्ट किया गया है। यजुर्वेद में कहा गया है कि प्रजा को दृढ़ और पुष्ट करो। उनकी आर्थिक स्थिति उन्नत करो। प्रजा के विकास कार्यों को करो।¹⁴

8. जनप्रतिनिधि संस्थायें – सभा और समिति

सभा और समिति अत्यन्त प्राचीन संस्थायें थीं। इन दोनों की उत्पत्ति प्रजापति से कही गई है। ये दोनों प्रजापति की पुत्रियाँ हैं।¹⁵ सभा आज की लोकसभा के समकक्ष मानी जा सकती हैं। इसमें सभी वर्गों का प्रतिनिधित्व होता था। सभी और समिति के संगठन में अन्तर होता था। सभा में वृद्ध, अनुभवी, ज्ञानी और प्रतिष्ठित व्यक्तियों को ही सदस्यता प्राप्त होती थी जबकि समिति में इस प्रकार का कोई प्रतिबन्ध नहीं था। इस प्रकार समिति लोकसभा के सदृश तथा सभा राज्यसभा के सदृश प्रतीत होता है।

समिति के सदस्य सामित्य कहा गया। अथर्ववेद के अनुशीलन से ज्ञात होता है कि पहले परिवार, फिर ग्राम, फिर ग्रामसभा आदि तदनन्तर सभा और उसके पश्चात् समिति का अस्तित्व होता था। समिति का कार्यक्षेत्र पूरा राष्ट्र होता था। समिति से बड़ी संस्था ‘आमन्त्रण’ हुई। यह संस्था समिति के मन्त्रिमण्डल के रूप में विकसित हुई और यह राष्ट्र की सर्वोत्तम संस्था हुई

ऋग्वेद के अन्तिम सूक्त में समिति और मन्त्र (मन्त्रणा) का उल्लेख है। इससे ज्ञात होता है कि समिति का कार्य विशिष्ट मन्त्रणा और विधि-निर्माण था।¹⁶ समिति कार्यपालका और न्यायपालिका का कार्य करती थी। लोककल्याण के लिए राजा का यह कर्तव्य होता था कि वह समिति का गठन करे। ऋग्वेद में समिति के कार्य को निर्दिष्ट किया गया है। राष्ट्र की सुरक्षा व्यवस्था और शत्रुनाशन, राष्ट्रीय आय की व्यवस्था, जनकल्याण और जनता का योगक्षेम तथा विविध शिल्पों की उन्नति।¹⁷ अथर्ववेद से ज्ञात होता है कि सभा और समिति दोनों के लिए संसद शब्द का प्रयोग होता था। सभा और समिति के प्रसंग में संसद शब्द का उल्लेख है – अस्थाः सर्वस्याः संसदो मामिन्द्र भगिण कृणु।¹⁸ इससे ज्ञात होता है कि सभा और समिति का कभी सामूहिक अधिवेशन हुआ करता था।

9. सचिव

विभिन्न विभागों में प्रशासन का प्रमुख सचिव कहलाता है। ऐतरेय ब्राह्मण में 'सचिव' शब्द का प्रयोग मिलता है। मरुत् देवों को इन्द्र का सचिव (मित्र) कहा गया है।¹⁹ चूंकि मरुत् इन्द्र के कार्य (वर्षण) में सहायता करते हैं ठीक उसी प्रकार जैसे आजकल सचिव मन्त्री के प्रशासनिक कार्यों में सहायता करते हैं।

10. संविधान

वेदों में संविधान शब्द का प्रयोग नहीं है। ऋग्वेद के एक मन्त्री में 'विधान' शब्द का उल्लेख है।²⁰ अथर्ववेद के एक मन्त्र से संविधान की रचना पर प्रकाश पड़ता है। मानवीय विधि-विधान का आदि निर्माता वरुण देवता है।²¹ वरुण देवता प्रथम न्यायाधीश था। उसने ही न्यायपालिका का प्रथम संविधान प्रस्तुत किया। अतः उसे धर्मपति नाम से सम्बोधित किया जाता है। वेदों में वरुण का बहुत गुणगान है। उनकी सबसे बड़ी विशेषता है— धृत्वतः – नियमों का कठोरता से पालन करना। वह स्वयं नियमों का पालन करता है और संसार में कहीं भी नियम विरुद्ध कार्य हो रहा है, उसकी सूचना उसको तुरन्त प्राप्त हो जाती है। उसके गुप्तचर सर्वत्र फैले हुए हैं।²² इससे ज्ञात होता है कि वरुण देवता सम्राट, न्यायाधीश विधि-प्रवर्तक और विधि का संचालक है।

11. कर व्यवस्था

लोक प्रशासन का अर्थव्यवस्था से घनिष्ठ सम्बन्ध है, क्योंकि राज्य के संचालन हेतु अर्थ अत्यावश्यक है। बिना अर्थ के राज्य संचालित नहीं हो सकता। राज्य यह धन राज्य के कर के रूप में ग्रहण करता है। ऋग्वेद में अनेक स्थलों पर राजा को प्रजा से कर (बलि) का अधिकारी बताया गया है। अग्नि ने अपनी शक्ति से प्रजा को करदाता बनाया।²³ करदाताओं को सुख पहुँचाना राजा कर्तव्य है।²⁴

उपसंहार

इस प्रकार उपर्युक्त अन्वेषण से यह स्पष्ट है कि सम्प्रति लोक प्रशासन विषय के अन्तर्गत जिन तत्त्वों, विचारधाराओं तथा विषय सामग्रियों का अध्ययन किया जाता है, वे आज से हजारों वर्ष पूर्व भारतीय संस्कृति मूल स्रोत वेदों के अन्तर्गत पाठ्य-विषय रूप में उपस्थित थे। अतः हम यह देखते हैं कि भारतीय संस्कृति में नेतृत्व क्षमता की महत्ता साथ ही नीति व नियम तथा लोक कल्याण के उत्तरदायी राजा अथवा राष्ट्राध्यक्ष के कर्तव्यों का वर्णन प्राप्त होता है, इसके साथ ही जनसभायें जैसे विद्वत परिषद् एवं जनप्रतिनिधि संस्थाएँ जैसे सभा एवं समिति का वर्णन भी प्राप्त होता है। भारतीय संस्कृति में सामाजिक नियमों को बनाये रखने के लिए संविधान कर व्यवस्था एवं दण्ड विधान का विस्तृत वर्णन है। अतएव 'भारतीय संस्कृति के अन्तर्गत लोकप्रशासन का सम्प्रत्यय अत्यन्त प्राचीनकाल से चला आ रहा है और पूर्व में वर्णित लोकप्रशासन की व्यवस्थाएँ वर्तमान समय में भी समीचीन प्रतीत होती हैं।

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पर्यटन और यौगिक आहार: एक वृहद परिदृश्य

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''असिस्टेन्ट प्रोफेसर, योग एवम् स्थास्थ्य विभाग, देव संस्कृति विश्वविद्यालय, हरिद्वार, उत्तराखण्ड।
'''असिस्टेन्ट प्रोफेसर, कम्प्यूटर विभाग, देव संस्कृति विश्वविद्यालय, हरिद्वार, उत्तराखण्ड।

सारांश

पर्यटन शब्द विष्वव्यापी है, इसकी लोकप्रियता को लेकर सभी एकमत हैं। प्रत्येक पर्यटक एक यात्री है। यात्रा के दौरान वह पर्यटन स्थल से सम्बद्ध जानकारी एकत्र करने और वहाँ निहित सम्भावनाओं को तलाशने की उसमें प्रबल इच्छा होती है। इस चल-अचल संसार में हम सब यात्री हैं किन्तु इस यात्रा का भान कम लोगों को होता है। जो अपनी अनवरत जारी रखने वाली जीवन यात्रा को पहचान जाते हैं वे जीवन को औचित्यपूर्ण भी बना लेते हैं। ऐसे में उनका जीवन अपने लिए और दूसरों के लिए भी मंगलविधान बन जाता है। भारतीय योगविद्या के साथ ज्ञान-विज्ञान के अनेकों आयाम जुड़े हुए हैं जिन्हें जानने के लिए यौगिक आहार का अवलम्बन लेना मनुष्य की प्राथमिक आवश्यकता है। इसीलिए योग ग्रन्थों में यौगिक आहार का विस्तृत वर्णन मिलता है। योगविद्या और यौगिक आहार भारत में पर्यटकों को पर्यटन के लिए सदा से आकर्षित करती रहे हैं। योग दर्शन में निहित योग-सूत्र तो धरती और अन्तरिक्ष के साथ उसके पार की यात्रा कर सकने की मानवीय सामर्थ्य की पुष्टि भी करते हैं। पर्यटक पर्यटन के लिए की जाने वाली यात्रा के प्रति जागरूक होते हैं। उनके लिए अपनी अनवरत चल रही जीवन यात्रा को समझ सकना सरल होता है। पर्यटक के पास प्रकृति में विद्यमान जैव-विविधता को देखकर प्रकृति से सम्पर्क साधने के अनेक अवसर होते हैं। योग की ओर उन्मुख होकर जब वह यौगिक-आहार का अवलम्बन लेता है, तो यौगिक आहार उसकी बुद्धि को पोषित एवं परिष्कृत कर देता है। अब प्रकृतिगत विविधता को देखकर वह मोहित या भ्रमित नहीं होता। प्रकृति की विविधता में वह एकता के सम्बन्ध-सूत्र को खोजता है। इस तरह से यौगिक आहार पर्यटक के लिए ज्ञान के नये क्षितिज खोलता है।

कूट शब्द- यौगिक आहार, पर्यटन।

प्रस्तावना

पर्यटन को योग से जोड़ने पर उसका स्वरूप भी योग जितना विस्तृत एवं व्यापक हो जाता है। योग मनुष्य की चित्त की वृत्तियों का निरोध है। जितना-जितना मनुष्य की चित्त वृत्ति का निरोध होता जाता है उतना-उतना उसके कार्यों में कुशलता आती जाती है। पर्यटन द्वारा मनुष्य स्वयं के और चारों तरफ की दुनिया के बीच सन्तुलन स्थापित कर लेता है और योग की ओर उन्मुख होकर कर्मों में कुशलता हस्तगत करता है। योग और यौगिक आहार के अवलम्बन से पर्यटक में परिषोधन और परिमार्जन की प्रक्रिया घटित होती है। पर्यटक का परिषोधित व्यक्तित्व पर्यटन के दौरान प्रकृति के सुन्दर, विषुद्ध रूप से सम्बन्ध साधनेकी

योग्यताप्राप्त कर लेता है। ऐसे में पर्यटन का उद्देश्य मनोरंजन मात्र न रहकर यौगिक रूप धारण कर आन्तरिक अहलाद एवं आनन्दानुभूति हो जाता है। पर्यटक की जिज्ञासु मनोभूमि में ज्ञान के गवाक्ष खुलते हैं। योग एवं यौगिक आहार के अवलम्बन से पर्यटक के भीतर सुप्त क्षमताओं का जागरण होता है और अपनी विकसित क्षमताओं एवं सम्भावनाओं द्वारा वह समाज और राष्ट्र का नानाविध हित करता है।

पर्यटन;

पर्यटन अर्थात् अंग्रेजी शब्द प्लवनतपेउष का सम्बन्ध प्लवनतष से है। प्लवनतष एक हिब्रू ;भ्रमइतमूद्ध शब्द है जोकि प्लवनतीष से उद्भूत है। इसका अर्थ है अध्ययन या खोज। प्लवनतष के दौरान पर्यटक की पर्यटन स्थल के प्रति व्यापार, रोजगार की सम्भावनाओं, स्वास्थ्य एवं शिक्षा लाभ, पर्यावरण व मनोरंजन से सम्बन्धित पूर्ण जानकारी प्राप्त करने की लालसा रहती है। 'जब मानव अपने न्यवसित स्थान से बाहर निकलकर दूसरे स्थान पर जाता है और वहाँ कुछ काल तक उसका ठहराव होता है तो उसकी इस क्रिया को पर्यटन कहते हैं।' (सहाय, 1995, पृ. 73)

'पर्यटन' प्लवनतपेउष शब्द के अधीन वे सारी क्रियाएं सम्मिलित हैं जोकि यात्रियों की आवश्यकताओं की पूर्ति करती है। पर्यटक स्थल प्राकृतिक संसाधनों, बुनियादी सुविधाओं, सांस्कृतिक विशेषताओं, विषिष्ट स्थानीय सुविधाओं से मिलकर उद्योग के एक जटिल उत्पाद के रूप में माना जा सकता है। (किम, 1998, पृ. 340) पर्यटन में यात्रा का अर्थ किसी प्रकार का पारिश्रमिक अर्जित करना नहीं होता है। 'पर्यटन' का अर्थ है अपने निवास स्थान को छोड़कर कहीं बाहर जाना। संस्कृत साहित्य में पर्यटक के लिए तीन शब्दों को प्रयोग किया गया है, जिनकी उत्पत्ति पर्यटन से हुई है।

पर्यटन— आराम एवं ज्ञान प्राप्ति के लिए यात्रा करना।

देषाटन— विदेशों में मुख्यतः आर्थिक लाभ के लिए यात्रा करना।

तीर्थाटन— धार्मिक लाभों के कारण यात्रा करना।

अर्थशास्त्री एवं पर्यटन लेखक श्री नोरमल ने पर्यटन को आय का मुख्य साधन माना है। पर्यटक स्वयं पर्यटन देश में कोई उत्पादन क्रिया नहीं करते हैं तथा न ही वे वेतन से संबंधित कोई रोजगार करते हैं। जो धन वे व्यय करते हैं वह विदेशों में अर्जित किया हुआ होता है।

1971 के उपरान्त पर्यटक शब्द की परिभाषा दी गई कि 'एक व्यक्ति जो कम-से-कम 24 घंटे के अर्से के लिए विदेशी पार-पत्र पर बिना देशान्तरवास व बिना रोजगार के उद्देश्य से यात्रा करें।' (कपूर, 2004, पृ. 3-4) पर्यटन किसी स्थान विशेष की यात्रा है और उस स्थान विशेष की यात्रा करने वाला पर्यटक है। पर्यटक का उद्देश्य यात्रा करने के साथ किसी स्थान विशेष पर चौबीस घंटे से अधिक खाली समय बिताने के लिए बिना धन लाभ अर्जन की इच्छा के ठहरना है।

भारत देश में चार प्रकार (रावत, 2002, पृ. 15-17) के पर्यटक भारतीय संस्कृति से प्रभावित होकर भ्रमण के लिए आते हैं। प्रथम श्रेणी के पर्यटक भारत में अपने कई प्रकार के व्यापारिक व आर्थिक कार्यों के लिए आते हैं। इनका कार्य यहाँ आकर कुछ दिन होटलों में ठहरना एवं वहाँ पर अपनी राष्ट्रीय, अन्तरराष्ट्रीय व्यापार गोशियों में भाग लेकर वापस अपने देश को चले जाना है। दूसरे श्रेणी के पर्यटकों में ऐसे सैलानी आते हैं जो अपने परिवार, मित्र, सहयोगी एवं समकक्ष व्यक्ति के साथ या अकेले ही अपने ही देश से बाहर यात्रा करते हैं। ये लम्बे समय तक टिकने वाले पर्यटक होते हैं। तृतीय श्रेणी सामान्य बजट के पर्यटक की हैं। ये लोग बुद्धिजीवी एवं लम्बे समय तक षोध करने के लिए विभिन्न देशों की सैर करते हैं, इनमें पर्वतारोही, ट्रैकर्स, जंगल

एवं बियाबान के खोजी दल होते हैं। चतुर्थ श्रेणी के पर्यटकों का वर्ग कुछ अलग सा होता है। इसमें मिश्रित वर्ग के पर्यटक आते हैं। ये कम बजट वाला पर्यटक है। इसमें छात्र-छात्राओं, षोधकर्ता, अन्वेषणकर्ता एवं बुद्धिजीवी लेखकों एवं पत्रकारों का वर्ग होता है जो कम बजट के आवासों में रहकर अपनी पर्यटन सम्बन्धी यात्रा जारी रखते हैं। ये पर्यटक तरह-तरह की पारिवारिक पृष्ठभूमि से सम्बन्ध रखते हैं। इनमें से कुछ लोग तो दो तीन वर्ष तक पर्यटन स्थल पर ठहरते हैं।

आहार के सम्प्रत्यय

आहार का अन्न, खाद्य, खाना, भक्ष्य, भोजन, रोटी, व्यंजन, खाद्य पदार्थ, पथ्य जैसे अनेक नामों से जाना जाता है। आहार से अभिप्राय है— ग्रहण करना। 'कोई भी पदार्थ जब अन्नमार्ग से ग्रहण किये जाने पर जीवनी षक्ति उत्पन्न करें, उसकी रक्षा तथा क्षतिपूर्ति करें, जीवन की प्रक्रिया को संयमित करें तथा षरीर के महत्त्वपूर्ण अंशों की उत्पत्ति में सहायक हो, उसे आहार कहते हैं।' (सिंह, 2017, पृ. 120) गायत्री महाविज्ञान में अन्न के सात्त्विक अर्थ को 'पृथ्वी का रस कहा गया है। (षर्मा, 2007, पृ. 291) पृथ्वी से उत्पन्न अन्न, जलादि से षरीर निर्मित होता है उसी से बढ़ता, पुष्ट होता और अन्त में सड़-गलकर पृथ्वी में ही मिल जाता है। प्राणी समुदाय (जन्तु एवं वनस्पतियाँ) आहार का उपयोग जीवन रक्षा के लिए करते हैं। डॉ विजय कुमार राय के अनुसार 'प्राणियों के लिए आहार वह द्रव्य होते हैं जो मुख मार्ग से ग्रहण किये जाते हैं, षरीर के लिए आवष्यक ऊर्जा उत्पादन, धातुओं की क्षतिपूर्ति करते हैं, षरीर की वृद्धि करते हैं, जीवनीय षक्ति बनाये रखते हैं एवं जीवन की विभिन्न प्रक्रियाओं में सहायक होते हैं।' (राय, 2010, पृ.158)

आहार किसी व्यक्ति की आवष्यकता की पूर्ति करे इसके लिए उसका सन्तुलित होना आवष्यक है। सन्तुलित आहार का अभिप्राय उस आहार से है जो समस्त पोषक तत्वों की षरीर की आवष्यकता के अनुसार पूर्ति करे। विभिन्न प्रकार के षरीर गठन, आयु, लिंग, व्यवसाय के व्यक्तियों और स्वस्थ व अस्वस्थ व्यक्तियों के लिए सन्तुलित आहार अलग-अलग होता है। आहार विज्ञान में सन्तुलित आहार को जिस प्रकार महत्त्वपूर्ण माना गया है वैसे ही योग ग्रन्थों में यौगिक आहार और मिताहार को महत्ता दी गयी है। इसीलिए आहार को योग साधना के आवष्यक तत्वों में गिना जाता है। योग ग्रन्थों में योग साधनओं के साथ-साथ आहार की भी विषद् चर्चा मिलती है।

यौगिक आहार से तात्पर्य उस आहार से है जो योग साधना में सहायक हो। हठ प्रदीपिका में 'गेहूँ, चावल, जौ, साठी चावल जैसे सुपाच्य अन्न, दूध, घी, खॉड, मक्खन, मिसरी, मधु, सूट, परवल जैसे फल आदि, पाँच प्रकार के षाक(जीवन्ती, बथुआ, चौलाई, मेघनाद तथा पुनर्नवा), मूंग, आदि तथा वर्षा का जल' को उत्तम योग साधकों के लिए पथ्यकारक भोजन कहा गया है। (हठ प्रदीपिका, 1/62) मित आहार— इन दो षब्दों से मिताहार षब्द बना है। मित अर्थात् सन्तुलित और आहार अर्थात् ग्रहण करना। अतएव कहा जा सकता है कि षरीर को स्वस्थ, सुन्दर और योग साधना के अनुकूल बनाये रखने के लिए ग्रहण किया गया सन्तुलित आहार ही मिताहार है। श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता इसी तथ्य के सम्बन्ध में युक्त (श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता, 6/17) की बात कहती है।

पर्यटन और यौगिक आहार में अन्योन्याश्रित सम्बन्ध—

जहाँ योग साधना में आहार की महत्ता स्वयं सिद्ध है, वहीं आहार की गणना पर्यटन के तत्वों में एक महत्त्वपूर्ण तत्व (मसमउमदज) के रूप में होती है। जैव विविधता पर्यटकों को सहज आकर्षित करती है। जैव विविधता में जीवटता होती है। जैव विविधता से परिपूर्ण क्षेत्र आहार की दृष्टि से भी अत्यन्त समृद्ध होता है। ये आहार प्राकृतिक होने के कारण यौगिक साधनाओं के लिए उपयुक्त भी होते हैं।

भारत में बढ़ते पर्यटन का मुख्य आधार यहाँ की जैव विविधता है। विष्व में मात्र भारत ऐसा देश है जहाँ सोलह प्रकार के जलवायु क्षेत्र पाये जाते हैं। यहाँ प्रत्येक पचास किलोमीटर के अन्तर पर जलवायु परिवर्तन स्पष्ट देखने को मिल जाता है। विष्व के अन्य देशों में ज्यादा से ज्यादा दो या तीन प्रकार के जलवायु क्षेत्र पाये जाते हैं। इसी जलवायु परिवर्तन के कारण भारत के जीव जगत और वनस्पति जगत के साथ यहाँ के रीति-रिवाजों एवं संस्कृति में पर्याप्त अन्तर दृष्टिगोचर होता है। यह अन्तर ही भारत में पर्यटन को बढ़ावा देने का मूल आधार है।

कृत्रिमता की चमक-दमक बाह्य दृष्टि से ही लुभावनी लगती है। कृत्रिमता में मनुष्य का वास्तविक स्वरूप विस्मृत हो जाता है। पर्यटन, योग विद्या एवं यौगिक आहार मनुष्य की मौलिकता को उजागर करते और उसकी प्रतिभा का संवर्धन करते हैं। योग विद्या भारतीय ऋशियों एवं योगियों की थाती है। आज योग के क्षेत्र में शिक्षा, स्वावलम्बन, रोजगार स्वास्थ्य जैसे अनेकों अवसर विद्यमान हैं। यहाँ की जैव विविधता भारत को यौगिक आहार की दृष्टि से भी समृद्ध बनाती है। भारत में विद्यमान ऋशियों एवं योगियों के आश्रम और योग साधनाएं पर्यटन को बढ़ावा दे रहे हैं। आहार मनुष्य की प्राथमिक आवश्यकता है और जैविक दृष्टि समृद्ध भारत यौगिक आहार से परिपूर्ण होने के कारण पर्यटकों को आकर्षित करता है।

पर्यटन और यौगिक आहार की समकालीन प्रासंगिकता-

मनुष्य अपने सृजेता की भाँति महान है। इसलिए उसने पुरुशार्थ-चतुष्टय के रूप में धर्म, अर्थ, काम और मोक्ष को जीवन का ध्येय बनाया और उसी ओर तत्पर हो चला। पर्यटन और योग साधनाएं किसी-न-किसी ध्येय के निमित्त की जाती हैं। रोटी, कपड़ा और मकान को मनुष्य की मूलभूत एवं निजी आवश्यकताएँ बताया गया है। इनमें भी रोटी प्रथम स्थान पर है। बात जब योग साधना की चल रही हो तो रोटी का अभिप्राय यौगिक आहार हो जाता है।

प्रकृति परिवर्तनीय है। इस परिवर्तनीय प्रकृति में कुछ ऐसा है जो षाष्वत, सनातन और अक्षुण्य है। मानवीय जिज्ञासा जब प्रकृति में निहित षाष्वत तत्त्व की खोज की ओर होती है तभी पुरुशार्थ-चतुष्टय की प्राप्ति उसके लिए सम्भव हो पाती है। अन्यथा वह धर्म-अर्थ या काम के किसी पड़ाव पर विश्राम लेने लगता है।

भारत की संस्कृति विविधता में एकता की संस्कृति है। पर्यटक को प्रकृति को निकट से देखने और उसके साथ सम्बन्ध साधने के अवसर उपलब्ध होते रहते हैं। महान् भौतिकविद् न्यूटन ने पृथ्वी की शक्ति को गुरुत्वाकर्षण बल के एक ही सूत्र में समेट लिया। जब एक पर्यटक प्रकृति व्यापी जैव-विविधता में एकता के सूत्र को खोज लेता है तो उसके धर्म(कर्त्तव्य) के निर्वाहन, अर्थ(धन) के उपार्जन, कामनाओं(इच्छाओं) की पूर्ति के साथ-साथ मोक्ष का मार्ग भी खुल जाता है। किन्तु यह सम्भव तब हो सकता है जब पर्यटन के दौरान पर्यटक को यथोचित(सम्यक्) आहार का अवलम्बन मिले। पर्यटन जहाँ मानवीय दृष्टि को व्यापक करता है वहीं यौगिक आहार दृष्टि को सूक्ष्म बनाता है।

यादृषं भक्षते अन्न बुद्धि भवति तादृषी ।।

अर्थात् ग्रहण किये गये अन्न के अनुरूप ही मनुष्य की बुद्धि हो जाती है। यह बात आहार की दूरगामी महत्ता को प्रतिपादित करती है। छान्दोपनिशद् में इसी सन्दर्भ में कहा गया है-

आहार पुद्धौ सत्त्वपुद्धिःसत्त्वपुद्धौध्रुवास्मृतिः।

स्मृतिलम्भे सर्वग्रन्थीनां विप्र मोक्षः।।(छान्दोपनिशद्, 7.26.2)

आहार पुद्धि अन्तःकरण को पुद्ध करती है। अन्तःकरण पुद्ध होने से बुद्धि निर्मल हो जाती है और संषय व भ्रम जाते रहते हैं जिससे मुक्ति का मिलना सहज हो जाता है। इस प्रकार यौगिक आहार का अवलम्बन किसी पर्यटक की व्यापक बुद्धि को सूक्ष्म

करके न केवल पुरुशार्थ—चतुष्टय की ओर तत्पर करता है अपितु उसकी प्राप्ति या सिद्धि भी दे सकता है जोकि मानव जीवन का चरम एवं परम ध्येय है।

निश्कर्ष

सम्पूर्ण विष्व एवं अखिल ब्रह्माण्ड के साथ मानव जीवन भी रहस्यों एवं विविधताओं से भरा हुआ है। इन्हीं विविधताओं में एकता स्थापित करने और ब्रह्माण्ड, विष्व एवं मानवीय जीवन के रहस्यों को खोलने में पर्यटन एवं यौगिक आहार सषक्त आधार सिद्ध हो सकता है। मानवीय जीवन यात्रा इतनी लम्बी है कि इसका सम्बन्ध इस जीवन से पूर्व (अतीत में) के बहुत से स्थानों से है और इस जीवन के पश्चात(भविष्य में) भी बहुत से स्थानों से सम्बन्ध हो सकता है। पर्यटन एवं यौगिक आहार जीवन यात्रा को पूर्ण करने का आधार बन सकता है। अपनी जिज्ञासु प्रवृत्ति के अनुरूप ही वह पर्यटन स्थल का चुनाव करता है ताकि पुरुशार्थ—चतुष्टय की प्राप्ति कर आप्तकाम हो जीवन की इतिश्री कर सके। योग एवं यौगिक आहार के बढ़ते हुए प्रभावों को देखते हुए यह कहना अतिषयोक्तिपूर्ण न होगा कि पर्यटन के क्षेत्र में यौगिक पर्यटन उसका एक अभिन्न अंग बन सकता है।

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- युक्ताहार.....(श्रीमद्भगवद्गीता, 6/17)
- आहार षुद्धौ सत्त्वषुद्धिः सत्त्वषुद्धौ ध्रुवा स्मृतिः। स्मृतिलम्भे सर्वग्रन्थीनां विप्र मोक्षः।। (छान्दोपनिशद्, 7.26.2)

Acceptability of Rhododendron Juice in Kulhad among College Students

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ABSTRACT

Rhododendron arboreum or Buransh Juice is used in the Himalayas since ages. Its unique acid-astringent flavour with amaranth red colour is highly sought by the known people. It is known for its medicinal and pharmacological properties. With changing trends in serving style, kulhads are coming back in the restaurants' table in the form of chai. To adopt this trend in juices an affective testing, convenience survey was conducted for which the objectives were 1) to find out the acceptability of Rhododendron juice among college students and 2) to identify and evaluate rhododendron juice in kulhad in terms of appearance, colour, odour, and taste. Four samples were tested with the help of 9 point hedonic scale where 9 was like extremely and 1 was dislike extremely. Sample 1 was juice served in glass; sample 2 was juice served in kulhad; sample 3 was juice served in refrigerated kulhad and sample 4 was juice kept in refrigerated kulhad kept for 1 hour at 5 °C. Total numbers of participants were 100. It was found that the participants were less likely to be affected by colour and appearance. However, Odour and taste affected the participants where sample 3 (6.36, 5.85) was more of in a median of scale but sample 4 (7.26, 7.48) showed a positive relation after a negative score in sample 2 (4.8, 4.02). Odour and taste can be improved by putting juice in the kulhads which gives an earthy aroma and with time it becomes intense and flavourful. Kulhads gives an aesthetic appeal to the consumer and modified shapes could be used in restaurants to serve the juice. Increase in use of kulhad will help to revive the pottery industry and thus creating employment.

Key Words: Rhododendron, Juice, Kulhad, Sensory evaluation, Students.

Introduction

Rhododendron arboreum or Buransh (name in Garhwali Language) is a beautiful tree known for its flowers and medicinal properties. It is also the state tree of Uttarakhand and the national flower of Nepal. This particular species grows in the central Himalayan belt. The tree is evergreen and is about 20m tall. The tree bears flowers from March to July ranges from deep red to pink colour. The tree also has religious significance as its flowers are offered to local gods (Negi et al. 2013). In pharmacology the tree is priced for its anti-inflammatory, anti-diarrhoeal, anti-diabetic, antioxidant properties. (Srivastava 2012). Medicinally the plant is used for treatment of diarrhoea, dysentery, headaches. (Bhattacharyya, 2011). The fresh corolla is used to make juice, jams, jellies etc. (Bhattacharyya, 2011). This has led to the formation of various cottage industries. Tewari et. al (2018) conducted organoleptic evaluation of the juice and found that the Colour is amaranth Red, odour is similar to beet root, taste is acrid followed by astringent.

Kulhad or Kulhar is a terracotta cup widely used in north India. It is a handle-less cup which is typically sold as unglazed and unpainted. The kulhads are known in the use since Indus valley civilisation. (Dhamijia 1992). Traditionally they are used to serve chai tea, yoghurt, hot milk, kulfi and some other dessert. Kulhad absorbs the liquid kept in it due to its porous nature. This further enhances the taste of dishes served in it. It gives an “earthy tone” to the dish or beverage. (Outlook India, August 2, 2004). Various vendors and restaurant serve the tea in the kulhads known as “kulhad chai”. This traditional crockery and glassware is becoming famous in hotels and restaurants too. (Waller 1999).

Quality is a desired attribute for any food product. Consumer chooses food on the basis of its quality and their individual likes and dislikes. When consumer makes a selection they basically look for food that is attractive in terms of colour, flavour, texture, the nutritional quality and shelf life or keeping quality and cost factor, other criteria which may affect their selection. Quality can be evaluated by sensory methods i.e. by sensory organs like eyes, nose and mouth or by objective methods i.e. by use of instruments.

As per International Organization for Standardization, sensory evaluation is a scientific discipline that applies principles of experimental design and statistical analysis to the use of human senses

(sight, smell, taste, touch and hearing) for the purposes of evaluating consumer products.(ISO, Standards catalogue, 67.240 - Sensory analysis)

With competitive nature in food and beverage industry the presentation style is also changing and will continuously change in the future also. There is increase in the demand of the presentation style that is more related to ethnic and regional. (Waller 1999). Therefore, a sensory evaluation on serving Rhododendron Juice in kulhad was conducted with following objectives:

- To find out the acceptability of Rhododendron juice among college students.
- To identify and evaluate rhododendron juice in kulhad in terms of appearance, colour, odour, and taste.

Methodology

In the current study, affective testing is done via hedonic scale

Participants

A convenience survey was conducted with random participants by the researcher. The location was confined to students, studying hotel management. Total 100 respondents were intercepted.

Samples

The researcher used 4 samples in the study. Packed unsweetened Rhododendron juice was purchased from Dehradun, which was locally produced. Further, it was refrigerated for 60 minutes. One glass and three kulhads were selected to serve juice. Chilled Juice was poured in three kulhad and kept in refrigerator for 60 minutes prior to experiment. The temperature of the room was 28 degree Celsius. At the time of experiment, total four samples were presented to the participants that were:

Sample one: Chilled juice was served in glassware.

Sample two: Chilled juice served in room temperature kulhad.

Sample three: Chilled juice served in refrigerated kulhad.

Sample four: Chilled juice served, which was kept for one hour in kulhad in refrigerator.

Instruments

A 9 point hedonic scale was used against every sample from like extremely (9) to dislike extremely (1). Four traits were tested that were appearance, colour, odour, and taste. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher itself.

Data analysis and Statistical Analysis

Data analysis was done based on the provisions and utility of services.

Result and discussion

The population considered for this research consisted of 100 students. A simple questionnaire was adapted to grade the responses of the students based on the degree of their sensory evaluation.

The median age of the students was 20.5. Further, it can be concluded that, the study was also free from bias by gender of the respondents, since the male respondents (n=52) and female respondents (n=48) were 52% and 48 %.

Table 1: Variables with respective mean

Variables	Sample 1	Sample 2	Sample 3	Sample 4
Appearance	7.48	5.23	6.08	6.34
Colour	6.88	4.67	6.16	6.32
Odour	6.84	4.80	6.36	7.26
Taste	5.52	4.02	5.83	7.48

The researcher intended to determine the perception of students for appearance of juice in all four samples. Out of which a highest of 38% of the respondents moderately liked the appearance of juice served in glassware, a highest of 36% of the respondents slightly disliked sample 2, a highest of 40 % of the respondents slightly liked sample 3 and a highest of 42 % of the respondents also slightly liked the sample 4. Further it can be analysed that the appearance of the rhododendron juice is moderately liked (7.48) in the glassware only and with every other sample it was low as compared to sample 1.

Colour is an essential part of sensory evaluation. Overall the colour of the rhododendron juice was slightly liked (6.88) by participants I sample 1 with a high of 38% participants stating moderately liked. However when sample 2 were served to participants a sudden drop was recorded (4.67) where as many 36 % respondents slightly dislike the colour. But with sample 3 (6.16) and sample 4 (6.36) colour was more of neutral in scale.

A significant positive relation of odour was observed in sample 4 (7.26) however when sample 2 was presented, participants were neutral (4.80). Also it was observed that a high of 60 %

participants moderately liked the sample 4. In against of sample 1 (6.84), it can be concluded that with time, the odour becomes an important factor for participants in sensory evaluation.

Taste improves from sample 1 (5.52) to sample 4 (7.48) except sample 2 (4.02). It was observed that participants liked aged (in kulhad) rhododendron juice as it reduced the sweetness of juice but increases the earthiness. It is worth noticing that every participant was on the positive scale for taste of sample 4.

Overall it can be stated that sample 1 most favourable for appearance and colour whereas, sample 4 is for odour and taste.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The most prominent changes were observed in Taste and odour of the juice. Also with time the aroma becomes earthier up to a certain level. However, the colour and appearance were not liked very much by the participants.

Kulhads have a unique place in Indian culture. Apart from its traditional uses in home, they are making their way in the restaurants also in the form of crockery. As the results are positive in regards to taste and odour, so it is suggested that the rhododendron juice can be stored in the kulhads for about one hour in refrigerator before serving it to consumers. In restaurants, modified shaped kulhads can be used in place of bottle or decanter. This will lead to the employment of the locals who are into pottery. The uses of rhododendron juice in restaurants as well as in household will increase the demand of the product and thus livelihood of the hill farmers. Further, this will help to revive the rural economy.

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Ecotourism as A Development and Conservation Tool in State Uttarakhand

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Abstract: This review paper is focused on ecotourism as a development and conservation tool in Uttarakhand state. Now it is well known that natural resources such as land, water, forest, mineral, energy etc. are degrading very fast due to different anthropogenic activities. This is happening due to overexploitation of natural resources by human. Tourism industry is fastest growing industry and it has tremendous effect on economy and environment. Positive impacts of tourism includes: increase economy, employment, exchange of ideas, knowledge and development of touristic place. On the other hand, tourism has some negative impacts on environment such as pollution; depletion of natural resources, biodiversity loss, generation of solid waste etc. therefore, there is urgent need of ecotourism to minimize the negative impacts of tourism on environment. Ecotourism helps in low impact upon a protected area's natural resources and recreation techniques, Involve stakeholders, ensures that wildlife is not harassed, and Respects the privacy and culture of local people.

Keyword: Tourism, Uttarakhand, Natural destination, touristic spot, Ecotourism

INTRODUCTION

Eco-tourism is a field of sustainable tourism and an alternative tourism, involves visiting natural areas in order to learn, to study, or to carry out activities eco-friendly or environmentally friendly, that is, a tourism based on the nature experience, which enables the economic and social development of local communities. Ecotourism focuses primarily on experiencing and learning about nature, its landscape, flora, fauna and their habitats, as well as cultural artifacts from the local area. Eco tourism, natural resources, cultural heritage, rural lifestyle and an integrated

tourism is a type of local economic activities. Therefore, ecotourism in natural and cultural areas are carried out with a number of elements in their natural landscape and cultural landscape as well as in the variety of recreational activities suitable for all kinds of environments. Ecotourism helps in community development by providing the alternate source of livelihood to local society which is more sustainable. Its main aim is to conserve resources, especially biological diversity, and maintain sustainable use of natural resources, which can bring ecological experience to travelers, conserve the ecological environment and enhance economic growth. However, attaining the objectives in ecotourism depends on whether they are environmentally and ecologically sustainable and economically appropriate. Ecotourism helps in involving local community for the conservation of the ecology and biodiversity of the area that biodiversity in return provides the economic incentives to the local community. Eco-tourism contributes to conservation of biodiversity; sustains the well-being of local people; involves responsible action on the part of tourist and the tourism industry; promotes small and medium tourism enterprises; requires lowest possible consumption of natural resources; stresses local participation, ownership, and business opportunities, particularly for rural people; and above all includes the learning experiences. Ecotourism, a unique subset of the tourism industry, is focused on the enhancement or maintenance of natural systems through tourism. The term **ecotourism** was coined by **Hector Ceballos Lascurain** in the year 1983. Ecotourism guarantees the sustainable use of environmental resources, while generating economic. Tourism is fastest growing industry of world especially in hilly region. India is nation of diversities. Various types of religions, community, society, caste live in India. Therefore, tourists visit from one part of country to another part for different purposes such as education, business, leisure, pleasure, eternal peace etc.

Uttarakhand is the 27th state of India which is also known as ‘Dev Bhoomi’ or the ‘Land of the Gods’ was established on November 2000. It is well known touristic state and various touristic spots such as, Haridwar, Badrinath, Kedarnath, Gangotri, Yamnotri, Mussorrie, Auly, Nainital, Kausani, Almora, Piran Kaliyar are famous spot of the state. Uttarakhand has a total area of 53,483 sq km of which around 86% area is mountainous and 70% is covered under forest. The State has a total population of 10, 116, 752 (Census 2011) with a density of 189 persons/sqkm. The state ranks 19th in terms of area coverage and 20th in terms of population in the country. The State is rich in natural resources especially water and forests with many glaciers, dense forests and rivers

making it an ideal destination for adventure, leisure and Eco-tourism. It is gifted with topographic diversity, pristine natural beauty and religious holy places. State also offers adventure tourism opportunities in the form of trekking, skiing, paragliding, camping, angling, mountaineering and rock climbing etc. The economy of the State has been largely dominated by Tourism. Tourism is already a major driver of economic growth and livelihood promotion in the state.

Ecotourism tries to raise environmental consciousness by exploring ecology and ecosystems and by providing environmental type experiences. Taking part in ecology actively and getting first hand impressions of how ecosystems work influence peoples' ways of thinking, which finally raises awareness of conservation and protection (Ecotourism–sustainable Tourism in National Parks and Protected Areas, 2005). According to Chesworth (1995), Ecotourism has six characteristics and these are Ecotourism involves travel to relatively undisturbed natural areas or archeological sites, It focuses on learning and the quality of experience, It economically benefits the local communities, Ecotourists seek to view rare species, spectacular landscapes or the exotic species, Ecotourists do not deplete natural resources but even sustain the environment, It focuses primarily on experiencing and learning about nature, its landscape, flora, fauna and their habitats, as well as cultural artifacts from the locality.

A symbiotic and complex relationship between the environment and tourist activities is possible when this philosophy can be translated into appropriate policy, careful planning and tactful practicum (Rahman, 2010). While the details vary, most definitions of eco-tourism boil down to a special form of tourism that meets three criteria: It provides for environmental conservation; it includes meaningful community participation; and it is profitable and can be self-sustained.

According to Weaver & Lawton, 2007 there are standards of Ecotourism such as protection of the Ecosystem, maintenance of the physico-chemical conditions of the area, maintenance of the quality of fresh water and marine resources, no wastes overflow and contamination of the environment (water, soil and air), conservation of local culture and history, culture of locality is maintained and historical structures are maintained as part of cultural heritage

Table-1: Showing the comparison between mass tourism and ecotourism

Characteristics of Mass Tourism	Characteristics of Ecotourism
Large group of visitors	Small groups of visitors
Urban	Rural
Touristic general marketing activities	Eco-marketing activities
Low biological diversity	High Biological diversity
Impact on natural Environment	High price with purpose of filtering the market
Impact on Natural Environment	Little impact on the natural environment
Advanced control options	Little impact on the natural environment
General development goals	Local development goals
Air, Water and Noise Pollution	Pollution Free

ECO-TOURISM IN UTTARAKHAND:

Uttarakhand previously known as Uttaranchal <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uttarakhand> - [cite note-6](#) is a northern state of India. It is also called Dev Bhoomi (Land of Gods). Uttarakhand is known for the natural beauty of the Himalayas, Bhabhar and Tarai and it was formed on 9 November 2000, from the State Uttar Pradesh. The state is divided into two divisions namely Kumaun and Garhwal with thirteen districts. Its temporary Capital is Dehradun and High Court at Nainital. As per 2011 Census of India Uttarakhand has a total area of 53,483 sq.km (1.6% of total geographical area of country) out of which 46035 sq. km (About 86%) is mountainous or hilly. Most of the northern part of Uttarakhand is covered by high Himalaya peaks and glaciers. Physiographically, state has three zones namely: The Himalaya, Shivalik and Tarai range. The total forest cover in Uttarakhand is about 67.10%. Two very important rivers of India originate in the glaciers of Uttarakhand, the Ganga and the Yamuna. They are fed by numerous lakes, glacial melts and streams. The forest cover diversity comprises tropical moist forests (500-1000m), Himalayan moist temperate forest (2000-3000 m), Sub alpine forests (3400-4000m) and Alpine forests (4000-5000m).

ECO-TOURISM SITES IN UTTARAKHAND

Uttarakhand is fully blessed with natural resources; it has 6 National parks, 6 Wildlife Sanctuaries, four conservation sites and one biosphere reserve. National Parks are very important protected areas which declared by International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN). These National parks provides habitat to wildlife and very few human activities are allowed in the buffer zone of National park. The plantation, cultivation, grazing, hunting and predating of animals, destruction of flowers are highly prohibited in National Parks. International Union of Conservation of Nature (IUCN) has declared National Parks in Category II of the protected areas. IUCN is global authority which works for conservation of Nature. There are six National parks (**Gangotri National Park, Govind Pashu Vihar National Park and Sanctuary, Jim Corbett National Park, Nanda Devi National Park, Valley of Flower National Park, Rajaji National Park**) in Uttarakhand. These National parks are best example of eco-tourism. Many tourists visit the National Parks without any disturbance and destruction. Another example of ecotourism in Uttarakhand is **Wildlife sanctuary which is an** area which provides protection and favourable living conditions to the wild animals. It provides habitat and safe living conditions to the wild animals especially to the endangered. For proper management of the sanctuary, rangers or guards are appointed to patrol the region. Governments ensure the safety of animals, from poaching, predating or harassing. In Uttarakhand about six wildlife sanctuaries are established such as Askot Wildlife Sanctuary, Binsar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kedarnath Wildlife Sanctuary, Nandhaur Wildlife Sanctuary, Sonanadi Wildlife sanctuary, Benog Mussoorie Wildlife sanctuary. The Nanda Devi Biosphere Reserve is an important eco-tourism site of Uttarakhand. It was established in **1988** NDBR Its name was named after famous peak of that area i.e Nanda Devi (7817 m) which is second highest peak of India. These National Parks, Wildlife Sanctuaries and biosphere reserve is home to various biodiversity such as fir, birch, rhododendron, and juniper, ramani, alpine, prone mosses, Leopards, Himalayan Musk deer, Himalayan tahr, rhesus macaque, brown bear, snow leopards, barking deer etc, Musk deer, Elephant, Himalayan monal etc. There are four conservation reserves sites have established in Uttarakhand namely, and could be great sites for development of eco-toursim. These conservation sites are Naina Devi Himalayan bird conservation reserve, Jhilmil Jeel conservation reserve, Asan wetland conservation reserve, and Pawalgarh Conservation reserve

Table-2: Touristic spot of State Uttarakhand

Name of Touristic Spot	Famous for	Positive impacts
Rishikesh, Auli, Trekking at Shri Hemkund Sahib, Jharipani, Maldevta, Tons Valley, Dhanaulti, Tehri	Adventure	Economy, Employment, Skill Development
Gangotri, Yamunotri, Kedarnath, Badrinath, Rishikesh, Shantikunj, Haridwar, Jageshwar, Baijnath, Piran Kaliyar, Hemkund Sahib, Nanda Devi	Pilgrimage, religious and Festivals	Economy, Employment, Infrastructure Development
Jim Corbett National Park, Rajaji National Park, Binsar Wildlife Sanctuary, Kedarnath Musk Deer Sanctuary, Nanda Devi National Park, Askot Musk Deer Sanctuary, Benog Wildlife Sanctuary, Govind Wildlife Sanctuary, Jhilmil Jheel, Asan Conservation site etc.	Natural resources and Wildlife	Economy, employment, recreation, wildlife protection, Perfect Examples of Eco-tourism
Mussourie, Nainital, Valley of Flowers, Almora, Kausani, Auli	seeing the sights	Economy, Employment, Skill Development
Rishikesh, Haridwar, Shantikunj, Champawat, Pithoragarh, Jageshwar, Almora, Nainital	Health, leisure, Rejuvenation	Economy, Employment, Skill Development
Mana, Chokhta, Chakrata, Deora, Pallyu, Shaukiyathal, Bageshwar, Chamoli, Almora and Tehri	Rural Tourism	Economy, Employment, Development of Rural Area

Conclusion

On the basis of above account it is concluded that Uttarakhand state has potential to develop in to Eco-tourism state of country. Ecotourism can be promoted in state by the development of natural areas by conservation measures and ensures active involvement, generating benefits for the local population. We should minimize the air, water, soil, noise pollution, biological diversity degradation, burden on natural resources without declining the tourism industry. National Parks,

Wildlife Sanctuaries, conservation sites and biosphere reserves may develop as eco-touristic spot. Tourists and policy makers should take the responsibility towards the destination and the environment by their choice itself, behavior and activities performed in that space, and therefore it is important to be informed about the quality and sensitivity of destinations. We should also keep in mind the numbers of tourists, accommodation, accessibility and protection of attraction. We should promote the tourism industry as well the conserve the natural resources of the area then we can achieve the goal of sustainable development.

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Contribution of Food and Cultural Tourism in strengthening cultural Relationship between Countries

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Abstract:

Increased pace of globalisation has opened up a wide range of socio-cultural exchange at every level of the social life of the people. This exchange is not limited only to ideas and social structures but also has a deep impact on day to day life including gastronomy, clothing, behaviour, market structures and many others. Among these gastronomy has established itself as one of the main tourist destinations. The link between the gastronomy, culture and tourism can possibly be developed as the interaction points where different cultures can be brought together and contribute in developing mutual respect for each other. The proposed paper is an attempt to identify those aspects of socio-cultural life of a country which can play a key role in building a bridge between diverse cultural groups on the basis of Russia India relations.

Keywords: Gastronomy, Cultural tourism, culture, tourism, relations

Culture has always been considered as the foundation of personality development, creativity and confidence building. Globalisation and technological advancements have introduced larger public with the existing cultural diversity around us. Similarly, travel to a different country is not a recent phenomenon, it has always excited people since historical times. However, tourism has acquired a unique role in modern societies. Among the most popular destinations chosen by tourists involve visits to the historical monuments, museums, galleries of art and shopping centres and others. These spots not only project the architectural specialities of a culture but familiarise tourists with life style as most often they are accompanied by traditional folk dances, plays, songs and the traditional food. Hence, food and culture inherent part of tourism. Consequently, as agreed by a number of scholars cultural tourism consists of the consumption of local culture by tourists and at the same time impact of foreign culture on local culture. Attempts have been to define cultural

tourism as to understand and become familiar with way of life and history of a specific location accompanied by a range of cultural factors which can be presented in the context of tourism, these factors may include the food, entertainment, architecture, drink, hand crafted and manufactured products or every element representing characteristics of way of life in a particular destination. (McIntosh and Goeldner, 1990). However, Richards- (1996) argues that this concept includes certain basic questions, such as:

- What kinds of culture should be included within the scope of cultural tourism?
- Does a visit to a museum turn an entire holiday into a cultural tourism experience?
- Are tourists who engage in cultural consumption actually culturally motivated-?

In an attempt to promote one's unique culture, several governments have come up with policies to develop tourism sector by making it more and more attractive for foreign tourists.

Gastronomy is simply an addition to tourism, being part of cultural social, environmental and economic history- of nations and their people. Food habits reflect the life style based on geographical areas, climatic conditions and religious beliefs. Though, from historical times there has been constant change in the field of gastronomy. Many argue that the change is due to the increased competitiveness in any given location. However, the change in the manner of cooking, choice of cooking a lot depends on the demand of it. Tourism not only promotes local culture but also introduces a locality with "the other" culture. In order to draw attention of national or international tourist the change is made according to the choice and liking of the visitors, though having a touch of local culture. Hence, several non-cultural activities may provide opportunities for familiarising tourist with each other in a destination. Furthermore, the ongoing debates regarding the effects of cultural tourism on societies and the culture itself introduce another issue where promoting this,, potential source of tourism growth" will actually contribute to communities in terms of cultural and environmental values or „penetrate sensitive cultural environments" and eventually diminish the very identity of destinations.

Russia India - Relations Soviet Period

Though Russia India relations have always been described as “Rusi-Hindi Bhai-Bhai” during Soviet period, nonetheless, India has been at a receiving end. Soviet government helped India not only in the field of military and the development of trade but also helped in providing training to develop skill. In addition to this a number of educational programs were promoted which extensively invited students from across the country. Magazines such as Soviet literature, Soviet women and short stories were distributed even in the remote areas of India, giving exposure to students about Russian and Soviet culture. Study in Soviet Union programs included fellowships for the students to study in the Soviet Union. This was the time when a large number of students travelled to different republics of USSR. In addition to this there were military and Navy training groups and some diplomatic groups who visited USSR. However, there were hardly any tourist groups.

Nonetheless, at no point it meant that the cultural exchange was one sided. As noted by scholar and Professor Yuri Lotman the cultural exchange is mutual and requires favourable historical condition, the cultural exchange between Russia and India was in the field of traditional medicines, learning Yoga, various traditional dance forms even Russian participation in making of indian films. However, Russian visits to India was restricted by the Soviet policy, it was only official groups visited the country.

Russia India - Relations Post - Soviet period

Economic crisis and collapse of USSR did change the relationship between the two countries. Many argued that there is a decline in the “Bhai-Bhai” relationship with the change in Rupee-Ruble trade, decline in the export import, and removal of subsidies and fellowship provided to the indian students. However, this period witnessed increase in mutual tourism, especially a large number of Russian tourists started coming to India. Though the interest of these tourist groups mostly remained, as ever before, in traditional indian medicines, and yoga, but new areas that emerged during post-collapse period was in the development of small scale industries. Silk, cotton, leather, food, homeopathic medicines are some of the major items that found market in Russian society.

There are a large number of Indian restaurants such as Darbar, Jagannath, Jai Hind, Gandhara and others were opened in Moscow post collapse of USSR, whereas during Soviet period there were only a few Indian restaurants Jal Tarang being in Moscow. However, to recall the presence of Russian restaurants in India there are hardly any, except for one Druzhba Cafe Centre in the Russian Cultural centre, Blinnaya in Malviya Nagar.

A very good example of cultural exchange which is taking place at the individual level is the efforts and enthusiasm of Dr. B. V. Ragozin, who is a first Russian citizen to have been awarded the degree of BAMC (Bachelor of Ayurvedic Medicine and surgery degree) from Gujarat, BNYT (Bachelor of Naturopathy and Yoga Therapy) and Doctor of Medicine in Alternative medicines from Calcutta. As per him the Russians got interested in practice of Ayurvedic medicines only in 1989 after the Chernobyl nuclear plant accident (Ragozin 2018: 2). However, the efforts initiated during Soviet period didn't last for very long, despite showing positive results by mutual cooperation of Russian and Indian doctors. The department, which was created by the Ministry of Healthcare of USSR to integrate traditional Ayurvedic medicine in 1990 and a new course was introduced in Moscow was disbanded excluding Ayurveda from medical practice without citing any reason (Ragozin 2018: 3). Post collapse of USSR, from 1996- 1998, Ayurveda was part of medical practice but subject to licensing, but after 2003 the license was not renewed. Though, the practice of Ayurvedic medicine continued in Russia as separate centers first among them being “NAAMI” headed by Dr. S. A. Mayskaya in Moscow (Ragozin 2018: 6).

It was only in April 2015 the second All-Russian Congress of Ayurvedic medicine took place which got the support of Healthcare Committee of the State Duma of the Russian Federation, Embassy of India in Russia and Ministry of AYUSH and the Department of Ayurveda of government of Maharashtra.

Traditional Indian cultural practices are widespread in Russia, especially spiritual. All World Gayatri Pariwar (AWGP) promotes traditional Indian spiritualities, yoga, meditation, medicines etc. and ways to self reliance by circulating translation of literature written by Pandit Shri Ram Sharma Acharya. The best example could be a paragraph from “Wealth of Awareness”, which

talks about 'Vidya' or 'knowledge'. The knowledge is described as a technique that guides as "how to identify and use thoughts, and the available resources". In order to use means and ways available at one's disposal general knowledge about world and materialistic things alone are insufficient. Hence, vidya is a technique, which helps a man, has to think at a level above to seek dignity and pride of human being.

A number of delegates visit Shanti kunj

UNESCO argues that placing culture at the heart of our strategies is both the condition for enabling sustainable development, and a powerful driving factor for its achievement.

Conclusion

Consequently, open and free interaction between the two countries and the development of tourism has given a platform for the further interaction and strengthening the relations.

The Role of Food in Promoting Bihar Tourism

(With Special Reference to Litti Chokha)

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Abstract

Our diet is a bank account, Good food choices are good investments is the same what goes with the Bihari people who are not miser when it comes to cooking good food. There is no doubt that their dishes seem rich and taste divine. Bihari food is absolutely delicious, one of the major reasons behind is the use of lavish amount of ingredients. Whether it be Oil, ghee, spices, sugar or the Serials. Bihari cuisine is definitely rich, mouth-watering and delicious.

Though Bihar is famous for many things through the world, whether it be the famous monuments or the rich culture and history, Litti and Chokha is a food that identifies the popularity of the Biharis among the rest in the Country. The next best thing to eating food is talking about it and Litti Chokha would be one of the best recipes to be discussed. As the name, itself is enough to water everyone's mouth and cause hunger in stomach. Litti Chokha is even preferred by the rich people and as it is not so expensive, that makes it easier for poor people too to afford it.

Litti Chokha is not all about its delightful taste but it is also a healthy cuisine because it does not require too much of cooking oil added to it, pure *desi ghee* is used with it but the ghee has its own health benefits unlike the refined oils. In this research paper, researcher has tried to bring the importance of food of Bihar especially Litti Chokha & its popularity amongst tourists thereby its role in Bihar tourism promotion.

Key Words- Litti Chokha, Bihar.

Introduction

Bihar is a state located in eastern part of India. It has a rich culture and heritage. The evidence of its existence is provided from the innumerable ancient monuments that can be found in the state. Bihar is a state of tourist attractions which is visited by large numbers of tourists from all over the world not only for the famous destinations and its history but also the rich cultural food found here. The favorite dish among Bihar's is Litti-Chokha. Litti is made up of Sattu, while chokha is made of smashed potatoes, tomatoes and brinjals..Bihar is also famous for a large variety of sweets which include Chhena Meethai, Kala Jamun, Kesaria Pedas, Khaja, Khurma, Pua & Mal Pua, Thekua, Murabba and Tilkut. Many of these originate in towns in Patna, which is the capital city of Bihar.

Litti Chokha is a remarkable dish of Bihar is not only popular in India today, but has also made a special mark globally. It is good for health as it requires no frying but includes all the nutrients. It is even eaten by the rich people and it is inexpensive that makes it easier for poor people to afford. As the state of Bihar is the land of Lord Buddha, the impact of his essence has to be big on its cuisine. However, the food habits of Bihar do not lean only towards vegetarian food. People in Bihar are also fond of meat and chicken dishes. Therefore, what we find is the mix of both the streams of food, vegetarian and non-vegetarian.

The staple diet of Bihar constitutes wheat and rice. In addition, vegetables are in abundance and cooked in a variety of ways. If one talks about the regular Bihar meal, it consists of dal, bhat, tarkari and achar. However, the menu changes with the seasons. Bihar witnesses four seasons every year.

Famous Bihar Street food

Street food doesn't only fill the stomach of many but also provides employment to many and also **helps in the growth of tourism sector**. It is the ready-made food available for the quick consumption. With the growing love of people for fast food, it is becoming more popular than ever before. When you are dying of hunger then you will not wait to make the food and then eat it, that is when street food comes to play its role.

Litti Chokha

Litti Chokha can be considered as a national dish of Bihar. It has become the soul food of Jharkhand as well as Bihar. It is good for health as it requires no frying but includes all the nutrients or roasting on wood coal that is the traditional way practice since many year.

How To Make Litti Chokha¹⁰

Litti Chokha is made using wheat, Sattu for the litti and brinjal and potato for chokha. The recipe has an original flavor of Indian spices. Litti chokha can be eaten for lunch, dinner or breakfast.

Ingredients Of Litti Chokha

- Brinjal
- Chopped garlic
- teaspoon lemon juice
- potatoes
- chopped onions
- chopped tomatoes
- chopped green chilli
- chopped coriander leaves

For Filling

- Sattu
- Teaspoon salt
- Chopped Onion
- teaspoon black Paper
- table spoon kala jira
- pickle
- table spoon red chilli powder
- teaspoon grated ginger
- chopped green chilli

- teaspoon mustard oil
- teaspoon lemon juice
- teaspoon thymol seeds/ajawain
- handful chopped coriander leaves
- teaspoon pickle masala

For Dough

- wheat
- pinch salt
- mustard oil
- water as required

Oven temp: 400C- 200 C

How To Make

Step 1

Preparing litti chokha is as easy as the process sounds, here are the simple steps through which the recipe can be cooked. To prepare the dough, take a bowl and add wheat flour as per the requirement, tablespoon mustard oil and a grip of salt in it. Add some water and then mixing it all together prepare a soft dough.

Step 2

The filling is prepared by, taking a bowl and mix Sattu (black gram flour), pickle masala, mustard oil, lemon juice, kala jira, ajawain, ginger, coriander leaves, green chillies, red chilli powder, black paper and salt together. Now divide the dough, flatten to the desired size and place a spoonful of the filling. Close the dough by the edges and roll it into a ball.

Step 3

Though it can be cooked in oven but preference is given to the traditional method. In traditional method first put these balls on a agithi or baking tray and baked turning both sides, till it is cooked properly. Put your oven on broil mode for 2-3 minutes turning both sides to get a crisp covering.

Step 4

To prepare the chokha, first wash, dry and slit the brinjal and tomatoes. Put them to roast on heat. Boil the potatoes. Once when the brinjal and tomatoes is fully roasted, peel the brinjal, potatoes and tomatoes and then mash them well. Transfer these into a bowl.

Step 5

Add garlic, salt, mustard oil, lemon juice, green chillies and chopped green coriander leaves in the bowl of mashed brinjal potatoes and tomatoes. Mix the ingredients well. The chokha is ready to be served.

Step 6

Plate the chokha in a serving Plate or you can use a bowl. place a teaspoon ghee on the litti and serve it with the chokha. You can also serve this dish with some chatani.

Popularity Of Litti Chokha

It is said that Litti was firstly cooked in the Magadh kingdom kitchen before it became popular in Bihar. It is said that at the times of Tantia Tope and Rani Lakshmi Bai, litti gained its popularity and was recognized as an important meal during war times, because it needed very less water and could be baked or roasted on the wood coal without the use of much utensils, thereby making it an easy dish to prepare. Another reason for its popularity back then was that it could stay fresh for as long as two to three days.

Benefits of litti chokha¹¹

There are many benefits of this food as it is lite and has no side effect as said by the people. It is also easy to carry and can be kept fresh for 2 to 3 days. As the food is cooked by roasting process and there is no use of refined oil, this food presents extremely healthy diet for each and every age people too. There is no less use of Fresh vegetables like bringle. Corriender leaves, tomatoes, green chillies, etc. Also there is no use of maida which causes digestion problem instead pure wheat flour is used which does not has such adverse effect on the human health. Overall the food has a very good and healthy impact on our body.

Other ingredient like Sattu which is very much known and famous among the bihari's is a perfect mixture of balanced nutrients which is prepared in the healthiest way. It is a dish which contains fiber and makes it healthy for the intestine, it also has cooling properties. Hence a drink made using Sattu is mostly drank in summer season in bihar which makes the people active and increases their efficiency of doing work.

Grilled brinjal which is a brilliant source of diet, we can also name litti chokha as a traditional food of Bihar as it has been cooked since many years in a traditional way that is on coal or anghithi. Though now a days or in the modern era litti chokha can also be cooked in oven but one very important factor which makes the Litti and Chokha absolutely delicious is the rustic or the homely way of cooking it.

Due to this reason the tourist or the people other than the Bihar state are more attracted toward having litti chokha in Bihar to experience the traditional touch.

Views Of Famous Personality On Litti Chokha

- According to a report by Hindustan Times, the beloved street food is all set to make its debut at the Manila food fest this year. The event is being organised by Manila's Word Streetfood Congress and will see participation by 17 countries. Of the 30 stalls, 2 have been allotted to India where our litti-chokha will be competing with food items from New York, Mexico and Thailand.¹
- Novelist Chetan Bhagat tweeted: "Litti chokha, a Bihari dish, totally needs to be available everywhere."²
- "Superb" Actor Sonakshi Sinha, of Bihari origin, tweeted back, asking him to get the dish for her in Mumbai.²
- "Litti chokha is a great health food," says Pushpesh Pant, the author of the voluminous *India: Cookbook*.²
- Ashok Chopra, father of actor Priyanka Chopra and a member of the Littichokha.com group, says: "I'm the son-in-law of a Bihari family and so my daughter has grown up on

litti chokha. It is an inexpensive diet that even the rich enjoy. Have *litti chokha* in the morning, and you can go about for the rest of the day without a meal.”²

- “It is a great proletarian food. A plate costs a mere Rs 10,” says Sheema Mookherjee, a senior editor at HarperCollins India who often orders it from a stall outside her office.²
- After having *litti chokha* Amir Khan said “I was fortunate enough to try *Litti-chokha* at this very shop in 2012 and I must admit I have grown a great liking for it because of its unique taste,” Khan said in the presence of hundreds of young boys and girls.³

Conclusion

- Whether it be Kashmir to Kanyakumari in the north to south or Arunachal Pradesh to Gujarat in the east to west, it is believed that each and every people eat *litti* and *chokha* with great joy.
- Views Of Common People From:
 - North(Kashmir)-Tasneem kausar says that “it is the food that we also cook during ramjan month because it is liked by everyone in the family.”
 - South(Andra Pradesh)Raghav Rao say “being south indian we are habituated eating *idli* and *dhosha* but having *litti chokha* brings a change of taste and is extremely delicious.”
 - East(Sikkim)Divya Gurung says “*litti chokha* is a good diet food and i mostly prefers it before going to office”
 - West(Rajasthan)Shivani Agarwal says “it tastes some what same like *dalbhati churma* and is a delightful dish.”
- There are many other famous dishes of bihar like *Thekua* which is the famous festival food made in *chatth Puja* or *Pua* which is made in *holi*, *tilkut* probably made by bihar people in *Makarsankranti*, *chandrakala*, *Khaja* is an exchange sweet made in Marriages, *Kesari Peda*, *Laung Latika*, which are equally cooked and eaten by the Bihari people. But the only dish

which is common and popular among all and over bihar is litti chokha. This is the dish that has gained a lot of popularity in today's day.

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